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TURLI TIKUV MASHINALARIDA MAHSULOTLARNI TIKISHGA VAQT SARFI ME'YORINI O'RGANISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yengil sanoat korxonalaridada mavjud bo'lgan vaqt meyorlari va asosiy turgan vazifalar, uskunalar, ishlab chiqarish hajmini ko'paytirish va yangi oqim liniyalarini qurish va ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha ish ko'rilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: trikotaj, nafas olish qobiliyati, gigroskopiklik, issiqlik uzatish, fiziologik sharoitlar, funktsional trikotaj matolar, kaput, kamuflyaj.

STUDYING THE TIME CONSUMPTION FOR SEWING PRODUCTS ON DIFFERENT SEWING MACHINES

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Abstract: his article deals with time standards and main tasks, equipment, production volume increase and construction of new flow lines and production efficiency improvement in light industrial enterprises.

Key words: knitwear, breathability, hygroscopicity, heat transfer, physiological conditions, functional knitted fabrics, hood, camouflage.

Kirish. Respublikamiz sanoat korxonalari oldida xozirgi kunda turgan asosiy vazifalardan biri: uskunalarni zamonaviylashtirish, yuqori sifatli, chiroyli kiyimlarni ishlab chiqarish hajmini ko'paytirish, tezda moslashuvchi yangi oqim liniyalarini qurish, tikuvchilik tarmog'ini jadal rivojlantirish hisobiga ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirishdan iborat.

Ushbu vazifalarni muvaffaqiyatli bajarish uchun korxonalarni qayta qurish, ishlab chiqarishni kompleks mexanizatsiyalashtirish va avtomatlashtirish, texnologiyani takomillashtirish talab qilinadi.

Zamonaviy kam operatsiyali texnologiyalar yaratish tikuvchilik mahsulotlariga ishlov berishni takomillashtirishdagi istiqbolli yo‘nalishlardan biri hisoblanadi.

Shundan kelib chiqib kiyim detallariga va uzellarining konstruksiyasida choklarni iloji boricha kamaytirish, namlab isitib ishlov berish, uskunalarni vibromaniken singari bir jarayonli turlarida materiallarga ularning termoplastik xususiyati hisobiga shakl berish, biriktirish va bezash jarayonlarini birlashtirish, yelim materiallardan keng foydalanish va hokazolar ana shunday kam operatsiyali texnologiyalarga kiradi.

Bugungi kunda tikuvchilik sanoatida kiyimni modellash bosqichida ham qo‘l mehnatining salmog‘i katta bo‘lib, bu mehnat unumdorligini o‘rishini sekinlashtiradi. Shuning uchun, ishlab chiqarishni mexanizatsiyalashtirish borasida ko‘pgina ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Bular tezyurar tikuv mashina va yarim avtomatlari, namlab isitib ishlash jihozlaridan iborat.

Quyida keltirilgan vazifalarni amalga oshirish bilan bir qatorda zamonaviy tikuv mashinalarida vaqt sarfi me‘yori ishlab chiqish tikuvchilik ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining oldidagi dolzarb muammolardan biridir.

Vaqt sarfini aniqlashda avvalom bor mehnat sarf vaqti me‘yori-bu ishlab chiqarilayotgan mahsulotning normasi (me‘yori) yoki tikish jarayonidagi har bir operatsiyaga ketadigan vaqt sarf normasini nazariy asoslashdan iborat.

Shunday ekan tikuvchilik korxonalarining texnologik jarayonlari mahsulot ishlab chiqarishning barcha jarayonlarini o‘z ichiga oladi va mehnat unumdorligini 85-90% ni tashkil qiladi.

Ushbu ishlarni quyida keltirilgan jadvallarda Moskva Davlat Universitetining olimlari tomonidan turli mahsulotlarni tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt me‘yori ishlab chiqilgan va ular ko‘rsatilib o‘tiladi.

1.1-jadval

Erkaklar ko'ylaklari va ustki kiyimlarini ishlab chiqarishga sarflanadigan vaqt

Mahsulotning nomi	Maishiy xizmat uyida mahsulot tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda							Yakka tartibdagi tikuvchi			Bichuvchi ishiga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda	
	Eng yuqori razryad	I-razryadli brigada quvvati			II-razryadli brigada quvvati			Eng yuqori razryad	I razryad	II razryad	Eng yuqori razryaddagi korxon	I va I I razryadlar
		pas t	o'rt a	yuq o ri	pas t	o'rt a	yuq o ri					
Qishki palto	26,0	18,2	16,5	14,8	16,8	15,3	13,8	31,2	21,8	20,2	3,76	2,20
Mavsumiy palto	24,0	16,9	14,5	13,0	14,9	13,5	12,1	28,8	19,2	17,9	3,76	2,2
Pidjak	23,5	15,5	14,1	12,7	14,5	13,2	11,9	28,2	18,6	17,4	3,36	1,96
Shim	4,5	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,4	4,2	4,0	1,17	0,75
Jilet	10,8	7,7	7,0	6,3	7,2	6,5	5,9	13,0	9,2	8,6	1,76	1,01
O'rt a mavsumiy palto	15,0	12,1	11,0	9,9	11,2	10,2	9,2	18,0	14,5	13,4	2,10	1,50
Plash	14,5	11,0	10,0	9,0	10,5	9,5	8,6	17,4	13,2	12,6	2,10	1,50
Qadalmali kurtka	12,0	9,4	8,5	7,7	8,7	7,9	7,1	14,4	11,3	10,5	1,62	1,15
Astarli kurtka	9,0	7,3	6,6	5,9	6,6	6,0	5,4	10,8	8,8	7,9	1,62	1,15
Qadalmali jilet	9,1	7,2	6,5	5,9	6,4	5,8	5,2	10,9	8,6	7,7	1,32	0,95
Tabiiy mo'ynali palto	26,0	18,2	16,5	14,8	16,5	15,0	13,5	31,5	21,8	19,8	3,76	2,20
Yarim kombinzon	6,9	4,6	4,2	3,8	4,3	3,9	3,5	8,3	5,5	5,2	1,56	0,84
Erkaklar sarochkasi	5,0	4,6	4,2	3,8	4,4	4,0	3,6	6,0	5,5	5,3	1,36	0,94

1.2-jadval

Ayollar ustki kiyimlarini ishlab chiqarishga sarflanadigan vaqt

Mahsulotning nomi	Maishiy xizmat uyida mahsulot tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda							Yakka tartibdagi tikuvchi			Bichuvchi ishiga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda	
	Eng yuqori razryad	I-razryadli brigada quvvati			II-razryadli brigada quvvati			Eng yuqori razryad	I razryad	II razryad	Eng yuqori razryadagi korxonalar	I va II razryadlar
		past	o'rta	yuqori	past	o'rta	yuqori					
Qishki palto	27,0	18,5	16,8	15,1	17,6	16,0	14,4	32,4	22,2	21,1	4,17	2,4
Mavsumiy palto	25,1	17,4	15,8	14,2	16,2	14,7	13,2	30,1	20,9	19,5	4,17	2,4
Jaket	22,0	14,9	13,5	12,2	14,3	13,0	11,7	26,4	17,9	17,2	3,4	1,95
Yubka	5,7	3,8	3,4	3,1	3,5	3,16	2,8	6,8	4,6	4,2	1,30	0,63
Ayollar shimi	4,8	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,6	4,2	4,0	1,50	0,80
O'rtamavsumiy palto	15,5	12,1	11,0	9,9	11,7	10,6	9,5	13,6	14,5	14,0	2,49	1,60
Qadalmali kurtka	15,0	9,9	9,0	8,1	9,0	8,2	7,4	13,0	11,9	10,8	2,20	1,30
Astarli kurtka	9,6	7,2	6,5	5,9	6,6	6,0	5,4	11,5	8,6	7,9	2,20	1,30
Qadalmali jilet	10,0	7,7	7,0	6,3	6,0	5,5	5,0	12,2	9,2	7,2	1,55	1,00
Tabiiy mo'ynali palto	27,0	18,2	16,5	14,8	17,6	16,0	14,4	32,4	21,8	21,1	4,17	2,40
Charmli palto	18,0	16,0	14,5	13,0	14,9	13,5	12,1	21,6	19,2	17,9	2,80	2,10
Plash	16,0	12,7	11,5	10,4	11,8	10,7	9,6	19,2	15,2	14,2	2,40	-

1.3-jadval

Ayollar yengil kiyimlarini ishlab chiqarishga sarflanadigan vaqt

Mahsulotning nomi	Maishiy xizmat uyida mahsulot tikishga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda							Yakka tartibdagi tikuvchi			Bichuvchi ishiga sarflanadigan vaqt, minutda	
	Eng yuqori razryad	I-razryadli brigada quvvati			II-razryadli brigada quvvati			Eng yuqori razryad	I razryad	II razryad	Eng yuqori razryadagi korxonalar	I va II razryadlar
		pas t	o'rt a	yuqor i	pas t	o'rt a	yuqor i					
Ko'ylaklik guruhlar												
Jun va ipak tolali gazlamalardan tayyorlanadigan ko'ylaklar	11,0	8,3	7,5	6,8	7,7	7,0	6,3	13,2	10,0	9,2	3,27	1,64
Xalat	10,8	7,9	7,2	6,5	7,5	6,3	6,1	13,0	9,3	7,5	3,27	1,64
Sarafan	9,5	7,5	6,8	6,1	6,9	6,3	5,7	11,9	9,0	8,3	3,27	1,60
Ko'ylak-palto	11,8	8,8	8,0	7,3	8,5	7,7	6,9	14,2	10,6	10,2	3,76	1,89
Paxtali gazlamalardan tayyorlanadigan ko'ylaklar	7,5	6,9	6,3	5,7	6,5	5,9	5,1	9,0	8,3	7,8	-	1,23
Jaketli guruh												
Jaket	9,0	7,7	7,0	6,3	7,2	6,5	5,9	10,8	9,2	8,6	2,42	1,22
Bluzka	9,5	7,3	6,6	5,9	6,8	6,2	5,6	11,4	8,3	8,2	2,42	1,22
Jilet	7,0	5,5	5,0	4,5	5,7	5,2	4,7	8,4	6,6	6,8	2,42	1,22
Belli buyumlar guruhi												
Yubka	4,9	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,9	4,2	4,0	1,3	0,65
Ayollar shimi	4,8	3,5	3,2	2,9	3,3	3,0	2,7	5,8	4,2	4,0	1,3	

Xulosa. Yuqorida keltirilgan jadvallardan xulosa qilib shuni ta’kidlash joizki, Rossiyalik olimlar tomonidan tikish jarayonidagi o’rtacha sarf vaqt me’yori maishiy xizmat uyining tikuvchi va yakka tartibdagi (uy sharoitida ishlaydigan) chevarlar shuningdek, bichuvchilari uchun ishlab chiqilgan bo’lib, unda qo’llanilgan tikuv mashina jihozlarining markasi va nomi keltirilmagan. Keyingi yillarda tikuvchilik ishlab chiqarish korxonalarini texnik darajasi va imkoniyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda turli xildagi assortimentlar sarf vaqt me’yorini tavsiya etildi.

Fan-texnika va ijtimoiy ishlab chikarishdagi o’zgarishlar, yangilanish davri texnika va texnologiyalarni yangi avlodini joriy etish, iqtisodiyotning yangi asosini yaratishdek murakkab sharoitda bormoqda. Bunday o’zgarishlar albatta, soha mutaxassisini bilim darajasini keng qamrovli, mukammal ayni paytda aniq mutaxassislikni egallashga qaratilgan bo’lishini taqozo etadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Raxmatovna.M.S.(2022). Analysis of women’s clothes sewing-a study to develop a norm of time spent on the technological process of knitting production. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research.2(03).16-21.
2. Raxmatovna.M.S.(2022).Research on the development of norms of time spend on the technological process of sewing and knitting production; basic raw materials, their composition and properties.Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal, 3(03), 28-32. ISSN:2776-0987, Volume3, Issue5,May,2022.7
3. Raxmatovna.M.S.(2021). The description of perspective fashion trends in men’s clothing. Innovative Technological:Methodical Research Journal,2(10),15-20.
4. Mamatqulova.S.,& Tadjikuziyev R.(2020).Метод оцінки рівня кваліфікації ремонтних робітників підприємства автомобільного обслуговування. Мистецтво Наукової Думки,(10), 41-44.
5. Nizamova, B. B., & Mamatqulova, S. R. (2021). Analysis of the Range Of Modern Women's Coats. The American Journal of Engineering and Technology, 3(9), 18-23.
6. Tursunova, X.Sh., Mamatqulova Saida Rahmatovna. (2020). Ayollar paltosi uchun gazlamalar taxlili. 3 rd international congress of the human and social science researches (itobiad).

XABARCHI MILLIY IJTIMOYIY TARMOG'INING TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola, O'zbekistonning milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i hisoblangan "Xabarchi"ning tahlili va uning jamiyatdagi o'rni hamda ahamiyatini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. "Xabarchi" tarmog'i foydalanuvchilarga yangiliklar, ijtimoiy muloqot va ma'lumot almashinuvini taqdim etish orqali milliy axborot maydonini kengaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Maqolada, ushbu tarmoqning texnik xususiyatlari, foydalanuvchi interfeysi, kontent yaratish jarayonlari va ulardagi innovatsion yondashuvlar tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, "Xabarchi"ning ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orasidagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va foydalanuvchilar uchun qulayliklar yaratishdagi strategiyalari ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Tarmoqning rivojlanish istiqbollari va kelajakdagi rejalari haqida ham fikr yuritiladi. Maqola, shu bilan birga, "Xabarchi"ning milliy axborot tizimida tutgan o'rni va uning ijtimoiy himoya tizimiga qo'shgan hissasini ham o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xabarchi, ijtimoiy tarmoq, veb-kontent yaratish, O'zbekiston milliy axborot, foydalanuvchi interfeysi, texnik xususiyatlar, innovatsion strategiyalar

ANALYSIS OF KhabARCHI NATIONAL SOCIAL NETWORK

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of Khabarchi, which is considered the national social network of Uzbekistan, and its place and importance in society. The Khabarchi network plays an important role in expanding the national information space by providing users with news, social communication and information exchange. The article analyzes the technical characteristics of this network, user interface, content creation processes and innovative approaches in them. Also, Khabarchi's unique features among social networks and user-friendly strategies will be considered. The network's development prospects and future plans are also discussed. The article also examines Khabarchi's role in the national information system and its contribution to the social protection system.

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Keywords: *Messenger, social network, web content creation, national information of Uzbekistan, user interface, technical features, innovative strategies.*

Zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari jamiyatimizning barcha jabhalarida tobora muhim rol o'ynayotgan bir paytda, milliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlar ham o'zining o'rinlarini mustahkamlamoqdalar. Ushbu maqola, O'zbekistonning milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i, "Xabarchi"ning tahliliga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, uning veb-kontent yaratish jarayonlari, foydalanuvchi interfeysi va texnik xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. "Xabarchi"ning milliy axborot maydonidagi ahamiyati va uning jamiyatdagi o'rni hamda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orasidagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi.

Bu tahlil orqali, "Xabarchi"ning foydalanuvchilarga taqdim etayotgan yangiliklar, ijtimoiy muloqot va ma'lumot almashinuv imkoniyatlari hamda bu jarayonlarda qo'llanilayotgan innovatsion yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, tarmoqning kelajakdagi rivojlanish istiqbollari va uning milliy axborot tizimida tutgan o'rni ham baholanadi. Maqola, "Xabarchi"ning jamiyatimizdagi o'zgarishlarga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatayotgani va bu o'zgarishlar bilan qanday integratsiyalashayotgani haqida ham fikr yuritadi.

"Xabarchi"ning tahlili, shu bilan birga, O'zbekistonning milliy axborot tizimida qanday muhim rol o'ynashi mumkinligini ko'rsatib beradi va bu borada qo'yilgan strategik maqsadlar hamda ularning amalga oshirilishi yo'llarini tahlil qiladi. Maqola, milliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning rivojlanishida duch keladigan qiyinchiliklar va to'siqlarni ham ko'rib chiqadi va bu borada amaliy yechimlar taklif etadi.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i O'zbekistonning axborot maydonida yangi bir qadam hisoblanadi. Ushbu tarmoqning tahlili, nafaqat texnik va dizayn jihatdan, balki ijtimoiy va madaniy o'lchovlarda ham muhimdir. Tarmoqning texnik xususiyatlari va foydalanuvchi interfeysi, uning ommabopligi va samaradorligini belgilaydi. Shu bilan birga, "Xabarchi"ning milliy madaniyatimizni aks ettirishdagi roli ham e'tiborga molikdir.

Adabiyotlar tahlilida, "Xabarchi"ning vujudga kelishi va rivojlanish bosqichlari, uning ijtimoiy funksiyasi va ijodiy jarayon qonuniyatlarini o'rganish muhimdir. Shuningdek, adabiyot nazariyasi, adabiyot tarixi va adabiy tanqid kabi sohalarda ham "Xabarchi"ning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va paydo bo'lish sabablari ko'rib chiqilishi kerak.

Milliy adabiyotimizning rivojlanishi doirasida, "Xabarchi"ning o'ziga xos milliy shaklni yuzaga keltirishdagi ahamiyati ham tahlil qilinishi lozim. Bu

borada, adabiyot tomonidan uzoq davr mobaynida yig'ilgan tajriba va an'analar, hamda xalq hayotidagi yangi davrlar adabiyotni yangi, yuqoriroq bosqichga ko'tarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Bundan tashqari, "Xabarchi"ning pedagogik jihatdan ham o'rganilishi kerak, chunki u ta'lim-tarbiya, ta'limiy va tarbiyaviy tizimlarni boshqarish sohasiga doir qonuniyatlarni aniqlash va o'rganishda yangi imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Pedagogikaning rivojlanish manbalariga turmush tarzi, an'analar va marosimlar, xalq pedagogikasida aks etgan ko'p asrlik amaliy tajriba, hamda jahon va milliy tarbiya amaliyoti kabi omillar kiradi.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining afzalliklari:

1. Milliylik: "Xabarchi" O'zbekistonning milliy axborot maydonini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, mahalliy aholining madaniyati va tiliga moslashtirilgan.

2. Foydalanuvchi Interfeysi: Foydalanish oson va intuitiv interfeysga ega, bu esa keng foydalanuvchi bazasini jalb qilish imkonini beradi.

3. Axborot Xavfsizligi: Mahalliy serverlarda joylashganligi sababli, foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlari yaxshi himoyalangan.

4. Ijtimoiy Integratsiya: Tarmoq orqali turli ijtimoiy qatlamlar o'rtasida muloqot va hamkorlikni rag'batlantiradi.

5. Ta'limiy Resurslar: Ta'lim va o'qitish uchun mo'ljallangan kontentlar bilan boyitilgan, bu esa foydalanuvchilarga bilim olishda yordam beradi.

6. Iqtisodiy Imkoniyatlar: Mahalliy bizneslar uchun reklama va marketing platformasi sifatida xizmat qiladi.

7. Ijtimoiy Himoya: Ijtimoiy himoya milliy agentligi va boshqa tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Ushbu afzalliklar "Xabarchi"ni nafaqat O'zbekiston ichida, balki xalqaro miqyosda ham tan olingan ijtimoiy tarmoq sifatida ajralib turishiga yordam beradi.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining kamchiliklari:

1. Texnik Cheklovlari: Ba'zi hollarda, tarmoqning texnik imkoniyatlari cheklangan bo'lishi mumkin, bu esa foydalanuvchilarga noqulayliklar tug'dirishi mumkin.

2. Xavfsizlik Masalalari: Raqamli xavfsizlik va ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar talab etiladi.

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3. Kontent Sifati: Tarmoqda taqdim etilayotgan kontentning sifati va uning foydalanuvchilarga ta'siri doimiy nazorat va yaxshilanishni talab qiladi.

4. Foydalanuvchilar Soni: "Xabarchi"ning foydalanuvchilar soni hali keng emas, bu esa uning ijtimoiy tarmoq sifatida samaradorligini cheklashi mumkin.

5. Xalqaro Integratsiya: Xalqaro darajada tan olinishi va integratsiyalashuvi uchun qo'shimcha sa'y-harakatlar zarur.

6. Qonuniy Cheklovlari: Qonuniy me'yorlar va cheklovlar tufayli ba'zi xizmatlar va imkoniyatlar cheklangan bo'lishi mumkin.

7. Moliyaviy Resurslar: Tarmoqni rivojlantirish va yangilash uchun zarur bo'lgan moliyaviy resurslar cheklangan.

Bu kamchiliklar tarmoqni yanada takomillashtirish va foydalanuvchilarga yaxshi xizmat ko'rsatish yo'lida diqqat qilinishi kerak bo'lgan jihatlar hisoblanadi.

"Xabarchi" yoshlar va katta yoshdagi aholi o'rtasida muloqotni rag'batlantirish orqali O'zbekistonning noyob demografik holatidan foydalanishga yordam beradi. Tarmoq, aholini ijtimoiy himoya qilish milliy strategiyasi doirasida ijtimoiy nafaqa olish jarayonini soddalashtirish va ijtimoiy himoyaga yo'naltirilgan xarajatlarni oshirishga hissa qo'shadi. "Xabarchi"ning faoliyati, yoshlarning huquqlarini ta'minlash va ishsizlik darajasini kamaytirish orqali siyosiy va diniy ekstremizmga qarshi kurashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Tarmoq, yoshlar uchun ta'lim va bandlik imkoniyatlarini yaxshilashga qaratilgan milliy tadqiqotlar va dasturlar orqali ta'lim va ish bilan ta'minlash sohalarida yordam beradi. "Xabarchi" yoshlarni jamiyatning siyosiy va iqtisodiy hayotida faol ishtirok etishga undaydi va ularning ovozini hukumat tomonidan eshutilishini ta'minlaydi.

Bu natijalar "Xabarchi"ning O'zbekiston jamiyatidagi muhim o'rni va uning kelajakdagi rivojlanish istiqbollari ko'rsatib beradi. Tarmoqning kelajakdagi yutuqlari va rivojlanishi, davlatning yoshlar siyosatini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlarga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, "Xabarchi"ning tahlili, uning texnik va ijtimoiy jihatdan rivojlanishini, shuningdek, milliy madaniyatimizni qanday aks ettirishini va jamiyatimizdagi o'zgarishlarga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini chuqurroq tushunishimizga yordam beradi. Bu tahlil, shu bilan birga, O'zbekistonning milliy axborot tizimida qanday muhim rol o'ynashi mumkinligini ko'rsatib beradi va bu borada qo'yilgan strategik maqsadlar hamda ularning amalga oshirilishi yo'llarini tahlil qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Ikromov, K., & Khakimova, D. (2024). Analysis of procedural functions of mysql in creating information systems. *Research and implementation*, 2(2), 201–208.
2. Xakimova Dilnozaxon Sa'dulla qizi. (2023). Shifokorlar tomonidan bemorlarga beriladigan dori ro'yhatini raqamlashtirish. qo'qon universiteti xabarnomasi, 1(1), 160–163. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.326>
3. Khomitjonovich, B. E. (2022). Creating an interbase database. *Conferencea*, 245-247.
4. Khomitjonovich, B. E. (2022). Developing algorithm for converting integer type variables into string view. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 105-108.
5. Божович Л. И. “Проблемы формирования личности” – М.: Воронеж, 1997 год.
6. Бондаренко С.М. “Проблема формирование познавательного интереса при классно-групповом и программированном обучении: по материалам психолого-педагогической литературы”.
7. Internetda o'zbek milliy kontentini rivojlantirish dasturi amalga <https://xabar.uz/uz/tehnologiya/internetda-ozbek-milliy-kontentini-rivojlantiri>.
8. 888-сон 21.10.2019. Internet jahon axborot tarmog'ida milliy kontentni <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4566279>.

RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLARDA FOYDALANISH DARAJASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola raqamlashtirishning rivojlangan davlatlarda foydalanish darajasi haqida. Raqamlashtirishning afzalliklari, tezlik va samaradorlik, raqamlashtirishning rivojlanishdagi ahamiyati va imkoniyatlari, davlatlar o'rtasidagi raqamlashtirish texnologiyalari bilan aloqahaqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli iqtisodiyot, dunyo tajribasi, iqtisodiy o'sish, raqamli Qozog'iston, raqamli transformatsiya, reteyl (chakana savdo), media sektori.

THE LEVEL OF USE OF DIGITIZATION IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

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Abstract. This article is about the level of use of digitization in developed countries. The advantages of digitization, speed and efficiency, the importance and opportunities of digitization in development, the relationship between countries with digitization technologies are given.

Key words: Digital economy, world experience, economic growth, digital Kazakhstan, digital transformation, retail (retail), media sector

Kirish. "Raqamli" davlatlar bugungi kunda Norvegiya, Shvetsiya va Shvetsariya hisoblanishadi. Raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojlangan 10 ta davlatlar qatoriga AQSH, Buyuk Britaniya, Daniya, Finlandiya, Singapur, Janubiy Koreya va Gonkong kiradi.

Dunyo tajribasini o'rganish natijasida shu narsa aniq bo'ldiki, raqamli iqtisodiyoti rivojlangan mamlakatlarda raqamli iqtisodiyotda davlat(hukumat)

bozor "o'yin" qoidalarini o'yinning barcha ishtirokchilari uchun belgilaydi va bunda davlatning eng muhim vazifasi sifatida o'yin ishtirokchilari uchun bir xil, teng huquqli va imkoniyatli sharoit yaratib berish hisoblanadi. Ya'ni, bozorda katta kompaniya bo'ladimi yoki kichik biznes, ular teng huquqli hisoblanadi. Ularga bir xil imkoniyatlar beriladi. Davlat qoidalarga amal qilinishi va oxir oqibatda oddiy iste'molchi sifatli, zamonaviy xizmat yoki mahsulot olishi ta'minlanadi.

Demak, raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojlanishi uchun davlat hamma uchun teng sharoit yaratib berishi, iloji boricha bozor qoidalari, qonunlar, shartnomalar shaffof bo'lishi, qonunlar bozor talabidan kelib chiqqan holda (ya'ni bozordagi rivojlanish tendensiyalarini oldindan aniqlay olishi va kerakli normativ hujjatlarni qabul qilishi) o'yin ishtirokchilari uchun erkinlik berishi zarur.

O'zbekistonda davlat ishtirokidagi kompaniyalar iqtisodiyotning anchagina ulushini egallaydi. Shuning uchun ularni raqamlashtirish mamlakat YAIM o'sishiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, davlat sektorining raqamli transformatsiyasi O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim drayverlaridan biri bo'la oladi.

O'zbekistonda davlat ishtirokidagi kompaniyalar iqtisodiyotning anchagina ulushini egallaydi. Shuning uchun ularni raqamlashtirish mamlakat YAIM o'sishiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, davlat sektorining raqamli transformatsiyasi O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim drayverlaridan biri bo'la oladi.

2020-yilda pandemiya tufayli jahon iqtisodiyoti hajmi 4,4 foizga kamaydi. Shu bilan birga, butun dunyoda raqamlashtirish jarayoni tezlashdi. Ya'ni mamlakatlar o'zlarini «bloklab», maktablar va sanoat tarmoqlari yopildi, raqamli sektorlar – masofaviy ta'lim, elektron tijorat yoki uydan ishlash xizmatlari – muhim ahamiyat kasb etib qoldi...

Ushbu tendensiya qaysi mamlakatda qanday namoyon bo'ldi?

Tafts universiteti qoshidagi fletcher maktabi xodimlari mastercard bilan hamkorlikda digital evolution scorecardning uchinchi nashrini ishlab chiqishdi. Quyida 4 ta asosiy omil: talab, taklif, institutlar va innovatsiyalarni kuzatib boradigan 160 ta ko'rsatkichga ko'ra, 45 dan ortiq turli manbalar to'plamidagi davlat va tijorat ma'lumotlaridan foydalanilgan tahlil natijalarini e'tiboringizga havola etamiz.

Taklif: raqamli ekotizimni yaratish uchun raqamli muhit va jismoniy infratuzilma qanchalik rivojlangan (bu keng polosali internetning mavjudligi,

onlayn-do‘konlardan tovarlarni yetkazib berishda yo‘llarning sifati va boshqa omillarni o‘z ichiga oladi)?

Talab: iste‘molchilar raqamli iqtisodiyotda ishtirok etishga tayyormi va bunga qodirmi? Ularda buning uchun zarur vositalar va ko‘nikmalar bormi?

Institutlar: mamlakat qonunlari (va hukumat harakatlari) raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradimi yoki to‘sqinlik qiladimi? Rasmiylar raqamlashtirishga sarmoya kirityaptimi? Davlat tomonidan qabul qilingan tartibga solish choralari ma‘lumotlardan foydalanish va saqlashni sekinlashtiradimi yoki aksincha?

Innovatsiyalar: innovatsion ekotizimning asosiy komponentlari qanchalik yetuk: a) iqtidor va kapitalga kirish, b) jarayonlar (masalan, universitetlar va biznes o‘rtasidagi hamkorlik) va c) mijozlarga yetib borish (yangi raqamli mahsulotlar va xizmatlar).

Ushbu ma‘lumotlar asosida iqtisodiyotning ikkita ko‘rsatkichi baholangan: mamlakatdagi raqamlashtirishning hozirgi holati va uning tezligi (12 yil davomida reyting ballari o‘sishi sur‘ati baholangan – 2008 yildan 2019 yilgacha). Quyidagi diagrammada hosil bo‘lgan «xarita» iqtisodiyotni to‘rtta zonaga ajratadi: yetakchilar, sekinlashuvchi, istiqbolli va muammoli.

Raqamli evolyusiya: holat va tezlik

Liderlar

Bu tarkibga raqamlashtirishning yuqori boshlang‘ich darajasi va sohada kuchli rivojlanish sur‘atlari bilan ajralib turadigan iqtisodiyotlar kiradi. Ayniqsa, uchta davlat alohida ajralib turadi. Bular: janubiy koreya, singapur va gongkong.

Estoniya, tayvan va baa esa innovatsiyalarga moslashish va institutsional yordam ko‘rsatish hamda doimiy ravishda indekslar bo‘yicha yetakchilar qatoriga kiradi. Qizig‘i shundaki, aqsh raqamli evolyusiyada singapurdan keyin ikkinchi o‘rinda turadi: bu hajmli va murakkablikdagi iqtisodiyot uchun ajoyib o‘shish sur‘atidir.

Bu mamlakatlar nimasi bilan ajralib turadi? Har biri o‘ziga xosdir, ammo tahlillar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, eng muvaffaqiyatlilari quyidagi ustuvorliklarni tanlagan:

- Raqamli iste‘molchi loyihalarini (elektron tijorat, raqamli to‘lovlar, ko‘ngilochar va boshqalar) amalga oshirishni qo‘llab-quvvatlash;
- It xodimlarni jalb qilish, o‘qitish va ushlab turish;
- Raqamli startaplarni rivojlantirish;
- Internetdan tez va ommaviy foydalanishni ta‘minlash – ham yer usti (masalan, optik tolali), ham mobil;

- Raqamli tovarlar, xizmatlar yoki mediani eksport qilishga ixtisoslashuv;
- Muvofiqlashtirilgan innovatsion jarayon: universitetlar, biznes va raqamli rivojlanishga mas'ul vazirliklar.

Istiqbollilar

Ushbu tarkibda raqamli iqtisodiyot infratuzilmasi hamon cheklangan. Ammo ularni tez raqamlashtirilayotganlar safidan deyish mumkin. Masalan, xitoy raqamli evolyusiya sur'ati bo'yicha jadal o'sib bormoqda, talab va innovatsiyalar uyg'unligi tufayli boshqa mamlakatlardan sezilarli darajada oldinda. Guruhning yana ikki taniqli a'zosi – indoneziya va hindistondir: ular o'sish sur'ati bo'yicha dunyoda uchinchi va to'rtinchi o'rinda. Shuningdek, keniya, vetnam, bangladesh, ruanda va argentina kabilar ham raqamli rivojlanishning jadal sur'atlarini boshdan kechirishmoqda. Bu raqamlashtirishning iqtisodiy tiklanishga foydasi katta ekanligidan dalolatdir.

Tahlillarga asoslanib, muvaffaqiyatli iqtisodlar quyidagi vazifalarga e'tibor qaratishi aniqlandi:

- Innovatsiyalarni kengroq targ'ib qilish uchun mobil internet tarmog'iga ulanish, uning mavjudligi va sifatini oshirish;
- Institutsional muhitni mustahkamlash va raqamli qonunchilikni rivojlantirish;
- Raqamli korxonalariga sarmoya kiritishni rag'batlantirish, raqamli ilmiy-tadqiqotlarni moliyalashtirish, it xodimlarini o'qitish va ish o'rinlarini yaratish uchun ilovalardan foydalanish;
- Gender, sinf, etnik kelib chiqish va geografiya bo'yicha raqamli vositalardan foydalanishdagi nomutanosiblikni kamaytirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar.

Sekinlashib qolganlar

Bu tarkibga yaxshi raqamli tizimlarga ega, ammo rivojlanish sur'ati pastlagan mamlakatlar kiradi. Ularning aksariyati yevropa ittifoqiga a'zo. Bu qisman yetuk bo'lgan, lekin o'sishning tabiiy kechikishi bilan bog'liq. Bundan tashqari, mintaqadagi ko'plab davlatlar mas'uliyatli va inklyuziv rivojlanish uchun ataylab o'sishni qurbon qilishni tanlashdi. Tezlikni tiklash uchun (o'z qadriyatlaridan voz kechmagan holda) bu mamlakatlar quyidagilarga ahamiyat berishi kerak:

- Raqamli platolardan himoya qilish: keyingi innovatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun barqaror institutsional ustunlarga, tartibga solish muhitiga va kapital bozorlariga qo'shimcha investitsiyalar;

Raqamli imkoniyatlardan teng foydalanishni ta'minlash va barcha iste'molchilarni maxfiylik buzilishi, kiberhujumlar va boshqa tahdidlardan himoya qilish uchun siyosat hamda tartibga solish vositalaridan foydalanishni davom ettirish (yangi raqamli ilovalar uchun ma'lumotlar mavjud bo'lganda);

- Raqamli ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislarni jalb qilish, o'qitish va saqlab qolish – ko'pincha immigratsiya siyosati islohotlari orqali;
- Yangi texnologik bo'shliqlarni aniqlash va ushbu sohalarda innovatsiyalarga yordam beradigan ekotizimlarni yaratish.

Qiyinchilikni boshdan kechirayotganlar

Nihoyat, afrika, osiyo, lotin amerikasi va janubiy yevropa mamlakatlarini o'z ichiga olgan oxirgi tarkib mavjud raqamli ekotizimdagi muammolar va past o'sish bilan ajralib turadi. Ushbu zonadagi davlatlar raqamli o'sishni iqtisodiy barqarorlik vositasi sifatida qo'llashda rivojlanayotgan iqtisodlardan namuna olishlari kerak. Xususan, raqamli segmentga talab yuqori bo'lgan muammoli iqtisodlarda quyidagi ustuvorliklar belgilanishi zarur:

- Asosiy infratuzilma muammolarini hal qilish uchun uzoq muddatli investitsiyalar;
- Raqamli mahsulotlar va xizmatlarning iste'molchilarga xavfsiz va keng tarqalishini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi institutsional muhitni yaratish – ayniqsa, bu mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish va ish o'rinlarini yaratishga hissa qo'shish;
- Aholining tarixan nochor qatlamlari uchun raqamli foydalanishni rivojlantirish tashabbuslarini qo'llab-quvvatlash (ayniqsa, davlat-xususiy sherikchilik orqali);
- Haqiqiy muammolarni hal qiladigan va shu tariqa raqamli vositalarni (masalan, raqamli to'lov platformalari) tarqatish uchun katalizatorlik vazifasini o'tovchi ilovalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash.

Misol uchun, "Raqamli Qozog'iston" davlat dasturini ko'rib chiqish mumkin. Rasmiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, uni amalga oshirishdan jami iqtisodiy samaradorlik 2018-2019-yillarda 2 mlrd. AQSH dollaridan ko'proqni tashkil etdi. Mana shuning o'zi axborot texnologiyalarini yoppasiga joriy etish foydasiga salmoqli dalil bo'la oladi, nazarimda.

Jahonda raqamli transformatsiya hali davom etmoqda. Hatto ilg'or mamlakatlarda ham bu jarayon tugallanmagan va raqamlashtirish darajasi tarmoqdan tarmoqqa qadar juda kuchli o'zgarib boradi. Ba'zi sohalar allaqachon ATning anchagina ta'siriga uchragan (moliyaviy xizmatlar, telekommunikatsiyalar, reteyl (chakana savdo), media sektori), boshqalari esa bu yo'lning boshida turibdi va raqamli texnologiyalarni ayrim jarayonlargagina

(neft-gaz va togʻ-kon tarmogʻi, qishloq xoʻjaligi, mudofaa sanoati) joriy etmoqda. Bu bilan birinchilardan boʻlib jadal transformatsiyalash ular uchun raqobatbardoshlikning garovi boʻlgan korxonalar shugʻullana boshladilar.

Transformatsiya — juda murakkab jarayon. Toʻqson toʻqqiz foiz holatda kompaniyalarda ishni nimadan boshlash kerakligi haqida tushuncha boʻlmaydi. “Expera-Suntronix” alyansi Oʻzbekistonda 20 yildan koʻproq vaqtdan beri kompleks axborot tizimlarini qurib kelmoqda va jarayonni tarkibiy qismlarga boʻlishi, loyihani amalga oshirish rejasini tuzishi, loyiha ofisini tashkil etishi mumkin. Lekin bu bilan xalqaro va mahalliy ekspertlarning butun bir jamoasi shugʻullanadi. Ana endi bugungi kungacha butkul boshqa vazifalarni bajarib yurgan korxonalar menejerini tasavvur qilib koʻring. Albatta, u qoʻyilgan vazifaga qanday yondashishni tushunmaydi.

Asosiy qism. Jahon banki hisob-kitoblari binoan, tezkor internet foydalanuvchilarining 10 foizga koʻpayishi yillik YaIM koʻlamini 0,4 foizdan 1,4 foizgacha oshirishi mumkin ekan. Shuningdek, raqamli iqtisodiyotning mamlakat YaIMdagi ulushi har yili taxminan 20 foizga oʻsishi (rivojlangan mamlakatlarda bu koʻrsatkich 7 foiz atrofida) uning ahamiyati belgilaydigan koʻrsatkich sifatida qaraladi.

2010 yilda Boston Consulting Group kompaniyasi raqamlashtirish koʻlamini 20ta mamlakatdan iborat guruh uchun 2,3 trillion dollarga (4,1 foiz YaIM) baholagan. Agar bu tendensiya saqlanib qolsa, 10-15 yildan keyin bunday iqtisodiyotning jahon YaIMidagi ulushi 30-40 foizga yaqinlashadi.

Rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlarda IT sohasida taxminan 1 foiz aholi mehnat qiladi, ushbu sektor ish oʻrinlarini boshqalarga solishtirganda nisbatan qamroq yaratadi. Biroq IT yoʻnalishining yuksalishi yangi texnologiyalarni oʻzlashtirayotgan boshqa sohalarda ish oʻrinlarining yaratilishiga turtki beradi (IT sohasida yaratilgan har 1ta yangi ish oʻrni uchun yondosh sohalarda 4,9ta ish oʻrni toʻgʻri keladi).

Raqamli iqtisodiyot tadbirkorlar va oʻzi uchun ishlaydigan insonlarga yangi ufqlarni dadil ochib bermoqda. Koʻpincha IT sohasining rivojiga qoʻshilgan hissa iqtisodiyotning rivojlanishi, yangi ish oʻrinlarining yaratilishi, odamlar va biznes uchun yangi turdagi xizmatlarning paydo boʻlishi, elektron hukumat loyihalari doirasida xarajatlarining qisqarishiga zamin yaratadi. Shu bilan bir vaqtda, axborot texnologiyalarini tatbiq etishdan hosil boʻlgan umumiy effekt kutilganidan samarasizroq boʻlib chiqadi va bir xil tartibda taqsimlanmaydi.

Bu kabi investitsiyalardan maksimal natija olish uchun texnologiyalarning Jahon banki tayyorlagan ma'ruzasida «analog to'ldiruvchilar» deb nomlangan boshqa omillar bilan o'zaro ta'sirini yaxshi tushunish talab etiladi.

Ular qatorida: faol ishbilarmonlik muhitini qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan hamda biznes va insonlarga raqamli iqtisodiyot texnologiyalaridan raqobat va innovatsiyalar, xarajatlarni qisqartirish, shuningdek, turmush farovonligini oshirish uchun foydalanishga imkon beradigan normativ-huquqiy baza;

- biznes menejmenti va davlat xizmatchilarida axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llashga doir to'laqonli ko'nikmalar;
- axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish yo'nalishida konsalting xizmatlarini ko'rsatadigan institutlar (davlat va xususiy) o'rin olgan.

Raqamli iqtisodiyot hosil qiladigan effektlarni to'liq sanab o'tish ancha murakkab ish, binobarin, elektron servislar va metama'lumotlardan foydalanish imkoniyati iqtisodiy obektlarga taqdim etadigan aloqalarni to'laqonli tarzda baholash ancha mushkuldir. Shu bois axborotlashtirishga sarflanadigan investitsiyalarning muhimligini, ayniqsa davlat darajasida asoslash bir qadar qiyin vazifa hisoblanadi. U yoki bu sohada yaratilgan gigabayt axborotni real holatda har doim ham hisoblab chiqishning imkonsizligi o'z-o'zidan tushunarli hodisadir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Ikromov, k., & khakimova, d. (2024). analysis of procedural functions of mysql in creating information systems. research and implementation, 2(2), 201–208.
2. Xakimova Dilnozaxon Sa'dulla qizi. (2023). Shifokorlar tomonidan bemorlarga beriladigan dori ro'yhatini raqamlashtirish. Qo'qon universiteti xabarnomasi, 1(1), 160–163. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.326>
3. Khomitjonovich, B. E. (2022). Creating an interbase database. Conferencea, 245-247.
4. Khomitjonovich, B. E. (2022). Developing algorithm for converting integer type variables into string view. Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research, 3(04), 105-108.
5. Z.Mamadiyarov, M.Maxmudova, M.Kurbonbekova Bank ishi. Darslik. – T.: «Innovatsion rivojlanish nashriyot-matbaa uyi», 2021 – 160 b.
6. Raqamli bank xizmatlari va uning afzalliklari – Mirzobek Komiljonovich Avezov 2022.
7. Bank tizimida masofaviy bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy shakllari – M. Egamova 2022.
8. Z.Mamadiyarov, M.Maxmudova, M.Kurbonbekova Bank ishi. Darslik. – T.: «Innovatsion rivojlanish nashriyot-matbaa uyi», 2021 – 160 b.

FIZIKA FANINI O‘QITISHDA LABORATORIYA ISHLARINING O‘RNI VA ROLI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Fizika fanini o‘qitishda laboratoriya ishlarining o‘rni va roli haqida fikr yuritiladi. Fizika o‘qitish jarayonida fundamental ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan fanlarning o‘qitilishiga alohida e‘tibor qaratish lozimligiga alohida e‘tibor berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Laboratoriya, fizik, virtual, ma‘ruza, ilmiy-texnik, masalalar, DTS, elektrodinamika

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF LABORATORY WORK IN TEACHING PHYSICS

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Abstract: This article discusses the place and role of laboratory work in the teaching of Physics. In the process of teaching physics, special attention has been paid to the teaching of fundamental subjects.

Keywords: Laboratory, physical, virtual, lecture, scientific and technical, issues, DTS, electrostatics

Fizika kursi o‘quvchilarni fanning turli sohalari bo‘yicha nazariy tayyorlash asoslarini ta‘minlash bilan birga ularni hozirgi axborotlar oqimi barq urib o‘sayotgan davrda ishlashga ham tayyorlaydi. Bundan kelib chiqib, fizikadan doimiy takomillashtirib turiladigan barcha o‘quv mashg‘ulotlarini (ma‘ruza, laboratoriya ishlari, masalalar yechish) o‘tkazish metodikasiga yuqori talablar qo‘yiladi. Ayniqsa bu, ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyot bilan bog‘liq ravishda jihozlari o‘zgarib turadigan laboratoriya praktikumi mazmuniga tegishlidir. Laboratoriya praktikumi o‘quvchilarning quyidagi nazariy-eksperimental ma‘lumotlarni egallashlarini nazarda tutadi: fizik hodisalarning asoslari va ularning qonuniyatlari bilan tanishtiradi, zamonaviy fizik o‘lchash asboblari bilan ishlash

ko'nikma va malakalarini hosil qiladi, fizik o'lchash metodlari va eksperiment natijalarini qayta ishlash usullari bilan tanishtiradi. Bundan tashqari, fizika ta'limining ma'ruza va boshqa shakllari bilan chambarchas bog'liq ravishda umumlashtirish, mustahkamlash, rivojlantirish va nazariyaning asosiy holatlarini chuqur o'zlashtirishni ta'minlash vazifalarini bajaradi. Fizik praktikum bir qator o'quv-tarbiyaviy masalalarni hal qiladi: - o'quvchilarni bilish metodologiyasi bilan amaliy va nazariy tanishtiradi (nazariya va eksperimentning birligi, o'lchash nazariyasi, absolyut va nisbiy xatoliklarni hisoblash va boshq.);

1. Fizika o'qitishda laboratoriya ishlarining o'rni va roli. Laboratoriya jihozlari va ular bilan ishlash.

2. Maktab darsliklarida berilgan laboratoriya ishlarini bajarishdagi muammolar. Virtual laboratoriya ishlari.

3. Namoyishli tajribalar va unga qo'yiladigan didaktik talablar. eksperimentni rejalashtirish va uni o'tkazishni o'rgatadi, o'quvchilarning tadqiqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi; - fizika kursining katta bo'limlari bo'yicha o'quvchining bilimlarini umumlashtiradi va sistemaga soladi; - o'quvchilarning fizika laboratoriyasidagi faoliyatini maksimal individuallashtiradi, mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi; - o'quvchilarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi (konstruktoralash, texnik qurilmalarni yig'ish, ularning ishlash tamoyilini o'rganish, asboblarni darajalash va b.). Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari o'quvchilariga umumta'lim fizikasi Davlat ta'lim standarti (DTS) ga mos keluvchi minimal bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni egallashlariga erishish uchun o'quvchilarni ularning qobiliyatlariga yarasha quyi bosqich ta'lim tizimidagi DTS ga mos ravishda izchil davom ettiradigan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni egallashlariga imkoniyat yaratish talab etiladi. O'quv jarayonini takomillashtirish, nafaqat o'quvchilar ko'z o'ngida, o'qituvchilar foydalanadigan tadqiqot metodlarining mohiyatini ochib berish, balki ular ongida o'zlari egallagan nazariy va amaliy bilimlarni boshqalarga, ya'ni o'quvchilarga tushuntirish va o'rgata olish malakalarini tarbiyalovchi metodlarni o'zlashtirishlarini ham nazarda tutadi. Hozirgi sharoitda pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarining texnika, tabiiy-matematika, jumladan fizika, yo'nalishlarida tahsil olayotgan o'quvchilarga fizik praktikumdan mashg'ulotlar tashkil etishda bir muncha qiyinchiliklarga duch kelinmoqda. Olib borilgan kuzatishlar, shuni ko'rsatdiki, buning asosiy sabablaridan biri, laboratoriya mashg'ulotlari o'tkazilayotgan bunday guruhlarda fizika va matematikadan tayyorgarligi va boshlang'ich eksperimental ko'nikmalarining shakllanganlik darajalari turlicha bo'lgan o'quvchilarning tahsil olayotganliklarida ekanligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Bundan tashqari guruhlarda eksperimental ishlarga layoqatli va, aksincha, eksperimental ishlarga nisbatan moyilligi bo'lmagan o'quvchilar hamma vaqt ham topiladi. Shunga qaramasdan, pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalari fizikamatematika fakultetining bitiruvchilari, fizikadan eksperimentni o'tkaza olish ko'nikmalarini egallashlari albatta zarur. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida har bir o'qituvchi, o'quvchilarga faqat fan asoslarini o'rgatish bilangina chegaralanib qolmasdan, ularning politexnik saviyalarini kuchaytirishi, olgan bilimlarini turmushga tatbiq qila bilish va ularning amaliy faoliyatlari uchun keng sharoit yaratib berishlari lozim. O'qitishni politexnikalashtirishda fizika fani muhim o'rin egallaydi. Fizika kursining «Elektrodinamika» bo'limi, xususan elektr toki mavzui bu sohada muhim o'rin tutadi, chunki turmushda va texnikada elektr asboblardan keng foydalanilmoqda. O'quvchilar fizika kursining har bir mavzusiga oid asosiy qonunqoidalar haqida talab darajasidagi bilimlarga ega bo'lishi uchun, o'qituvchi dars materiallarini og'zaki bayon etish bilan bir qatorda shu mavzuga doir tajribalarni o'tkazishi, o'rganilayotgan hodisani ular ko'z oldilariga keltirishlariga va bu borada tafakkur faoliyatini rivojlantirishga erishishlari zarur. Laboratoriya ishlarining har biri o'ziga xos xarakterga ega bo'lib, ma'lum bir maqsadni ko'zda tutadi. Shuning uchun laboratoriya ishlari o'tilgan yoki yangi bayon etiladigan mavzuga doir fizik hodisa va jarayonlarning mohiyatini aniq anglab olishga imkon berishi hamda nazariy bilimlarni amalda tasdiqlashi lozim. Fizika kursida shunday mavzular ham borki, ularga doir tajribalar o'tkazishda yakka asbob emas, balki bir qancha asbob va detallardan tashkil topgan qurilmalardan foydalanishga to'g'ri keladi. «Elektrodinamika» bo'limiga tegishli ko'pgina mavzular (ayniqsa, elektr toki) bo'yicha o'tkaziladigan tajribalarning deyarli hammasi ana shular jumlasidandir. Fizikadan laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarini o'tkazishdagi ko'p yillik tajriba natijalarimiz quyidagi xulosaga olib keldi: o'quvchilarning fizikadan laboratoriya praktikumiga «kirish»dagi tayyorgarlik darajasi turlicha, mulohazalari tarqoq bo'lib, «chiqish»da esa, hamma bu masalada ma'lum «umumiy maxrajga keltiriladi». Laboratoriya ishlarini fizik praktikum tarzida bajarishning foydali ekanligi bir qator tadqiqotlarda o'z tasdig'ini topgan. Unda laboratoriya ishlarini bajarish, o'quvchilarning individual moyilligi, qiziqishlarini hisobga olish va ularning ijodiy qobiliyatlarining rivojlanishi uchun katta imkoniyat yaratadi. Fizik praktikum ko'rinishidagi laboratoriya ishlari, tanlangan ishlarga tegishli kurs, qism o'rganilgandan keyin qo'yiladi. Unda o'quvchilar ikki kishidan bo'lib, oldindan olingan topshiriq bo'yicha butunlay mustaqil ishlaydilar. Bunda ular maxsus qo'llanmalardan foydalanadilar. Praktikum ishlari nisbatan murakkab,

ularni bajarish uchun ishlatiladigan asbobuskunalar, ayrim hollarda, ilmiy-tekshirish laboratoriyalarida va ishlab chiqarishda ishlatiladigan texnik asboblar bo'ladi. Fizik praktikum - fizikaga oid bilimlarni mustahkamlash, kasbiy va eksperimental tayyorgarlik sifatini oshirishdagi eng istiqbolli metoddir. Uning o'z oldiga qo'ygan eng asosiy maqsadlaridan biri – muayyan o'lchash metodini va o'lchash natijalarini to'g'ri tahlil va talqin qilishga o'rgatish orqali bo'lajak fizika o'qituvchilarining eksperimental ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdan iborat. Fizik praktikumning umumiy masalalari sifatida quyidagilarni ta'kidlash lozim: fizika o'qitishdagi umumiy masalalarning optimal bajarilishiga yordam berish (fikrlashni rivojlantirish, bilish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish va boshqalar); fizikadan bilimlar tizimligini ta'minlash, mavzular, bo'limlar va predmetlararo bog'lanishlarni o'rnatish; fizika kursining eng muhim masalalari bo'yicha bilimlarni umumlashtirish va mustahkamlash (chuqurlashtirish); politexnik ta'limni amalga oshirishga yordam berish (o'quvchilarni ba'zi bir texnik asboblar bilan tanishtirish, texnikada uchraydigan fizik kattaliklarni aniqlash metodlarini o'rgatish va boshqalar). Fizika kursidan praktikum o'tkazishda esa, quyidagi maqsadlar nazarda tutiladi: a) o'quvchilarga fizikaning asosiy qonunlarini va fizik hodisalarni chuqurroq o'zlashtirishlariga yordamlashish; b) o'quvchilarni ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlariga ijodiy yondashishga, eksperimental metodni to'g'ri tanlay bilishga, fizik kattaliklarning qiymatlarini o'lchashga va ularni nazariya bilan taqqoslashga, xulosalar chiqarishga o'rgatish; v) zamonaviy asbob-uskunalar, hamda fizik o'lchash natijalarini matematik jihatdan ishlab chiqish metodlari bilan tanishtirish. Bu umumiy maqsad, fizika praktikumida o'quvchilarning bilim darajasiga qarab, har bir konkret holda turlicha yo'llar bilan amalga oshiriladi. Fizika praktikumida laboratoriya ishlarini bajarayotgan o'quvchilar oldiga qo'yiladigan masalalar quyidagi uch xil ko'rinishda bo'lishi mumkin: 1) fizik kattalikni o'lchashning eng ma'qul metodi va o'lchash asboblari kompleksini o'quvchilarga ko'rsatib beriladi; 2) o'lchash metodi ko'rsatiladi, o'lchash uchun kerakli asboblarni o'quvchining o'zi tanlashi lozim; 3) o'quvchidan muayyan fizik kattalikni ko'rsatilgan aniqlikda o'lchash talab qilinadi. Eksperimentdan olingan ma'lumotlar hamma vaqt ma'lum xatolikka ega bo'ladi. Bu xatolikning yuzaga kelishiga, asosan, tajriba sharoiti, o'lchash usulining yoki fizik asboblarning nomukammalligi sabab bo'ladi. Eksperimentator sezgi organlarining tabiiy holda xatolikka yo'l qo'yishi va o'lchov asboblarning nomukammalligi tufayli har qanday o'lchashda fizik kattaliklarning taqribiy qiymatlari aniqlanadi. O'lchash aniqligi, avvalo o'lchov asboblarning o'lchash aniqligi bilan belgilanadi. Fizik kattalikni asbobning o'lchash aniqligidan katta

aniqlikda o'lash mumkin emas. Har bir laboratoriya ishida, turli fizik kattaliklar turlicha aniqlikda o'lanadi. Biror o'lashning aniqligi, boshqalarinikiga ta'sir qiladi. Xatoliklar hisoblab ko'rsatilgandagina o'lash natijasi, ya'ni tajribadan olingan ma'lumotlar, muayyan ma'no kasb eta boshlaydi. Shunday tarzda ishlangan eksperiment natijasini nazariy yoki jadval ma'lumotlari bilan taqqoslab ko'rish mumkin. Xatoliklarni hisoblashning qator usullaridan, ayniqsa konkret tajribaning fizik mohiyatini to'g'ri va yaqqol ochib beradiganini tanlay bilish muhimdir. Bu ijodiy jarayon o'quvchidan muayyan eksperimental ko'nikmani, sinchkovlikni, mantiqiy tahlil malakasini talab qiladi. Fizik praktikumga doir ishlar frontal laboratoriya ishlariga nisbatan keyingi bosqichdagi qiyin ishlar turiga kiradi. Hammadan avval bu eksperimental tadqiqot masalasining o'zidan iborat. Masalaning nazariyasini mustaqil o'rganish va takrorlash, qurilmani yig'ish, tajribani bir necha marotaba qayta bajarish, eksperiment natijalarini yozib olish, baholash va ularning to'g'rilik darajasini tekshirib ko'rish talab qilinadi. Praktikumning har bir ishi ilgari o'zlashtirib olingan ma'lumotlarni qo'llash va yangi bilimlar olishga imkon beradigan eksperimental masalalarni hal qilishni taqozo qiladi. Bu ishlar o'quvchilarni keng tarqalgan texnik asboblardan va maxsus laboratoriya asbob-uskunalari, hozirgi zamon fan va texnikasida foydalaniladigan o'lash metodlari bilan tanishtiradi, o'lchov asboblarining qo'llanilish chegarasini aniqlay olish, hamda eksperimental qurilmani tushungan holda mustaqil yig'ish ko'nikma va malakalarini hosil qiladi. Fizika tabiat haqidagi fundamental va yetakchi fanlardan biridir.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati

1. Ospennikova E.V. Umumta'lim maktablarida fizikani o'qitishda AKTdan foydalanish: Uslubiy qo'llanma / E.V. Ospennikova . – M.: Binom. Bilimlar laboratoriyasi, 2011. – 655 b. (<http://www.lbz.ru/books/264/5107/>).
2. Smirnov, A.V. Fizika o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish metodikasi [Matn]: darslik. talabalar uchun yordam yuqori _ ped. ta'lim muassasalari / A.V. Smirnov - M.: "Akademiya" nashriyot markazi, 2008. - 240.
3. Maktabda fizika o'qitish nazariyasi va metodikasi. Umumiy savollar [Matn]: darslik. oliy ta'lim talabalari uchun qo'llanma . ped . darslik muassasalar / S.E. Kamenetskiy, N.S. Purisheva, N.E. Vazhevskaya [va boshqalar]; tomonidan tahrirlangan S.E. Kamenetskiy, N.S. Purisheva . – M.: Akademiya, 2000. – 368 b.
4. Serikov V.V. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim: hodisa, tushunchalar, texnologiyalar: Monograph.yu - Volgograd: Peremena, 2000.
5. Lukyanova M.I. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan darsni tashkil etishning nazariy va uslubiy asoslari // Bosh o'qituvchi. Zamonaviy maktabni boshqarish. – 2006. - 2-son.

DIAGNOSIS AND INTENSIVE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES TO ACHIEVE THE TARGET LEVEL OF GLYCED HEMOGLOBIN AND REDUCE THE RISK OF VASCULAR COMPLICATIONS

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Annotation. *Control of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) requires multifactorial behavioral and pharmacological treatment to prevent the development or slow the progression of complications. The main characteristics of T2DM - hyperglycemia and insulin resistance in combination with oxidative stress, low-level inflammation, epigenetic changes, genetic predisposition, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, causing endothelial dysfunction, from the earliest stages are responsible for the metabolic environment that increases vascular risk in patients. Almost all patients with T2DM are at high and very high cardiovascular risk. The largest studies of the late 20th - early 21st centuries. demonstrated a significant reduction in intensive care complications early in the disease and a “legacy effect” with long-term historical significance of HbA1c control during their observational extensions. Reductions in HbA1c levels may also play a role in mediating the beneficial effects on cardiovascular risk observed with newer glucose-lowering drugs. The desires for glycemic control and organ-specific protection do not exclude, but complement each other. Reassessing individual glycemic goals and achieving them at regular intervals with early intensification of therapy is key to overcoming clinical inertia.*

KEYWORDS: *diabetes mellitus type 2; glycohemoglobin HbA1c; vascular complications; clinical inertia; Gliclazide MB*

ДИАГНОСТИКА И ИНТЕНСИВНОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА ДЛЯ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ЦЕЛЕВОГО УРОВНЯ ГЛИКИРОВАННОГО ГЕМОГЛОБИНА И СНИЖЕНИЯ РИСКА СОСУДИСТЫХ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ

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Аннотация. Контроль сахарного диабета 2 типа (СД2) требует многофакторного поведенческого и фармакологического лечения для предотвращения развития или замедления прогрессирования осложнений. Основные характеристики СД2 - гипергликемия и инсулинорезистентность в сочетании с окислительным стрессом, вялотекущим воспалением, эпигенетическими изменениями, генетической предрасположенностью, активацией ренин-ангиотензин-альдостероновой системы, вызывающей дисфункцию эндотелия, с самых ранних стадий ответственны за метаболические процессы. окружающей среды, которая увеличивает сосудистый риск у пациентов. Практически все пациенты с СД2 относятся к группе высокого и очень высокого сердечно-сосудистого риска. Крупнейшие исследования конца 20 - начала 21 веков. продемонстрировали значительное снижение осложнений интенсивной терапии на ранних стадиях заболевания и «наследственный эффект» с долгосрочной исторической значимостью контроля HbA1c во время их наблюдательного расширения. Снижение уровня HbA1c также может играть роль в обеспечении положительного влияния на сердечно-сосудистый риск, наблюдаемого при применении новых сахароснижающих препаратов. Стремление к гликемическому контролю и органоспецифической защите не исключают, а дополняют друг друга. Переоценка индивидуальных целей гликемии и их достижение через регулярные промежутки времени при ранней интенсификации терапии является ключом к преодолению клинической инерции.

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет 2 типа; гликогемоглобин HbA1c; сосудистые осложнения; клиническая инерция; Гликлазид МВ.

Introduction. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a heterogeneous disease with varying age of onset, degree of obesity, insulin resistance, and tendency to develop complications. Maintaining normal glucose homeostasis is determined by a high degree of interaction between the liver, muscles, adipocytes, pancreas, kidneys and the neuroendocrine system, ensuring a stable level of glycemia [1]. Control of T2DM involves multifactorial behavioral and pharmacological treatment to prevent the development or slow the progression of complications and maintain quality of life. Synergistic effects on multiple pathophysiological mechanisms, potentially leading to long-term therapeutic efficacy without increasing the risk of adverse events, are important for successful therapy. Hyperglycemia and insulin resistance - the main characteristics of T2DM - in combination with oxidative stress, low-level inflammation, epigenetic changes, genetic predisposition, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, causing endothelial dysfunction, from the earliest stages are responsible for the metabolic environment that increases vascular risk in patients [2]. The organic interaction between the microvasculature and resident tissue cells becomes dysfunctional under the influence of these factors. Microvascular dysfunction in diabetes precedes anatomical microvascular complications in the heart, brain, blood vessels, kidney, retina, nervous tissue, muscles and other organs. The assumption of the reversibility of microvascular damage with concomitant dysfunction in the early stages of the disease, provided adequate interventions, is substantiated. Unfortunately, even when diagnosing T2DM, vascular pathology is detected - up to 50% of cases [3]. Moreover, according to the UK Biobank, with a median follow-up of 11 years, the risk of developing such clinical outcomes as chronic kidney disease (CKD), chronic heart failure (CHF), atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) increases gradiently even in people with prediabetes , according to glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) indicators, which do not yet have diagnostic values for T2DM [4]. According to the European Society of Cardiology (European Society of Cardiology), almost all patients with T2DM and type 1 diabetes (T1DM) over 40 years of age are at high and very high cardiovascular risk [5]. How should patients with diabetes be treated from the onset of the disease and what indicators should be followed? The cornerstone in assessing the effect of glycemic control on the development of complications in patients with T1DM during intensive treatment was laid by the DCCT (Diabetes Control and Complications Trial) study [6]. The DCCT study (mean glycosylated hemoglobin HbA1c level ~7% (53 mmol/mol)) showed a reduction in the development and progression of early microvascular and neurological

complications associated with diabetes, by 34–76% compared to the traditional treatment group (HbA1c at ~9% (75 mmol/mol)) for an average of 6.5 years of therapy. Intensive therapy was associated with weight gain and a threefold increase in the risk of hypoglycemia. At the end of DCCT, a long-term observational study, EDIC (Epidemiology of Diabetes Interventions and Complications study), was initiated. Despite the convergence of HbA1c levels between the two groups, the development and progression of complications was still significantly less in the intensive treatment group compared with the conventional treatment group; this phenomenon has been called "metabolic memory". The DCCT trial demonstrated a significant reduction in early complications with intensive care, and the phenomenon of metabolic memory during the EDIC period contributed to a significant reduction in the burden of complications over time—a 57% risk of cardiovascular events and a 33% mortality rate in the intensive treatment group compared with traditional treatment group [6]. Follow-up up to 29 years identified HbA1c as the strongest modifiable risk factor for a first cardiovascular event (RR 1.38; 95% CI 1.21–1.56 per 1% HbA1c); serious cardiovascular event (MACE) - non-fatal myocardial infarction (MI), non-fatal stroke, cardiovascular death (RR 1.54; 95% CI 1.30–1.82) [7]. In T2DM, the importance of early targeting (from the onset of the disease) on glycemic control to prevent complications was shown in the UKPDS (United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study) study [8, 9]. This research, initiated almost 50 years ago when routine therapeutic interventions of today were not yet available (eg, the use of statins), has had a tremendous impact on the practice of treating T2DM. The UKPDS study, initiated in 1977 at the John Radcliffe Hospital in Oxford (UK), had three stages: the first - from 1977 to 1997. (almost 43,000 patient-years of observation), the second - from 1997 to 2007. (67,000 patient-years), the third - from 2001 to 2021. (78,000 patient-years). In summary, a 44-year follow-up period has now been reached, and data are available on the long-term effects of intensive glycemic control in T2DM. A total of 4209 people (23 clinical sites) with newly diagnosed T2DM, mostly white men, were randomized at baseline. The effect of intensive glycemic control with either insulin or sulfonylureas (metformin in overweight patients) was studied compared with traditional therapy. Diabetes complications, diabetes-related mortality, and all-cause mortality were recorded. The results of the first period of UKPDS are well known and have formed the basis of the global concept of treatment of T2DM: intensive glycemic control reduced the risk of all diabetes-related endpoints, microvascular complications, MI and all-cause mortality. And

treatment with metformin was associated with a greater reduction in risk, making the drug a first-line treatment for many years. Although the glycemic differences between the intensive control and usual care groups disappeared soon after the end of the study, the benefits of the former were maintained during the observation period. However, UKPDS continues to be a source of data influencing the global concept of T2DM treatment. The main question after 44 years of UKPDS research, highlighted at the 2022 EASD Congress, is whether there is a “legacy effect”, i.e. Does the effect of strict glucose control persist after the end of the initial active phase of the trial? First identified in the 30-year UKPDS analysis [10], this effect remains virtually unchanged up to 44 years of follow-up. Data were presented for all endpoints related to diabetes, MI, microvascular complications, and all-cause mortality. In the sulfonylurea/insulin group compared with conventional therapy, the relative risk reduction after 44 years was 10, 15, 26 and 11%, respectively, and for metformin compared with conventional therapy the corresponding figures were: 19, 31, 10 and 25% [11]. . These significant results highlight the critical importance of identifying and aggressively treating T2DM “at the earliest opportunity.” One of the study coordinators, Professor Ruri Holman, when explaining the “legacy effect”, emphasized the long-term historical importance of HbA1c control, as a potential increase in all-cause mortality was identified for a 1% increase in HbA1c levels (Figure 1). Prof. R. Holman suggested that the “legacy effect” is essentially a protection against hyperglycemia, which activates oxidative stress, the formation of proteins, advanced glycation end products, and epigenetic changes leading to the effects of inflammatory proteins. He added that the larger size of metformin's "legacy" effect suggests that additional drug-related protective mechanisms, such as inhibition of inflammatory pathways, may be at play. Later N. Laiteerapong et al. [12] determined the effect of delayed glycemic control in a cohort study of 34,737 patients with newly diagnosed T2DM. The authors examined the associations between HbA1c 9.0% (>75 mmol/mol) and various periods of early exposure (0–1, 0–2, 0–3, 0–4, 0–5, 0–6, and 0–7 years), the incidence of micro- and macrovascular complications and mortality in these patients with an average follow-up of 13 years. Compared with HbA1c 6.5% (>48 mmol/mol) was associated with more frequent micro- and macrovascular events, and HbA1c >7.0% (>53 mmol/mol) was associated with increased mortality. These results support the idea that immediate treatment, aimed at careful and long-term glycemic control immediately after diagnosis, necessary to prevent the long-term risk of diabetes complications and increased mortality. The significance of the

first UKPDS results for the scientific community and practical medicine is illustrated by the fact that after their presentation, a whole cascade of multicenter studies on similar issues was launched. In order to evaluate the protective role of effective glycemic control to prevent fatal and non-fatal cardiovascular events in patients with T2DM, but with a long history of the disease and high cardiovascular risk, several large-scale prospective studies with a similar design were initiated almost simultaneously - ACCORD (Action to Control Cardiovascular Risk in Diabetes), VADT (Veterans Affairs Diabetes Trial) and ADVANCE (Action in Diabetes and Vascular Disease: Preterax and Diamicron Modified Release Controlled Evaluation) [13–15]. The ACCORD and VADT trials used a strategy of rapid intensification of therapy with the introduction regimens of multiple oral antihyperglycemic agents and insulin, whereas the ADVANCE trial used a much more cautious escalation strategy with the original gliclazide MB (Diabeton MB®) and other drugs, resulting in a much faster reduction in HbA1c (within 3–6 months) in ACCORD and VADT compared with 2 years in the ADVANCE study. This resulted in significant weight gain in patients in the intensive glycemic control groups in the ACCORD (3.5 kg) and VADT (8.4 kg) studies, but not in the ADVANCE study (0.1 kg). In addition, the incidence of severe hypoglycemia in the ACCORD and VADT studies was 6 times higher than in the ADVANCE study.

Conclusion. We can conclude that the second decade of the 21st century. has already become routinely characterized as a time of paradigm shift in the treatment of T2DM. The cardio-reno-metabolic approach and the expansion of NGLT-2 drugs into other areas of medicine (primarily cardiology and nephrology) open up promising prospects for improving the prognosis of patients. At the same time, the above data on the importance of early achievement of target glycemic control emphasize that in T2DM, it is the combination of approaches that provides maximum benefits for patients: providing organ protection with glucose-lowering drugs with proven properties to influence outcomes and prognosis, as well as achieving adequate glycemic control throughout the course of the disease (the duration of which is often measured over several decades), with the inevitable need to both overcome clinical inertia and take into account the dynamically changing individual characteristics of the status of a particular patient.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбилов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ.

- Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensialdiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 special):135-138.
20. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
21. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of COVID-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2

22. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):381-386.
23. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования.* 2023;4(1):131-133.
24. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
25. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *PEDAGOG.* 2022;5(5):341-345.
26. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health.* 2022;8:67-72.
27. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(11).
28. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
29. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR).* 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
30. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX.* Published online 2020:460-461.
31. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 special):259-264.
32. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149).* 2023;1(9):121-123.
33. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfiyeva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education.*

2023;4(12):107-117.

34. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
35. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. HERPETIC MENINGITIS. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
36. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
37. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
38. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
39. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
40. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o'zgarishlar. *so'ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
41. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.
42. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.
43. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):337-340.
44. Daminov AT, Saqullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):139-142.
45. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O'g'li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(6):408-412

IGG4-RELATED DISEASES IN THE BACKGROUND OF DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *IgG4-related disease (IgG4-CD) is characterized by the appearance of tumor-like foci in one or more organs, occurring synchronously or metachronously, due to fibroinflammatory changes with hypersecretion of immunoglobulin G subclass 4 (IgG4) in tissues and/or serum. Diabetes mellitus (DM) develops in 43–68% of patients with IgG4-related pancreatitis. Diabetes in the setting of IgG4-SD can be caused by both damage to the endocrine pancreas and the use of glucocorticosteroids, but its course is moderate, with a rare need for insulin therapy. In both cases, the use of genetic engineering biological therapy with rituximab may be accompanied by an improvement in carbohydrate metabolism. This article presents a clinical observation of the course of diabetes and the characteristics of the need for antidiabetic therapy over a period of 1.5 years in a patient receiving treatment for IgG4-CD.*

KEYWORDS: *IgG4-related disease; diabetes; autoimmune pancreatitis; glucocorticoids; rituximab*

IGG4-АССОЦИИРОВАННЫЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ НА ФОНЕ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА

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***Аннотация.** IgG4-ассоциированное заболевание (IgG4-CD) характеризуется появлением опухолеподобных очагов в одном или нескольких органах, протекающих синхронно или метахронно, вследствие фибровоспалительных изменений с гиперсекрецией иммуноглобулина G подкласса 4 (IgG4) в тканях и/или сыворотке крови. Сахарный диабет (СД) развивается у 43–68% больных IgG4-ассоциированным панкреатитом. Сахарный диабет на фоне IgG4-SD может быть обусловлен как поражением эндокринной системы поджелудочной железы, так и применением глюкокортикостероидов, но течение его умеренное, с редкой необходимостью инсулинотерапии. В обоих случаях применение генно-инженерной биологической терапии ритуксимабом может сопровождаться улучшением углеводного обмена. В статье представлены клиническое наблюдение течения сахарного диабета и особенности необходимости антидиабетической терапии на протяжении 1,5 лет у пациента, получающего лечение по поводу IgG4-CD.*

Ключевые слова: IgG4-ассоциированные заболевания; диабет; аутоиммунный панкреатит; глюкокортикоиды; ритуксимаб.

Introduction. IgG4-related disease (IgG4-S3) is an immune-mediated chronic systemic disease characterized by the appearance of tumor-like foci in one or more organs, occurring synchronously or metachronously, due to fibroinflammatory changes with hypersecretion of immunoglobulin G of the 4th subclass (IgG4) in tissues and/or blood serum [1]. Endocrine manifestations of IgG4-CD include pancreatitis with the development of diabetes mellitus (DM), as well as Riedel's fibrosing thyroiditis and lymphocytic hypophysitis. Autoimmune pancreatitis within the framework of IgG4-C3 (AIP type 1) is often accompanied by damage to other target organs with the development of sialadenitis, biliary stenosis, interstitial lung disease, orbital pseudotumor, nephritis, etc. In such cases, a biopsy of these organs with the detection of characteristic histological signs of the disease, such as moiré-like fibrosis, obliterating phlebitis, lymphoplasmacytic infiltration, makes it possible to verify the diagnosis. Similar histological changes can be detected in the tissues of the pancreas, but its biopsy is not performed in routine clinical practice for IgG4-C3 [2]. In the early stages of the disease, clinical symptoms may be absent. As the disease progresses, signs of cholestasis appear, which forms when the pancreas compresses the common bile duct, as well as such nonspecific clinical manifestations as mild or moderate abdominal pain, general fatigue, and weight loss. In 17% of patients, the disease

may be asymptomatic [3]. In such cases, damage to the pancreas may be an incidental finding during instrumental examination of the abdominal organs. AIP type 1 is characterized by a diffuse increase in the size of the pancreas with the formation of a “sausage-shaped appearance”, a rectangular shape at the tail (“clipped tail sign”). Involvement of the main duct of the gland is also noted with damage to more than 1/3 of its length in one fragment or in the form of a multifocal lesion with alternating areas of narrowing or disappearance of the duct without previous dilatation or other signs of obstructive pancreatitis [4]. Laboratory data show signs of cholestasis, increased levels of total protein and gammaglobulins, IgG4 in the blood, and increased ESR [5]. According to studies, diabetes develops among 43–68% of patients with IgG4-AIP, but its course is moderate, with a rare need for insulin therapy. Diabetes may be the first and only manifestation of type 1 AIP [6]. Glucocorticosteroids (GCS) are used as first-line drugs for the treatment of AIP type 1, and in fairly high doses - 0.6 mg/kg/day. Interestingly, during GCS therapy, a “paradoxical” effect of improving glycemic parameters may be observed [7]. This article describes the course of diabetes and changes in antidiabetic therapy over 1.5 years in a patient treated with IgG4-SD.

CASE DESCRIPTION The patient is a Caucasian man, 41 years old, who applied to the Federal State Budgetary Institution “Research Institute of Rheumatology named after. V.A. Nasonova” in October 2020 with complaints of severe general weakness, jaundice of the skin, diffuse skin itching, discomfort in the epigastrium, nausea, and weight loss of 26 kg since January 2020. Since 2017, he has noted the emergence and increase of general weakness and fatigue. In March 2019, attacks of hepatic colic appeared and he received symptomatic therapy. At the end of 2019, a hematologist diagnosed acquired hemophilia with deficiency of factors IX, XI, XII. Due to the absence of a specific hemorrhagic clinical picture, it is recommended to refrain from specific therapy. Also, at the end of 2019, swelling of the eyelids appeared in the morning. According to computed tomography (CT) of the orbits from March 2020, a massive enlargement of the lacrimal glands on both sides and hyperplastic polysinusitis was detected. In May 2020, an MRI of the abdominal cavity revealed a large hypodense formation in the pancreas with edema of the parapancreatic tissue, lymphadenopathy in the area of the parapancreatic tissue, and multiple low-density foci in both kidneys. The IgG4 value in the blood was 3 g/l (0.1–1.35 g/l). In August 2020, he applied for a correspondence consultation at the Federal State Budgetary Institution “NIIR named after. V.A. Nasonova”, the diagnosis was established: IgG4-S3 (autoimmune pancreatitis? dacryoadenitis, sialadenitis?). At the end of August

2020, with clinical manifestations of obstructive jaundice, the patient was hospitalized in a surgical hospital at his place of residence. Due to acquired hemophilia, surgical treatment was refused. A number of studies were completed in October 2020. According to positron emission tomography combined with CT (PET-CT): accumulation of a radiopharmaceutical (^{18}F -FDG) was recorded in the spleen, thickened lacrimal glands, and kidneys; totally in the enlarged pancreas; in the lymph nodes: cervical-supraclavicular, retromammary and axillary, mediastinal (upper paratracheal, preaortic at the level of the left main bronchus, bifurcation bronchopulmonary), hepatic hilum, common and external iliac on both sides. On a CT scan of the abdominal organs, attention is drawn to a diffuse increase in the size of the pancreas. As part of the differential diagnosis, lymphoproliferative disease was excluded, however, due to the atypical clinical picture (severe, extensive multiorgan damage), BCL2-negativity, the absence of mutations involving the BCL6/3q27, cMYC/8q24, BCL2/18q21 gene loci, the absence of B-cell clonality, the diagnosis of lymphoma was excluded. In October 2020, due to deterioration of his condition - severe general weakness, icteric skin, diffuse skin itching, feeling of discomfort in the epigastrium, nausea, weight loss (by 26 kg since January 2020), he was hospitalized in the hospital of the Federal State Budgetary Institution "NIIR named after. V.A. Nasonova" for verification of diagnosis and correction of therapy. During the examination: total bilirubin 285.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, direct bilirubin 274.51 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, alkaline phosphatase 214.0 U/L, fasting glucose 11.7 mmol/L (Table 1). Immunological blood test: rheumatoid factor - negative, IgG4 12.5 g/l (normal) Considering the severity of the condition, the active inflammatory process, insulin therapy was chosen for the initial treatment of diabetes: Glulisine 6 U 3 times a day, Glargine 20 U/day (Table 2). During subsequent hospitalizations in October-November, rituximab 500 mg was reintroduced intravenously. A total of 2000 mg of rituximab was administered, and pulse therapy with methylprednisolone was performed twice (250 mg with a gradual reduction in the dose of methylprednisolone, first to 24 mg/day, then 22 mg /day for 1 month). Subsequently, Glimpiride 4 mg/day, Linagliptin 5 mg/day were used as antidiabetic therapy in October 2020; in December 2020, the dose of methylprednisolone was reduced to 12 mg. To correct hyperglycemia, he was again transferred to Glulisine 6 U 3 times / day, Glargine 12 U / day. In December 2020, he was hospitalized at the NIIR. Before admission to the hospital, the patient was objectively noted to have swelling of the feet, and subsequently a decrease in pastosity. The occurrence of this condition was regarded as an effect of the therapy. Since December 2020, over the course of several weeks, positive

dynamics of edema have been noted, as well as a decrease in the intensity of jaundice, and an improvement in overall well-being. PET-CT was performed in March 2021. Compared with PET-CT from October 2020, pronounced positive dynamics were observed in the form of resorption of all previously determined changes in the lymph nodes, lacrimal glands, pancreas, liver, kidneys, prostate gland, seminal vesicles, and resolution of pericardial effusion. In March 2021, he was hospitalized at the Research Institute of Rheumatology for the planned administration of rituximab 500 mg, pulse therapy with methylprednisolone 250 mg followed by methylprednisolone 1 mg/day, a change in hypoglycemic therapy - a reduction in insulin doses - Glargine 7 U 1 r/day, Actrapid 5 U 2 times a day, and in December 2021 he was hospitalized again for the planned administration of rituximab 500 mg. DM therapy was changed - insulin was canceled and Ipragliflozin 50 mg/day was prescribed. Currently, therapy with long-acting metformin 500 mg/day is being carried out with full achievement of individual glycemic targets. The choice of glucose-lowering therapy was made based on the severity of the patient's condition, and subsequently, at the outpatient stage, based on the indicators of carbohydrate metabolism and medications available for obtaining. Subsequently, Glimepiride 4 mg/day, Linagliptin 5 mg/day were used as antidiabetic therapy in October 2020; in December 2020, the dose of methylprednisolone was reduced to 12 mg.

CONCLUSION. Diabetes developing against the background of IgG4-D3 can be caused by both damage to the endocrine part of the pancreas and the use of corticosteroids. In both cases, the use of genetic engineering biological therapy with rituximab may be accompanied by an improvement in carbohydrate metabolism, either due to a reduction in the dose of GCS, or against the background of regression of pancreatitis. Features of the course of diabetes in patients with IgG4-CD require further study with the study of larger samples of patients.

References

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбилов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-

- 191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
 5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
 6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
 7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
 8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
 9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
 10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
 11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
 12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
 13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating

- hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensionaldiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
21. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
22. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.

23. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
24. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
25. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li bja. endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *PEDAGOG*.2022;5(5):341-345.
26. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
27. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
28. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
29. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
30. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
31. Negmatova GS, Hakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
32. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
33. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
34. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone

- for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
35. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. HERPETIC MENINGITIS. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
36. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
37. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
38. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
39. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
40. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o`zgarishlar. *So`ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
41. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.
42. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.
43. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):337-340.
44. Daminov AT, Sa`dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):139-142.
45. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O`g`li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(6):408-412.

OLIV TA'LIM TALABALARI O'RTASIDA JISMONIY RIVOJLANISHNI OSHIRISHDA VOLEYBOLNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola oliy ta'lim tizimida talabalar o'rtasida jismoniy rivojlanishni rag'batlantirishda voleybolning ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Dunyo miqyosida mashhur sport turi bo'lgan voleybol ko'plab jismoniy imtiyozlarni taklif etadi, jumladan yurak-qon tomir tizimi, mushaklarning kuchi, chaqqonlik, muvofiqlashtirish va moslashuvchanlik. Voleybolda muntazam ishtirok etish orqali talabalar o'zlarining umumiy salomatligi va farovonligini yaxshilashlari, muvozanatli turmush tarzini shakllantirishlari mumkin. Bundan tashqari, sport ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirni, jamoada ishlashni va etakchilik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi va har tomonlama rivojlanishga hissa qo'shadi. Ushbu maqola voleybolning oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalariga ta'sirini o'rganadi va uning umrbod jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirishdagi rolini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: voleybol, oliy ta'lim, jismoniy rivojlanish, yurak-qon tomir sog'ligi, mushaklarning kuchi, epcillik, muvofiqlashtirish, moslashuvchanlik, ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, jamoada ishlash, yetakchilik qobiliyatlari.

ROLE OF VOLLEYBALL IN INCREASING PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AMONG STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the importance of volleyball in promoting physical development among students in higher education. A globally popular sport, volleyball offers many physical benefits, including cardiovascular, muscular strength, agility, coordination and flexibility. By regularly participating in volleyball, students can improve their overall health and well-being, and build a balanced lifestyle. In addition, sports develop social interaction, teamwork and leadership skills and contribute to all-round development. This article examines the impact of volleyball on college students and highlights its role in lifelong fitness.

Key words: volleyball, higher education, physical development, cardiovascular health, muscular strength, agility, coordination, flexibility, social interaction, teamwork, leadership skills.

Kirish. Jismoniy faollik shaxsning umumiy rivojlanishida, ayniqsa oliy ta'limning shakllanish yillarida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Sport va ko'ngilochar mashg'ulotlar bilan shug'ullanish nafaqat jismoniy tayyorgarlikni yaxshilaydi, balki ijtimoiy muloqot va shaxsiy o'sishni ham rag'batlantiradi. Turli sport turlari orasida voleybol o'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishini rag'batlantirish uchun ajoyib tanlov sifatida ajralib turadi.

1. Kardiovaskulyar Fitness

Voleybolda muntazam ishtirok etish doimiy harakatni talab qiladi, bu yurak-qon tomir salomatligini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi. Sakrash, sho'ng'in va tez yo'nalishni o'zgartirish kombinatsiyasi yurak tezligini oshiradi va shu bilan chidamlilik va chidamlilikni oshiradi. Voleybol bilan doimiy shug'ullanish orqali talabalar mustahkam yurak-qon tomir tizimini rivojlantiradilar, bu esa keyingi hayotda yurak bilan bog'liq kasalliklar xavfini kamaytiradi.

2. Mushaklar kuchi va chidamliligi

Voleybol yuqori va pastki tananing mushaklarini, jumladan qo'llar, elkalar, oyoqlar va yadrolarni tez-tez ishlatishni o'z ichiga oladi. Spiking, blokirovka va sho'ng'in kuch va quvvatni talab qiladi, bu esa ozg'in mushak massasining rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Bundan tashqari, o'yin davomida harakatlarning takroriy tabiati mushaklarning chidamliligini oshiradi, bu esa o'quvchilarga o'yinlar va mashg'ulotlar davomida optimal ishlash imkonini beradi.

3. Chaqqonlik va muvofiqlashtirish

Voleybolning dinamik tabiati tezkor reaksiyalar va aniq harakatlarni talab qiladi. O'yinchilar to'pning traektoriyasini oldindan bilishlari, o'z pozitsiyalarini mos ravishda o'zgartirishlari va turli xil ko'nikmalarni mohirlik bilan bajarishlari kerak. Bunday talablar chaqqonlik, muvofiqlashtirish va fazoviy ongni kuchaytiradi, motorni boshqarish va sezgirlikni yaxshilaydi.

4. Moslashuvchanlik

Voleybol to'pini qabul qilish, uzatish ko'nikmalarni bajarish uchun keng ko'lamlil harakatni talab qiladi. Sport bilan shug'ullanadigan muntazam cho'zilish mashqlari va dinamik harakatlar moslashuvchanlik va bo'g'imlarning harakatchanligini yaxshilaydi, jarohatlar xavfini kamaytiradi. Kengaytirilgan moslashuvchanlik, shuningdek, umumiy jismoniy sifatlar va boshqa jismoniy faoliyatda ishlashni yaxshilaydi.

5. Ijtimoiy hamkorlik va jamoaviy ish

Voleybolda ishtirok etish o'quvchilar o'rtasida do'stlik va jamoaviy hamkorlikni rivojlantiradi. Strategiyalash, muloqot qilish va o'yin rejalarini amalga oshirish uchun jamoadoshlar bilan hamkorlik qilish qimmatli shaxslararo

ko'nikmalarni singdiradi. Bundan tashqari, jamoaviy sportning qo'llab-quvvatlovchi muhiti o'zaro hurmat, hamdardlik va hamkorlikni rivojlantiradi va akademik hamjamiyatda ijobiy ijtimoiy muhitga hissa qo'shadi.

6. Yetakchilik mahorati

Voleybol o'quvchilarga maydonda ham, maydon tashqarisida ham yetakchilik fazilatlarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatini beradi. Sardorlar va jamoa rahbarlari qaror qabul qilish, jamoadoshlarini rag'batlantirish va hamjihatlikni rivojlantirish kabi rollarni o'z zimmalariga oladilar. Bunday tajribalar o'quvchilarni turli sohalarda kelajakdagi yetakchilik rollariga tayyorlab, ishonch, chidamlilik va mas'uliyatni rivojlantiradi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, voleybol oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalari o'rtasida jismoniy rivojlanish va yaxlit farovonlikni oshirish uchun samarali vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Sport yurak-qon tomir tizimini, mushaklar kuchini, chaqqonlikni, muvofiqlashtirishni va moslashuvchanlikni yaxshilaydigan keng qamrovli mashqlarni taklif qiladi. Bundan tashqari, voleybol ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sirni, jamoaviy ish va etakchilik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi va umumiy kollej tajribasini oshiradi. Voleybolni talabalar shaharchasidagi dam olish dasturlari va maktabdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarga kiritish orqali ta'lim muassasalari talabalarga faol, sog'lom turmush tarzini olib borish va muhim hayotiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish imkonini beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati

1. Faigenbaum, A. D., & Myer, G. D. (2010). Resistance training among young athletes: safety, efficacy and injury prevention effects. *British journal of sports medicine*, 44(1), 56-63.
2. Federation Internationale de Volleyball. (n.d.). Volleyball: A sport for all.
3. Silva, A. S., Da Silva, P. H., Oliveira, J. M., & de Almeida, F. N. (2019). Agility in volleyball athletes. *Journal of Physical Education*, 30, e3013.
4. Tan, J. C., & Lam, W. K. (2017). Effects of flexibility training on eccentric exercise-induced muscle damage in the hamstring of female volleyball players. *Hong Kong Physiotherapy Journal*, 37(2), 85-91.
5. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Sport seksiyasi mashg'ulotlarini mazmuni, tashkillash va o'tkazish metodikasi. *Scientific Impulse*, 2(15), 312-316.
6. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Voleybolchilarning ruhiy tayyorgarliklari. *Scientific Impulse*, 2(15), 323-327.
7. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Voleybol sport musobaqalariga tayyorlash va qatnashish, musobaqa turlari. *Scientific Impulse*, 2(15), 317-322.
8. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Umumta'lim maktabi dasturlarida sport o'yinlari. *Научный Фокус*, 1(9), 285-289.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
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9. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida yosh voleybolchilarni tayyorlash jarayoni. Научный Фокус, 1(9), 290-295.
10. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida yosh voleybolchilarda jismoniy va maxsus ish qobiliyatlarining tasnifi. Научный Фокус, 1(9), 280-284.
11. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida voleybol seksiyasining maqsad va vazifalari. Pedagog, 7(2), 122-127.
12. qizi Po'latova, S. I. (2023). Voleybolchilar tayyorlash jarayonini boshqarish. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 46-50.
13. qizi Po'latova, S. I. (2023). Voleybol o'yinini o'rgatishning pedagogik asoslari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 174-178.
14. Po'latova, S. (2023, November). Kasb-hunar maktablarida voleybol seksiyasi ishini rejalashtirish. In Conference on Digital Innovation: "Modern Problems and Solutions".
15. Po'latova, S. (2023, November). Bo'lg'usi mutaxassis-kadrlarni tayyorlashning dolzarb masalalari. In Conference on Digital Innovation: "Modern Problems and Solutions".

11-12 YOSHLI O'QUVCHI QIZLAR UCHUN VOLEYBOLNING FIZIOLOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK FOYDALI XUSUSIYATLARI

Sulaymonov Jaxongir Solijonovich

O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti Farg'ona filiali Sport o'yinlari nazariyasi va uslubiyati kafedrsi assistent o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Voleybol o'ynash 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlarning tanasi va ongiga katta ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Yurak-qon tomir sog'lig'ini, tayanch-harakat tizimini mustahkamlash, suyak zichligi va psixologik farovonlikni mustahkamlash orqali voleybol o'smir qizlar uchun jismoniy faoliyatga yaxlit yondashuvni taklif etadi. O'qituvchilar, ota-onalar va siyosatchilar sog'lom va baxtli avlodni tarbiyalash uchun qizlarni voleybol kabi sport turlariga jalb etish muhimligini tan olishlari kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: ota-onalar, voleybol, jismoniy faollik, o'quvchi qizlar, o'smirlik, sog'likka foyda, o'qituvchilar, sog'lom va baxtli, avlod, tarbiyalash.

PHYSIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL BENEFITS OF VOLLEYBALL FOR SCHOOLGIRLS AGED 11-12 YEARS.

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Abstract: Playing volleyball can have a great positive effect on the body and mind of 11-12-year-old schoolgirls. By promoting cardiovascular health, musculoskeletal health, bone density, and psychological well-being, volleyball offers a holistic approach to physical activity for teenage girls. Educators, parents and policy makers need to recognize the importance of getting girls involved in sports like volleyball to raise a healthy and happy generation.

Key words: parents, volleyball, physical activity, schoolgirls, adolescence, health benefits, teachers, healthy and happy, generation, parenting.

Kirish

Muntazam jismoniy faollik maktab yoshidagi bolalarning jismoniy va ruhiy salomatligini mustahkamlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Biroq, ko'plab qizlar o'g'il bolalarga qaraganda kamroq jismoniy faoliyat bilan shug'ullanishadi, bu esa keyinchalik hayotda potentsial salomatlik nomutanosibligiga olib keladi. Dinamik

jamoaviy sport turi bo'lgan voleybol 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlarning faolligi uchun qiziqarli va samarali usulni taklif etadi. Ushbu maqola voleybolning ushbu yosh guruhidagi qizlarning tanasi va ongiga ijobiy ta'sirini o'rganishga qaratilgan.

Umuman olganda, voleybol 11-12 yoshli maktab o'quvchilarining jismoniy va ruhiy rivojlanishiga yaxlit yondashuvni ta'minlaydi, sog'lom va faol turmush tarzini targ'ib qiladi, shuningdek, qimmatli hayotiy ko'nikmalarni beradi.

Yurak-qon tomir salomatligi: Voleybol bilan shug'ullanish yurak-qon tomir tizimini yaxshilashga yordam beradigan yugurish, sakrash va sho'ng'in kabi doimiy harakatni talab qiladi. Voleybol bilan muntazam shug'ullanish yurak va o'pka faoliyatini yaxshilaydi, keyingi hayotda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytiradi. Bundan tashqari, voleybolning intervalgacha tabiati, yuqori intensiv mashg'ulotlardan so'ng qisqa dam olish intervallari bilan yurak-qon tomir chidamliligi va samaradorligini oshiradi.

Muskul-skelet tizimining kuchi: Voleybol turli mushak guruhlarini, jumladan, oyoqlar, yadro, qo'llar va elkarni o'z ichiga oladi va bu umumiy mushak-skelet tizimining kuchiga hissa qo'shadi. To'pni to'sish yoki to'sish uchun sakrash tananing pastki kuchini oshiradi, tepadan o'tish va xizmat ko'rsatish esa tananing yuqori mushaklarini rivojlantiradi. Bundan tashqari, voleybolda zarur bo'lgan yo'nalishning tez o'zgarishi va tez reflekslar chaqqonlik va muvofiqlashtirishni kuchaytiradi, bu esa umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlikni yaxshilaydi.

Suyak salomatligi: O'smirlik suyak rivojlanishi uchun juda muhim davr bo'lib, voleybol kabi og'irlikni ko'taruvchi mashg'ulotlarda qatnashish suyak salomatligiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Voleybol mashqlari va o'yinlari paytida sakrash va qo'nishning takroriy ta'siri suyaklarning o'sishi va zichligini rag'batlantiradi, keyinchalik hayotda osteoporoz xavfini kamaytiradi. Muntazam voleybol mashg'ulotlari bilan shug'ullanadigan maktab o'quvchilarining suyaklari kuchliroq bo'ladi, bu tez o'sish va rivojlanishning ushbu bosqichida ayniqsa muhimdir.

Psixologik farovonlik: Jismoniy salomatlikdan tashqari, voleybol 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlar uchun ko'plab psixologik afzalliklarni taklif etadi. Voleybol kabi jamoaviy sport turlari ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, hamkorlik va muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi, o'yinchilar o'rtasida tegishlilik va do'stlik tuyg'usini rivojlantiradi. Qolaversa, voleybolning raqobatbardoshligi shaxsning rivojlanishi uchun qimmatli bo'lgan chidamlilik, qat'iyat, sport mahorati kabi fazilatlarni singdiradi. Voleybol bilan muntazam shug'ullanish, shuningdek, stress va

tashvishlarni kamaytirishga yordam beradi, maktab o'quvchilarining umumiy ruhiy farovonligini oshiradi.

Fiziologik foydalari

Yurak-qon ishlab chiqaradi: Voleybol doimiy harakat, sakrash va tez yugurishni o'z ichiga oladi, bu yurak-qon ishlab chiqarishligi va yurak sog'lig'ini yaxshilaydi.

Mushaklar rivojlanishi: Voleybol o'ynashni turli mushaklarni davolash, shu va hokazolarni yo'qotishlar, muntazamning kuchini va ishlashini o'ziga olib kelishi mumkin.

Suyakning mustahkamligi: Voleybolning og'irlikni ko'taruvchi tabiati, ayniqsa sakrash va qo'nish, suyaklarning rivojlanishi va zichligiga yordam beradi.

Muvofiqlashtirish va tozalash: Voleybol qo'llar va tanani o'rtada aniqlashtirish talab qiladi. Ush ko'rinishini mashq qilish uchun ishlatish mumkin bo'lgan tozalash va tozalash mumkin.

Moslashuvchanlik: Voleybolda sho'ng'in, blokirovka va to'p bilan muomala qilish kabi dinamik harakat bo'g'inlar va harakat doirasini rag'batlantiradi.

Og'irlikni boshqarish: Voleybol muntazam jismoniy faollik sog'lom vazni saqlashga yordam beradi, semirishni va u bilan bog'liq sog'liq muammolarini nazorat qiladi.

Psixologik foydalari

Jamoaviy ish: Voleybol o'yinchilar o'rtasida hamkorlik, muloqot va o'zaro yordamni rag'batlantiradigan jamoaviy sport turidir. Bu qizlarga jamoada ishlashning ko'rishni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi va tuyg'usini rivojlantirish.

O'z-o'ziga ishonch: Voleybol mahoratini egallash va jamoao muvaffaqiyatiga yosh qizlarda o'ziga bo'lgan hurmat va ishonchni qo'shish.

Intizom va diqqat: Voleybol texnikani samarali ishlash uchun konsentratsiya va intizomni talab qiladi. Muntazam amaliyot diqqatni jamlash va intizomni yaxshilash mumkin, bu esa hayotning sohalariga, masalan, akademiklarga boshqa mumkin.

Stressni bartaraf etish: Jismoniy faollik, shu narsa voleybol o'ynash stressni kuchaytirishgan va kayfiyatni yaxshilaydigan endorfinlarni hosil qiladi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, jismoniy faollik, ayniqsa, o'smirlik davridagi bolalarning umumiy farovonligi uchun juda muhimdir. Ommaviy jamoaviy sport turi bo'lgan voleybol 11-12 yoshli o'quvchi qizlar uchun ko'plab

fiziologik va psixologik imtiyozlarni beradi. Ushbu ilmiy maqolada voleybol o'ynashning organizmga ijobiy ta'siri, jumladan, yurak-qon tomir tizimi, mushak-skelet tizimining mustahkamligi, muvofiqlashtirish va ruhiy farovonlik yaxshilanishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu imtiyozlarni tushunish o'qituvchilar, ot-onalar va siyosatchilarni maktab yoshidagi qizlar o'rtasida voleybol va shunga o'xshash jismoniy mashg'ulotlarni ommalashtirish muhimligi haqida xabardor qilishi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati

1. Faigenbaum, A. D., Myer, G. D., & Lloyd, R. S. (2013). Youth resistance training: updated position statement paper from the national strength and conditioning association. *Journal of strength and conditioning research*, 23(5), S60-S79.
2. Lloyd, R. S., Faigenbaum, A. D., Stone, M. H., Oliver, J. L., Jeffreys, I., Moody, J. A., ... & Myer, G. D. (2014). Position statement on youth resistance training: the 2014 international consensus. *British journal of sports medicine*, 48(7), 498-505.
3. Malina, R. M., & Bouchard, C. (2014). *Growth, maturation, and physical activity* (2nd ed.). Human Kinetics.
4. Toftegaard-Støckel, J., Nielsen, G. A., & Ibsen, B. (2011). Health outcomes of youth soccer players: a systematic review. *Sports Medicine*, 41(12), 1033-1053.
5. Karimova, G. (2022). Bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining innovatsion faoliyatini tashkil qilish zaruriyati va omillari. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1238-1243.
6. Каримова, Г. (2022). Шахмат-мактабўқувчилари интеллектуал ривожланишининг воситаси сифатида. *Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 343-346.
7. Ikromjon, Y., & Shaxnoza, P. L. (2022, November). Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchisi kasbining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va talablari. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 67-78).
8. qizi Po'latova, S. I. (2023). Voleybolchilar tayyorlash jarayonini boshqarish. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(12), 46-50.
9. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda to'pni uzatish texnikasi. *Pedagog*, 6(11), 14-18.
10. Solijonovich, S. J., & Xasanov, A. T. (2023). Kasb-hunar maktabida voleybol sektsiyasi ishini tashkillash samaradorligi. *O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali*, 2(15), 117-122.
11. Abduraxmonov, S. (2023). Gandbolchilarning sport tayyorgarligi tizimi. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(10), 195-197.
12. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda hujum qilish texnikasi. *Научный Фокус*, 1(7), 570-574.
13. Сулейманов, Д. С., & Гайратжан, У. Р. С. (2023). Гигиенические основы питания волейболистов. *O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali*, 2(23), 42-48.

14. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Professional ta'lim muassasalarida voleybol bo'yicha sport seksiyalarini tashkil etish metodikasini takomillashtirish.(Yosh voleybolchilarda jismoniy va maxsus ish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion metodlari asosida). Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(17), 63-66.
15. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida voleybol seksiyasining maqsad va vazifalari. Pedagog, 7(2), 122-127.
16. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida yosh voleybolchilarda jismoniy va maxsus ish qobiliyatlarining tasnifi. Научный Фокус, 1(9), 280-284.
17. Xasanov, A. T., & Anvarov, D. M. (2023). Yosh suzuvchilarda chidamlilikni rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali, 2(18), 1283-1289.
18. Mirzatiillo o'g'li, A. D. (2024). Kroll usulida ko'krakda suzish. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(17), 400-402.
19. NI Latipova. "Talabalar ijtimoiy tashabbuskorligini rivojlantirishda ta'lim muassasasining ijtimoiy-madaniy muhiti rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari". Scholar 1 (28), 20-24.

TURLI TIKUV MASHINALARIDA CHOKLASHDA PARALLEL SAKROVCHI IGNALARNING MATEMATIK MODELI

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Annotatsiya: Taklif etilayotgan tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida, trikotaj matolaridan tayyorlangan erkaklar vetrovkasi, bolalar polo ko'ylagi, hamda, futbolka mahsulotlarni tikish va choklashda, elastikli xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan materiallarni choklari sifatli mustahkam bo'lishida, parallel sakrovchi ignalarning roli katta ahamiyatga egadir.

Bunday parallel ignali tikuv mashinalarini tadbiq etish natijasida respublikamizda import o'rnini bosa oladigan arzon va raqobatbardosh trikotaj matolardan tayyorlangan maxsulot ishlab chiqarish bilan bir vaqtda tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida, foydalanish imkoniyati tikuv texnologiyalariga yangi qadam bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: integral-differensial, fizik-matematik model, parallel ignalar, tikuv mashinasi, tayyor mato

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF PARALLEL JUMPING NEEDLES IN SEWING MACHINES

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Abstract: In the proposed sewing-knitting industry, in the sewing and stitching of men's windbreakers, children's polo shirts, and t-shirts made of knitted fabrics, the role of parallel knitting needles is of great importance in the quality and durability of seams of materials with high elastic properties. .

As a result of the implementation of such parallel needle sewing machines, the possibility of using them in the sewing-knitting industry will be a new step in sewing technologies, along with the production of products made of cheap and competitive knitted fabrics that can replace imports in our republic.

Key words: integral-differential, physical-mathematical model, parallel needles, sewing machine, finished fabric

Kirish. Elastikli xususiyati yuqori bo‘lgan materiallarni tikishda sifatli tikilish va nuqsonsiz choklash uchun mavjud mashinaning vaqt birligida harakat mexanizimini konstruksiyasini takomillashtirish orqali ham erishish mumkin. Mavjud mashinada parallel ignalar oyoqning ko‘tarish balandligi 5-13 mm gacha, tikuv uzunligi 5 mm, parallel ignalar soni bitta, iplar soni ikkita bo‘lib. avtomatik ravishda ishlaydi.

Buning uchun tajriba o‘tkazish maqsadida Jack A4 B-C tikuv mashinasining tezligi 6000 rpm, ignalar orasidagi masofa 5,6 (6,4) mm, tikuv uzunligi 4,4 mm, oyoq ko‘tarish 5 mm. Joylashtiruvchi o‘rnatilgan doimiy servomotor, doimiy o‘zgaruvchan tezlikni boshqarish qulay bo‘lib, mexanik tikuv mashinasi tashqi va yashirin, ichki shikastlanishlarsiz har qanday matolarni tikish va choklash eng yaxshi va sifatli sanoat tikuv mashinasi tanlab olindi. (1-rasmga qarang)

Tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida parallel sakrovchi ignalarning choklashdagi nuqsonli bo‘lish yoki bo‘lmaslik muammosini xal qilishning asosiy manbasi raqobatbardosh zamonaviy matematik usullar hamda kompyuter texnologiyalardan foydalanishdir. Yangi texnologiyalarni qo‘llash natijasida jahon bozorida yuqori sifatli, raqobatbardosh mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish tikuv-trikotaj sanoatining eng muhim vazifasidir [1].

1-rasm. JACK A4 B-C tikuv mashinasi mexanizimning ichki sxemasi

1. Mashinani harakatga keltiruvchi mexanizim bosh valik. Harakat yo‘nalishi.

2. Ilgarilanma harakat va moki iplarini harakatga keltiruvchi konussimon silindr mexanizimi.

3. Tikuv mashinasi harakatida choklashni amalga oshiruvchi parallel ignalarning sakrash mexanizimi.

4. Trikotaj matolarning choklashdagi ilgarilanma harakat mexanizimi. Harakat yo'nalishi.

Tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida parallel sakrovchi ignalarning choklashdagi nuqsonli bo'lish yoki bo'lmaslik muammosini xal qilishning asosiy manbasi raqobatbardosh zamonaviy matematik usullar hamda kompyuter texnologiyalardan foydalanishdir. Yangi texnologiyalarni qo'llash natijasida jahon bozorida yuqori sifatli, raqobatbardosh mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish tikuv-trikotaj sanoatining eng muhim vazifasidir [1].

Shuningdek tikuv mashinasi bosh valigidagi aylanma harakat kuch ta'sirida paralel harakatlanayotgan ignalarni sakrashini moddiy nuqta deb olib, uning differensial tenglamasini integralasak. F kuchi ta'sirida harakatlanuvchi m massali ignaning moddiy nuqta uchun koordinata ko'rinishidagi nuqtaning harakat tenglamalarini aniqlaymiz. Tuzilgan fizik-matematik modellar yechimlaridan foydalanib choklash grafiklarini tasvirlanadi.

Bu yerda bizga ma'lumki F kuch vaqtga bog'liq, kuch nuqtaning fazodagi ignalarning holatiga bog'liq, kuch nuqtaning tezligiga ya'ni materiallarni choklashda ignalardan qoladigan teshikchalar harakatiga bog'liq.

Massasi m bo'lgan ignalar majburiy kuch ta'siri ostida T vaqt birligidagi harakatini quyidagi vector kuch formula bilan ifodalasak.

$$\vec{F} = \bar{i}b_1 \cos \alpha t + \bar{j}b_2 v_y + \bar{k}b_3 z \quad (1)$$

Bu erda b_1, b_2, b_3 boshlang'ich holatdagi ba'zi doimiy koeffitsientlar

$$x_0 = 0, y_0 = 0, z_0 \neq 0,$$

$$v_{x_0} = 0, v_{y_0} \neq 0, v_{z_0} = 0$$

Nuqtaning harakat tenglamalarini koordinata shaklida aniqlash kerak bo'ladi.

Buning uchun dekart koordinatalar o'qlariga T vaqt birligida sakrovchi ignalar qoldirgan eskizlarini proyeksiyasi, shu nuqtalar uchun differensial tenglamalar sistemasi tuzamiz

$$\begin{cases} m \frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} = a_1 \cos \alpha t \\ m \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} = a_2 v_y \\ m \frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} = a_3 z \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

(2) differensial tenglamalar sistemaning birinchi tenglamasini ikkita birinchi tartibli tenglama sifatida ifodalansa quyidagi (3) tenglama kelib chiqadi

$$\begin{cases} m \frac{dv_x}{dt} = a_1 \cos \alpha t \\ \frac{dx}{dt} = v_x \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

(3) tenglamalar sistemasidagi birinchi tenglama ikkita o'zgaruvchili tenglama bo'lgani uchun tezlikning x o'qiga va T vaqtga proyeksiyasi bo'yicha o'zgaruvchilarni ajratib olamiz. Ya'ni

$$mdv_x = a_1 \cos \alpha t dt \quad (4)$$

(4) tenglamani integrallab yuboramiz va (5) tenglama hosil qilamiz.

$$\int mdv_x = \int a_1 \cos \alpha t dt \quad (5)$$

$$v_x = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha t + C_1 \quad (6)$$

(3) differensial tenglamalar sistemasidan ikkinchi tenglamasini o'ng tomonidagi ifodaga (6) tenglamani o'ng tomonini tenglab X o'qiga proyeksiyasining vaqtga bog'liqliq. Tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha t + C_1 \quad (7)$$

(7) tenglamani o'zgaruvchilarini ajratib integrallab yuborsak natijada tenglamani yechimini aniqlaymiz

$$dx = \left(\frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha t + C_1 \right) dt \Rightarrow X = -\frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2} \cos \alpha t + C_1 t + C_2 \quad (8)$$

C_1 va C_2 o'zgaruvchilarni dastlabki shartlar asosida aniqlaymiz. (8) ifodaga X o'qi koordinatasining $t=0$ qiymatini qo'yib, C_2 ni hisoblaymiz.

$$0 = -\frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2} \cos \alpha 0 + C_1 0 + C_2 \quad \text{bundan} \quad C_2 = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha^2}$$

C_1 ni $t=0$ dagi v_x (6) tenglamadan aniqlaymiz $0 = \frac{a_1}{m\alpha} \sin \alpha 0 + C_1$

demak, $C_1 = 0$. Shunday qilib, (2) tenglamalar sistemaning birinchi

tenglamasining yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega $x = -\frac{a_1}{ma^2} \cos \alpha t + \frac{a_1}{ma^2}$

(2) tenglamalar sistemaning ikkinchi tenglamasi ham ikkita tenglama shaklida ifodalandi

$$\begin{cases} m \frac{dv_y}{dt} = a_2 v_y \\ \frac{dy}{dt} = v_y \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Birinchi tenglamadagi o'zgaruvchilarni ajratib, integrallab yuboramiz.

$$m \frac{dv_y}{dt} = a_2 v_y \Rightarrow \ln v_y = \frac{a_2}{m} t + \ln C_3 \text{ bundan } v_y \text{ ni topamiz}$$

(9) tenglamaning ikkinchi tengligini o'ng tomoniga olib borib qo'yamiz

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = C_3 e^{\frac{a_2 t}{m}}$$

tenglamani o'zgaruvchilarini ajratib, integrallab yuborsak

$$y = C_3 \frac{m}{a_2} e^{\frac{a_2 t}{m}} + c_4 \quad y = c_1 e^x + c_2 e^{-x} + c_3 \cos kx + c_4 \sin nx$$

yechimga ega bo'lamiz. C_3 va C_4 o'zgaruvchilarni dastlabki shartlar bilan aniqlanadi.

Yuqoridagi differensial tenglamalar sistemasining yechimlarini, bigalikda tasvirini matkad, geogebra ta'minot dasturi yordamida ko'rilsa ignalarni sakrashi natijasida quyidagi grafiklar hosil qilinadi.

$K=n=6$ $c_1=c_2=0$ $C_3=1, C_4=1$ Silindirsimon valni aylanish tezligi 3000 ayl/daq bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrashidan hosil bo'lgan orqa tomon chok grafigi ko'rinishi. Sakrash oralig'i 6-6.5 mm ga teng. Tasvirdan shuni ko'rish mumkinki choklar orasidagi masofa qisman uzoqlashi nuqsonsi lekin chok mustahkamligi yuqori emas. Elastiklik xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan mato uchun bunday choklash matoni tirishib qolish imkoniyatini beradi

$K=4.4$, $n=4.4$ $C_1=C_2=0$, $C_3=C_4=1$ silindirsimon valni aylanish tezligi 3000 ayl/daq bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrashidan hosil bo'lgan orqa tomon choki grafik ko'rinishi. Sakrash oralig'i 2-2.5 mm ga teng. Tasvirdan shuni ko'rish mumkinki dastlabki harakatdagi choklashda nuqson bilan boshlansada, tikuvning qolgan qismida choklar orasidagi masofa qisqa nuqsonsiz chok mustahkamligi yuqori. Elastiklik xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan mato uchun bunday choklash matoni tirishib qolishga imkoniyat beramadi. Chok tekis va chiroyli ko'rinishga ega.

$K=n=5$ $c_1=c_2=0$, $C_3=C_4=1$ Silindirsimon valni aylanish tezligi 3000 ayl/daq bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrashidan hosil bo'lgan orqa tomon chok grafigi ko'rinishi sakrash oralig'i 4-4.5 mm ga teng. Tasvirdan shuni ko'rish mumkinki choklar orasidagi masofa o'rtacha nuqsonsiz chok mustahkamligi yuqori. Elastiklik xususiyati yuqori bo'lgan mato uchun bunday choklash matoni tirishib qolishga imkoniyat beramadi. Chok tekis va chiroyli ko'rinishga ega.

Xulosa.

Tikuv vaqtida bosh silindirsimon valning aylanishi tezligi 4000 ayl/daq va undan yuqori bo'lganda paralel ignalarning sakrash oralig'i 2-2.5mm, 4-4.5mm, 5-5.5 mm bo'lganda silindrsimon valning tezligi hisobiga ilgarilanma vektorial harakat tezlashadi. Natijada tikuv mashinasida choklangan trikotaj matoning choklarida nuqsonlar soni ortib iplarning uzulishlari ortib boradi. Bu esa tikuv mashinasida choklangan matolarning nuqsonini ortishi bilan sifatsiz choklar nuqsonli bo'lishiga olib keladi.

Adabiyotlar

1. N.T.Ismailov*, A.Rakhmonov. Deformation of reinforced yarn Technical science and innovation. 2023. Special edition.pp.94-99.
2. Хомяков Е.С. Теория кручения и деформации текстильной пряжи послыной структуры/ Е.С.Хомяков, А.К. Наумов//Изв. вузов. Технология текстильной промышленности: Иваново, ИГТА, № 4 (340), – 2012. – с. 64–67.

3. И.И.Мигушов.Механика текстильной нити и ткани.М.Легкая индустрия 1980 г. С.130-137.
4. Исмаилов Н.Т., Ҳ Т Бобожонов. Выбор параметров крутки армированной пряжи// Универсум: Технические науки: электрон. научн. журн. Сентябрь 2022. № 9 (102). г. Москва. с 29-32.
5. Dissertatsiya N. T. Ismailov “Chirmoviqsimon ip ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasi” Namangan 2023 yil
6. Исмаилов Н.Т. Математический модел расчета деформационных протсессов технологии текстильных оболочек "Экономика и сотсиум" №10(77) 2020. с. 508-517.
7. Tursunova, X.Sh., Mamatqulova Saida Rahmatovna. (2020). Ayollar paltosi uchun gazlamalar taxlili. 3 rd international congress of the human and social science researches (itobiad).
8. Raxmatovna.M.S.(2022). Analysis of women’s clothes sewing-a study to develop a norm of time spent on the technological process of knitting production. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research.2(03).16-21.
9. Raxmatovna.M.S.(2022).Research on the development of norms of time spend on the technological process of sewing and knitting production; basic raw materials, their composition and properties.Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal, 3(03), 28-32. ISSN:2776-0987, Volume3, Issue5,May,2022.7
10. Raxmatovna.M.S.(2021).The description of perspective fashion trends in men’s clothing.Innovative Technological:Methodical Research Journal,2(10),15-20.

TUMORS OF THE FEMALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM DURING DIABETES MELLITUS

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Relevance. *The article discusses various pathophysiological conditions and processes leading to the development of tumor diseases in diabetes mellitus. These include obesity, hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, inflammation, and oxidative stress. Data from epidemiological studies are presented in which it was found that diabetes mellitus (both type 1 and type 2) increases the relative risk of developing tumors of the female reproductive system, such as ovarian and endometrial cancer, while for cervical cancer, vaginal cancer and vulvar cancer, such a relationship has not been clearly identified.*

Keywords: *diabetes; endometrial tumors; ovarian tumors; signaling pathways; neoplasm proteins.*

ОПУХОЛИ ЖЕНСКОЙ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ САХАРНОМ ДИАБЕТЕ

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Актуальность. В статье рассматриваются различные патофизиологические состояния и процессы, приводящие к развитию опухолевых заболеваний при сахарном диабете. К ним относятся ожирение, гипергликемия, гиперинсулинемия, воспаление и окислительный стресс. Представлены данные эпидемиологических исследований, в которых установлено, что сахарный диабет (как 1-го, так и 2-го типа) повышает относительный риск развития опухолей женской репродуктивной системы, таких как рак яичников и эндометрия, тогда как при раке шейки матки, раке влагалища и при раке вульвы такая взаимосвязь четко не выявлена.

Ключевые слова: диабет; опухоли эндометрия; опухоли яичников; сигнальные пути; белки новообразований.

Introduction. The assumption that there is a relationship between diabetes mellitus (DM) and malignant neoplasms was made more than 100 years ago [1]. The risk of developing cancer increases with both type 1 (DM1) and type 2 (DM2) diabetes [2]. Among all causes of death in patients with diabetes, cancer ranks second after cardiovascular diseases [3]. It should also be noted that approximately 8–18% of cancer patients suffer from diabetes [4]. Meta-analyses and large population-based studies have shown that diabetes is associated with an increased risk of mortality in cancer [5]. However, the underlying mechanisms of

the relationship between different types of diabetes and cancer (especially tumors of the female reproductive system) have not been summarized in detail. This review analyzes this relationship and describes the mechanisms of its occurrence.

Materials and methods. This literature review was carried out with the aim of critically assessing the collected material. The authors performed an electronic search for publications in the PubMed, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases. The search terms included the words “diabetes mellitus”, “gynecologic cancers”, “ovarian cancer”, “endometrial cancer”, “cervical cancer”, “vaginal cancer” and “vulvar cancer”. The authors independently reviewed those articles whose titles and abstracts were relevant to the search terms. Disagreements between authors regarding eligibility were resolved by consensus. The review included studies published primarily within the last 15 years. Full texts of articles and their abstracts were analyzed.

Epidemiological aspects. The number of people with diabetes continues to increase worldwide, significantly increasing the burden on the healthcare system. According to the latest data, in 2021, the global prevalence of both types of diabetes among adults was 537 million people, and by 2045 it is expected to increase to 783 million people [6]. Diabetes is a fairly common disease among cancer patients, and is a proven risk factor for some solid malignancies, such as pancreatic, liver, colon, kidney, bladder and breast cancer [7]. Epidemiological studies have shown that cancers of the female reproductive system, including endometrial and ovarian (OC) cancer, are more common in people with diabetes. One meta-analysis showed a statistically significant association of T2DM with the risk of endometrial cancer (overall relative risk (RR) 2.10; 95% confidence interval (CI) 1.75–2.53). This meta-analysis also reported an association between T1DM and endometrial cancer (overall RR 3.15; 95% CI 1.07–9.29). In a study by Liu X. et al. provides data demonstrating that patients with T2DM have an increased risk of developing the types of cancer already mentioned above (colon, liver, pancreas, kidney), including endometrial cancer. The authors of the article suggest that the increased risk of developing cancer in patients with diabetes compared to their relatives is associated with various severe metabolic disorders [8]. It should be noted that many studies provide evidence that the incidence of cancer of the ovary, esophagus, endometrium, vulva and vagina, and thyroid gland is higher among women with T1DM.

Pathophysiological conditions and processes leading to the development of oncological diseases in diabetes mellitus

Hyperglycemia. Epidemiological data have shown that hyperglycemia is directly associated with an increased risk of colorectal, liver, gastric, lung and pancreatic cancer [10]. Cells of most types of malignancies predominantly express glucose transporter type 1, which has a high affinity for glucose. It is also worth mentioning the Warburg effect, in which in tumor cells glucose follows the energetically inefficient glycolysis pathway with a high level of lactate production. Increased glycolysis in tumor cells provides the materials necessary for the synthesis of nucleotides, amino acids and lipids [11]. Hyperglycemia stimulates the production of advanced glycation end products (AGEs). AGEs interact with a specific AGE receptor, which leads to activation of the NF- κ B (nuclear factor κ B) signaling pathway and the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cells, thereby accelerating oxidative stress and leading to the activation of pro-inflammatory signaling pathways [10]. It has been demonstrated that AGEs and activation of downstream pathways promote tumor transformation of epithelial cells [12]. For example, hyperglycemia has been shown to stimulate the proliferation of pancreatic cancer cells through induction of epithelial growth factor (EGF) expression and transactivation of its receptor (EGFR) [13]. EGF and its receptor, in turn, play an important role in the pathogenesis of tumors of the female reproductive system, for example, ovarian cancer and cervical cancer (CC) [14]. In addition, hyperglycemia is responsible for DNA damage, which is the first stage of tumorigenesis [15].

Hyperinsulinemia. In T2DM, insulin resistance leads to the development of compensatory hyperinsulinemia. High concentrations of insulin in the blood play a key role in the pathogenesis of malignant neoplasms, which has been demonstrated in numerous studies both in vitro and in vivo [17]. Using endometrial cancer cell culture, it was found that, on the one hand, hyperinsulinemia leads to a slowdown in the process of mesenchymal-epithelial transition (as a consequence, metastasis and tumor invasion) by inhibiting the expression *COL1A1* (gene encoding the α 1 chain of type I collagen), *IRS2* (insulin receptor substrate-1), however, on the other hand, increases the level of expression *AMFR* (Autocrine Motility Factor Receptor), *FAF1* (FAS-associated factor 1), *MPP3* (Membrane Palmitoylated Protein 3), *PIP2* (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-diphosphate), *VEGFA* (vascular endothelial growth factor), as well as genes of other proteins that promote tumor development and progression [18]. It is assumed that the metabolic effects of insulin, which include the transport of

glucose into the cell, are mediated by activation of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway, while the mitogenic effect is exerted on cells through Ras/Raf/MAPK (Rat sarcoma virus/RAF protooncogene serine/threonine-protein kinase/MitogenActivated Protein Kinase) signaling pathway, in this pathway the downstream kinases are MEK (Mitogen-Activated Kinase) and ERK (Extracellular signal-Regulated Kinase). Proinsulin and insulin have similar stimulatory effects on MAPK activation, proliferation and migration of breast cancer cells [19]. It is also necessary to note the importance of insulin-like growth factors (IGFs), which are involved in the development of malignant tumors [20].

Obesity. It is widely known that the majority of patients with prediabetes or T2DM are overweight or obese [23]. In obesity, according to the working group of the International Association for the Study of Cancer, there is an increased risk of developing 13 different neoplasms, including endometrial, esophageal, kidney and pancreatic cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, cancer of the gastric cardia, meningioma; multiple myeloma, colorectal cancer, postmenopausal breast cancer, ovarian, gallbladder and thyroid cancer [24]. An umbrella review of systematic reviews and 204 meta-analyses also found an association between obesity and cancer. This association was especially pronounced for cancer of the gastrointestinal tract and cancer of the female reproductive system [25]. Data from 8 observational studies involving 635,642 patients suggest that bariatric surgery is associated with a reduced risk of all types of cancer (pooled odds ratio (OR) 0.72; 95% CI 0.59–0.87)), as well as obesity-related cancers (pooled OR 0.55; 95% CI 0.31–0.96), including breast cancer (pooled OR 0.50; 95% CI 0.25–0.99) [26].

Inflammation and oxidative stress. Inflammation is one of the key connecting elements between diabetes and cancer. Chronic low-grade inflammation in hypertrophied adipose tissue plays an important role in the pathogenesis of obesity-associated insulin resistance [34]. In turn, chronic inflammation is associated with increased levels of the already mentioned oxidative stress and ROS, which are critical for many processes in cancer development [35]. In addition, due to hyperglycemia, advanced glycation end products and their receptors lead to the development of oxidative stress and increased inflammation, which promotes cell growth, angiogenesis and metastasis [11]. Various studies have identified increased circulating levels of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 (interleukin-1), IL-6 (interleukin-6) and TNF- α (tumor necrosis factor-alpha) in patients with diabetes [36]. TNF- α promotes tumor development by activating NF- κ B and increasing the production of ROS

and reactive nitrogen species, which can cause DNA damage. This cytokine also stimulates the growth, proliferation, invasion and metastasis of tumor cells, as well as angiogenesis [37]. Elevated levels of IL-6 have been found in patients with pancreatic cancer, breast cancer, B-cell lymphoma and myeloma [38].

Conclusion. Tumors of the female reproductive system continue to be a serious problem for both patients and the healthcare system. The article provides a literary analysis to assess the influence of chronic hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, systemic inflammation and oxidative stress, as well as changes in the level of sex hormones observed in diabetes on the formation of tumors of the female reproductive system.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.

11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensialdiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of COVID-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 special):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of deipeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 special):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abdvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.

40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. *I*. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o'zgarishlar. *so'ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Pretibial myxedema: pathogenetic features and clinical aspects. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 special):695-702.
45. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.
46. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda COVID-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.
47. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):337-340.
48. Daminov AT, Sa'dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 Special):139-142.
49. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O'g'li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(6):408-412.
50. Ulugbekovna NP, Bakhtiyorovna RI, Almosovich RA, Takhirovich DA. Thyroid Diseases during Pregnancy and their Impact on Maternal and Fetal Outcomes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):188-190.
51. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Time-restricted nutrition as a new strategy for the therapy of obesity and comorbid conditions. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 Special):660-667.
52. Nilufar R, Adkhamjon K. TO The development of cardiovascular diseases effects of environmental factors. *fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya jurnali | Journal of science, education, culture and innovation*. 2022;1(4):100-101.
53. Xoldorov X, Omonov F, Jumayev I, Daminov AT. TYPE 1 Diabetes as a risk factor for bone health in childhood. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2023;2(8):131-135.

ВОЗРАСТНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ КАРДИРЕСПИРАТОРНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается комплексный подход в изучении возрастных особенностей изменения деятельности систем внешнего дыхания, газообмена и энергетического обмена детей и подростков в условиях жаркого климата Узбекистана при выполнении различных по характеру, объёму и интенсивности мышечных нагрузок.

Ключевые слова: адаптация, функциональная система, газообмен, кислород, мышечная деятельность, гибкость, подвижность.

AGE-RELATED FEATURES OF CHANGES IN THE ACTIVITY OF THE CARDIORESPIRATORY SYSTEM

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Annotation. This article examines a comprehensive approach to the study of age-related characteristics of changes in the activity of external respiration systems, gas exchange and energy metabolism of children and adolescents in the hot climate of Uzbekistan when performing muscle loads of different nature, volume and intensity.

Key words: adaptation, functional system, gas exchange, oxygen, muscular activity, flexibility, mobility.

Темпы изменения размеров тела, функциональных характеристик органов и систем не остаются постоянными на протяжении индивидуального развития организма, а закономерно изменяются(1). Изучение деятельности различных функциональных систем детей и подростков в изменяющихся условиях окружающей среды актуально не только потому, что развивающийся организм ребёнка большой степени подвержен её влиянию, но и потому, что эти воздействия во многом определяют ход его дальнейшего развития. Стрессовые раздражители

внешней среды, в том числе и мышечная работа, изменяют величину и характер приспособительных реакций детского организма.

Продолжают оставаться актуальными широкие и всесторонние исследования возрастных особенностей адаптации организма к условиям, возникающим при выполнении напряжённой мышечной работы, вытеснение путей расширения функциональных возможностей растущего организма и возможного диапазона его тренированности.

Адаптационные возможности организма детей и подростков к воздействиям нескольких жизненно важных систем, действующих по принципу саморегуляции, к числу которых относятся системы газо- и энергетического обмена и дыхания. Дыхание человека связано с физической работоспособностью и отражает общую активность центральной нервной системы, состояние напряжения организма, а максимальный расход воздуха при вдохе и выдохе позволяет косвенно судить о способности дыхательных мышц к интенсивной работе(2). В.И. Сергиевский, Ю.Н. Иванов отличают некоторые особенности внешнего дыхания(3).

Использован комплексный подход в изучении возрастных особенностей изменения деятельности систем внешнего дыхания, газообмене и энергетического обмена детей и подростков в условиях жаркого климата Узбекистана при выполнении различных по характеру, объёму и интенсивности мышечных нагрузок. Интенсивность обмена веществ и энергии связана с возрастом, питанием, мышечной работой и экологическими изменениями во внешней среде(4).

Мы исследовали возрастные особенности физиологического состояния школьников города Куvasая. Регистрированы антропометрические данные, показатели внешнего дыхания и физическая работоспособность у школьников 3-11 класса. Испытуемые были дети проживающих промышленного города Куvasая. Определяли максимальное потребление кислорода, частота дыхания, жизненная ёмкость лёгких и физическая работоспособность с помощью PWC170.

Результаты исследования показали, что частота дыхательных движений у школьников с возрастом уменьшается, ЖЕЛ увеличивается. Максимальное потребление кислорода при выполнении дозированной физической работы у школьников уменьшается после уроков.

Установлено что возрастные изменения показателей энергетического обмена и внешнего дыхания характеризуются последовательным

повышением их абсолютных значений в связи с увеличением длины и массы тела в возрастающей потребности организма в кислороде.

Таблица. Изменение физической работоспособности и максимального потребления кислорода у школьников разного возраста. n=166

ШКОЛЬНИКИ	класс	PWC ₁₇₀ кгм ³ /мин,		МПК мл/мин/кг	
		До уроков	После уроков	До уроков	После уроков
мальчики	11	819	531	48,29	42,36
	8	547	453	57,52	52,60
	3	396	339	69,41	62,15
девочки	11	423	327	35,97	33,98
	8	360	279	48,51	43,72
	3	296	217	65,35	62,48

Данные наших исследований подтвердили мнение о том, что с возрастом и повышением уровня подготовленности происходят закономерные сдвиги в респираторной системе, газообмене и энергетическом обмене, свидетельствующие о повышении их экономичности в условиях относительного покоя и при мышечных напряжениях.

В подростковом возрасте характеризующимся интенсивным развитием мускулатуры и эффективным влиянием на этот процесс физических упражнений, следует рекомендовать постепенное увеличение последних в режиме дня школьников, а также повышение их объёма и интенсивности на уроках физической культуры. Необходимо подчеркнуть, что указанное внедрение физических упражнений в режим дня и повышение двигательной активности должны происходить при обязательном учете возрастно-половых особенностей и уровня подготовленности школьников, а также при систематическом врачебном контроле за состоянием здоровья и степенью воздействия мышечных нагрузок повышенной напряженности.

В ходе исследования выявлены возрастные и половые границы ответных реакций растущего организма на предлагаемые мышечные нагрузки. Установлено направленность изменений этих реакций,

проявляющееся в том, что с возрастом ответные реакции организма детей и подростков на нагрузку одной и той же мощности становятся менее выраженными. Этот факт может расцениваться таким образом, что в процессе роста и развития организма совершенствуются его адаптационные способности и повышаются мобилизационные возможности. Кроме того это свидетельствует о совершенствовании нервно-гуморальной регуляции двигательных и вегетативных реакций как на уровне органов и систем, так и на уровне целостного организма. При этом необходимо подчеркнуть, что мальчики проявляют лучшие адаптационно-мобилизационные способности, выражающиеся в общей и специальной экономизации двигательных актов и меньших энерготратах на их выполнение. Старший школьный возраст, отличающийся высоким уровнем развития энергообеспечивающих систем, устойчивостью к дефициту кислорода, что следует считать наиболее оптимальным для включения в режим дня продолжительных и достаточно интенсивных физических упражнений. Последнее особенно благоприятно отражается на воспитании выносливости.

Изучение возрастной и сезонной динамики внешнего дыхания и газообмена при выполнении учебно-тренировочных нагрузок повышенных объёмов и интенсивности позволяют отметить гибкость, подвижность и высокую вариативность адаптационных механизмов данных систем организма.

При этом процесс адаптации функциональных систем к интенсивной мышечной деятельности у физически более подготовленных школьников осуществляется не только путём расширения функциональных возможностей организма, но и путём повышения устойчивости его к недостатку кислорода, которая оказалась максимальной у школьников младшего возраста.

Полученный экспериментальный материал убедительно свидетельствует о том, что в онтогенезе определенным образом перестраивается энергообеспечение мышечной деятельности. Было подтверждено мнение И.А. Корниенко о том, что младший школьный возраст при выполнении мышечной работы отличается специфическими функциональными возможностями, проявляющимися высоким уровнем развития систем тканевого окисления и наличием адаптивных механизмов, позволяющим интенсивно снабжать работающие ткани кислородом.

Таким образом, исследование возрастных особенностей энергетического обмена и внешнего дыхания детей и подростков, проживающих в регионе жаркого климата, позволило охарактеризовать организацию метаболических процессов в покое и при мышечной деятельности.

Список использованных источников

1. Фарбер Д.А., Корниенко И.А., Сонькин В.Д. Физиология школьника М.: Педагогика, 1990. - 64 с.
- 2.. Атамухамедова М. и др. Влияние умственной деятельности у учащихся на газообмен в различных экологических условиях //Символ науки. – 2019. – №. 3. – С. 81-82.
3. Atamukhamedova M. R., Yormatov G. S., Erkaev E. A. Relations between basic exchange and sprint //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 304-308.
4. Atamukhamedova M. R., Eminov A. Y., Boratov O. M. Changes in the respiratory and blood system as a result of physical exercises //CHANGES. – 2019. – Т. 10. – С. 10-2019.
5. Атамухамедова М. Р., Саидова А. Я. Функциональные сдвиги в организме детей в неблагоприятных условиях окружающей среды //Проблемы и перспективы развития экспериментальной науки. – 2018. – С. 136-138.
5. Rakhimzhanovna A. M., Adkhamzhanovich A. A., Avazkhanovich E. A. Physical performance indicators in young swimmers //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 59-62.
6. Атамухамедова М. Р., Аминжанов А. А. Показатели физической работоспособности у молодых пловцов //Интернаука. – 2021. – №. 37-1. – С. 9-10.
7. Атамухамедова М. Р., Эргашев А. А. Санитарно-гигиеническое значение вентиляции производственных помещений //Интернаука. – 2021. – №. 37-1. – С. 19-21.
8. Атамухамедова М. Р., Саидова А. Я. Питание при железодефицитной анемии //Новая наука: история становления, современное состояние, перспективы развития. – 2020. – С. 267-269.
9. Атамухамедова М. Р., Саидова А. Я. Основные правила питания при занятиях спортом //Новая наука: история становления, современное состояние, перспективы развития. – 2020. – С. 265-267.
10. Атамухамедова М., Кузиев О., Исроилюжонов С. Уровень вентиляции и произвольное апноэ дыхания //Наука в современном обществе: закономерности и тенденции. – 2019. – С. 265.
11. Атамухамедова М. Р., Аминжанов А. А., Исраилжанов С. И. Экологические особенности энергетического метаболизма у детей в связи с антропогенными изменениями во внешней среде //проблемы и перспективы развития экспериментальной науки. – 2018. – Т. 134.

12. Атамухамедова М. Р. Адаптивные изменения систем внешнего дыхания детей и подростков при мышечной деятельности //Universum: медицина и фармакология. – 2022. – №. 2 (85). – С. 16-18.
13. Атамухамедова М., Саидова А. Влияние возрастных особенностей организма на обмен веществ //Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences. – 2021. – С. 287-292.
14. Atamukhamedova M. R., Erkaev E. A. Physiological indicators of the body of adolescents engaged in swimming //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 362-367.
15. Atamukhamedova M. R., Erkaev E. A. Methods of distance learning of biology course in higher educational institutions //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 354-358.
16. Raximjanovna A. M., Yakubovna S. A. Sport Bilan Shug'ullanuvchi O'smirlarning Asosiy Ozuqalarga Bo'lgan Extiyoji //Amaliy va tibbiyot fanlari ilmiy jurnali. – 2022. – С. 275-279.
17. Raximjanovna A. M. Jismoniy Mashqlar Ta'sirida Kardiorespirator KoRsatkichlarning OZgarishi //Amaliy va tibbiyot fanlari ilmiy jurnali. – 2022. – С. 266-268.
18. Atamuxamedova M. Изучение физической работоспособности пловцов //Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 87-90
19. Ўринбоева, М. С. (2020). Табиатга экологик муносабатларнинг маънавий-ахлоқий тамойиллари ва мезонлари. Science and Education, 1(2), 590-596.
20. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. Вестник науки и образования, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
11. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. Вестник науки и образования, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
13. Rasulova, S. A., & Azimov, U. A. (2020). Formation of axiological consciousness in the era of globalization. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(4), 228-231.
14. Akbarovna, U. M. (2019). Rasulova Shoira Azizovna Vliyaniye temperamenta na deyatelnost i povedeniye cheloveka. Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya, (19-3), 73.
15. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Инсон ахлоқий-экологик маданиятини фалсафий жиҳатлари. Экономика и социум, (3-2 (82)), 273-275.
16. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Man-ecologist-entonic philosophical culture. Экономика и социум, (3-2), 273-275.
17. Тухтаров, И. М., Хакимов, А. М., Олтмишева, Н. Г., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). О модели воспитания нравственной культуры у молодежи. Экономика и социум, (3-2 (82)), 459-466.
18. Ўринбоева, М. С., & Расулова, Ш. А. Экологик барқарор тараққиётни

INTERACTIONS OF GABA AND HYPOGLYCEMIC DRUGS***Davranova Aziza Davranovna****Samarkand State Medical University**Assistant of the Department of Endocrinology, Scientific adviser****Shermurodov Shehroz Shermurod****Samarkand State Medical University****Rabbimov Ortiqboy Yaxshiboy o'g'li****Samarkand State Medical University****Nosirova Madinabonu Abdurazzoq qizi****Samarkand State Medical University****Omonova Dilorom****Samarkand State Medical University*

Annotation. *Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a leading cause of premature mortality and disability. Despite a significant number of drugs, the effectiveness of therapy aimed at normalizing glycemic levels and preventing complications does not fully satisfy doctors and patients. Therefore, the search for new approaches for the prevention and treatment of diabetes and its complications continues. Significant resources are used to develop new drugs, but recently the possibility of using "old" widely available drugs with newly discovered pleiotropic properties has been justified. These may include gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) preparations and agents that directly or indirectly activate GABAergic transmission, which have a pronounced pancreoprotective effect, which has been widely discussed in foreign literature in the last 10–15 years. However, there are few such publications in the domestic literature. It has been established that the content of GABA in β -cells in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes decreases, and this correlates with the severity of the disease. Genetic suppression of GABAA receptors causes a significant decrease in β -cell mass and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, which confirms the importance of GABA in ensuring glucose homeostasis and the advisability of replenishing GABA deficiency in diabetes with its additional administration. It has been established that in animals with diabetes, GABA suppresses apoptosis and stimulates the regeneration of β -cells, increases β -cell mass and insulin production. Experimental data have been obtained indicating the synergistic effect of GABA when combined with glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonists, dipeptidyl peptidase type 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors, when a more pronounced pancreoprotective effect is observed, due to a decrease in oxidative and nitrosative stress, inflammation, an increase in the level of Klotho protein, Nrf-2 activity and antioxidant defense enzymes, suppression of NF- κ B activity and the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines. As a result, all this leads to a decrease in apoptosis and death of β -cells, an increase in β -cell mass, insulin production and at the same time a decrease in glucagon levels, insulin resistance.*

Keywords: *GABA; β cells, α cells, diabetes, insulin, enzymes, DPP-4.*

ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЕ ГАМК И ГИПОГЛИКЕМИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ*Давранова Азиза Даврановна**Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет
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Аннотация. Сахарный диабет (СД) является ведущей причиной преждевременной смертности и инвалидности. Несмотря на значительное количество препаратов, эффективность терапии, направленной на нормализацию уровня гликемии и предотвращение осложнений, не в полной мере удовлетворяет врачей и пациентов. Поэтому поиск новых подходов к профилактике и лечению сахарного диабета и его осложнений продолжается. На разработку новых лекарств тратятся значительные ресурсы, но в последнее время обоснована возможность использования «старых», широко доступных препаратов с вновь открытыми плейотропными свойствами. К ним можно отнести препараты гамма-аминомасляной кислоты (ГАМК) и средства, прямо или косвенно активирующие ГАМКергическую передачу, обладающие выраженным панкреопротекторным действием, что широко обсуждается в зарубежной литературе в последние 10–15 лет. Однако подобных публикаций в отечественной литературе немного. Установлено, что содержание ГАМК в β -клетках у больных сахарным диабетом 1 и 2 типа снижается, и это коррелирует с тяжестью заболевания. Генетическая супрессия ГАМК-рецепторов вызывает значительное снижение массы β -клеток и глюкозо-стимулируемую секрецию инсулина, что подтверждает значение ГАМК в обеспечении гомеостаза глюкозы и целесообразность восполнения дефицита ГАМК при сахарном диабете с помощью ее дополнительного введения. Установлено, что у животных с сахарным диабетом ГАМК подавляет апоптоз и стимулирует регенерацию β -клеток, увеличивает массу β -клеток и продукцию инсулина. Получены экспериментальные данные, указывающие на синергический эффект ГАМК при сочетании с агонистами рецепторов глюкагоноподобного пептида-1 (ГПП-1), ингибиторами дипептидилпептидазы 4-го типа (ДПП-4) и ингибиторами натрий-глюкозного котранспортера 2 (SGLT-2). , когда наблюдается более выраженный панкреопротекторный эффект за счет снижения окислительного и нитрозативного стресса, воспаления, повышения уровня белка Клото, активности Nrf-2 и ферментов антиоксидантной защиты, подавления активности NF- κ B и экспрессии провоспалительные цитокины. В результате все это приводит к уменьшению апоптоза и гибели β -клеток, увеличению массы β -клеток, выработке инсулина и одновременно снижению уровня глюкагона, инсулинорезистентности.

Ключевые слова: ГАМК; β -клетки, α -клетки, диабет, инсулин, ферменты, ДПП-4.

Introduction. Diabetes mellitus (DM), due to its widespread prevalence and severity of complications, is a major medical, social and economic problem [1]. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of patients with diabetes has more than doubled over the past 20 years: according to the register of patients with diabetes, as of January 1, 2021, 4,799,552 (3.23%) patients were registered at the dispensary [2]. According to forecasts of the International Diabetes Association, the number of patients with diabetes will reach 642 million people by 2040 [2]. The use of modern drugs has significantly improved the quality of life of people suffering from diabetes. However, in more than 2/3 of patients it is not possible to achieve target glycemic values, and it is also not always possible to prevent the loss of pancreatic β -cells and numerous complications of diabetes. This encourages the search for new targets and new drugs, the use of combination therapy, and the development of new strategies and new technologies for the treatment of diabetes [1, 3, 4]. Types 1 and 2 diabetes are associated with progressive death of β -cells with the participation of the immune system and inflammation, oxidative and nitrosative stress, glucose and lipotoxicity. One of the areas of treatment for diabetes is the use of drugs that suppress apoptosis and death of β -cells and activate their proliferation and regeneration, increasing insulin production [5–9]. Such properties were noted in incretins, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), inhibitors of sodium-glucose cotransporter type 2 (NGLT-2), etc., but with monotherapy it is not always possible to achieve normoglycemia, reduce apoptosis and death of β -cells, and enhance their regeneration and increase in β -cell mass, prevent the development of complications of diabetes [9]. In order to increase the effectiveness of antidiabetic therapy for diabetes, a combination of 2 or even 3 hypoglycemic drugs that give a synergistic effect is widely used [4, 10]. In recent years, a number of studies have been published on the synergistic effect of GABA and some hypoglycemic agents of the latest generation, reflecting their effect on glucose homeostasis, the functioning of β -cells, and the formation of additional positive therapeutic effects [9]. In this review, we present data demonstrating the synergistic interaction of GABA and drugs with GABAergic action in combination with drugs that have an incretin-like effect: glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists (GLP-1R), dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and NGLT- 2, having previously considered their class-specific properties, including pleiotropic ones. The search was carried out in the Pubmed, eLibrary, Medline databases using the keywords: diabetes mellitus, gamma-aminobutyric acid, glucagon-like peptide-1, GLP-1R agonists, glucose-dependent insulinotropic peptide (GIP), dipeptidyl peptidase

inhibitors, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors. The search was carried out over the period from 2021 to 2023, but the review presents the results of studies published mainly over the last 3 years, which is due to the journal's requirements for the maximum volume of work and the number of sources.

Role of gaba in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism. Since the discovery of GABA and its inhibitory properties in the brain (BM), much of our understanding of its physiological role has changed significantly. It was found that GABA is detected in almost all tissues and organs. In pancreatic tissues, the GABA content is comparable to that in the GM and is highly expressed in α - and β -cells of the islets of Langerhans [6, 11]. The GABA content in β -cells in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes decreases, and insulin secretion is impaired [12, 13]. This supports the contention that loss of GABA correlates with the pathogenesis of diabetes [8]. In the pancreatic islets, insulin-producing β -cells express GABAA and GABA B receptors, which are encoded by different intracellular pathways and form different signal transduction mechanisms [6, 12, 14, 15]. Once released, GABA influences the activity of α - and β -cells of the pancreas through ionotropic GABAA receptors and metabotropic GABAB receptors. The effect of GABA on α - and β -cells differs; on the former it has an inhibitory effect, reducing the production and release of glucagon, on β -cells it has a stimulating effect, increasing insulin secretion [15]. GABA in pancreatic β -cells through GABA A receptors activates calcium-dependent signaling pathways and voltage-dependent channels, triggers the PI3K/Akt, CREB-IRS-2 and SIRT-1 signaling cascades, which may be decisive in the regulation of mass and functions β -cells [11, 15]. Obesity plays a key role in the development of insulin resistance, diabetes and its complications [16, 17]. Therefore, reducing insulin resistance is an independent task for the prevention and treatment of diabetes. GABA has therapeutic potential against obesity, which is associated with the suppression of oxidative stress and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress. GABA reduced the expression of the adipogenic transcription factor PPAR- γ in the adipose tissue and liver of mice fed a fat-rich, high-calorie diet. GABA controls the activity of NADPH oxidase (NOX4) during dysmetabolism associated with high-fat and carbohydrate-rich foods, causing the breakdown of IRE-1a, which sulfonates RIDD-SIRT. Administration of GABA significantly increased AMPK and SIRT-1 levels in obese mice [17], decreased insulin resistance, increased liver glycogen levels, improved lipid profile, and decreased glucose and glycated hemoglobin levels [18, 19]. GABA significantly reduced insulin resistance by activating the expression of the glucose transporter gene (GLUT-4), suppressing

the gluconeogenesis pathway in the liver, reducing the expression of the FOXO1 and Pepck genes, and simultaneously increasing the expression of the IRS-2 and Akt2 genes [18]. GABA stimulates phosphorylation of CREB through cAMP element binding protein (AMPK), known as a key transcription factor responsible for insulin gene maintenance and β -cell survival, thereby promoting increased β -cell mass. The trophic effects of GABA are formed through the activation of the Akt and CREB signaling pathways independently of each other, but activation of both pathways is required for an optimal response. The involvement of Ca^{2+} and CREB and their glucose-dependent activation of β -cell IRS-2 is important for the plasticity of the β -cell response to increased insulin demand. GABA-induced activation of CREB is simultaneously associated with increased levels of IRS-2 transcript expression [6, 15, 20]. The role of the GABAergic system in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism is also confirmed by the fact that genetic suppression of GABA receptors significantly reduced the mass of β -cells and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, which led to disruption of glucose homeostasis [8, 9].

Conclusion. The development of innovative drugs requires significant resources. An alternative to this could be the identification of new targets for already known drugs, which open up other indications and prospects for their use in complex therapy. These may include GABA and drugs with GABAergic action, which, judging by many publications, can improve the functional state of β -cells, reduce oxidative stress and inflammation. Currently, data have accumulated on the synergistic effect of GABA when combined with GLP-1R agonists, DPP-4 inhibitors and SGLT-2 inhibitors with increased pancreatic protective action, which is due to a decrease in oxidative stress and inflammation, an increase in the level of Klotho protein, Nrf-2 activity and antioxidant defense enzymes, suppression of NF- κ B activity and the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines. This led to a decrease in β -cell death, an increase in β -cell mass, insulin production, and at the same time a decrease in insulin resistance.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.

4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиеров ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабети COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*.2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensialdiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash.*Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.I. 2021;2(3):37-41.

17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinova MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinova XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 special):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412

31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of MultidimensiResear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfiyeva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o'zgarishlar. *so'ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Pretibial myxedema: pathogenetic features and clinical aspects. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):695-702.
45. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.
46. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.

47. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):337-340.
48. Daminov AT, Sa'dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):139-142.
49. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O'g'li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(6):408-412.
50. Ulugbekovna NP, Bakhtiyorovna RI, Almosovich RA, Takhirovich DA. Thyroid Diseases during Pregnancy and their Impact on Maternal and Fetal Outcomes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):188-190.
51. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Time-restricted nutrition as a new strategy for the therapy of obesity and comorbid conditions. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):660-667.
52. Nilufar R, Adkhamjon K. TO The development of cardiovascular diseases effects of environmental factors. *Fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya jurnali | Journal of science, education, culture and innovation*. 2022;1(4):100-101.
53. Xoldorov X, Omonov F, Jumayev I, Daminov AT. Type 1 diabetes as a risk factor for bone health in childhood. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2023;2(8):131-135.
54. Daminov AT, Xurramova S, Islomov A, Ulashev M, Ikramov R, Mirzakhakimov P. Type 2 diabetes and bone mineral density in postmenopausal women. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
55. Berkinov A, Safarov F, Tursunova S, Daminov AT. Vitamin d status in senior residents of samarkand region. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2023;2(8):136-140.

MA'NAViy MADANIYAT JAMIYAT BARQARORLIGI OMILI

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O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti Farg'ona filiali katta o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada jamiyatning barqaror rivojlanishida ijtimoiy ong sakllari bo'lmish ma'naviy madaniyat tushunchasi va uni insonlar tomonidan boyitib borilishi xaqidagi dunyo olimlarining fikrlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jamiyat, barqarorlik, madaniy jarayonlar, ma'naviyat, ijtimoiy ong, sinergetik, gnosyologik tahlil.

SPIRITUAL CULTURE SOCIETY STABILITY FACTOR

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Abstract. This article covers the opinions of world scientists about the concept of spiritual culture, which is a source of social consciousness in the sustainable development of society, and its enrichment by people.

Key words: society, stability, cultural processes, spirituality, social consciousness, synergistic, epistemological analysis.

Kirish. XXI asrga kelib ma'naviyat butun insoniyat uchun dolzarb ma'naviy ozuqaga aylanib ketdiki, natijada usiz har qanday qudratli jamiyat yoki davlat tanazzulga yo'l tutishi aniq bo'lib qoldi. Prezidentimiz Sh. M. Mirziyoyev alohida ta'kidlaganidek, bugungi kunga kelib xalqimiz va yurtimizning istiqbolini belgilashda, "...insoniyat dunyosining buyuk bir yoritgichi – ma'naviyat chirog'i bor. Bu chiroqning boshqalardan farqi shuki, u insonning ongi va tafakkurini yoritadi, qalbi, vijdonini uyg'otadi, odamiylik hissini kuchaytiradi.

O'zbekistonning yangi uyg'onish davrini yaratishga kirishar ekanmiz, har bir yurtdoshimizning qalbi va ongida ana shunday ma'naviyat shu'lasini porlashi va u bizni ezgu ishlarga undab, yuksak mas'uliyat tuyg'usi bilan yashashga da'vat etishi zarur".

Shunday ekan, har bir inson hamda kamol topib kelayotgan yosh avlod uchun ma'naviyat suv bilan havodek naqadar zarurligini unutmasligimiz

darkor.Ma'lumki, masala va muammoning mohiyatini anglab yetish chog'ida uning mazmunini ochib berish maqsadida ishlatiladigan tushuncha va kategoriyalarning mazmun-mohiyatiga e'tibor qaratish juda muhim sanaladi. Shu ma'noda ma'naviyat va madaniyat tushunchalari ham alohida ilmiy tahlillarga muhtoj bo'lib, ayrim tadqiqotchilar tomonidan muayyan ko'lamda talqin etilgan.

Ma'naviyat tushunchasining ma'no-mazmuni haqida fikr yuritganda uning jamiyatda tutgan rolini teran anglamasdan turib ma'naviy madaniyat haqida so'z yuritib bo'lmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat ma'naviyatning real hodisa sifatida yuzaga chiqishi, uning voqeiy bo'lish jarayonining yuzaga kelishidan iborat. Nazariy ongning bir qismi bo'lgan ma'naviy madaniyatning shakllari amaliyot bilan bog'liq. Voqelikka nisbatan yoshlar ongida ham ma'naviy madaniyatning elementlari shakllanib, milliylik bilan bog'liq ravishda ijtimoiy ong rivojlanadi.

Ma'naviyat asosiy tushunchalar izohli lug'atida "ma'naviyat – inson ruhiy va aqliy olamini ifodalovchi tushuncha" sifatida keltirilgan bo'lsa, O'zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasida esa, "ma'naviyat – kishilarning falsafiy, huquqiy, ilmiy, badiiy, ahloqiy, diniy tasavvurlarini o'z ichiga oladi", deyilgan. Har bir ta'rifning funktsionallik va individuallik jihatlari mavjud bo'lib, inson vujudining ma'nosi, manfaatlar to'qnashuviga moyilligi, uning benazir va mukammal mavjudotligini ifodalaydi.

Birinchi Prezidentimiz Islom Karimov esa "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch" asarida ushbu tushunchaga bergan o'zining quyidagicha mashhur ta'rifida: "Ma'naviyat – insonni ruhiy poklanish, qalban ulg'ayishga chorlaydigan, odamning ichki dunyosi, irodasini baquvvat, iymon-e'tiqodini butun qiladigan, vijdonini uyg'otadigan beqiyos kuch, uning barcha qarashlari mezonidir", deb ta'kidlaydi. Mazkur ta'rifning o'ziga xos tomoni shundaki, unda ma'naviyat insonning diniy va dunyoviy hayot bilan bog'liq ko'rinishlarning ifodasi sifatida falsafiy tarzda mohiyatini ilmiy muomalaga kiritishga yo'naltirilgan.

Ma'naviyat bilan madaniyatni tahlil etish chog'ida ular o'rtasidagi dialektik aloqadorlik, sinergetik tamoyillar mavjudligini ko'ra bilish juda muhim. Ma'lumki, ma'naviyat ham, madaniyat ham hech kimda tug'ma bo'lmaydi, instinktlar orqali tabiatan berilmaydi. U shaxsning jamiyatda ijtimoiylashuvi negizida ahloq, did, idrok, his-tuyg'ularning ta'siri ostida shakllanadi va, shunday deyish joiz bo'lsa, ongsizlikdan onglilik, anglanganlik tomon ulg'ayishida vujudga keladi. Har bir voyaga yetib kelayotgan yigit-qiz shaxsiy hayotiy tajribasi asosida, mustaqil ravishda bevosita tevarak-atrofdagi kishilarning, jamiyatning va

o‘t ‘gan ajdodlarning to‘plagan tajribalarini o‘zlashtiradi. Yoshlar ham ijtimoiy amaliyot mahsuli bo‘lgan madaniyatni o‘zlashtirish bilan birga, unga o‘z ta’sirini o‘tkazadi. Yoshlar ijtimoiy ongining shakllanishi jarayonida moddiy va ma’naviy madaniyatni boyita boradi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi. Tadqiqotning uslubiy asosini ilmiy bilishning ob’ektivlik (xolislik), tarixiylik, sistemalilik, retrospektiv va qiyosiy tahlil usullari tashkil etadi.

Tahlil va natijalar. Fanda madaniyatga berilgan ta’riflar ham juda ko‘p. Masalan, akademik E.Yusupovning fikricha, “madaniyat – bu kishilar faoliyatining jamiyat iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy-siyosiy va ma’naviy hayot sohasida yaratgan, o‘zlarining ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun ishlab chiqargan boyliklar tizimidir” . Ko‘rinib turibdiki, akademik olimimiz bergan bu ta’rifda madaniyat asosan insonning yashash tarzi bilan bog‘liq madaniy faoliyatni o‘z ichiga olganligiga asosiy urg‘u berilgan.

Falsafa bo‘yicha qomusiy lug‘atda “madaniyat (so‘zning o‘zagi arabcha madina, ya’ni shahar ma’nosidan kelib chiqqan holda – madinalik, shaharlik, ta’lim-tarbiya ko‘rganlik) – tabiat va o‘zaro munosabatlarda aks etadigan inson faoliyatining o‘ziga xos usuli” , - deb talqin etilgan. Bunda madaniyatning insonning tabiat bilan munosabatlarning uyg‘unlashuviga e’tibor qaratilgan.

Madaniyatga ta’rif bergan olimlar orasida turli soha xodimlari, jumladan, siyosatdonlarni ham ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Jumladan, G.V. Plexanov tomonidan, “madaniyat inson va jamiyat yaratgan moddiy va ma’naviy boyliklar (qadriyatlar) yig‘indisi ekanligi ta’kidlanadi” . Ko‘rinib turibdiki, uning ta’rifida madaniyat bevosita inson faoliyati bilan bog‘liq ijtimoiy munosabatlarning mahsuli sifatida olib qaralgan va o‘z-o‘zidan ravshanki, unda marksizm falsafasining tarixni materialistik tushunish nazariyasining ta’siri ko‘zga yaqqol tashlanib turibdi.

Madaniyat, mohiyatan, shaxs va jamiyat o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlik bo‘lib, birinchi marta adabiyotda “madaniyat” so‘zi nazariy atama sifatida “Toskulian suhbatlari”da (mil. av. 45 y) qadimgi Rimning mashhur notig‘i va faylasufi, tarixchi Mark Tuliyy Sitseron tomonidan qo‘llanilganligini alohida ta’kidlash o‘rinlidir. Bu o‘rinda shuni ham ta’kidlash lozimki, o‘sha paytda bu atama adabiyotda qishloq xo‘jaligi atamasi (qayta ishlash) vazifasini bajargan. Chunki dastlab madaniyatni majoziy ma’noda tabiat va jamiyat hodisalarining inson ongiga ta’siriga nisbatan, keyin esa inson ongi mahsuli va asosida yaratilgan falsafiy an’analarning davomi sifatida ishlatishgan. Shuning uchun Suqrot ham madaniyatni falsafiy tarzda ifodalab, falsafaning inson hayotiga ta’siri usullari tizimida «madaniyat aql – falsafa» degan tezisni maydonga olib chiqqan edi. Bu

esa madaniyatning falsafiy bilim ekanligiga qaratilgan ilmiy qarash ekanligini ta'kidlash borasidagi birinchi urinishlar edi. Shu vaqtdan boshlab ushbu so'zning ma'naviy jihati tarixiylik mazmuniga ega bo'lib, ijtimoiy jarayonga xos ma'no kasb eta boshladi.

XVII asrda kelib madaniyat inson tomonidan amalga oshiriladigan munosabatlarning ijobiy va salbiy natijasi, shaxsning tashqi va ichki mohiyatini ifodalovchi tushuncha sifatida keng qo'llanila boshlandi. Bu ham, tabiiyki o'z davriga xos ilm-fan va ijtimoiy ishlab chiqarish yutuqlarining ifodasi tarzida aks etgan mazmun va mohiyatdan iborat bo'lganligi bilan e'tiborga loyiq.

XIX asrda esa ko'plab madaniyatshunoslar yetishib chiqa boshlaganligi ko'zga yaqqol tashlanadi. Ayniqsa, Yevropada ilmiy-falsafiy tafakkur rivoj topganligi fan tarixida alohida sahifa ochdi va bu holat madaniyat kategoriyasini tushunishga nisbatan yondashuvlarda ham o'z aksini topmasdan qolmadi, deyishimiz mumkin. Rus olimasi E.A.Orlova aytganidek, "shu davrdan boshlab "madaniyat" tushunchasi "sivilizatsiya", "ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy formatsiya", global mintaqalashtirish" kategoriyalari bilan kesishadigan bo'ldi" [8].

XX asrda Yevropa madaniyatshunosligida T. Parsons madaniyatni ijtimoiy harakatni tahlil qilish sifatida, K. Levi-Strauss esa o'z asarlarida tabiiy jarayonlarga qarshi bo'lgan hodisalarning tanlangan maydoni, deb qaraydi. XX asrning ikkichi yarmidan boshlab bu tushunchaga ko'plab rus faylasuflari, jumladan, N. Berdyayev, V. Ivanov, L. Shestov, V. Rozanovlar yuqori madaniyatni anglash sohasidagi ko'plab qimmatli g'oya va ilmiy tasavvurlarni olib kirishdi.

Madaniyatning mohiyatini tushunishda rus faylasuflaridan biri V.S.Biblerning fikri, o'ylaymizki, o'ziga xosligi bilan e'tiborga molik. Uning fikricha:

- madaniyat insonga xos bo'lib, bir vaqtda borliqda mavjud bo'lishligi va odamlar uchun hamkorlik aloqasi shaklida namoyon bo'ladi;
- madaniyat – inson o'z mohiyati va shaxsiyatini aqliy anglab yetishi, ijtimoiy hayotda o'rnatilgan qoidalarga so'zsiz amal qilish holatidir. Madaniyat - bu o'z taqdiriga nisbatan erkin qaror qabul qilish va qayta belgilash, uning tarixiy va umumbashariy javobgarligini anglash shaklidir;
- madaniyat dunyoning birinchi ixtirosi.

Bunda V.S.Bibler madaniyatning bu uchta ko'rinishiga xos turli belgilarni o'z ichiga olgan noyob va universalligini emas, balki, madaniyatning alohida bo'limlarga ajratilishidir, deb ta'kidlaydi.

Bizning atrofimizdagi dunyoda mavjud bo'lgan ma'naviy madaniyatni ongli ravishda anglab yetish voqelik ikkilamchi tabiatga o'tishini shaxs

madaniyati sifatida qabul qilishi natijasida obyektivlikdan subyektivlikka erishiladi. Mazkur madaniyat inson uchun ijtimoiy va tarixiy tajriba, dasturlarni to'plash asosida ijtimoiy ehtiyojlarga asoslangan faoliyat va harakatni oldinga yo'naltiradi. Borliqni inson ongida aks etishi, shu asosda o'z ijod mahsulini yaratishi natijasida ma'naviy madaniyat paydo bo'ladi.

Ma'naviy madaniyat, aslida, kishilik jamiyati tarixida asrlar davomida shakllangan inson tafakkurining mahsuli bo'lib, unda insonning voqelikka stixiyali tarzda yondashuvi asosida ma'naviy dunyoqarash vujudga kelgan. Astasekinlik bilan tevarak-atrofdagi narsa va hodisalarga aqliy munosabatning rivojlanishi negizida ma'naviy madaniyat unsurlari ijobiy va foydali ahamiyat kasb etgan va shuning uchun avloddan-avlodga meros sifatida qoldirish uchun zarur deb topilgan. Bu esa, o'z navbatida insonning aql-zakovatida yangicha tafakkur tarzi shakllanishi bilan birga, borliqning narsa va predmetlari, hayvonot olami, koinot, megaolam va umuman dunyo to'g'risidagi qarashlarining kengayishiga olib kelgan.

Ma'naviy ishlab chiqarish jarayonida siyosiy va huquqiy mafkura, falsafa, ahloq, san'at sohasidagi erishilgan yutuqlar saralanib boradi. Ular ma'naviy boyliklarni yaratuvchi shaxslar tomonidan qayta ishlanib, sayqallanadi va odamlarning ehtiyojlarini qondirish tomonga yo'naltiriladi. Shu boisdan "ma'naviy madaniyat – insonning ma'naviy xususiyat va xislatlari, jamiyatning madaniy darajasini aks ettiruvchi tushuncha" sifatida olib qaraladi. Unda insonning oddiy yashashi bilan bog'liq kundalik turmushning muhim ehtiyojlari tizimi jamiyat bilan bog'liq holda ifodalangan.

S.Otamurodov fikriga ko'ra esa, "ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish va o'zlashtirish vositasidir". Bunda voqelikda inson mehnati natijasida yaratiladigan moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar, shaxs ma'naviy qiyofasining yuksalishiga xizmat qiladigan ahloq qoidalariga rioya etish masalalari aks etgan.

Biroq, ushbu o'rinda ta'kidlash lozimki, bizningcha, S. Otamurodovning bu fikri muhokama etilayotgan masala yuzasidan mutlaq haqiqat darajasi uchun da'vogarlik qila olmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish tushunchasidan ancha kengroq tushuncha. Binobarin, olimning badiiy aks ettirish jihatini mutlaqlashtiradigan bo'lsak, siyosiy, ilmiy, huquqiy aks ettirish kabi jihatlar ushbu yondashuv doirasiga sig'may qolishi tabiiydir. Shunday ekan, ma'naviy madaniyatni voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishga tenglashtirish asossiz, balki voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishni ma'naviy madaniyatni shakllantirish vositalaridan biri deyish to'g'ri bo'ladi.

Ilohiyot nazariyasi nuqtai nazaridan yondashuvda insonning ma'naviy borlig'i uchun najot bilan muloqot orqali sodir bo'ladigan ilohiy inoyat, insonning ichki o'zgarishi va iymon orqali uning qadriyatlari va ma'naviy (ilohiy) ga bo'lgan munosabatining o'zgarishlari tushuniladi. Taniqli rus faylasufi I. Ilin bu to'g'rida shunday deb yozadi: "barcha ma'naviy madaniyatning asosiy manbai - bu bizga berilgan Ilohiylik. Xudo tomonidan beriladigan yaxshi va jonli narsalarda sevgi va iymon mavjud va uni e'zozlaymiz". Bu fikrlardan har bir dinda xudoga sig'inish ilohiylik kasb etishini ko'rishimiz mumkin va o'zimizning unga e'tiqodimiz orqali o'zligimiz, ichki hissiyotlarimizni bag'ishlaymiz.

Xulosa. Ma'naviy madaniyatga ta'sir qiluvchi omillardan biri jamiyatning ma'naviy yangilanishi jarayonida odamlar ma'naviyatni shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan turli aloqalar, yangi avlodlarning o'z rivojlanishida yangi qadriyatlar to'plashi, bilim, g'oyalar, tajriba orttirishi bilan bog'liqligidir. Shu bilan birga kundalik an'analar bilan bog'liq diniy hamda dunyoviy tafakkur ham ana shu omillardan biri sanaladi. Diniy tafakkurda inson ma'naviy ongiga ta'sir qiladigan ilohiy hodisalar va jarayonlar asosiy o'rin egallaydi. Bunda ma'naviy madaniyatning rivojlanish jarayoni jamiyatning taraqqiyot yo'nalishini belgilaydigan ko'rsatkich vazifasini bajaradi.

Ma'naviyat subyektning barqaror holati darajasida to'liq namoyon bo'lib, ma'naviy madaniyatning yuqori darajasiga aylanadi. Ushbu jarayonning mohiyatini sharqning buyuk allomasi Abu Nasr Forobiy juda chiroyli va mantiqiy ta'riflaganligini keltirish juda o'rinli bo'ladi: "Bu esa tabiiy hayot ruhining yo'g'on tomirlar vositasi bilan qalbdan a'zolarga yuborilishi bilan bajo keladi", deb yozgan edi alloma.

Jamiyatda ma'naviy madaniyatni rivojlantirish uchun milliylikni saqlash bilan birga, undan yiroqlashish, insoniyat tarixiga chuqur kirib borish ham maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi. Shu tarzda yoshlar kamolotiga xizmat qiladigan ijtimoiy-falsafiy tafakkurni shakllantirish, jamiyatda ajdodlar yaratib qoldirgan moddiy va ma'naviy merosning naqadar buyuk xazina ekanligini anglab yetish mumkin bo'ladi. Har bir yosh avlod ongli ravishda o'zining ma'naviy-mafkuraviy olamini milliy va umuminsoniylik uyg'unligida kamol toptirishi ertangi kun uchun bevosita ma'naviy boylikka aylanadi. Ijtimoiy hayotda moddiylik va ma'naviylikning uyg'unligi va o'zaro ta'siri natijasida aqlan yetuk, ahloqan barkamol, jismonan sog'lom, e'tiqodi butun inson tarbiya topadi. Inson o'zining teran fikri, rang-barang qarashlari, boy tushuncha va tasavvurlari va g'oyalar dunyosi yordamida turlicha madaniyatlarni biri-biridan farqlab boradi.

Takliflar. Har bir xalq uchun ma'naviy madaniyatning o'ziga xos boshqa xalqlardan farqlanadigan jihatlari mavjud bo'lib, undan foydalanishda ijobiy tomonlarni olishi . Xalqimizning buyuk allomalari Forobiy, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Navoiy, Bobur va boshqalarning asarlarida turli xalqlar madaniyatlarining o'zaro aloqasi va bir-biriga o'zaro ta'siri keng yoritilgan ulardan unumli foydalanish. Mutafakkirlarning asarlari bugungi kunda ko'plab tillarda tarjima qilinib, boshqa xalqlarning manfaatlari bilan mos bo'lganligi bois ularning ma'naviy boyliklari qatoridan ham mustahkam joy olish.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Ўринбоева, М. С. (2020). Табиатга экологик муносабатларнинг маънавий-ахлоқий тамойиллари ва мезонлари. *Science and Education*, 1(2), 590-596.
2. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
3. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
4. Rasulova, S. A., & Azimov, U. A. (2020). Formation of axiological consciousness in the era of globalization. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(4), 228-231.
5. Akbarovna, U. M. (2019). Rasulova Shoiraz Azizovna Vliyaniye temperamenta na deyatelnost i povedeniye cheloveka. *Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya*, (19-3), 73.
6. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Инсон ахлоқий-экологик маданиятини фалсафий жиҳатлари. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (82)), 273-275.
7. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Man-ecologist-entonic philosophical culture. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2), 273-275.
8. Тухтаров, И. М., Хакимов, А. М., Олтмишева, Н. Г., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). О модели воспитания нравственной культуры у молодежи. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (82)), 459-466.
9. Ўринбоева, М. С., & Расулова, Ш. А. Экологик барқарор тараққиётни таъминлашда ахлоқнинг функциялари. Тошкент-2021, 104.

THE MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY

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Abstract: *Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a disease that accompanies a person for a long period of time. The greatest danger of diabetes is undoubtedly associated with complications that develop due to its damaging effects on blood vessels, particularly diabetic nephropathy (DN), which develops in approximately 20.1% of patients with diabetes of the 1st type and 6.3% of patients with diabetes of the 2nd type. In patients with diabetes of the 2nd type, diabetic nephropathy ranks third among causes of death after diseases of the cardiovascular system and oncological pathologies. There are many mechanisms of damaging effects of various factors that play a key role in the development of renal pathology in diabetes. We focused on a more detailed examination of the effect of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone (RAAS), direct damaging effects of hyperglycemia, polyol glucose metabolism, and hyperlipidemia, endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and transforming growth factor β (TGF- β). Based on the knowledge of the pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy, very promising targets have been identified for the correction of this pathology.*

Key words: *diabetic nephropathy, hyperglycemia, diabetic kidney disease.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ НЕФРОПАТИИ.

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Аннотация: Сахарный диабет (СД) – заболевание, сопровождающее человека в течение длительного периода времени. Наибольшую опасность СД, несомненно, связаны с осложнениями, развивающимися вследствие его повреждающего воздействия на сосуды, в частности с диабетической нефропатией (ДН), которая развивается примерно у 20,1% больных СД 1-го типа и у 6,3% больных СД 1-го типа и 6,3% больных СД 1-го типа. 2-й тип. У больных сахарным диабетом 2-го типа диабетическая нефропатия занимает третье место среди причин смерти после заболеваний сердечно-сосудистой системы и онкологических патологий. Существует множество механизмов повреждающего действия различных факторов, играющих ключевую роль в развитии патологии почек при сахарном диабете. Мы сосредоточились на более детальном изучении влияния ренин-ангиотензин-альдостерона (РААС), прямых повреждающих эффектов гипергликемии, метаболизма полиоловой глюкозы и гиперлипидемии, эндотелиального фактора роста (VEGF) и трансформирующего фактора роста β (TGF- β). На основании знаний о патогенезе диабетической нефропатии определены весьма перспективные цели коррекции этой патологии.

Ключевые слова: диабетическая нефропатия, гипергликемия, диабетическая болезнь почек.

Effects on biochemical and structural changes in renal membranes. At present, the search is underway for promising drugs that can affect the structure and biochemical composition of the basement membranes of the renal glomeruli. One of such drugs, which has already passed experimental and clinical trials, is sulodexide (Alfa Wassermann, Italy), which is a low-molecular-weight heparin. This drug, without affecting the blood coagulation system, is able to increase the content of heparan sulfate in the glomerular membranes, restore the selective permeability of the renal filter and prevent the development of sclerotic processes in the kidney tissue. We tested this drug in 18 patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (9 people with microalbuminuria and 9 people with proteinuria). The drug was administered intramuscularly once a day, 5 days a week (with a 2-day break) for 3 weeks. In 89% of patients, a significant antiproteinuric effect was noted, reaching its maximum by the end of the treatment period, and protein excretion in the urine decreased in patients with both microalbuminuria and proteinuria. This effect persisted for the next 6 weeks after discontinuation of treatment, although there was some tendency to re-increase albuminuria. In addition, the antiatherogenic effect of sulodexide was noted: the atherogenic coefficient of serum decreased. When assessing the condition of the fundus of the eye in patients treated with sulodexide, a positive trend was revealed in the non-proliferative and preproliferative stages of diabetic retinopathy and stabilization of the process in the proliferative stage of retinopathy. Thus, this drug had a beneficial effect not only on the course of DN, but also on the wall of retinal vessels. Another inevitable consequence of hyperglycemia is non-enzymatic glycosylation of the structural proteins of the glomerular basement membrane, which also leads to disruption of their configuration and loss of normal selective permeability to proteins. To interrupt the non-enzyme glycosylation reaction, the drug aminoguanidine is successfully used in the experiment, which irreversibly reacts with glycosylation products, thereby stopping this process. However, no clinical trials of this drug have been conducted to date. Increased glucose metabolism along the polyol pathway under the influence of the enzyme aldose reduction leads to the accumulation of sorbitol (osmotically active substance) in insulin-independent tissues, also contributing to the development of late complications of diabetes mellitus. To interrupt this process, the clinic uses drugs from the group of aldose reductase inhibitors (tolrestat, statil). A number of studies have demonstrated a decrease in albuminuria in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus receiving aldose reductase inhibitors. However, the clinical efficacy of these drugs is more pronounced in the treatment of diabetic neuropathy

or retinopathy and less so in the treatment of DN. This may be due to the fact that the polyol pathway of glucose metabolism plays a smaller role in the pathogenesis of diabetic kidney damage than the vessels of other non-insulin-dependent tissues.

Effects on vasoactive factors of vascular endothelium and platelets. The vascular endothelium and platelets are the cells most sensitive to the effects of high glucose concentrations. Endothelial cell dysfunction consists in the overproduction of biologically active substances involved in the processes of intravascular coagulation and regulation of vascular tone (endothelin-1, endothelial relaxation factor, prostacyclin). Platelet dysfunction in uncompensated diabetes mellitus is manifested by high production of coagulation factors, as well as excessive release of thromboxane A₂ (TCA₂), which causes vasospasm and platelet hyperaggregation. All of these endothelial and platelet factors, causing spasm and thrombotic occlusion of blood vessels, contribute to the development and progression of both micro- and macroangiopathies in diabetes mellitus. Therefore, drug correction of the activity of these factors could help prevent the rapid progression of late vascular complications of diabetes mellitus. Medications that correct the synthesis of vasoactive endothelial factors (endothelin-1 and endothelial relaxation factor) are at the stage of experimental development and in the future have a real chance to take a leading place in the treatment of diabetic angiopathies. At the same time, drugs that affect the prostacyclin-thromboxane system have already been developed and are widely used in nephrological practice for the treatment of chronic renal diseases. In the practice of diabetologists, these drugs have not yet been widely used, although their use for the treatment of diabetic angiopathies (and, above all, DN) is pathogenetically justified. For example, TCA₂ not only causes vasospasm and platelet hyperaggregation, but also has a direct damaging effect on the structure and function of the kidneys, provoking the development of proteinuria and accelerating the process of sclerosing of renal tissue. In this regard, it seemed expedient to investigate the effect of a drug that blocks excess production of TCA₂ on renal function in patients with DN. For this purpose, we used ibustrin (Pharmacia, Switzerland), which is an inhibitor of the enzyme cyclooxygenase, which is involved in the formation of TCA₂ from arachidonic acid. Treatment was provided to 16 patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus with proteinuric stage DN (proteinuria did not exceed 1 g/day). All patients also had different stages of diabetic retinopathy and impaired blood supply to the lower extremities, diagnosed by Doppler sonography of the arteries of the feet. Ibustrin was prescribed 1 tablet 2 times a day (400 mg/day) for 3 months. At the end of the course of treatment, there was an improvement in renal function: glomerular

filtration rate increased in 13 (81%) patients, daily proteinuria decreased in 12 (75%) patients. The efficacy of treatment against retinopathy directly depended on the stage of pathological changes in the fundus vessels: among patients with the non-proliferative stage of retinopathy, improvement was noted in 83%, in the presence of the preproliferative stage — in 40% of patients, but in patients with the proliferative stage there was practically no positive dynamics. Increased blood flow in the lower extremities during treatment with ibustrin was observed in 62% of patients. Such a high efficacy of ibustrin in the treatment of vascular complications of diabetes mellitus, found in our study, can be explained by the timely initiation of the use of this drug, i.e., at relatively early stages of the development of angiopathies (in proteinuria not exceeding 1 g/day; in the non-proliferative or preproliferative stage of retinopathy; in the initial decrease in blood flow in the lower extremities). In the later stages of vascular complications, the efficacy of the drug would appear to be minimal. Thus, in our study. The assumption of the efficacy of the use of drugs blocking the synthesis of TCA2 in the complex treatment of diabetic angiopathies, especially when prescribed at the early stages of vascular complications, has been confirmed.

Purpose: to study common complications and preventive measures for diabetes mellitus in people of different ages.

Materials and methods: studying complications of the disease, data were collected from patients Endocrinological center for Samarkand the years. The data of 30 patients were studied, of which 14 were men and 16 women.

Study results: The most common complication among patients was diabetic nephropathy in 15 patients. According to the results of the study, untimely treatment of diabetic nephropathy leads to chronic renal failure. The initial signs of nephropathy were an increased amount of urination, frequent increases in blood pressure, swelling, and deterioration in health. Instrumental laboratory tests showed an increase in creatinine. Of the 15 patients with diabetic nephropathy, 5 patients are over 47 years old, 7 patients are from 30 to 45 years old and 2 patients are from 25 to 30 years old. Treatment began with a conservative method; in 4 patients, conservative treatment did not show results and hemodialysis was prescribed.

Conclusion. Summarizing all of the above, we can conclude that the pathogenesis of the development of DN is quite complex and has a number of its own features. This problem has spread all over the world and has not lost its relevance today. Treatment of the last stage of DN is not only a complex process, but also, due to some economic aspects, very expensive. It's much easier to do prevention of vascular complications and try to prevent the disease from progressing to end-stage renal failure, how to treat patients with chronic renal

failure using hemodialysis. Therefore, despite detailed study existing problem, question of correction nephropathy remains open to this day.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбилов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод при резус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет и COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *Miasto Przyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmun tireoidit bilan kasallangan bemorlardagi funksional buzilishlarning differensial diagnostikasida qalqonsimon bez zichligini aniqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2. *I*. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 special):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.

28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 special):259-264.
34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.

STRUCTURE OF THE CAUSES OF INFERTILITY IN MEN AND WOMEN IN SAMARKAND AND SAMARKAND REGION

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Annotation. *The structure of the causes of infertility was studied in 100 couples (200 people) suffering from infertility in the city of Samarkandey, Samarkand region (50 families each). It was found that in the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (diffuse goiter with subclinical hypothyroidism, ovarian failure with menstrual dysfunction, polycystic ovary syndrome, hyperandrogenism, luteal phase deficiency, impaired folliculogenesis), as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system (TORCH -infections). In the examined men, the main role in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism).*

Keywords: *reproductive health, infertility, male and female hypogonadism.*

СТРУКТУРА ПРИЧИН БЕСПЛОДИЯ У МУЖЧИН И ЖЕНЩИН САМАРКАНДА И САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

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Аннотация. Структура причин бесплодия изучена у 100 пар (200 человек), страдающих бесплодием в городе Самарканде Самаркандской области (по 50 семей). Установлено, что у обследованных женщин основное место в генезе бесплодия занимают гормональные дисфункции (диффузный зоб при субклиническом гипотиреозе, овариальная недостаточность с нарушением менструальной функции, синдром поликистозных яичников, гиперандрогения, недостаточность лютеиновой фазы, нарушение фолликулогенеза), а также а также воспалительные заболевания мочеполовой системы (TORCH-инфекции). У обследованных мужчин основную роль в генезе бесплодия играют гормональные дисфункции (андрогенная недостаточность, связанная с избыточной массой тела, нарушением сперматогенеза, гипергонадотропным и гипогонадотропным гипогонадизмом).

Ключевые слова: репродуктивное здоровье, бесплодие, мужской и женский гипогонадизм.

Introduction. The problem of infertility in marriage, despite significant advances in diagnosis and treatment, remains the most pressing medical and social problem of our time [3–10]. According to WHO (1993), with an infertility rate of 15% and above, its impact on demographic indicators significantly exceeds the total impact of miscarriage and perinatal losses, and therefore this problem has not only medical and biological, but also important social significance [8, 11]. In this regard, WHO has developed a special research program on human reproduction, the main directions of which are studying the frequency and causes

of infertility, standardizing the examination of infertile couples [11]. According to WHO estimates, in Uzbekistan the frequency of infertile marriages significantly exceeds the critical level and is becoming a national problem. Despite the urgency of the problem, there is no unified methodology for identifying and examining infertile couples [1, 2]. In addition, a number of medical and social aspects of this problem have not yet become the subject of scientific analysis. The problem of individual prediction of the risk of female infertility has not been solved. Despite a significant number of publications devoted to various issues of infertility, insufficient attention is paid to the prevention of this pathology [3]. According to O.N. Petrushenkova [7], the frequency of infertility at a large industrial enterprise involved in the automotive industry was 15.1%, which exceeds the critical level determined by WHO experts (15%), at which infertile marriage represents a national problem due to its significant impact on demographic indicators. The prevalence of primary female infertility was 4.5%, secondary - 10.6% [7]. It has been shown that infertility in marriage is caused by impaired reproductive function of women in 83.1% of cases. In 16.9% of married couples suffering from infertility, reproductive dysfunction was diagnosed in both spouses. The structure of the causes of female infertility is dominated by: tubal-peritoneal factor (38.5%), endocrine infertility (27.7%), genital endometriosis (23.0%). In 50.8% of women, infertility is caused by a combination of 2–4 factors. The most common causes of male infertility are: idiopathic oligozoospermia (36.3%), genital infection (27.3%) and varicocele (18.2%).

Purpose of the study— to study the structure of the causes of infertility in men and women in the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region according to screening data.

Material and research methods. From October 2020 to June 2023, we conducted sociological and medical studies in a comparative aspect among families from rural and urban areas in the context of individual territories representing the corresponding regions of the country, in order to determine the causes of infertility (endocrine, non-endocrine, etc.) in spouses and selection of further management tactics and possible treatment (Samarkand and Samarkand region: Nurabad, Urgut and Pstdargom districts). A total of 100 married couples were examined - 200 people (100 men and 100 women of fertile age). The study material included men and women of reproductive age who are in infertile marriages and undergoing treatment for infertility or are registered in regional endocrinological dispensaries. The sample size is 200 people (100 men and 100

women), or 100 families. The study covered families in the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region - 50 families each (Nurabad, Urgut and Pastdargom districts). Also, 50 individuals were examined using the Beck Anxiety Inventory (25 men and 25 women). The following methods were used during the study: the first stage - focus group, conversation, questionnaire for identifying depression and anxiety (Beck); as well as specially developed questionnaires for this medical study, etc.; the second stage is sampling. All study participants were divided into four groups. The first group is women suffering from infertility, aged 18 to 35 years. The second group is men suffering from infertility, aged 25 to 40 years. The third group is parents whose child (male or female) suffers from infertility. The fourth group is representatives of social institutions of the local community: leaders and activists of the mahalla committee, leaders and members of the mahalla women's council, doctors of the local medical institution. In mixed groups (third and fourth), the distribution of participants by gender was also taken into account, i.e. the marginal ratio was 7:3. A total of 8 focus groups were conducted, with a focus group including 20 people. Sociological questionnaires have been developed for focus groups - separately for the husband, for the wife, and for the mother-in-law. During the study, 50 people (25 couples) out of 200 participants underwent psychological testing (Beck Anxiety and Depression Inventory). The answer in the first column is 0 points, the answer in the second column (slightly) is 1 point, the answer in the third column (moderate) is 2 points, the answer in the fourth column is 3 points. Then all points are summed up. The total score is interpreted as follows: 0–5 points—normal anxiety, 6–8—mild anxiety, 9–18—moderate anxiety, above 19—high anxiety. At the third stage, if necessary, patients were sent for further examination: CT/MRI of the pituitary gland, ultrasound of the genital organs, hormonal studies (LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone, testosterone, TSH, prolactin), folliculometry (FM), spermogram, etc. FM was performed vaginally with ultrasound method starting from the 7th–8th day of the menstrual cycle (MC). For completeness of information, FM data were compared with BT and hormonal parameters.

Research results and discussion. The frequency of complaints of respondents on the Beck anxiety scale for the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region is presented. According to the results of the analysis of the Beck scale, as can be seen from the table. 1, residents of Tashkent and the Samarkand region are not significantly susceptible to depression and anxiety in relation to infertility. Of the 200 men and women examined in Samarkand and the Samarkand region, 40 women and 40 men were examined, married from one to

five years and suffering from primary or secondary infertility. In table. Figure 2 shows the structure of the causes of infertility in examined women aged 25 to 35 years suffering from infertility in Samarkand and the Samarkand region. As can be seen, in the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (diffuse goiter with subclinical hypothyroidism, ovarian failure with menstrual dysfunction, polycystic ovary syndrome, hyperandrogenism, luteal phase deficiency, impaired folliculogenesis), as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system (TORCH - infections). The structure of the causes of infertility in examined men aged 25 to 40 years suffering from infertility in Samarkand and the Samarkand region is given. In the examined men from the city and village, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism). Thus, in men with infertility, significantly low values of average values of LH, FSH, free and total testosterone (hypogonadotropic hypogonadism) were found against the background of normoprolactinemia. Women were characterized by significantly low levels of LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone on the 14th day of MC against the background of hyperprolactinemia, that is, anovulatory cycles. Infertility does not have a direct negative impact on the process of socialization of people with this diagnosis in the family, in the local community and at work [12]. This revealed fact indicates a deep transformation of values taking place in society. According to the modern understanding of the hierarchy of values, a person in himself is the highest value, without taking into account whether he is capable or incapable of childbearing. The reproductive function of a person is important, one might say the most important, for a person and for society, but it is not decisive, primary and decisive in determining the meaning of a person's life [13, 14]. Thus, for the normal and full socialization of a person diagnosed with infertility into public, social institutions, there are no objective or subjective obstacles. The socialization of people diagnosed with infertility depends critically on family members, and primarily on the husband or wife and their parents [16, 17].

Conclusions

1. According to the results of the Beck scale, residents of Tashkent and the Samarkand region are not significantly susceptible to depression and anxiety regarding infertility.

2. In the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction, as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system.

3. In the examined men, the main role in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism). 4. In men with infertility, significantly low values of average values of LH, FSH, free and total testosterone (hypogonadotropic hypogonadism) were found against the background of normoprolactinemia. Women were characterized by significantly low levels of LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone on the 14th day of the menstrual cycle against the background of hyperprolactinemia (anovulatory cycles).

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет и COVID-19. Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. Научный журнал. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржоновна КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. MiastoPrzyszłości. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. Educational Research in Universal Sciences. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensi onaldiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash.Science and Education. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection.Science and Education. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. MedFarm. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidsis. Educational Research in Universal Sciences. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. Educational Research in Universal Sciences. 2024;3(4 Special):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. Евразийскийжурналмедицинскихиестественныхнаук. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinova MG. Course of COVID-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2

23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *pedagog.* 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования.* 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health.* 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR).* 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX.* Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149).* 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfiyeva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):346-348.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud.* 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. *1.* Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149).* 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o`zgarishlar.so `ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Pretibial myxedema: pathogenetic features and clinical aspects. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):695-702.
45. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilanbirgalikdakechishxususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(2):516-519.
46. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.* 2023;34:78-81.
47. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):337-340.
48. Daminov AT, Sa`dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(3 special):139-142.
49. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O`g`li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(6):408-412.
50. Ulugbekovna NP, Bakhtiyorovna RI, Almosovich RA, Takhirovich DA. Thyroid Diseases during Pregnancy and their Impact on Maternal and Fetal Outcomes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149).* 2023;1(8):188-190.
51. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Time-restricted nutrition as a new strategy for the therapy of obesity and comorbid conditions. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(4 special):660-667.
52. Nilufar R, Adkhamjon K. TO The development of cardiovascular diseases effects of environmental factors. *Fan, ta`lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya jurnali / Journal of science, education, culture and innovation.* 2022;1(4):100-101.
53. Xoldorov X, Omonov F, Jumayev I, Daminov AT. Type 1 diabetes as a risk factor for bone health in childhood. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal.* 2023;2(8):131-135.

OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA SOG'LOM TURMUSH TARZINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida inson salomatligi, jismoniy barkamolligi, sog'lom turmush tarzi madaniyatini shakllantirish hamda talaba yoshlarni jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlariga jalb qilish masalalari haqida so'z yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sog'lom turmush tarzi, salomatlik, omil, meyoriy hujjat.

PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses issues of human health, physical fitness, the formation of a healthy lifestyle culture in higher educational institutions, as well as the involvement of students and youth in physical culture and sports activities.

Key words: healthy lifestyle, health, factor, regulatory document.

Kirish. Salomatlik – insoniyat rivojining muhim tarkibiy qismlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Millat salomatligini ta'minlash sog'lom turmush tarzi tufayligina amalga oshiriladi. Sog'lom turmush tarzi - bu faol mehnat, ijod og'ushida yashash, kuchli jismoniy va ruhiy yuklamalarni, o'ta xavfli va zararli ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillarni yengil ko'tara oladigan har tomonlama taraqqiy etgan shaxsning shakllanish jarayonidir. Oliy o'quv yurti talabalari bo'sh vaqtini to'g'ri taqsimlash, kun tartibi, dam olishga va mehnat tartibiga rioya etishi sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarining shakllanishida muhim ahamiyatga egadir.

Sog'lom turmush tarzi to'g'ri ovqatlanish bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkilotining ma'lumotiga ko'ra, jismoniy faollik hamda ovqatlanish me'yor va qoidalariga amal qilmaslik insonning erta o'limiga olib keluvchi qator kasalliklarning rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi. Bundan jiddiy xulosa

qilgan holda zararli odatlardan voz kechib, ommaviy sport bilan doimiy shug'ullanish, to'g'ri ovqatlanish tamoyillariga rioya qilish, xususan tarkibida tuz, qand va yog' miqdori ko'p bo'lgan hamda xamirli taom va shirinliklarni, non mahsulotlarini me'yoridan ortiq iste'mol qilmaslikni, bir so'z bilan aytganda, sog'lom turmush tarzini kundalik hayotga aylantirish zarur ekanligini bugungi davrning o'zi taqozo etmoqda. Sog'lom turmush tarzini hayotga keng tatbiq etish va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari sifatida talabalar orasida sog'lom ovqatlanish madaniyatini keng targ'ib qilish zarur.

Respublikamizda sog'liqni saqlash hamda jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohalarini yanada isloh qilish bo'yicha qabul qilingan normativ-huquqiy hujjatlarda ushbu tizimlarni takomillashtirish bilan bir qatorda, aholi o'rtasida sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish masalalari dolzarb hisoblangan. Jumladan, 2025 yilga qadar O'zbekiston Respublikasi sog'liqni saqlash tizimini, jismoniy tarbiya va sportni rivojlantirish konsepsiyalari hamda sog'lom turmush tarzini keng tatbiq etish va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari tasdiqlandi va ijroga qaratildi [1,3,4].

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. M. Mirziyoyev tomonidan 2020-yil 30-oktabrdagi PF-6099-son Farmoni qabul qilingan. Ushbu farmonning asosiy maqsadi jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanish hamda sog'lom turmush tarzi bo'yicha hayotiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish orqali har bir fuqaroda kasallikka qarshi kuchli immun tizimi paydo bo'lishini ta'minlash, zararli odatlardan voz kechish, to'g'ri ovqatlanish tamoyillariga amal qilish, tiklash va rehabilitatsiya ishlari hamda ommaviy jismoniy faollik tadbirlarini tizimli va samarali tashkil qilish, bu borada tegishli infratuzilma va boshqa zarur shart-sharoitlarni yaratishdan iborat.

Ma'lumki, oliy ta'lim muassasalarida inson salomatligi, jismoniy barkamolligi, sog'lom turmush tarzi madaniyatini shakllantirish uchun kurashar ekanmiz o'z maqsadimizga erishish uchun millatni sog'lom turmush tarzida yashashga o'rgatishimiz kerak bo'ladi. Sog'lom avlod deganda, biz faqat jismonan baquvvat farzandlarni emas, balki ma'naviy jihatdan ham boy va sog'lom avlodni nazarda tutishimiz lozim. Zero, ma'naviy sog'lom bo'lmasdan turib, jismonan sog'lom bo'lish mumkin emas. Har ikkala tushuncha bir biriga mos bo'lib, ham jismonan, ham ma'naviy sog'lom avlodga ega bo'lgan xalqni engib bo'lmaydi. Biz jismonan sog'lom, yuksak ma'naviyatli va yagona milliy g'oya asosida jiplashgan millatni shakllantirishni bosh maqsad qilib qo'yar ekanmiz uni sog'lom turmush tarzida yashashga o'rgatishimiz kerak bo'ladi.

Bugungi kunda jahonda inson salomatligi, jismoniy barkamolligi va imkoniyatlarini o'rganish, jismoniy yetuklikning inson aqliy va ijtimoiy faolligiga ta'sirini o'rganish, xususan, oliy ta'lim tizimi talabarlari ilmiy-amaliy pedagogik modellarini yaratish va ularni amalga oshirishda innovatsion usullar, texnologiyalarni qo'llash maqsadida ko'plab tadqiqot ishlari olib borilmoqda.

Oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarida jismoniy irodalilik, chidamlilik, g'alabaga intiluvchanlik kabi sifatlarning shakllanishida jismoniy tarbiya dars mashg'ulotlarini va sport to'garaklarining ahamiyati yuqoridir. Sababi, talabalarda sportchiga xos xarakter, xislatlar jismoniy tarbiya va sport faoliyatida, to'garaklar orqali asta-sekin shakllanadi hamda bu xislatlar uning doimiy sifatiga aylanadi. Hususan, jismoniy sifatlari yaxshi shakllangan talaba hayotiy faoliyatda ham jismonan baquvvat bo'ladi. Yoshlarni har tomonlama sog'lom, barkamol bo'lib yetishishida jismoniy madaniyat ta'limini milliy qadriyatlarga tayangan holda zamonaviy ko'rinishda tashkil etish, jismoniy tarbiya, sog'lomlashtirish, salomatlikni mustahkamlash, sog'lom turmush tarzini targ'ib qilishda yangicha yondashuv asosida o'tkazishni taqozo etmoqda.

Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish mumkinki, jismoniy barkamollik– ruhiy v aqliy yetuklikning asosi bo'lib, sog'lom tana sog'lom fikrlash qobiliyatiga ega bo'ladi. Shuning uchun, ta'lim tizimi yosh avlodning ham jismoniy, ham ruhiy rivojlanishi uchun qulay sharoitlarni yaratishi kerak. Har bir inson, har bir oila jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan shug'ullanishni odat darajasiga chiqarishi bilan birga, qadriyat sifatida hurmat qilishi jamiyatning uzluksiz ravishda jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Zayniddinov T. B. Sog'lom turmush tarzini to'g'ri tashkil qilishda jismoniy tarbiya va sport mutaxassislarining pedagogik faoliyati //Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan). – 2019. – №. 2 (75). – S. 58-64.
2. Ibraimov X. I. Ta'lim jarayonida jismoniy madaniyat va ruhiy barkamollik uyg'unligi masalalari // “Hozirgi taraqqiyot bosqichida jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlarini tashkil qilishning istiqbollari: muammo va yechimlar”. – 2022. – B. 14.

SPORTCHI FAOLIYATIDA MOTIVATSIYANING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada har qanday sohada, har qanday kasbda psixologiyaning o'rni, jumladan, sport sohasida ham psixologiyaning va eng asosiysi sportchi faoliyatida motivatsiyaning o'rni haqida fikrlar yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Psixologiya, motivatsiya, motiv, extiyoj, istak, xarakat, sportchi, malaka, sport.

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN THE ACTIVITIES OF AN ATHLETE

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Abstract: This article examines the role of psychology in any field, any profession, including in the field of sports, and most importantly, the role of motivation in the activities of an athlete.

Key words: Psychology, motivation, motive, need, desire, action, athlete, skill, sport

Motivatsiya bu – maqsadga yo'naltirilgan hatti -harakatlarni boshlaydigan, boshqaradigan va saqlaydigan jarayon. Motivatsiya xulq- atvorni faollashtiradigan biologik, hissiy, ijtimoiy va bilim kuchlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Asosan motivatsiya ikkita turga bo'linadi. Bular:

- 1) Tashqi turtki motivatsiya
- 2) Ichki motivatsiya.

Tashqi turtki motivatsiya bu – shaxsning tashqi tomonidan kelib chiqadigan va ko'pincha sovrinlar, pul, ijtimoiy tan olish, maqtash kabi mukofotlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ichki motivatsiya bu – shaxsning ichidan kelib chiqadigan motivlar, masalan: muammoni hal qilishda shaxsiy qoniqish uchun murakkab krasvordlarni bajarish v.h.k. Psixologiya, motivatsiya, motiv, sport bu atamalarni o'zaro bir biri bilan bog'lar ekanmiz , sport va sportchi faoliyatida psixologiyaning va motivatsiyaning o'rni va ahamiyati juda katta albatta.

Yosh avlod salomatligini saqlash va mustahkamlash muammosi zamonaviy jamiyatning eng muhim muammolaridan biridir. Motivatsiya bu – kuch va xarakter sizga qiyinchiliklarni, muammolarni ko‘ngilsizliklarni, umidsizliklarni yengishdava kurashishda davom etishga imkon beradi. Motivatsiya cheksiz quvvatga ega bo‘lgan yoqilg‘idir, bu sportchilarni eng mashaqqatli mashq va yutuqlarga erishishiga undaydi. Motivatsiya har bir buyuk sportchi va har qanday katta sport yutug‘i uchun muvaffaqiyatningasosiy kalitidir.

Sportchi motivatsiyaning xususiyatlari, sportchi motivatsi amalda odatdagidek bir xil. Bir nechta o‘zgarishlar bilan sportchi motivatsiyasi ikki qismdan iborat. Bular:

- 1) Qisqa muddatli
- 2) Uzoq muddatli.

Qisqa muddatli motivatsiya bu – shu yerda va hozirda to‘siqni yengib o‘tish, muayyan vaqt ichida aniq maqsadga uchun qaror qilish. Uzoq muddatli motivatsiya bu – katta maqsadga erishish uchun qaror, bu yo‘l kichik muvaffaqiyatlardan iborat. Yuqoridagi fikrlarga asoslangan holda sport va sportchi faoliyatida motivatsiya. Biron bir bellashuv yoki mashg‘ulot oldidan ishtirokchilarga ya’ni sportchilarga murabbiy tomonidan motivatsiya beriladi. Bunda murabbiy yetarlicha bilim va ko‘nikmaga ega bo‘lgan o‘z ishining mutaxassisi bo‘lsa maqsadga muvofiq bo‘ladi. Yoki biron bir jamoaviy o‘yinlar oldidan ham bu hodisani yaqqol ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Ko‘pincha o‘yin oldidan (asosan raqib jamoa kuchli bo‘lsa) murabbiy jamoaning jangovor holatini ko‘tarish maqsadida jamoadagi motivni kuchaytirish uchun suxbat o‘tkazadi va jamoani jangga yani o‘yinga tayyorlaydi.

I.A.Djidaryanning fikriga ko‘ra “sportchi faoliyatining motivatsiyasi” tushunchasiga quyidagicha izoh berish mumkin: “Motivatsiya bu – sportchishaxsining o‘ziga xos holati bo‘lib, u o‘zining ehtiyoj va imkoniyatlarini sport faoliyati predmeti bilan o‘zaro bog‘liqligini ta’minlashi natijasida o‘sha vaqtdagi sport natijasini yuqori darajasiga erishish maqsadini amalga oshirish asosida namoyon bo‘ladi” .

Albatta, bu ta’rif motivatsiya to‘g‘risidagi yakuniy xulosa emas, uning mohiyati sportchini yuqori sport natijasiga intilishiga nima turtki berishining sababi to‘g‘risida sport mutaxassiga yo‘llanma berishi bilan izohlanadi.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo‘lsak sport va sportchi faoliyatida nafaqat kuch, mashq, mashg‘ulot va eng asosiysi psixologiya va motivatsiya ham juda katta o‘rin egallaydi. Jannatmakon yurtimizda sport va sportchilar faoliyatiga juda katta e’tibor qaratilgan. Sport turlari judayam ko‘p va ularning faoliyatida,

muvaffaqiyatidan psixologiya va motivatsiyaning o'zni ham beqiyos. Muhtaram yurtboshimiz ham yosh avlod va kelajak ravnaqi uchun sport sohaslarini rivojlantirish va yuksaltirish yo'lida juda katta islohatlar olib bormoqdalar Jumladan, futbol va futbolchi faoliyatida motivatsiyaning o'rniga keladigan bo'lsak, rivojlanib, o'sib borishar ekan albatta muvaffaqiyatga erishiladi va bu jarayonda ularga motivatsiya eng katta kuch bo'ladi desak adashmagan bo'lamiz nazarimda. Motiv va motivatsiyasiz hech qanaqa yutuq va muvaffaqiyatga erishib bo'lmaydi va insonni kuch g'ayratga to'la bo'lib yurishida motivatsiyaning alohida o'zni bor.

Mashhur "Real" futbol jamoasining murabbiysi Zinedin Zidan o'zining ikkinchi murabbiylik davridagi ilk mag'lubiyati futbolchilarda motivatsiya yetarli emasligi bilan ham qisman bog'liq ekanini ta'kidladi. Shunday ekan futbolchilar balki boshqa sport va sportchilar faoliyatida ham motivatsiyaning alohida o'zni bor. Maydonga yig'ilgan futbolchilar jamoasining motivatsiyasi ya'ni kuchi faqatgina ularning o'zlarida emas balki ularning kiygan kiyimlari, murabbiyning mahorati va futbolchilarga eng katta kuch va motivatsiya ularning maydonga yig'ilgan muhlislari ularning qichqiriqlar, qarsaklari va qo'llab quvvatlashlari futbolchilar uchun balki boshqa soha vakillari uchun ham katta motivatsiya bo'ladi. Futbolchilar o'yin jarayonida ularga bo'lgan ishonchni ko'taringki kayfiyatni o'qishlarni va eng asosiysi o'zlarining vatan bayrog'ini ko'rib, xalqning ishonchini oqlash uchun o'zlariga motivatsiya olib astoyidil harakat qilishadi. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash joizki yuqorida aytilganimizdek nafaqat futbol balki boshqa jamiki sohalarda faoliyat bilan birgalikda psixologiya va motivatsiyaning o'zni beqiyos va tugalmas o'rin olgan desak adashmagan bo'lamiz nazarimda. Insoniyat hayot kechirib istiqomat qilib borar ekan albatta mag'lubiyatlar ularning ketidan g'alabalar kelib ketaveradi. Inson mag'lubiyatga yuz tutgan vaqtlarida ham albatta psixologiyaga yuzlanadi va o'zi uchun kerakli bo'lgan motivatsiyani olib yana hayotda olg'a qadam tashlash uchun kuch yog'adi. Psixologiya, motiv va motivatsiya insoniyat hayotida juda katta o'rin egallagan desak hech ham adashmagan bo'lamiz albatta.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati.

1. Arziqulov Dilshod Ne'matovich Psixologiya va sport psixologiyasi. Chirchiq
2. Oybek Hayitov Sport faoliyati psixologiyasi. Toshkent 2021.
3. Y.Mashrapov Sport psixologiyasi. Toshkent 2018. 4. R.Mahmudov va A.G'ulomov Sport psixologiyasi fanidan tavsiyanomalar. Toshkent 2008. 5. Baratov.Sh.R Psixologiya nazariyasi va tarixi. Toshkent 2019.
4. Djuxonova, N., & Qovlonbekov, A. (2023, February). Oilaviy nizolar va ularning tavsifi. In Conference Zone (pp. 289-296).

5. Ibrohimjonovna, T. N. (2023). Oiladagi ajrimlarni psixologik muhokamasi. *Ijodkor o'qituvchi*, 3(30), 463-466.
6. Abdulaziz, Q. (2023). Oilaviy ajrimlarni oldini olishda nikoh oldi omillarining ahamiyati va oila mustahkamligiga ta'siri. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(9), 1490-1497.
7. Abdullajon o'g'li, Q. A. (2022). O'smirlarda ichki nizolarning psixologik xususiyatlari, ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari va hamkorlik masalalari. *Pedagogs jurnali*, 11(2), 22-30.
8. Mirzayeva, D., & Ergashov, U. B. (2023). Dastxat matn sifatida. *Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана*, 1(5 Part 2), 60-62.
9. Ergashev, U. B. (2023). Sportchilar faoliyati davomida xorijiy tillarning o'rni va ahamiyati. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 387-390.
10. Ulug'bek, E. (2023). dastxat matnlarida murojaat shakllarining qo'llanishi. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 15, 453-459.
11. Nurmatova, M., Ergashov, U. B., & Ergasheva, S. (2023). Pragmalingvistikaning shakllanishi va o'rganilishi. *Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана*, 1(5 Part 2), 23-24.
12. Usmonova, D., & Ergashov, U. B. (2023). Dastxat matnlarining grammatik xususiyatlari. *Наука и инновация*, 1(7), 18-20.
13. Ergashov, U., & Rahimov, Z. (2023, May). Signature and its relationship to speech styles. In *International Conference on Business Management and Humanities* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 68-69).
14. Ergashov, U., & Sulaymonov, M. (2023). Sportchilar dasxatlarining funksional ahamiyati va xoslanishining bugungi kundagi o'rni. *Gospodarka i Innovacje.*, 32, 1-4.

MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI MODELI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ma'lumotlar bazasini tanlanlash va o'rnatib ko'rish. Tanlangan ma'lumotlar bazasi turini va tilini hisobga olish va ma'lumotlar bazasini o'rnatib ko'ring. bu, dasturni ishga tushirish va ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun iloji bor bo'lgan platformani belgilashdir. Ma'lumotlarni yozish va o'qish uchun interfeysni yaratish. ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'qish, yangilash va o'chirish uchun foydalanuvchi interfeysini yaratish kerak. Bu interfeys, dasturning ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan qanday muloqot qilish haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Ma'lumotlar, baza, interfeys, madel, tur, qo'shish, ayirish

DATABASE MODEL

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Abstract. This article is about selecting and installing a database. Try installing the account and database for the selected database type and language. this is to specify the platform where it is possible to run the application and store the data. Create an interface for writing and reading data. you need to create a user interface to add, read, update and delete data. This interface describes how the application communicates with the database.

Key words. Data, base, interface, model, type, addition, subtraction

Kirish. Ma'lumotlar bazasi modeli qurish uchun bir nechta asosiy qadamlar mavjud. quyidagi jarayon ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurish uchun umumiy qadamlarni ta'riflaydi.

Kerakli ma'lumotlarni aniqlang. ma'lumotlar bazasining asosiy qadami, ma'lumotlar turi va strukturasi bo'yicha qanday ma'lumotlarni saqlash kerakligini aniqlashdir. bu qadamda, maqsad va talablarga muvofiq ma'lumotlarni tanlash juda muhim.

Ma'lumotlar strukturasi (schema) tuzing. ma'lumotlar bazasining tuzilishi yoki shema tuzilishi, saqlangan ma'lumotlarning turlari, ularning aloqasi va qanday xususiyatlarini o'z ichiga oladi. ma'lumotlar bazasining qo'llaniladigan tili (sql, nosql) va ma'lumotlar bazasining turlari (relational, document-based, graph, etc.) ham bu jarayonning bir qismini bildiradi.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini tanlang va o'rnatib ko'ring. tanlangan ma'lumotlar bazasi turini va tilini hisobga oling va ma'lumotlar bazasini o'rnatib ko'ring. bu, dasturni ishga tushirish va ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun iloji bor bo'lgan platformani belgilashdir. Ma'lumotlarni yozish va o'qish uchun interfeysni yaratish. ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'qish, yangilash va o'chirish uchun foydalanuvchi interfeysini yaratish kerak. bu interfeys, dasturning ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan qanday muloqot qilishini belgilaydi.

Ma'lumotlarni kirishing va chiqarish uchun operatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash. ma'lumotlarni ma'lumotlar bazasiga kiriting va uningdan chiqarishni o'rganish juda muhim. buning uchun moslashtirilgan so'rov tili va metodlarni o'rganishingiz lozim. Xavfsizlik vaqti. ma'lumotlarni himoyalash juda muhim. ma'lumotlar bazasi xavfsizligi uchun xavfsizlik protokollari, autentifikatsiya va avtorizatsiya usullari qo'llanilishi kerak.

Indekslash va optimallashtirish. ma'lumotlar bazasining tez ishlashini ta'minlash uchun ma'lumotlar bazasini indekslash va so'rovni optimallashtirish zarur bo'ladi. Ushbu qadamlar, ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurishda asosiy elementlardir. har bir qadamni diqqat bilan bajarish, ma'lumotlar bazasining ishlashini saqlashga yordam beradi. Ma'lumotlar bazasi (mb) modeli, ma'lumotlar bazasini (mb) yaratish va uni qo'llab-quvvatlashda foydalaniladigan boshqa yordamchilar va usullar to'plamini aks ettiradi. mb modellari ma'lumotlarni saqlash, boshqarish va ularga kirishni tashkil etadi. ularning o'sishi va aks etishi uchun ma'lumotlarni qanday tashkil etish va ma'lumotlar orasidagi aloqalarni boshqarishga dair ko'p usullar mavjud bo'ladi.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurishni o'rganishda quyidagi bosqichlar o'rinli. ma'lumotlar bazasini talab qilish (requirements analysis). bu bosqichda,

tizimning kerak bo'lgan ma'lumotlar turi va miqdori aniqlanadi. talablar tashkil etishning yo'l harakatlari shuni o'z ichiga oladi: ma'lumotlar bazasining turi (relational, nosql, graph, va h.k.), ma'lumotlar bazasining o'lchami, yozuvlar soni, xususiyatlari va boshqalar.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi skemasi (database schema) yaratish. skema, ma'lumotlar bazasidagi jadvallar (tables), ustunlar (columns), indekslar va boshqa obyektlarni belgilovchi bog'lanishlar tuzilishidir. mb modelini yaratishda skema shakllanadi va ma'lumotlar o'z joyini topadi.

Ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'zgartirish, o'chirish (crud) operatsiyalari. ma'lumotlarni qo'shish, o'zgartirish, o'chirish va ma'lumotlarni ko'rish (read) operatsiyalari mb modelini ishlatishning asosiy qismlaridan biridir.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish. mb boshqarishda, ma'lumotlarni saqlash, ularga kirishni boshqarish, xavfsizlik va farq qiluvchi huquqni boshqarish kabi muammolarga duch keladi. bu qisimda, mb uchun interfeys tuzish, monitoring va tuning usullari, ma'lumotlar tarqatma va tiklama (backup and recovery) jarayonlarini belgilash kabi chora-tadbirlar amalga oshiriladi.

Integratsiya va boshqa sistemalar bilan aloqa. ko'p ma'lumotlar tizimlari boshqa tizimlar, xizmatlar, yoki ilovalar bilan integratsiya qilinishi kerak. mb modellari, boshqa sistemalar bilan to'lovlarni amalga oshirish va ma'lumot almashishni osonlashtirish uchun imkoniyatlarni ta'minlaydi.

Tizimni monitoring qilish va o'zgartirishlar kiritish. tizimning ishlash holatini nazorat qilish, monitor qilish va zarur bo'lgan o'zgartirishlarni kiritish, buning orqali tizimni mustahkamlashning muhim qismlaridan biridir.

Dastur tuzish bo'yicha ko'p texnologiyalarni, masalan, sql, nosql, mongodb, mysql, postgresql, firebase, va h.k. ishlatish mumkin. shuningdek, obyektory tuzilmalarda, entity-relationship (er) modellari va yoshlar uchun tuzilmalar uchun klass va jadvallar ishlatish mumkin.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi modeli qurish quyidagi bosqichlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Malablar tushirish. ma'lumotlar bazasi modelini qurishdan oldin, talablarni tushirish kerak. bu, qaysi ma'lumotlar saqlanishi kerakligini, ularning formati, aloqador so'rovlarni qanday bajarish, va ma'lumotlarga qanday qo'shimcha operatsiyalarni amalga oshirish kerakligini o'z ichiga oladi.

Ma'lumotlar modelini rivojlantirish. ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun kerakli tuzilmalar va algoritmlarni rivojlantirish. bu qadamda, ma'lumotlarni qanday kiritish, o'qish, yangilash, va o'chirish kerakligini belgilash kerak. Xa'lumotlar bazasini rivojlantirish. ma'lumotlar bazasini qanday saqlash va boshqarishni rivojlantirish. bunda, ma'lumotlarni strukturizatsiya qilish, indekslash,

bog'lovchilar, ma'lumotlar bazasiga so'rov yozish, va boshqa muhim jarayonlarni belgilash kerak.

Xavfsizlik. ma'lumotlar bazasining xavfsizligi muhimdir. ma'lumotlarni himoyalash, ruxsat berish vaqtlarini boshqarish, avtorizatsiya va autentifikatsiya tuzilmalari qo'llanish kerak.

Testlar va tahlil. modelni test qilish va tahlil qilish uchun testlarni yaratish. bu, modelning ishlashini tekshirish, muammolarni aniqlash va ularni tuzatish uchun muhimdir. Monitoring va optimallashtirish. ma'lumotlar bazasi va modelni monitoring qilish, ularning ishlashini to'g'ri kelish uchun kerak. muammolar aniqlanganida, modelni yangilash va optimallashtirish lozim.

Integratsiya. ma'lumotlar bazasi va modelni dasturlash tillari, frameworklari yoki boshqa dasturlash vositalari bilan integratsiya qilish.

Dokumentatsiya. barcha qadamlarni, ma'lumotlar bazasini, modelni, va dasturlashni tushunadigan dokumentatsiya yaratish. Bu bosqichlarni tuzish, modelni ishga tushirish va uning ishlashini ta'minlashda yordam beradi. har bir tashqi ma'lumotlarni integratsiya qilish, ma'lumotlar bazasini tozalash va tuzatish, hamda dastur tuzilishini rivojlantirish jarayonida o'zining o'ziga xos muammolari bo'ladi.

Asosiy qism. Ma'lumotlar bazalari bilan ishlash (yaratish, tanlash, o'chirish).

Dasturni ishga tushirish uchun u ishga tushirilganda u ishlaydigan ma'lumot bazasini yaratish kerak (barcha ma'lumotlar u erda saqlanadi). axborot bazasini yaratish rejimiga o'tish uchun dasturni ishga tushirish oynasida "qo'shish" tugmachasini bosish kerak. natijada, rasmda ko'rsatilgan oyna.

Ma'lumotlar modellari turli sohalarda, maqsadlari va platformalarda farqli bo'lishi mumkin. Ammo umumiy maqsadlar uchun, quyidagi jarayonni foydalanish mumkin:

Ma'lumot to'plash. Ma'lumotlar to'plangan va tarqalgan bo'lishi kerak. Bu ko'p o'chib ketishi mumkin, ammo boshqa uchun o'rganishda yoki dasturlar ustida tajribani oshirishda foydalanishingiz mumkin.

Tahlil va O'rganish. Ma'lumotlar analiz qilinishi, to'g'rilanishi, xilma-xil qismlarga bo'lishi kerak. Bu, asosiy maqbul narsalarni aniqlash va ularni ma'lumotlar modellari uchun yo'nalish bilan ta'minlashga yordam beradi.

Modelning O'rnatilish. Modelning o'rnatilishi o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar bo'yicha, masalan, kategoriyalar, eigenvectors, yoki ko'nikma. Modelni O'qish. Modelni yaratish uchun o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar asosida uni o'qish. Bu

algoritmlar uchun ma'lumotlarning bir qismini modelning biror qismini aniqlash uchun o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar asosida egallaydi.

Testlash va Baholash. Modelni tekshirish uchun mustahkam va mustahkam bo'lishi kerak. Bu to'g'ri natijalarni ta'minlash va uni optimallashtirishga yordam beradi.

Ommaviy Tarqatish. Modelni ishga tushirish uchun uni amalga oshirish uchun integratsiyaga tayyorlash. Bu xizmatning keng tarqalishi, API orqali qo'llanish yoki dastur tizimi ichida integratsiya qilishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Bu umumiy jarayonni tushuntirish uchun yordam beradi, ammo maqsadga mos holda ushbu jarayonni dastlabki qadamlariga o'zgartirishingiz mumkin. Maqsadlar, ma'lumotlar va dastur orqali platformalarga bog'liq bo'lgan ma'lumotlar modellari uchun o'zgarimoqchi bo'lgan turlicha muammolarni yechish uchun o'zingizga mos usulni tanlashni maslahat beraman.

Ma'lumotlar modellari kabi tushuncha bilan tanishishdan, ularning turlarini, tasniflarini o'rganishdan, shuningdek, batafsil tavsifni ko'rib chiqishdan oldin, ushbu tushunchalarni va barcha sohalarni o'z ichiga olgan informatikaning ma'nosini tushunishimiz kerak., o'rganigan. Ushbu maqolada biz ushbu fanning asosiy atamalari va ustunlarini ko'rib chiqamiz, xususan, ma'lumotlar tuzilmalarining turlari, ulardagi munosabatlar va boshqalar haqida gapiramiz.

Ma'lumotlar modeli tuzilishini o'rganishga o'tish uchun siz ushbu ma'lumotlar va ma'lumotlarning printsiplial jihatdan nima ekanligini tushunishingiz kerak.

Mutlaqo insoniyat jamiyati mavjudligining har qanday daqiqasida ma'lumot juda katta rol o'ynadi, ya'ni inson tomonidan atrofimizdagi keng va xilma-xil dunyodan olingan ma'lumotlar. Misol uchun, hatto ibtidoiy odamlar ham bizga qoyatosh rasmlari yordamida o'zlarining oddiy turmush tarzi va an'analari haqida ma'lumot qoldirgan. O'shandan beri odamlar ko'plab ilmiy kashfiyotlar qilishdi, o'zlarining o'tmishdoshlari haqida ma'lumot to'plashdi va kundalik ma'lumotlarni to'plashdi.yangiliklar, shu tariqa tobora ko'proq hajmdagi ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lib, ularga qimmatlilik va ishonchlilik kabi sifatlarni beradi.

Vaqt o'tishi bilan ma'lumotlar miqdori shunchalik katta va ulkan bo'lib qoldiki, insoniyat uni mustaqil ravishda o'z xotirasida saqlash, uni qo'lda qayta ishlash va unda biron-bir amalni bajarishga qodir emas edi. Aynan shuning uchun ham bugungi kundagi fundamental fan - informatikaga ehtiyoj paydo bo'ldi, uning ko'lami axborotning turli xil o'zgarishlari bilan bog'liq bo'lgan inson faoliyati sohasini o'z ichiga oladi. Informatika hayotimizning deyarli barcha

sohalarini qamrab oladi: oddiy matematik hisob-kitoblardan tortib murakkab muhandislik va arxitektura dizaynigacha, shuningdek, animatsion va animatsion filmlar yaratishgacha. U o'z oldiga axborotni avtomatlashtirilgan qayta ishlash, tizimlashtirish, saqlash va uzatish kabi asosiy maqsadlarni qo'yadi.

Bugungi mavzuda biz ma'lumotlarning tuzilishiga alohida to'xtalamiz, ya'ni ma'lumotlar modeli haqida gapiramiz. Biroq, bundan oldin suhbatimiz mavzusiga bevosita bog'liq bo'lgan boshqa ba'zi fikrlarga aniqlik kiritish kerak. Ya'ni: ma'lumotlar bazalari va DBMS.

Ma'lumotlar bazalari (MB) tuzilgan ma'lumotlar turidir.

Bu atama mantiqiy bog'liq bo'lgan umumiy ma'lumotlar to'plamiga ishora qiladi. Ma'lumotlar bazalari - bu katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lgan dinamik saytlarda faol foydalaniladigan tuzilmalar. Masalan, bu turli xil onlayn-do'konlarning resurslari, mablag'lar portallari ommaviy axborot vositalari yoki boshqa korporativ manbalar.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimlari (DBMS) - ma'lumotlar bazalarini yaratish, ularni kerakli shaklda saqlash va ulardagi kerakli ma'lumotlarni tezkor qidirishni tashkil qilish uchun mo'ljallangan turli xil dasturiy ta'minot to'plami. Keng qo'llaniladigan DBMSga misol sifatida Microsoft Office-ning bir qatorida chiqarilgan Microsoft Access-ni keltirish mumkin. Ushbu ma'lumotlar bazasining o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, unda VBA tili mavjudligi tufayli Accessning o'zida ma'lumotlar bazalari asosida ishlaydigan ilovalar yaratish mumkin.

Ma'lumotlar bazalarini bir nechta turli mezonlarga ko'ra tasniflash mumkin:

- ✓ Model turiga ko'ra (ular muhokama qilinadi).
- ✓ Saqlash joyi bo'yicha (qattiq disk, operativ xotira, optik disklar).
- ✓ Foydalanish turi bo'yicha (mahalliy, ya'ni bir foydalanuvchi unga kirish huquqiga ega; o'rtacha, ya'ni ma'lumotlar bazasidagi ma'lumotlarni bir necha kishi ko'rishi mumkin; umumiy - bunday ma'lumotlar bazalari bir nechta serverlarda va shaxsiy kompyuterlarda joylashgan., ya'ni ulardagi ma'lumotlarni ko'rish imkoniyati juda ko'p odamlarga tegishli).
- ✓ Ma'lumotlar mazmuniga ko'ra (ilmiy, tarixiy, leksikografik va boshqalar).
- ✓ Bazaning aniqlik darajasi bo'yicha (markazlashtirilgan va taqsimlangan).
- ✓ Bir jinsliliigi bo'yicha (mos ravishda heterojen va bir jinsli).

Shuningdek, boshqa ahamiyatsiz funksiyalar uchun.

Bunday ma'lumotlar bazasining asosiy qismi ma'lumotlar modellaridir. Ular ifodalaydixborot tuzilmalari va ularni qayta ishlash, kerakli ma'lumotlarni qidirishni tashkil etish jarayonini soddalashtirish va tezlashtirish bo'yicha operatsiyalar to'plami.

Ma'lumotlar bazalarining xilma-xilligi mavjud, ammo ularning barchasi yanada keng tarqalgan va fundamental modellarga asoslangan. Axborot ma'lumotlari modellarining tasnifi ham juda ko'p turli xil turlarga bo'linadi. Bu erda eng ko'p ishlatiladigan toifalar:

- ✓ ierarxik model;
- ✓ tarmoq diagrammasi;
- ✓ relational model;
- ✓ obyektga yo'n altirilgan sxemalar.

Bu turdagi ma'lumotlar modellarining barchasi bir-biridan ulardagi ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish va saqlash xususiyati bilan farqlanadi.

Foydalanuvchi yuqoridagi har qanday turdagi ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratishi mumkin. Ammo shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, ma'lumotlar modelini tanlash ba'zi omillarga bog'liqlikni aniqlaydi.

Eng muhim mezon - mijoz tomonidan foydalaniladigan DBMS ma'lum bir modelni qo'llab-quvvatlaydimi. Aksariyat DBMSlar shunday tuzilganki, foydalanuvchiga foydalaniladigan ma'lumotlar modeli taqdim etiladi, biroq ularning ba'zilari bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta turli analoglarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Keling, ularning xususiyatlarini birma-bir ko'rib chiqaylik.

Bu ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish modellarining turlaridan biri bo'lib, ularni umumiydan xususiya qarab tartiblangan elementlar to'plami sifatida tashkil qiladi.

Tuzilish - bu teskari daraxt. Muayyan faylga kirish uchunbitta yo'l bor.

Ierarxik model uchta asosiy shartga javob berishi kerak:

- ✓ Har bir quyi darajadagi tugunni faqat bitta yuqori darajadagi tugunga ulash mumkin.
- ✓ Ierarxiyada faqat bitta asosiy ildiz tugun mavjud bo'lib, u boshqa tugunlarga bo'ysunmaydi va yuqori darajada.
- ✓ Ierarxiyadagi har qanday tugunga ildiz tugunidan faqat bitta yo'l bor.

Munosabatlar turi birdan ko'pga.

U asosan ierarxiyaga tayanadi va u bilan juda ko'p umumiyliklarga ega. Ularning orasidagi asosiy farq havola turi bo'lib, u ko'pdan ko'pga munosabatni bildiradi, ya'ni havolalar turli tugunlar o'rtasida mavjud bo'lishi mumkin.

Tarmoq modelining afzalligi shundaki, u boshqa modellarga qaraganda xotira va tezlik jihatidan kamroq shaxsiy kompyuter resurslarini sarflaydi.

Ushbu sxemaning kamchiligi shundaki, agar siz saqlangan ma'lumotlarning strukturasi o'zgartirishingiz kerak bo'lsa, siz ushbu tarmoq modeli asosida ishlaydigan barcha ilovalarni o'zgartirishingiz kerak bo'ladi, chunki bunday tuzilma mustaqil emas.

Bugungi kunda eng keng tarqalgan. Ushbu ma'lumotlar modelidagi ob'ektlar va ular o'rtasidagi munosabatlar jadvallar bilan ifodalanadi va ulardagi munosabatlar ob'ektlar sifatida qaraladi. Bunday jadvaldagi ustunlar maydonlar, qatorlar esa yozuvlar deb ataladi. Har bir relyatsion model jadvali mos kelishi kerak quyidagi xususiyatlar:

- ✓ Uning barcha ustunlari mutlaqo bir xil, ya'ni bitta ustunda joylashgan barcha elementlar bir xil turdagi va ruxsat etilgan maksimal hajmga ega bo'lishi kerak.
- ✓ Har bir ustunning o'ziga xos nomi bor.
- ✓ Jadvalda bir xil qatorlar bo'lmazligi kerak.
- ✓ Jadvaldagi satrlar va ustunlarning paydo bo'lish tartibi ixtiyoriy bo'lishi mumkin.

Munosabat modeli, shuningdek, ushbu jadvallar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar turlarini, jumladan, birga-bir, bir-ko'p va ko'p-ko'p munosabatlarini hisobga oladi.

Jadvalli relyatsion modelga asoslangan ma'lumotlar bazalari moslashuvchan, moslashuvchan va yuqori darajada kengaytirilishi mumkin. Har bir ma'lumot obyektiga eng kichik va foydali bo'laklarga bo'lingan.

Obyektga yo'naltirilgan ma'lumotlarni qurish modelida ma'lumotlar bazalari tegishli funksiyalarga ega qayta foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan dasturiy ta'minot elementlari to'plami bilan belgilanadi. Bir nechta ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan ma'lumotlar bazalari mavjud:

- ✓ Multimedia ma'lumotlar bazasi.
- ✓ Gipermatn ma'lumotlar bazasi.

Birinchi media ma'lumotlarini o'z ichiga oladi. U turli xil tasvirlarni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin, masalan, aloqador modelda saqlanmaydi.

Gipermatnli ma'lumotlar bazasi har qanday ma'lumotlar bazasi ob'ektini istalgan boshqa ob'ekt bilan bog'lash imkonini beradi. Bu turli xil ma'lumotlar to'plamida aloqani tashkil qilish uchun juda qulaydir, ammo bunday model o'tkazishda idealdan uzoqdir. raqamli tahlillar.

Ehtimol, ob'ektga yo'n altirilgan model eng ommabop va qo'llaniladigan modeldir, chunki u munosabatlar kabi jadvallar ko'rinishidagi ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin, lekin undan farqli o'laroq, jadval yozuvlari bilan cheklanmaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. "Deep Learning" - Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, va Aaron Courville tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob ma'lumotlar modellari, maxsus maqsadli neuron tarmoqlari, va shunga o'xshash muddatlarga bo'lgan intensiv tushunchalarni bermoqda.
2. "Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning" - Christopher M. Bishop tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob, ma'lumotlar modellari va moslashtirish uchun qo'llaniladigan asosiy tushunchalarni ta'lim etadi.
3. "Hands-On Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow" - Aurélien Géron tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob amaliy ma'lumotlar modellari va TensorFlow, Keras, va Scikit-Learn kutubxonalaridan foydalanishni o'rganishga yordam beradi.
4. "Python Machine Learning" - Sebastian Raschka va Vahid Mirjalili tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob Python kutubxonalarini yordamida ma'lumotlar modellari yaratishni o'rganishni maqsad qilgan.
5. "Data Science for Business" - Foster Provost va Tom Fawcett tomonidan yozilgan bu kitob, ma'lumotlar modellari va o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar bilan ishlashni biznes va ish tajribasiga taalluqli qiladi.

ZAMONAVIY YOSHLAR MA'NAVIY MADANIYATINI BOYIB BORISH OMILLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy jamiyat va uning istiqboli taraqqiyotidagi turli yondashuvlar va yoshlarda moddiy dunyoning o'tkinchiligi, ma'naviy madaniyatning asrlar davomida e'zozlanishi borasidagi tushunchalarni shakllantirishdagi fikrlar yoritilgan

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar ma'naviy madaniyati, jamiyat, taraqqiyot, ma'naviy tarbiya, yangi zamon ma'naviyati, an'analar, qadriyatlar, salohiyat, sotsiogenez

FACTORS OF ENRICHING THE SPIRITUAL CULTURE OF MODERN YOUTH

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Abstract. In this article, various approaches to the development of modern society and its prospects, and thoughts on the formation of young people's understanding of the transitoriness of the material world and the appreciation of spiritual culture over the centuries are highlighted.

Key words: moral culture, society, development, moral education, modern culture, traditions, values, culture, sociogenesis

Bugungi kunga kelib yoshlar masalasi bilan shug'ullanish, ularning intellektual salohiyatini to'laqonli rivojlantirish, bu borada tadrijiylik negizida milliy strategiya va mexanizmlarni yaratish zamon talabiga aylanib qoldi. Bunda yoshlar davr ruhiyati, ma'naviy qiyofasi, ahloqiy ideallari bilan mavjud jamiyatdagi paradigmali holatlarni vujudga keltirib yuboradi. Bu jarayonda ular turli qarama-qarshiliklarga duch kelishi, rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasidan andoza olgan holda voqelikka falsafiy-madaniy nuqtai nazardan yondashishlari namoyon bo'ladi. "Jamiyatda insonning ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijasida olingan ma'lumotlar falsafaning obyektiv qonunlarni ochishi va umumiy kategoriyalarni ishlab

chiqishi uchun empirik ma'lumotlar bo'la oladi". Shu boisdan ulardagi kelajakka qaratilgan ma'naviy madaniyatning ba'zi masalalarini hisobga olish juda muhimdir.

Yoshlarning ma'naviy madaniyati tushunchasi quyidagi tarkibiy qismlarni qamrab kiradi: kognitiv madaniyat; siyosiy madaniyat; ahloqiy madaniyat; huquqiy madaniyat; estetik madaniyat. Ushbu asosiy qismlardan tashkil topgan yoshlar ma'naviy madaniyati insonning barcha ijtimoiy hayot sohalarida mujassamlashadi. Yoshlar ma'naviy madaniyati o'z tarkibiy qismiga ma'naviy tarbiyani ham qamrab oladi. Jamiyatda bu jarayon konsepsiya sifatida odamlarning ilm doirasini kengaytiradi. Maqsad va vazifalarni amalga oshirishda ma'naviy tarbiya tashabbuskorlik, vijdonlilik, poklik, adolat g'oyalariga sadoqat tuyg'ularini qaror toptiradi. Yoshlarda moddiy dunyoning o'tkinchiligi, ma'naviy madaniyatning asrlar davomida e'zozlanishi borasidagi tushunchalarni shakllantiradi. Yoshlarning moddiy madaniyatni o'zlashtirishi natijasi bo'lgan bevosita ma'naviy ishlab chiqarish jarayoni o'zining xilma-xil ko'rinishlari va qiyofalarini ham namoyon etib boradi. Unda yoshlar o'zining iqtidori, intilishi va tashabbuslari bilan ma'naviy jarayonlarni harakatga keltirib boradi "Moddiy madaniyatni ma'naviy madaniyatdan ajratib bo'lmaydi, ayni paytda ma'naviy madaniyat ham moddiy madaniyatsiz yuzaga kelmaydi, ular o'zaro bog'liq holda rivojlanib boradi". Natijada yoshlarning intellektual salohiyati doirasida ma'naviy munosabatlar ham betakror ko'rinishlarda boyib boradi. Shunday ekan, har bir inson hamda kamol topib kelayotgan yosh avlod uchun ma'naviyat suv bilan havodek naqadar zarurligini unutmasligimiz darkor. Ma'lumki, masala va muammoning mohiyatini anglab yetish chog'ida uning mazmunini ochib berish maqsadida ishlatiladigan tushuncha va kategoriyalarning mazmun-mohiyatiga e'tibor qaratish juda muhim sanaladi. Shu ma'noda ma'naviyat va madaniyat tushunchalari ham alohida ilmiy tahlillarga muhtoj bo'lib, ayrim tadqiqotchilar tomonidan muayyan ko'lamda talqin etilgan.

Ma'naviyat tushunchasining ma'no-mazmuni haqida fikr yuritganda uning jamiyatda tutgan rolini teran anglamasdan turib ma'naviy madaniyat haqida so'z yuritib bo'lmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat ma'naviyatning real hodisa sifatida yuzaga chiqishi, uning voqeiy bo'lish jarayonining yuzaga kelishidan iborat. Nazariy ongning bir qismi bo'lgan ma'naviy madaniyatning shakllari amaliyot bilan bog'liq. Voqelikka nisbatan yoshlar ongida ham ma'naviy madaniyatning elementlari shakllanib, milliylik bilan bog'liq ravishda ijtimoiy ong rivojlanadi.

Ma'naviy madaniyat, aslida, kishilik jamiyati tarixida asrlar davomida shakllangan inson tafakkurining mahsuli bo'lib, unda insonning voqelikka stixiyali tarzda yondashuvi asosida ma'naviy dunyoqarash vujudga kelgan. Asta-sekinlik bilan tevarak-atrofdagi narsa va hodisalarga aqliy munosabatning rivojlanishi negizida ma'naviy madaniyat unsurlari ijobiy va foydali ahamiyat kasb etgan va shuning uchun avloddan-avlodga meros sifatida qoldirish uchun zarur deb topilgan. Bu esa, o'z navbatida insonning aql-zakovatida yangicha tafakkur tarzi shakllanishi bilan birga, borliqning narsa va predmetlari, hayvonot olami, koinot, megaolam va umuman dunyo to'g'risidagi qarashlarining kengayishiga olib kelgan.

Ma'naviy ishlab chiqarish jarayonida siyosiy va huquqiy mafkura, falsafa, ahloq, san'at sohasidagi erishilgan yutuqlar saralanib boradi. Ular ma'naviy boyliklarni yaratuvchi shaxslar tomonidan qayta ishlanib, sayqallanadi va odamlarning ehtiyojlarini qondirish tomonga yo'naltiriladi. Shu boisdan "ma'naviy madaniyat – insonning ma'naviy xususiyat va xislatlari, jamiyatning madaniy darajasini aks ettiruvchi tushuncha" sifatida olib qaraladi. Unda insonning oddiy yashashi bilan bog'liq kundalik turmushning muhim ehtiyojlari tizimi jamiyat bilan bog'liq holda ifodalangan.

S.Otamurodov fikriga ko'ra esa, "ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish va o'zlashtirish vositasidir". Bunda voqelikda inson mehnati natijasida yaratiladigan moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar, shaxs ma'naviy qiyofasining yuksalishiga xizmat qiladigan ahloq qoidalariga rioya etish masalalari aks etgan.

Biroq, ushbu o'rinda ta'kidlash lozimki, bizningcha, S. Otamurodovning bu fikri muhokama etilayotgan masala yuzasidan mutlaq haqiqat darajasi uchun da'vogarlik qila olmaydi. Chunki ma'naviy madaniyat voqelikni badiiy aks ettirish tushunchasidan ancha kengroq tushuncha. Binobarin, olimning badiiy aks ettirish jihatini mutlaqlashtiradigan bo'lsak, siyosiy, ilmiy, huquqiy aks ettirish kabi jihatlari ushbu yondashuv doirasiga sig'may qolishi tabiiydir. Shunday ekan, ma'naviy madaniyatni voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishga tenglashtirish asossiz, balki voqelikni badiiy aks ettirishni ma'naviy madaniyatni shakllantirish vositalaridan biri deyish to'g'riroq bo'ladi.

Ma'naviyat asosiy tushunchalar izohli lug'atida "ma'naviyat – inson ruhiy va aqliy olamini ifodalovchi tushuncha" sifatida keltirilgan bo'lsa, O'zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasida esa, "ma'naviyat – kishilarning falsafiy, huquqiy, ilmiy, badiiy, ahloqiy, diniy tasavvurlarini o'z ichiga oladi", deyilgan. Har bir ta'rifning funktsionallik va individuallik jihatlari mavjud bo'lib, inson vujudining ma'nosi,

manfaatlar to‘qnashuviga moyilligi, uning benazir va mukammal mavjudotligini ifodalaydi.

Ma’naviyat bilan madaniyatni tahlil etish chog‘ida ular o‘rtasidagi dialektik aloqadorlik, sinergetik tamoyillar mavjudligini ko‘ra bilish juda muhim. Ma’lumki, ma’naviyat ham, madaniyat ham hech kimda tug‘ma bo‘lmaydi, instinktlar orqali tabiatan berilmaydi. U shaxsning jamiyatda ijtimoiylashuvi negizida ahloq, did, idrok, his-tuyg‘ularning ta’siri ostida shakllanadi va, shunday deyish joiz bo‘lsa, ongsizlikdan onglilik, anglanganlik tomon ulg‘ayishida vujudga keladi. Har bir voyaga yetib kelayotgan yigit-qiz shaxsiy hayotiy tajribasi asosida, mustaqil ravishda bevosita tevarak-atrofdagi kishilarning, jamiyatning va o‘tgan ajdodlarning to‘plagan tajribalarini o‘zlashtiradi. Yoshlar ham ijtimoiy amaliyot mahsuli bo‘lgan madaniyatni o‘zlashtirish bilan birga, unga o‘z ta’sirini o‘tkazadi. Yoshlar ijtimoiy ongining shakllanishi jarayonida moddiy va ma’naviy madaniyatni boyita boradi.

Har bir voyaga yetib kelayotgan yoshlarning oilada, mehnatda, o‘qishda, odamlar orasida va jamiyat ijtimoiy-falsafiy hayotidagi harakatlari ma’naviy madaniyat mezonlari bilan o‘lchanadi. Agarda yoshlar tarbiyasida ana shu umumiy zanjirning birorta bo‘g‘inida uzilish ro‘y bersa, bunda voyaga yetayotgan yoshga ham, jamiyatga hamda oilaga ham ma’lum darajada zarar yetadi. Yoshlarning dunyoqarashi, didi, ilm-fan va kasb-hunarga nisbatan munosabati yordamida ahloqini ham tarbiyalash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ma’naviy madaniyat har bir yoshning birinchi qadamidan, “qush uyasida ko‘rganini qiladi” deganidek, oilada, ota-ona, aka-uka, opa-singil namunasidan boshlanadi. Sekin-asta bog‘cha va maktabda beriladigan ahloqiy saboqlar natijasida jamiyatdagi aloqalarning tobora kengayib borishi orqali butun umri davomida sayqallanib boradi.

Ma’naviy madaniyat aslida ma’lum miqdor, sifat va ma’naviy munosabatlarning to‘plami, inson ongi va ma’naviy faoliyatining mahsuli sanaladi. Unda ma’naviy ong va faoliyat bilan bog‘liq ijtimoiy jarayonlar qonuniy tarzda mavjud jamiyatda o‘sib kelayotgan yosh avlodni ham ruhan, ham ma’nan, ham jismonan kamol topishiga xizmat qilishi oddiy hayot tarzi ta’sirida amalga oshadi. Bu jarayonda yoshlar voqelikka o‘zlarining zavqli munosabatlarini in’ikos ettirib, borliqdagi narsa va hodisalarning mohiyatini anglab boradi. Yoshlar ma’naviy madaniyati deyarli jamiyatning ideallarini qamrab oladigan ma’naviy munosabat, ong, faoliyatning mazmun-mohiyatini o‘zida ifodalaydi. “Binobarin, odamzodning ongiga qanday fikr, g‘oya, nuqtai nazar, olam va unda odamning o‘rni qarashlar to‘g‘risidagi bilim singigan bo‘lsa, shunga muvofiq,

uning fe'l-atvori, hatti-harakati, butun faoliyati tus oladi". Bularning barchasi pirovard oqibatda har bir shaxsning o'zligini tezroq anglashida namoyon bo'ladi.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Ўринбоева, М. С. (2020). Табиатга экологик муносабатларнинг маънавий-ахлоқий тамойиллари ва мезонлари. *Science and Education*, 1(2), 590-596.
2. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
3. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
4. Rasulova, S. A., & Azimov, U. A. (2020). Formation of axiological consciousness in the era of globalization. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(4), 228-231.
5. Akbarovna, U. M. (2019). Rasulova Shoira Azizovna Vliyaniye temperamenta na deyatelnost i povedeniye cheloveka. *Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya*, (19-3), 73.
6. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Инсон ахлоқий-экологик маданиятини фалсафий жиҳатлари. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (82)), 273-275.
7. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Man-ecologist-entonic philosophical culture. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2), 273-275.
8. Тухтаров, И. М., Хакимов, А. М., Олтмишева, Н. Г., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). О модели воспитания нравственной культуры у молодёжи. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (82)), 459-466.
9. Ўринбоева, М. С., & Расулова, Ш. А. Экологик барқарор тараққиётни таъминлашда ахлоқнинг функциялари. Тошкент-2021, 104.

O'SPIRINLARNING AXBOROTDAN FOYDALANISH MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING AXAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada yoshlar o'rtasida axborotlardan foydalanishda mavjud muammolar va axborot madaniyatini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos uslublari, uning yoshlar kamolotidagi tutgan o'rni haqida qarashlar bayon etilgan

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar, axborot, axborot madaniyati, internet, ta'lim

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING A CULTURE OF USING INFORMATION AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation: This article describes the existing problems of the use of information among young people and approaches to the formation of information culture, its role in the development of youth.

Keywords: the youth, information, information culture, the Internet, education

Har qanday mamlakat o'z taraqqiyot yo'lini belgilashda avvalo kelajak rejalarini qurib, unda albatta yoshlarga e'tiborni kuchaytiradi. Shundan kelib chiqadigan bo'lsak bugungi kun jahon hamjamiyati oldida turgan eng muhim masalalardan biri yoshlar masalasidir. Yoshlarga bugungi kun rivojlangan texnologiyalar asri va axborot makoni juda keng imkoniyatlar yaratib berishi bilan birgalikda zararli axborot shaklidagi katta xavfni shakllantirmoqda. Bunday yoshlar kelajagiga o'zining salbiy ta'sirini o'tkazuvchi omillardan ularni asrabavaylash uchun yoshlar o'rtasida axborot madaniyatini rivojlantirish zarur bo'lib, o'z navbatida bu jamiyat siyosiy savodxonligi darajasiga ham yuqori darajada o'zining ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Insoniyat ertangi kuni uchun kurashar ekan bunda yosh avlodning munosib davomchi sifatida shakllanishi uchun har tomonlama chuqur islohotlar amalga oshirib borishi va bunda yoshlarning mas'ullik hissini ham shakllantirib borishi talab etiladi. Sababi yoshlar oldiga qo'yilayotgan maqsadlar ularda qat'iy rioya qilinishi talab etiladigan me'yorlarni

ham yuzaga keltiradi. Yoshlar axborot iste'molchisi sifatida avvalo axborot tasnifini anglashi, ulardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini to'liq anglab yetishi, zararli axborot maydoni ta'siridan o'zini himoya qilish prinsiplarini anglab yetishi, zamonaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanganda talab etiladigan me'yorlarni to'liq anglab yetishi bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan xulosalar bugungi kun talabidir.

Axborot asri insoniyatga tezkor axborot taqdim qilish bilan birgalikda undan noo'rin foydalanish tufayli ko'plab muammolarni shakllantirmoqda, bu o'z navbatida eng katta ta'sirini yoshlar o'rtasida namoyon etmoqda. Shu sababli yoshlar o'rtasida axborotdan to'g'ri foydalanish, ayniqsa o'smir davri yoshlarida axborotdan samarali foydalanish yoki ijtimoiy xavfli axborotlardan ularda immunitet shakllantirish talabi ortib bormoqda.

Mazkur masalada, davlat tomonidan olib borilayotgan islohotlar esa taxsinga loyiqdir. Zero, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoyev "Biz yoshlarga doir davlat siyosatini hech og'ishmasdan, qat'iyat bilan davom ettiramiz. Nafaqat davom ettiramiz, balki bu siyosatni eng ustuvor vazifamiz sifatida bugun zamon talab qilayotgan yuksak darajaga ko'taramiz. Yoshlarimizning mustaqil fikrlaydigan, yuksak intellektual va ma'naviy salohiyatga ega bo'lib, dunyo miqyosida o'z tengdoshlariga hech qaysi sohada bo'sh kelmaydigan insonlar bo'lib kamol topishi, baxtli bo'lishi uchun davlatimiz va jamiyatimizning bor kuch va imkoniyatlarini safarbar etamiz"[1] deb ta'kidlaganida yoshlar orasida har qanday ijtimoiy xavf keltirib chiqaruvchi omillarga qarshi kurashish nazarda tutilgan desak mubolag'a qilmaymiz.

Bugungi jamiyat a'zolari qaysidir ma'noda telekommunikatsiyalar ta'sirida hayot kechirar ekan buning o'z navbatida ham salbiy ham ijobiy xususiyatlari mavjuddir. Ilmiy tahlillarga ko'ra, tezkor axborot va kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi natijasida dunyodagi turli xalqlar va elatlar orasida globallashuv jarayonlari sodir bo'layotgan vaqtda butun insoniyat, jumladan xalqimiz ma'naviyatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatish mumkin bo'lgan turli mafkuraviy tahdidlar asosida yashamoqda.[2]

Butun dunyoda bo'lgani kabi mamlakatimizda ham ta'lim sohasiga zamonaviy qarash va texnologiyalarning keng jalb qilinishi rivojlanib bormoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida ta'lim sohasida ham axborot iste'moli xususiyatlarini ilmiy tadqiq qilish va uning yoshlarga ta'sirini har tomonlama chuqur tahlil qilingan xulosalar shakllantirishni talab etmoqda. Aynan malakatimizda ham axborot olami aynan internet va kommunikatsiya sohasi texnologiyalaridan foydalanish ko'lami ham kun sayin oshib borib, kundalik zaruriy ehtiyoj sirasiga kirib

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bormoqda. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, O'zbekistonda internet xizmatidan foydalanuvchilar soni - 22,1 milliondan oshdi. Shundan mobil internet foydalanuvchilari soni - 19 millionni tashkil etmoqda. Mamlakat bo'yicha aholi punktlarining mobil aloqa bilan qamrab olinishi darajasi 97 foizni, mobil internet qamrovi esa 87 foizni tashkil etdi. 26 mingga yaqin "uz" domenidagi veb-saytlar faoliyat olib bormoqda. 200 dan ortiq veb-sayt ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida ro'yxatga olingan. Internetning ta'sir kuchi beriladigan materiallarning tezkorligi, ko'tarilayotgan masalalarning dolzarbligi hamda tahliliylik darajasi va mavjud muammolarning samarali yechimlarini taklif etishiga ko'p darajada bog'liq.[3] Bu raqamlar o'z navbatida jamiyatning ajralmas qismiga aylanib qolgan axborot olamini yanada chuqurroq anglashga imkon beradi.

Mustaqil O'zbekiston yoshlari rivojlangan texnologiyalar asrida munosib ishtirokchi bo'lib, mazkur sohaga taalluqli mahsulot va vositalardan keng foydalanmoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida axborotdan foydalanish bo'yicha madaniy ko'nikmalarni ijtimoiylashtirish orqali ularning yosh va dunyoqarashidan kelib chiqib axborot iste'molini rivojlantirishni talab etadi. Ta'limni axborotlashtirish strategiyasi va taktikasi ishlab chiqilayotgan bir vaqtda, axborot-resurs markazlarining o'zni ham beqiyosligicha qolmoqda. Unda axborot-resurslarining shiddat bilan kirib kelishi esa axborotlashuv jarayonini yana ham jadallashtirmoqda. Shunga qaramay, badiiy asarlar, qomuslar, lug'atlar, gazeta va jurnallarning tobora katta qismi matnli fayllar ko'rinishida tarqalmoqda. Elektron va bosma nashrlar bir-birini mustasno etmaydi, balki bir-birini to'ldiradi, binobarin, kelajakda kutubxonalarda ham virtual, ham an'anaviy kitobga o'rin topiladi. Kuzatishlarimiz shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, kitobxon texnik va ma'lumotnoma adabiyotlardan ko'proq elektron shaklda foydalanadi.[4]

Shuningdek bugungi kunda yoshlar ayniqsa ular klassifikatori (yosh darajasi)ga ko'ra axborotdan foydalanish ko'nikmalari, ularni ma'naviy dunyosini boyitishda axborot vositalarining o'zni, axborotlarning asnifi va ulardan foydalanish chegaralarini aniqlashda echimini topmagan va ijtimoiy ahamiyati yuqori bo'lgan ilmiy ishlar olib borish zaruratligicha qolmoqda. Yoshlar o'rtasida axborotlardan samarali foydalanishni tashkil etish uchun fanlararo integratsiya rivoji ham alohida o'rin tutadi va bunda aynan pedagogika sohasi bilan axborot texnologiyalari sohasini o'zaro integratsiya qilish orqali ularning pedagogik hamda texnik xususiyatlari bo'yicha iste'molchi bo'lgan yoshlarga ta'sirchan imkoniyatlar yaratish mumkin. Aynan bunda pedagogic tarbiya nuqtai nazari birlamchi omil bo'lib xizmat qilishi lozim.

References

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M.Erkin va farovon, demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz.- T., O'zbekiston: NMIU, 2016. 14-bet.
2. Raxmonaliyevich, T. R. (2022, December). O'smir yoshdagi o'quvchilarda axborotdan foydalanish madaniyatini shakllantirishda ijtimoiy-psixologik omillarning o'rni. In *Interdiscipline innovation and scientific research conference* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 27-29).
3. Qovlonbekov, A. (2023, February). Oilaviy nizolar va ularning tavsifi. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 289-296).
4. Abdulaziz, Q. (2023). Oilaviy ajrimlarni oldini olishda nikoh oldi omillarining ahamiyati va oila mustahkamligiga ta'siri. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(9), 1490-1497
5. Abdullajon o'g'li, Q. A. (2022). O'smirlarda ichki nizolarning psixologik xususiyatlari, ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari va hamkorlik masalalari. *Pedagogs jurnali*, 11(2), 22-30.
6. Ergashov, U., & Rahimov, Z. (2023, May). Signature and its relationship to speech styles. In *International Conference on Business Management and Humanities* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 68-69).

DIFFUZ TOKSIK BUQOQDA IMMUNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR

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Annotatsiya. Maqolaning ushbu sharhi DTB kabi endokrinologiya sohasidagi dolzarb kasallikka bag'ishlangan. Kasallikning klinik ko'rinishlari bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta tizimlarga ta'sir qiluvchi qalqonsimon bez gormonlarning ko'p ajralishi bilan bog'liqligi ko'rsatilgan. Kasallik shakllanishining immunologik mexanizmlari ko'rsatilgan Yurak-qon tomir tizimining shikastlanishi DTB ning tez-tez uchraydigan jiddiy asoratlari bo'lib, u ko'pincha yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarida birinchi o'rinda turadi. Uning klinik ko'rinishi va kasallikning borishi va natijasini aniqlash yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Diffuz toksik buqoq, klinik ko'rinishlari, immunopatogenezi

IMMUNOLOGIC CHANGES IN DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITERS

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Abstract. This review of the article is devoted to an actual disease in the field of endocrinology, such as DTB. It has been shown that the clinical manifestations of the disease are associated with multiple secretions of thyroid hormones that affect several systems at the same time. The immunological mechanisms of the formation of the disease are indicated. Damage to the cardiovascular system is a frequent serious complication of DTB, and it often ranks first among cardiovascular diseases. Its clinical presentation and determination of the course and outcome of the disease are explained.

Key words: Diffuse toxic goiter, clinical manifestations, immunopathogenesis.

Kirish. Diffuz toksik buqoq - bu qalqonsimon bezning autoimmun kasalligi. Qalqonsimon bezda anti-rTTH va aylanib yuruvchi autoantitalarning, va ularni rag'batlantiruvchi autoantitalar gipertiroidizmga olib keladi. DTB qalqonsimon bez antigenlariga, xususan, retseptorlarga nisbatan immunitetning tolerantligining buzilishi natijasida yuzaga keladi. . DTB xavfi ayollar uchun 3% va keksa erkaklar uchun 0,5% ni tashkil qiladi . Kasallik 30 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha ko'p hollarda G'arb mamlakatlari aholilarida uchrashi aniqlangan. Qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining klinik ko'rinishi qalqonsimon bez gormonlarining ko'pligi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta turli xil kasalliklarga olib keladi. Shuning uchun DTB bilan bog'liq belgilar va alomatlar juda katta farq qilishi va umumiy holatga sezilarli darajada ta'sir qilishi mumkin.

Umumiy simptomlar: titroq, yuqori haroratga sezgirlik, odatiy ovqatlanish bilan ham vaznning yo'qolishi, asabiylashish, qalqonsimon bezning kengayishi (buqoq), tartibsiz hayz sikli, erektil disfunktsiya yoki libidoning pasayishi, charchoq, tez-tez yurak urishi va boshqalar . Tireotoksikoz bo'lgan 3000 dan ortiq bemorlarni o'rganishda bemorlarning 50% dan ortig'i 61 yoshdan oshganligi ma'lum bo'ldi va kasallikning har uchtadan 1 tasi kamroq klassik belgilariga ega. Ko'pchilik bemorlarda atriyal fibrilatsiya tez-tez kuzatiladigan belgi sifatida kuzatilgan.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi: Diffuz toksik buqoqda immunologik o'zgarishlarni va bez gormonlarining boshqa kasalliklar kelib chiqishidagi rolini o'rganish.

Tadqiqotning borishi : Tireotoksikoz kamdan-kam hollarda davriy falajlikga olib kelishi mumkin (o'tkir mushaklarning falaji va og'ir gipokaliyemiya). Osiyolik erkaklarda ko'proq uchraydi va ko'pincha infeksiya, spirtli ichimliklar, qiyin hazm bo'luvchi uglevodlar yoki og'ir jismoniy faoliyat tufayli paydo bo'ladi. Tireotoksikozli bemorlarda kamdan-kam hollarda jigar faoliyatining buzilishi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan "qalqonsimon bo'ron" deb ataladigan hayot uchun xavfli holat kuzatiladi, ruhiy holatdagi o'zgarishlar, isitma, qo'zg'alish, yurak etishmovchiligi va taxikardiya belgilari ko'proq uchraydi . Jarrohlik amaliyotlari , tug'ish, infeksiya, travma kabi hodisalar vaziyatni yomonlashtirishi mumkin. DTB oftalmopatiya bemorlarning taxminan 30-50%i da mavjud. Bemorlarda : ko'zda qum yoki begona narsa hissi, haddan tashqari qichishish hissi, (ko'pincha shamol, sovuq havo, yorqin yorug'lik ta'sirida yomonlashadi), diplopiya, retrookulyar og'riq yoki noqulaylik, loyqa ko'rish, rangni ko'rishning desaturatsiyasi, ba'zida ko'rishning yo'qolishi kuzatiladi. DTB oftalmopatiyasining xarakterli belgilari ekzofthalmos (ekzofthalmos), lakrimatsiya

va periorbital shish. Orbital chuqurlik, retrookulyar mushaklarning o'sish darajasi, retrookulyar tolalar va yog 'to'qimalari ekzoftalmos darajasiga ta'sir qiladi. Ekzoftalmos odatda assimetrikdir, lekin simmetrik ham bo'lishi mumkin, bunda ko'z qovoqlari orqasida bosim hissi kuzatiladi. Periorbital shish odatda ekzoftalmozga hamroh bo'lib, uni niqoblab keladi. Ko'p kuzatiladigan yana bir holat bu yurak urishining tezlashishi hisoblanadi. Asosan fibrillatsiya, taxikardiya kabi o'zgarishlar bilan uchrashi aniqlangan. Boshqa autoimmun kasallik bilan assotsiatsiya DTB bilan og'rigan bemorlarning taxminan 20 foizida mavjud. Tadqiqot natijalari DTB bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 16,7 foizida boshqa autoimmun kasallik ham borligini ko'rsatdi: Shegren kasalligi (0,8%), tizimli qizil yuguruk va sarkoidoz (<0,1%), 1-toifa qandli diabet (0,9%), glyuten kasalligi (1,1%), ko'plab sklerozlanishlar (0,3%), revmatik polimiyalgiya (1,3%), revmatoid artrit (1,9%), surunkali autoimmun gastrit (2,4%), vitiligo (2,6%).

DTB ning immunopatogenezi :Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilganidek, qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining boshlanishi qalqonsimon bezga nisbatan immunitetga chidamlilikning buzilishi bilan bog'liq.

Genetik jihatdan ekologik va endogen omillarni o'z ichiga olgan autoimmun multifaktorial jarayon orqali kasallik yuzaga keldi. Ko'p sonli tadqiqotlar qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining faol bosqichi Th1 ustunligi bilan bog'liqligini ko'rsatdi. Immun javob DTB ning nofaol yoki keyingi bosqichlari Th1dan Th2ning immun javobiga o'tish bilan bog'liq. Qizig'i shundaki, xavf bilan bog'liq bo'lgan genlarni hisobga olsak, ma'lum ta'sirga ega bo'lgan taxminan 70% T hujayralarida o'zgarish yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Kasallik patogenezida T limfotsitlarining ahamiyatini katta. DTB da autoimmun reaksiya bezga infiltratsiya qiluvchi B hujayra klonlari tomonidan pTTH ga autoantitalarning ishlab chiqarilishiga olib keladi. Ularning harakatlariga ko'ra, antitanalar TSH-R ni quyidagicha tasniflash mumkin: qalqonsimon bezni ogohlantiruvchi antitanalar (TSAb), tiroid blokirovka qiluvchi antitanalar (TBAb) va neytral antitanalar. pTTH ga antikorlar DTB patogenezida va uning qalqonsimon bezdan tashqari ko'rinishlarida ishtirok etadi. Gipertiroidizm TSAb bilan bog'liq, bunda TSH ning TSH-R ga bog'lanishi bilan bir xil quyi oqim ta'siriga olib keladi, masalan, adenilat siklaza faollashishi keyingi siklik adenozin monofosfat (cAMP) ishlab chiqarishga olib keladi. Bu esa tirotsitlarning ko'payishiga, qalqonsimon bezning o'sishiga va sekretsiyaga olib keladi. Qalqonsimon bez gormonlari (T4 va T3). T4 (va ayniqsa T3) salbiy teskari aloqa orqali oldingi gipofiz bezidan TSH sekretsiyasini ingibatsiya qiladi. Qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarida TBAb va neytral antitalarning roli unchalik aniq emas. TBAblar TSH-R ning A bo'linmasi bilan

bog'lanib, TSH ta'sirini va uning follikulyar hujayralarga ta'sirini bloklaydi. Neytral antitanalar cAMP shakllanishiga yoki TSH bog'lanishiga ta'sir qilmasdan retseptorga bog'lanadi. Shu asosida bez giperplaziyasi, gormon sekretsiyasidagi buzulishlar kelib chiqadi. TG darajasining oshishiga javoban eng erta yurak-qon tomir o'zgarishlar periferik qon tomirlarda qon tomir qarshiligi va venoz tomirlarning siqilishining kuchayishi hisoblanadi. Ushbu o'zgarishlar natijasida qonning teskari oqimi tufayli o'ng bo'lmachada diastolik bosim pasayadi, yurakdan qonning chiqishi refleksli ravishda o'zgaradi. Bir qator tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, DTB da aylanuvchi qon hajmining 30-50% ga kamayishi kuzatiladi. Ushbu o'zgarishlarning molekulyar asoslari to'liq aniq emas. Vazoaktiv omillar (masalan. katexolaminlar, prostatsiklinlar, endotelinlar) tomirlarning silliq mushaklari qisqarishining muhim regulyatorlari bo'lib, ular tizimli qon tomir qarshiligi ta'minlaydi. Nazariy jihatdan, T3 to'g'ridan-to'g'ri silliq mushaklarga ta'sir qilishi mumkin, hujayralar yoki o'z harakatlarini endotelial hujayralar orqali amalga oshiradi, vazoaktiv moddani chiqarishi mumkin. Qisqarish mexanizmi miyokarddagiga o'xshaydi, lekin silliq mushak hujayralarida Ca^{2+} bog'lanadi va kalmodulin deb ataladigan molekulyar kompleks, miyozin yengil zanjirlarini fosforlashtiradigan fermentni faollashtiradi. Bu o'z navbatida, aktinomiozin kompleksida qisqarishni keltirib chiqaradigan o'zaro bog'lanishlarning shakllanishini faollashtiradi. Tizimli qarshilik va yuqoridagi sabablar taxikardiya va aritmiyaga sabab bo'ladi. Bu yural qon tomir tizimida kuzatiladigan asosiy o'zgarishlar hisoblanadi.

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, DTB klinik jihatdan, qon zardobida ATA ning mavjudligi va infiltratsiya bilan tavsiflanadi. Qalqonsimon bezdagi patalogik jarayon autoreaktiv limfotsitlar, autoimmun reaksiyada B hujayra klonlari tomonidan TSAb ishlab chiqarishni keltirib chiqaralishi tufayli sodir bo'ladi. Ushbu antitanalar qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarining patogenezida va uning ekstratiroidal namoyon bo'lishida hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. DTB uchun xavf omillari genetik moyillik va endogen omillar o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirlarni o'z ichiga oladi. DTG ning immunopatogenezida Th1 immun javobi ustunlik qiladi, bunda Th1 ximokinlari asosiy rol o'ynaydi. DTB tomonidan jalb qilingan hujayralarda Th1 limfotsitlari IFN-g va TNF-a ishlab chiqarishini ko'payishiga olib keladi, bu esa Th1 ximokinlarining sekretsiyasini rag'batlantiradi, qalqonsimon bez hujayralari, autoimmun jarayonni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Arteriolalarning silliq mushak hujayralariga ta'sir qiluvchi TG, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri diastolik bosimga va tomirlar qarshiligiga, jumladan, aylanuvchi qon hajmi o'zgarishiga, taxikardiya va aritmiya paydo bo'lishiga olib keladi. Bu taxmin

boshqa tadqiqotlar tomonidan ham tasdiqlanadi . Fenilefrin infuziyasidan keyin DTB bilan og'rigan bemorlarda kasallik va uning asoratlari sezilarli pasayish kuzatildi. Masalan, yurak mushaklarida va boshqa to'qimalarda gipoksiya ancha kamaygan.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод при резус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет и COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *Miasto Przyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.

13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmun tireoidit bilan kasallangan bemorlardagi funksional buzilishlarning differensial diagnostikasida qalqonsimon bez zichligini aniqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2. *1*. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovna XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. HERPETIC MENINGITIS. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
41. Berkinov A, Safarov F, Tursunova S, Daminov AT. Vitamin d status in senior residents of samarkand region. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2023;2(8):136-140.
42. Taxirovich DA, N SY, I IM, Z SM. Vitamin-d yetishmovchiligining qandli diabet 1-tip rivojlanishiga ta'siri. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:74-77.

- 43 Khatamov, O. K., & Ortikov, S. M. (2019). Use from the international experiences in employment the population in uzbekistan. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 364-371.
- 44 Muhammadiyevich, O. S. (2023). Main problems of population employment and ways to solve them. *American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development* (2993-2750), 1(4), 10-13.
- 45 Ismatov, S. A., & Ortikov, S. M. (2020). The population bandhini tamines, turmus of regine oshirildi humiliation tagirova and using Uzbekistana characteristic.(foreign experience in providing employment, improving well-being and its specifics for uzbekistan). *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 521-526.
- 46 Хатамов, О., & Ортиков, Ш. (2019). Аҳоли бандлигини таъминлаш моделлари ва ундан Ўзбекистон шароитида фойдаланиш имкониятлари. *Экономика и инновационные технологии*, (4), 48-59.
- 47 Xatamov, O. Q., & Ortiqov, S. M. (2019). Models of employment of the population and opportunities for its use in the conditions of Uzbekistan. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 2019(4), 8.
- 48 Mukhammadiyevich, O. S. (2023). Experiences in the study and analysis of population employment in foreign countries. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
- 49 Ortikov, S. M. (2021). Experience in statistical study and analysis of employment in foreign countries. *Thematics Journal of Business Management*, 10(7).

BO'LAJAK JISMONIY MADANIYAT O'QITUVCHILARINI TURISTIK FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

Fazliddin Boqiyev

O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti Farg'ona filiali o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasini takomillashtirish ta'limga turli yondashuvlarni birlashtirish hamda amaliy tajribaga sinab ko'rish ko'nikmalarini tarbiyalash va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo'llash bo'yicha ko'rsatlalar berilgan

Kalit so'zlar: Sayyohlik faoliyatini rejalashtirish, nazariy bilimlar, amaliy bilimlar, turizm menejmenti, jismoniy tarbiya, jismoniy mashq, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TRAINING FUTURE PHYSICAL CULTURE TEACHERS FOR TOURIST ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: This article provides instructions on improving the methodology of training future physical culture teachers for tourism activities, combining different approaches to education, training skills to test practical experience, and using modern technologies

Key words: Tourism planning, theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge, tourism management, physical education, physical exercise, knowledge, skills, competence

Jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasini takomillashtirish ta'limga turli yondashuvlarni birlashtirish, amaliy tajribaga urg'u berish, tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini tarbiyalash va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni o'z ichiga qamrab olishni nazarda tutadi. Bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlashni kuchaytirish bo'yicha tuzilgan reja.

Yaxlit o'quv rejasini ishlab chiqish

Nazariy bilimlarni turistik faoliyat bilan bog'liq amaliy ko'nikmalar bilan birlashtirgan o'quv dasturini ishlab chiqish, jumladan, ochiq havoda yetakchilik, navigatsiya, xavflarni boshqarish va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish. Turistik

tajribani har tomonlama tushunish uchun geografiya, ekologiya, turizm menejmenti va madaniyatshunoslik kabi fanlarni o'quv dasturiga kiritish.

Tajribali o'rganish imkoniyatlari.

Sayyohlik faoliyatini rejalashtirish, yetakchilik qilish va baholashda amaliy tajriba bilan ta'minlash uchun ekskursiyalar, amaliyotlar va ochiq havoda ekspeditsiyalarni amalga oshirish.

Mahalliy sayyohlik agentliklari, milliy bog'lar va ochiq havoda ta'lim markazlari bilan hamkorlik qilib, talabalar uchun real dunyoda o'rganish imkoniyatlarini taklif qiling.

Simulyatsiya va stseneriy asosidagi trening.

Favqulodda vaziyatlarga javob berish mashqlari, guruhni boshqarish muammolari va qaror qabul qilish simulyatsiyasi kabi haqiqiy turistik vaziyatlarni taqlid qilish uchun simulyatsiya mashqlari va stseneriy asosidagi treninglardan foydalaning.

Talabalar uchun chuqur o'rganish tajribasini yaratish uchun virtual haqiqat (VR) va kengaytirilgan haqiqat (AR) texnologiyalarini qo'shing.

Fanlararo yondashuv.

Ta'lim tajribasini boyitish uchun turli kafedralar, jumladan, jismoniy tarbiya, turizmshunoslik, psixologiya va ekologiya fanlari professor-o'qituvchilari o'rtasida fanlararo hamkorlikni rag'batlantirish.

Turistik faoliyat bilan bog'liq murakkab muammolarni hal qilish uchun talabalardan turli sohalardagi bilim va ko'nikmalarni qo'llashni talab qiladigan fanlararo loyihalarni rivojlantirish.

Madaniy kompetensiya va xilma-xillikka o'rgatish

Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni turli xil madaniyatlarga ega bo'lgan turistlarning turli guruhlari bilan ishlashga tayyorlash uchun madaniy kompetensiya va xilma-xillikdan xabardorlik bo'yicha treninglarni ta'minlash.

Talabalarning turli til va madaniy kelib chiqishi bo'lgan sayyohlar bilan samarali muloqot qilish qobiliyatini oshirish uchun til kurslari yoki madaniy immersion tajribalarini taklif qiling.

Texnologiyalar integratsiyasi.

GPS-navigatsiya qurilmalari, sayohatni rejalashtirish va xavfsizlik uchun mobil ilovalar, virtual sayohatlar va interaktiv o'quv modullari uchun onlayn platformalar kabi texnologiya vositalarini birlashtirish.

Talabalarga mas'uliyatli va barqaror turizm amaliyotlarini targ'ib qilish uchun ijtimoiy media va raqamli marketing strategiyalaridan qanday foydalanishni o'rgatish.

Axloqiy va barqaror turizm amaliyotlari.

Axloqiy va barqaror turizm amaliyotlarining muhimligini ta'kidlash, jumladan, atrof-muhitga ta'sirni minimallashtirish, mahalliy hamjamiyatlarni hurmat qilish va mas'uliyatli turizm tashabbuslarini qo'llab-quvvatlash. O'quv dasturiga axloqiy dilemmalar va barqaror turizm strategiyalari bo'yicha amaliy tadqiqotlar va muhokamalarni kiritish.

Doimiy baholash va fikr-mulohazalar.

O'quvchilarning o'zlashtirishlarini nazorat qilish va ularning mashg'ulotlari davomida takomillashtirish yo'nalishlarini aniqlash uchun uzluksiz baholash va qayta aloqa tizimini joriy etish. Uzluksiz o'rganish va kasbiy rivojlanishga yordam berish uchun o'z-o'zini aks ettirish va tengdoshlarni baholashni rag'batlantirish.

Ushbu strategiyalarni amalga oshirish orqali ta'lim muassasalari bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasini oshirish, ularni mas'uliyatli va barqaror turizm amaliyotini targ'ib qilish uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma va munosabatlar bilan qurollantirish, shu bilan birga sayyohlar uchun esda qolarli va boyituvchi tajribalarni taqdim etishi mumkin.

Bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini turistik faoliyatga tayyorlash nazariy bilimlarni ham, amaliy ko'nikmalarni ham qamrab oluvchi ko'p qirrali yondashuvni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu yerda foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan nazariy asos:

Turizm industriyasi haqida tushuncha.

Talabalarni turizm industriyasining tushunchalari, tamoyillari va tendentsiyalari bilan tanishtirish. Bu turizmning har xil turlari (ekoturizm, sarguzasht turizmi, madaniy turizm va boshqalar), turistlarning xulq-atvori, turizmning mahalliy jamoalar va atrof-muhitga ta'siri haqida umumiy ma'lumotni o'z ichiga oladi.

Ochiq havoda ta'lim va sarguzasht turizmi.

Ochiq ta'lim tamoyillari, sarguzasht turizmi faoliyati va xavfsizlik protokollari haqida bilim berish. Bunga xavflarni boshqarish, favqulodda vaziyatlarda tartib-qoidalar, navigatsiya qobiliyatlari va atrof-muhitni boshqarishni tushunish kiradi.

Jismoniy tayyorgarlik va salomatlik.

Turistik faoliyat kontekstida jismoniy tayyorgarlik va salomatlik muhimligini ta'kidlash. Turistlar uchun ham, gidlar uchun ham muntazam jismoniy faollik, to'g'ri ovqatlanish, suvni namlash va dam olishning afzalliklari haqida talabalarga o'rgatish.

Geografiya va madaniyatshunoslik.

Turizm faoliyatiga tegishli geografik ob'ektlar, diqqatga sazovor joylar va madaniy ob'ektlarni o'rganish. Bu mahalliy hudud geografiyasini, tarixiy diqqatga sazovor joylarni, madaniy meros ob'ektlarini va mahalliy bilimlarni tushunishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Muloqot va shaxslararo muloqot qobiliyatlari.

Sayyohlar, hamkasblar va mahalliy jamoalar bilan muloqot qilish uchun zarur bo'lgan muloqot va shaxslararo munosabatlarni rivojlantirish. Bunga samarali og'zaki va og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqot, faol tinglash, nizolarni hal qilish va madaniy sezgirlik kiradi.

Etakchilik va guruh boshqaruvi.

Turistik faoliyat davomida o'quvchilarni yetakchilik qobiliyatlari va guruhlarni boshqarish usullariga o'rgatish. Bunga guruh dinamikasi, qaror qabul qilish, muammolarni hal qilish va tashqi muhitda nizolarni hal qilish kiradi.

Ekologik ta'lim va barqarorlik.

Talabalarga atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, barqaror turizm amaliyoti va ochiq havoda mas'uliyatli dam olish haqida ma'lumot berish. Bunga hech qanday iz qoldirmaslik tamoyillari, ekologik ta'sirni minimallashtirish va barqaror turizm tashabbuslarini ilgari surish kiradi.

Birinchi yordam va favqulodda vaziyatlarga javob berish.

Turistik faoliyat davomida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan favqulodda vaziyatlarga talabalarni tayyorlash uchun birinchi tibbiy yordam, CPR va cho'l tibbiyoti bo'yicha treninglar o'tkazish. Bu umumiy jarohatlar, kasalliklar va atrof-muhit xavf-xatarlarini tan olish va ularga javob berishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Huquqiy va axloqiy mulohazalar.

Turistlarni yo'naltirish bilan bog'liq huquqiy va axloqiy mulohazalar, jumladan, javobgarlik masalalari, risklarni boshqarish va turistlar, mahalliy jamoalar va atrof-muhitga nisbatan axloqiy xatti-harakatlarni muhokama qilish.

Kasbiy rivojlanish va sertifikatlash.

Talabalarni sayyohlik sanoati bilan bog'liq professional sertifikatlar, masalan, cho'lda birinchi yordam, ochiq havoda etakchilik yoki ixtisoslashtirilgan rahbarlik sertifikatlari olishga undash.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Xasanov, a. T., & anvarov, d. M. (2023). Yosh suzuvchilarda chidamlilikni rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali, 2(18), 1283-1289.

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2. Mirzatillo o'g'li, a. D. (2024). Kroll usulida ko'krakda suzish. *Новости образования: исследование в хxi веке*, 2(17), 400-402.
3. Sog'lom avlod tarbiyasi-barchamizning muqaddas insoniy burchimiz Sog'lom avlod davlat dasturini tasdiqlashga bag'ishlangan majlisda so'zlangan nutq, 2000 yil 24 fevral.
4. Abdullayev A. va boshqalar. "Jismonan barkamol avlod orzusi". Farg'ona, 2003 y.
5. "Barkamol avlod tarbiyasida sog'lom turmush tarzi jismoniy madaniyati" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari. Farg'ona, 2011.
6. Majidov, R. R., Boqiyev, F. H., Raximov, D. R., Saydaxmadov, A. V., Soliyev, I. S., & Abduqodirov, D. S. (2023). Jismoniy tarbiya va sport pedagogikasi dars mashg'ulotlarini samaradorligini oshirishning usullari. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(1), 28-32.
7. Ринбоева, М. С. (2020). Табиатга экологик муносабатларнинг маънавий-ахлоқий тамойиллари ва мезонлари. *Science and Education*, 1(2), 590-596.
8. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
9. Усмонова, М. А., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2019). Влияние темперамента на деятельность и поведение человека. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-3 (73)), 56-58.
10. Rasulova, S. A., & Azimov, U. A. (2020). Formation of axiological consciousness in the era of globalization. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(4), 228-231.
11. Akbarovna, U. M. (2019). Rasulova Shoirazizovna Vliyanie temperamenta na deyatelnost i povedeniye cheloveka. *Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya*, (19-3), 73.
12. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Инсон ахлоқий-экологик маданиятини фалсафий жиҳатлари. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (82)), 273-275.
13. Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). Man-ecologist-entonic philosophical culture. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2), 273-275.
14. Тухтаров, И. М., Хакимов, А. М., Олтмишева, Н. Г., & Расулова, Ш. А. (2021). О модели воспитания нравственной культуры у молодежи. *Экономика и социум*, (3-2 (82)), 459-466.

ARTERIAL GIPERTONIYADA BUYRAK USTI BEZINING MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHI

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Annotatsiya. Maqola arterial gipertenziyada buyrak usti bezlaridagi morfologik o'zgarishlarni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Buyrak usti bezining patomorfologik xususiyatlari tanatogenezning miya va yurak variantlari bilan vafot etgan odamlarda bezlardagi arterial gipertenziya bilan bog'liq o'zgarishlarni aniqlashga asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: buyrak usti bezlari, arterial gipertenziya, morfologiya, limfoid infiltratsiya, insult, monositlar

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE ADRENAL GLAND IN ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of morphological changes in the adrenal glands in arterial hypertension. The pathomorphological characteristics of the adrenal gland are based on the detection of changes associated with arterial hypertension in the glands in people who died with cerebral and cardiac variants of thanatogenesis.

Key words: adrenal glands, arterial hypertension, morphology, lymphoid infiltration, stroke, monocytes.

Kirish. Hozirgi vaqtda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari dunyoda yetakchi o'rinni egallaydi o'lim sababi bo'yicha birinchi o'rinda turadi Arterial gipertenziya kasallanish va o'lim prognozini belgilovchi asosiy xavf omillaridan biridir. Uzoq muddatli yuqori qon bosimi muhim hayotiy organlarda bir qator asoratlarni rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: Morfologik parametrlarni qiyosiy o'rganish, buyrak usti bezlarining morfofunktsional holatini arterial gipertenziyada turlicha aks etishini kuzatish.

Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari. Morfologik tadqiqot ob'ekti sifatida 50 yoshdan 84 yoshgacha bo'lgan 102 erkak va ayolning buyrak usti bezlari olindi. Bemorlar Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan endokrinologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand viloyati filiali arxividan kasallik tarixi tahlil qilib olindi. Arterial gipertenziya bilan hayot kechirganlar va turli sabablarga ko'ra vafot etganlar - hayotga mos kelmaydigan mexanik shikastlanishlar: miyada qon ketishi ("Insult" guruhi) va o'tkir chap qorincha yetishmovchiligi, sof arterial gipertenziya olindi. Materiallar to'plami davlat muassasasi klinikalarining patologik bo'limi ma'lumotlari negizida amalga oshirildi. Seksiyonal materialni gistologik tekshirish uchun buyraklar o'rtasidan, kapsula mavjud bo'lgan buyrak usti bezlarining qismlari, shuningdek, barcha uchta zonadan material olingan Gematoksilin va eosin bilan bo'yalgan, kapsulaning holati, korteksning glomerulyar, fasikulyar va retikulyar zonalar va medulla o'rganilgan. Lipidlarning taqsimlanishi va miqdorini aniqlash maqsadida glomerular zona bo'yalgan, tashqi qismini tekshirish uchun Sudan bilan bo'yashdan foydalanilgan. Fasikulyar zonaning o'rta va ichki qismlari, shuningdek, retikulyar zonada har bir holatda buyrak usti bezlarining har birida, fokusning mavjudligi va diffuz mononuklear infiltratsiya, limfotsitlar, monotsitlar, plazma hujayralari soni va korteksning tegishli zonalarida joylashgan fibroblastlar va medulla, qon sirkulatsiyasi va turli strukturaviy shishlar, kortikal zonalardagi o'zgarishlar o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, har xil arterial gipertenziyaning o'limdan oldingi ko'rinishlari va natijada o'limga olib keladigan asoratlari, morfologik holatning o'zgarishiga turli xil tekshirilgan buyraklarda turlicha aniqlangan. Avvalo shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, bu barcha ko'rsatkichlar insult yoki yurak yetishmovchiligidan o'lgan bemorlar buyragida farq qiladi. O'lgan gipertensiv bemorlarda shikastlanishdan, sababi aniqlanmagan va boshqa yurak kasalliklaridan o'lganlarga nisbatan morfologik o'zgarishlar ancha rivojlangan. Ro'yxatga olingan na'munalarda o'ng buyrakka nisbatan chap buyrak usti bezining retikulyar zonasida lipid tarkibining kamayishi yoki ortishi glomerular

zona va buyrak usti bezining medullasini qon bilan ta'minlashidagi chuqur patalogik o'zgarishlar aniqlangan . Mexanik shikastlanishdan vafot etgan bir guruh gipertenziv bemorlar bilan solishtirganda, insult va o'tkir chap qorincha yetishmovchiligidan vafot etganlarda kortikal zonalarda sezilarli darajadagi qon ta'minoti buzulishi va chap va o'ng buyrak usti bezlarining medullasidagi o'zgarishlar aniqlangan. Chap buyrak usti bezida yadro-sitoplazmatik nisbat ortishi va medullaning fokal limfotsitar infiltratsiyasining kuchayishi; o'ngda ko'proq - retikulyar zonaning lipodistrofiyasi aniqlangan. Shunday qilib, tanatogeneznining yurak varianti ko'proq morfologik o'zgarishlarga sabab bo'ladi. Fasikulyar va retikulyar zonalarda qon ta'minoti buzulishi o'limning yurak variantida miya bilan solishtirganda ko'proq kuzatilgan. Bundan tashqari, tanatogeneznining yurak varianti, ko'proq aniq fokal limfoid infiltratsiya va buyrak usti hujayralarining vakuolizatsiyasi bilan kechgan jarayon. Buyrak usti bezi po'stloq qismining morfologik o'zgarishi har bir bemorda kuzatildi 10% bemorda sezilarli o'zgarish sezilmadi bunga sabab 10 % bemorlar Antigipertenziv dori vositalarni regular qabul qilib yurgan shu sababli strukturaviy o'zgarish yuzaga kelmagan.

Xulosa: Shunday qilib, buyrak usti bezlarining morfologik parametrlari, uning funksional holatini aks ettirish maqsadida arterial gipertenziya bilan kasallanishdagi o'lim natijalari olindi, nafaqat kasallikning mavjudligi kasallanish , balki o'lish mexanizmlaridan biri ekanligi asoslandi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбилов АН угли, Сабилова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хг в системе мать-плацента-плод при резус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
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6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет и COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *Miasto Przyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin D deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmun tireoidit bilan kasallangan bemorlardagi funksional buzilishlarning differensial diagnostikasida qalqonsimon bez zichligini aniqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2. *I*. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.

20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
26. Khatamov, O. K., & Ortikov, S. M. (2019). Use from the international experiences in employment the population in uzbekistan. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 364-371.
27. Muhammadiyevich, O. S. (2023). Main problems of population employment and ways to solve them. *American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development* (2993-2750), 1(4), 10-13.
28. Ismatov, S. A., & Ortikov, S. M. (2020). The population bandhini tamines, turmus of regine oshirildi humiliation tagirova and using Uzbekistana characteristic.(foreign experience in providing employment, improving well-being and its specifics for uzbekistan). *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 521-526.
29. Хатамов, О., & Ортиков, Ш. (2019). Аҳоли бандлигини таъминлаш моделлари ва ундан Ўзбекистон шароитида фойдаланиш имкониятлари. *Экономика и инновационные технологии*, (4), 48-59.
30. Xatamov, O. Q., & Ortiqov, S. M. (2019). Models of employment of the population and opportunities for its use in the conditions of Uzbekistan. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 2019(4), 8.
31. Mukhammadiyevich, O. S. (2023). Experiences in the study and analysis of population employment in foreign countries. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
32. Ortikov, S. M. (2021). Experience in statistical study and analysis of employment in foreign countries. *Thematics Journal of Business Management*, 10(7).

DORIXONA MALUMOTLAR BAZASINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. *Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish - bu retsept bo'yicha dori-darmonlarni tarqatish, saralash, qadoqlash va hisoblashning elektron jarayoni. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish ko'plab turli maqsadlarga ega, jumladan, samaradorlikni oshirish, mehnat xarajatlarini minimallashtirish va aniqlikni oshirish. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish bozorida, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish birinchi marta mashhur bo'lganida, tabletkalarni hisoblash yagona usullardan biri edi. Endi ko'proq foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan avtomatlashtirish mashinalari mavjud.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ma'lumotlar bazasi, avtomatlashtirish, dorixona, samaradorlik*

PHARMACY DATABASE AUTOMATION

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Abstract. *Pharmacy automation is the electronic process of dispensing, sorting, packaging and counting prescription drugs. Pharmacy automation has many different goals, including increasing efficiency, minimizing labor costs, and increasing accuracy. In the pharmacy automation market, when pharmacy automation first became popular, pill counting was one of the only methods. There are now more accessible automation machines.*

Key words: *database, automation, pharmacy, efficiency*

Polaris Market Research & Consulting ma'lumotlariga ko'ra , global dorixona avtomatlashtirish bozori 2023 yilda 5,24 milliard dollarga baholangan va 2030 yilga kelib 10,4 milliard dollarga yetishi kutilmoqda, bu prognoz davrida CAGR darajasida 8,02 foizga o'sadi [1].

Dori-darmonlarni tarqatish : Dori-darmonlarni tarqatish dorixonalar uchun katta muammodir, chunki u ko'plab xatolar va ifloslantiruvchi moddalarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Dori-darmonlarni qulay paketlarga, shu jumladan blister paketlarga va tasmali qadoqlarga tarqatadigan mashinalar mavjud.

Yozuvlarni sinxronlashtirish : Dori vositalaridan foydalangan holda, farmatsevtlar bemorlarning dori-darmonlarini qo‘lda kiritmasdan sinxronlash va kuzatib borish imkoniyatiga ega. Endi bulutli tahlillar inventarizatsiyani kuzatib boradi, talabni bashorat qiladi va ushbu hisobotlarga bulutga asoslangan kirishni ta’minlaydi.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirishda aqlli texnologiyaning roli

Ishlab chiquvchilar dorixonani avtomatlashtirish qurilmalari va dasturlarini yaratishda ko‘p jihatdan sun’iy intellektdan foydalanadilar. AI jo‘natish va qadoqlash mexanizmlarida muhim sifat nazorati funksiyasini bajaradi. U dorini suratga olish, uni tortish va ma’lumotlar bazasidagi rasm va vazn ma’lumotlari bilan solishtirish orqali to‘g‘ri dori yuborilganligini ikki marta tekshiradi[2].

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirishning afzalliklari

Aniqlik va xavfsizlikning oshishi : Dori vositalarining noto‘g‘ri o‘lchanishi yoki ifloslanishi dorixonalar uchun ham, ularning mijozlari uchun ham katta xavf tug‘diradi, shuning uchun farmatsevtlar uzoq vaqt hushyor turishlari kerak, bu soliqqa tortuvchi vazifadir. Boshqa tomondan, mashinalar operatsiyalar sonidan qat’i nazar, aralashmalarning aniq og‘irligi va nisbati va dori vositalarining sterilligini ta’minlashi mumkin.

Yaxshilangan samaradorlik va resurslarni taqsimlash : Amerika farmatsevtlari assotsiatsiyasi jurnali o‘z tadqiqotida ta’kidlaganidek, farmatsevtlar an’anaviy hisoblash va quyish usuliga nisbatan robotli tarqatish moslamalari bilan to‘ldirilgan 100 ta retsept uchun 46,5 daqiqadan ko‘proq vaqtni tejashlari mumkin. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish bozorida dorixona xodimlari bu

vaqtni mijozlarga yaxshi xizmat ko'rsatish yoki dori-darmonlarni tadqiq qilish va ishlab chiqishda ishtirok etish uchun ajratishlari mumkin.

Geriatrik populyatsiyaning ko'payishi, dori-darmonlarni ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarining qisqarishi va bir nechta shifoxonalarda ish jarayonini yaxshilangan va to'g'ri boshqarish, ayniqsa Xitoy, Hindiston va Indoneziya kabi rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlarda bozor eksponentsial o'sishini ta'minlaydigan asosiy omillardir[3].

Farmatsevtika sanoati jadal rivojlanmoqda, eskilari avtomatlashtirilgunga qadar yangi ish o'rinlari paydo bo'ladi. Robotlar odatiy va zerikarli vazifalarni bajaradilar, mutaxassislar esa ijodkorlik, empatiya va nuanslarga e'tibor berishni talab qiladigan murakkab vazifalarni bajarishlari mumkin. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish bozorida, avtomatlashtirish mavjud bo'lgan holda, farmatsevtlar bemorlar bilan ko'proq shug'ullanishlari va kichik sog'liq muammolari, shu jumladan ruhiy salomatlik va giyohvand moddalarni suiiste'mol qilish bo'yicha ma'lumot, maslahatlar, diagnostika va davolashni taqdim etishlari mumkin.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish deganda dorixonada dori-darmonlarni saqlash va tarqatishdan tortib inventar va yozuvlarni boshqarishgacha bo'lgan turli vazifalarni soddalashtirish va yaxshilash uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish tushuniladi. U keng doiradagi vositalar va tizimlarni o'z ichiga oladi, ularning har biri ish jarayonining muayyan sohalariga qaratilgan.

Dorixonada avtomatlashtirish, shuningdek, shtrix-kodlarni skanerlash va tekshirish tizimlarini joriy etish orqali inson xatolarini kamaytirish va dori vositalari xavfsizligini oshirishda, bemorlarga to'g'ri dori-darmonlar berilishini ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bundan tashqari, elektron retseptlash (elektron retseptlash) tizimlarining integratsiyasi tibbiyot xodimlari va dorixonalar o'rtasida retsept bo'yicha ma'lumotlarning uzluksiz va xavfsiz almashinuvini osonlashtiradi, bu esa yanada soddalashtirilgan va bemorga yo'naltirilgan sog'liqni saqlash tajribasiga hissa qo'shadi.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish, shuningdek, farmatsevtlar uchun qimmatli vaqtni ochib beradi, bu ularga shaxsiylashtirilgan bemorlarni parvarish qilish va dori-darmonlar bo'yicha maslahat berishga e'tibor qaratishga imkon beradi va natijada hamma uchun yaxshi sog'liq tajribasiga olib keladi.

Dorixonalarni kengaytirish va kelajakka ishonch hosil qilishda mijozlarimizning aksariyati dasturiy ta'minotning bevosita va bilvosita afzalliklarini tushunishni talab qiladi. Albatta, bu investitsiyalar bo'yicha ongli ravishda qaror qabul qilishga yordam beradi va sizning e'tiboringizni yaxshilash uchun barcha imkoniyatlarga qaratadi. Shuning uchun, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlarining ba'zi asosiy afzalliklari[4].

Yaxshiroq ishlash tezligi va aniqligi

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish insonning aniqligi bilan solishtirganda mahsulotlarni tez va aniq qayta ishlashni ta'minlaydi. Bu xatolarni kuzatish, ifloslanishni kamaytirish va saqlash yoki tarqatish uchun aniq tortish bilan to'g'ri dori-darmonlarga o'z vaqtida kirish imkonini beradi.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari vazifalarni mukammal bajarish, aniqlik va izchillikni ta'minlash va har safar to'g'ri natijalarni ta'minlash orqali ushbu xavfni yo'q qiladi, xizmat ko'rsatish zarur bo'lgan kamdan-kam holatlar bundan mustasno.

Haqiqiy vaqtda inventarni kuzatish

Albatta, javonlarni qidirish yoki inventar darajasini taxmin qilish uchun vaqtingiz yo'q. Yaxshi rejalashtirilgan dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimi har bir dori-darmonni real vaqt rejimida kuzatib boradi, vaqt va xarajatlarni tejaydi va mavjudligini ta'minlaydi, shunda siz zaxiralar, muddati o'tgan dori-darmonlar va o'g'irlik bilan xayrlashishingiz mumkin.

Ushbu dasturiy ta'minot barcha ma'lumotlarni, jumladan, xaridlar, sanalar, amal qilish muddati, belgilangan dozalar va mijozlar ma'lumotlarini saqlaydi. Siz bir nechta joylarda inventarizatsiyani osongina boshqarishingiz va bemorlarga ishonchli xizmatlarni taqdim etishingiz mumkin.

Ish yukini va mehnat xarajatlarini kamaytirish

Avtomatlashtirish sizning jamoangizning ko'nikmalarini odatiy vazifalardan yuqori mas'uliyatli vazifalarga o'tkazish orqali optimallashtiradi. Aqlli ravishda rejalashtirilgan dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari tibbiyot mutaxassislariga bemorlarni parvarish qilish va dori-darmonlarni sinxronlashtirish, yulduzlar reytingi va maslahat savdolari kabi biznesni rivojlantirish tashabbuslariga e'tibor qaratish imkonini beradi.

Siz bemorlar va strategik sa'y-harakatlarga ko'proq vaqt ajratish uchun xodimlaringizni bo'shatib, operatsiyalarni soddalashtirishingiz mumkin. Shunday

qilib, sizning dorixonangiz qo‘shimcha ish haqi yoki yollashsiz murakkabroq vazifalarni hal qilishi mumkin.

Masalan, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish Walgreensga (Amerikadagi ikkinchi yirik dorixonalar tarmog‘i) ish yukini kamida 25 foizga kamaytirishga va har yili 1 milliard dollardan ko‘proq tejashga yordam berdi .

Bemorlarni parvarish qilish, konsultatsiyalar va bemorlarni o‘qitish va emlash kabi foyda keltiradigan faoliyatga ko‘proq sarmoya kiritish samaradorlikni oshiradi va operatsion xarajatlarni yo‘q qiladi va daromad va foyda marjasini oshiradi.

Ishtirok etish va bemorni parvarish qilishni yaxshilaydi

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish ma‘muriy vazifalardan qimmatli vaqtni tejaydi, shuning uchun siz bemorlarga yaxshiroq yordam ko‘rsatishga e‘tibor qaratishingiz mumkin. Bu bemorlar bilan mazmunli muloqot qilishni, ularning muammolarini hal qilishni va ularga salomatlik va salomatlik haqida ma‘lumot berishni osonlashtiradi.

Avtomatlashtirilgan retseptlar va boshqa texnologik integratsiyalashgan xizmatlar bemorlarga 24/7 aniq xizmat ko‘rsatishni osonlashtiradi va sizni yanada ishonchli qiladi. Bemorlar retseptlar va kerakli tibbiy yordamga qulay foydalanishlari mumkin, bu ularni qoniqtiradi va mijozlaringizga ijobiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi.

Ma‘lumotlar xavfsizligi va maxfiyligi

Bemor haqidagi ma‘lumotlar va dori vositalari bilan ishlash xavfsizligini ta‘minlaydigan turli qonun va qoidalar mavjud. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish, xuddi avtomatlashtirilgan retseptlarni bajarish kabi, ushbu talablarga muammosiz mos keladi.

Bu nafaqat mijozlarning salomatligi va ma‘lumotlar xavfsizligi to‘g‘risida ishonch hosil qiladi, balki jarayonlarni soddalashtiradi va xavfsizlikni oshiradi. Dorixona menejrlari giyohvand moddalar yoki mijozlar ma‘lumotlarini noto‘g‘ri ishlatishning oldini olish uchun avtomatlashtirishga ishonishlari mumkin.

Ma‘lumotlar bilan ishlash, dori-darmonlarni inventarizatsiya qilish va dori-darmonlarni tarqatish kabi takrorlanadigan vazifalarni avtomatlashtirish uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish vaqtni tejaydi va aniqlikni ta‘minlaydi. Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari yuzlab muntazam vazifalarni bir martalik hal qilish imkonini beradi.3

Mijozlarning buyurtmalari va dori-darmonlar tafsilotlarini kuzatish va boshqarish haqida gap ketganda, avtomatlashtirish aqlli yozuvlarni saqlashga yordam beradi. Nafaqat bu, dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlari sizga retseptlar, buyurtmalar, inventar ma'lumotlari va bemor ma'lumotlariga bir joyda kirish va boshqarish imkonini beruvchi to'liq huquqli boshqaruv panelini taqdim etadi.

Bu qalam-qog'oz yozuvlariga qaraganda ancha aniqroq va murakkabroq. Bundan tashqari, bemorlarga sifatsiz dori-darmonlarni sotib olishga majbur bo'lmasligi uchun retseptlangan dori vositalarining inventarizatsiyasini kuzatish osonroq bo'ladi.

Dori-darmonlarni qadoqlash va etiketlash ajralmas, ammo oddiy vazifalardir. Bu nozik masala bo'lsa-da, avtomatlashtirilgan qadoqlash va etiketkalash xatolar uchun kamroq joy qoldiradi. Bundan tashqari, qadoqlash paytida har qanday ifloslanishni kamaytirishga yordam beradi.

Dorixona ma'lumotlarini boshqarish tizimini qadoqlash va etiketkalash mashinalari bilan ulash ishni osonlashtiradi va murakkablashtiradi. Bu bemorning ismlarini, dori tafsilotlarini, dozasini va hatto shoshilinch telefon raqamini dori-darmonlarni yetkazib berish paketida muammosiz chop etishning ishonchli usuli.

Dorixonani avtomatlashtirish dasturiy ta'minot, robototexnika va mashinalarni o'z ichiga olgan to'liq tizim integratsiyasi bilan dori vositalarini tayyorlashni osonlashtiradi. Bu hamma narsa steril muhitda amalga oshirilishini ta'minlaydi, xatolar va ifloslanishni yo'q qiladi.

Sun'iy intellekt (AI) dorixonani avtomatlashtirishning muhim jihati bo'lib, dori-darmonlarni tarqatishda aniqlikni ta'minlaydi. U dori-darmonlarni suratga olish va saqlangan ma'lumotlarga solishtirish orqali o'zaro tekshiradi va aniqligini kafolatlaydi[5].

Bemorga yo'naltirilgan sun'iy intellekt chatbotlari simptomlar asosida birjadan tashqari dori vositalarini tanlashda yordam beradi va onlayn yoki qo'ng'iroqlar orqali retsept bo'yicha buyurtmalarni osonlashtiradi. Bundan tashqari, AI farmatsevtika kompaniyalariga muhim iste'molchi ma'lumotlarini to'plash va tahlil qilish imkonini beradi, bu esa biznesning mustahkam o'sishiga yordam beradi.

Dori vositalarining uzluksiz kuzatilishini ta'minlash uchun blokcheyndan foydalanish mumkin. Har bir dori ishlab chiqarishda noyob kodni oladi, keyin u blokcheynga kiritiladi. Dori-darmonlarni ulgurji sotuvchidan tortib to

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
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dorixonagacha, bemorni kasalxonaga yetkazishgacha sotish, shifokor yoki bemorni qaytarish yoki yaroqlilik muddati tugaganligi sababli yo‘q qilish bilan bog‘liq har bir keyingi harakatlar qayd etiladi.

Dorixona boshqaruvi va boshqa sog‘liqni saqlash dasturlarini ishlab chiqishda RPA dori vositalarini avtomatlashtirilgan saqlash, shtrix kodlar yordamida qidirish, buyurtmalarni joylashtirish va qaytishni kuzatish kabi jarayonlar uchun aniqlikni ta‘minlaydi. Bundan tashqari, u bemorlar ma‘lumotlarini boshqarishni soddalashtiradi, tez yangilanishlar, saqlash va olish imkonini beradi, shu bilan birga parvarish qiluvchilar, shifokorlar va boshqa organlar uchun hisobotlarni osonlikcha ishlab chiqaradi[6]. Ushbu texnologiyalarni dorixonani avtomatlashtirish tizimlariga integratsiyalash ularni chinakam ilg‘or va kelajakka moslashtirishi mumkin. Dorixonalarni avtomatlashtirish bozori 2024 yil holatiga ko‘ra 4 697,67 million AQSh dollarini tashkil etadi. 2028 yilga kelib CAGR 7,80% bo‘lgan holda 6 983,16 million dollarga yetishi kutilmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Philip O.Anderson, Susan M.McGuinness, Philip E.Bourne. Pharmacy Informatics. USA 2010.
2. Stephen Goundrey-Smith. Information Technology in Pharmacy An Integrated Approach. USA 2012.
3. <https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en/expert-insights/artificial-intelligence-in-pharmacy-are-you-ready>
4. Edward H. James J. Biomedical Informatics. Fourth edition. Springer-Verlag London 2014. Н.В. Макарова. Информатика. Тошкент 2005й.
5. М.М.Арипов, J.U.Мухаммадиев. «Informatika, informatsion texnologiyalar»,Тошкент. 2005у.
6. Ф.М.Зокирова «Информатика и информационные технологии»Тошкент-2007 у.

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA TA'LIM TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR (OLY TA'LIM TIZIMI MISOLIDA)

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston Respublikasida Oliy ta'lim tizimidagi islohotlar, kamchiliklar va yutuqlar haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'lim to'g'risidagi qonun, oliy ta'lim muassasalari, strategik amaliyotlar, modernizatsiya, akkreditatsiya, Axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiya (AKT), inklyuziv ta'lim

REFORMS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM)

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Abstract. This article provides information about reforms, shortcomings and achievements in the system of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Law on education, higher education institutions, strategic practices, modernization, accreditation, information communication technology (ICT), inclusive education,

O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimida 2024-yilgacha bir qator yutuqlarga erishildi. Maktab bitiruvchilarini oliy ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasi 9 foizdan 28 foizga ko'tarildi. 2030 yilda esa 50 foizga etkazish rejalashtirilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, davlat grantlari 2 barobarga ko'paytirish mo'ljallangan.

Ikkinchidan, Respublikamizda 2020-yil 23-sentabr kuni Ta'lim to'g'risidagi qonunni yangi tahriri kuchga kirdi. Unga ko'ra, Oliy ta'lim tizimida talabalarni qamrovini kengaytirish masalasi alohida e'tirof etildi. Qonunning 57-moddasida Nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlarining faoliyatini litsenziyalash va ularni sonini yana ham oshirishga doir chora tadbirlar alohida takidlangan. Ta'lim sifatini nazorat qilish davlat inspeksiyasining 2023-yil 23-avgustda bergan ma'lumotiga ko'ra Respublikamizda xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni 65 ta,

Davlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni 115 ta, Xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni 30 tani tashkil qilmoqda.¹ Umumiy ta'lim olayotgan talabalar soni 1 029 522 nafar bo'lsa, hundan xotin-qizlar soni 492 580 nafar, erkaklar soni esa 537 700 nafarni tashkil etadi.²

O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimida 2024-yilgacha bir qator kamchiliklarga ham yo'l qo'yildi. Birinchidan, ta'lim sifati: Ko'pgina muassasalar eskirgan o'quv dasturlari, cheklangan resurslar va malakali professor-o'qituvchilarning etishmasligi tufayli yuqori akademik standartlarni saqlab qolish uchun kurashmoqda.

Ikkinchidan, infratuzilma: Ba'zi universitetlar talabalar uchun o'qish tajribasiga to'sqinlik qiladigan eskirgan xonalar, kutubxonalar va laboratoriyalar kabi jihozlarning etarli emasligidan aziyat chekmoqda.

Uchinchidan, resurslardan foydalanish: Talabalar ko'pincha darsliklar, tadqiqot materiallari va texnologiyalar kabi muhim manbalarga kirishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi, bu ularning o'qishlari bilan to'liq shug'ullanish qobiliyatini cheklaydi.

To'rtinchidan, tadqiqot va innovatsiyalar: Akademik mukammallikni oshirish va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishga hissa qo'shish uchun oliy ta'lim muassasalarida tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarga ko'proq sarmoya kiritishga ehtiyoj bor.

Beshinchidan, boshqaruv: byurokratik qog'ozbozlik, korrupsiya va shaffoflikning yo'qligi kabi muammolar universitetlarni samarali boshqarishga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin.

Oltinchidan, ishga joylashish: Diplomlarga ega bo'lishlariga qaramay, bitiruvchilar ba'zan oliy ta'limda olgan ko'nikmalari va mehnat bozori talablari o'rtasidagi nomuvofiqlik tufayli ish topishda qiynaladilar.

O'zbekiston taraqqiyot sari intilayotgan bir paytda, muhim o'zgarishlarni boshdan kechirayotgan muhim tarmoqlardan biri oliy ta'lim tizimidir. O'zbekiston Respublikasida bir qator strategik amaliyotlar va islohotlar orqali oliy ta'lim tizimini zamonaviy metodlar, o'qitish tizimi va innovatsiyalar, mukammallikni rivojlantirish maqsadida qayta shakllantirmoqda. Bunga misol qilib turli xil yo'nalishlarni misol qilib olishimiz mumkin:

O'quv dasturlari va o'qitish metodlarini modernizatsiya qilish:

Oliy ta'lim tizimini tubdan isloh qilishda o'quv dasturlari va o'qitish uslublarini modernizatsiya qilish asosiy o'rin tutadi. O'zbekistonda ta'lim

¹ <https://fledu.uz/uz/ozbekistondagi-oliy-talim-muassasalari-soni-va-unda-qancha-talaba-talim-olishi-statistikasi/>

² <https://www.google.com/search?q=o%27zbekistonda+nodavlat+oliy+ta%27lim+muassasalari+soni+nechta>

dasturlarini jahon standartlari va turli sohalardagi rivojlanayotgan tendentsiyalarga moslashtirish asosiy maqsadlardan biri hisoblanadi. O'quv dasturlarini yangilash, fanlararo yondashuvlarni joriy etish va amaliy o'rganish tajribalarini o'z ichiga olish orqali universitetlar talabalarni bugungi rivojlanayotgan mehnat bozorida muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun zarur bo'lgan ko'nikma va bilimlar bilan tarbiyalanmoqda.

Sifat kafolati va akkreditatsiya

O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim dasturidagi ta'lim sifatini ta'minlash birinchi o'rinda turadi. Universitetlar va dasturlarning samaradorligini baholash va monitoring qilish uchun mustahkam, sifatli va kafolatli mexanizmlar hamda akkreditatsiya jarayonlari yaratilgan. Ushbu chora-tadbirlar orqali institutlar akademik mukammallikning yuqori standartlari, professor-o'qituvchilar malakasi va infratuzilmani ta'minlash uchun javobgar bo'ladi, bu esa O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimining umumiy ishonchi va obro'sini oshiradi.³

Tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish O'zbekiston iqtisodiy o'sish va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarning muhim rolini tan oladi. Shu bois oliy ta'lim muassasalarida tadqiqot va innovatsiyalar madaniyatini yuksaltirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Moliyaviy yordam, tadqiqot markazlarini tashkil etish va sanoat hamkorlari bilan hamkorlik qilish orqali universitetlarda zamonaviy o'quv metodik usul yaratish va texnologik taraqqiyotga hissa qo'shib, tabiiy, aniq va ijtimoiy fanlar bo'yicha ilg'or tadqiqot ishlarida faol ishtirok etmoqda.

Xalqaro hamkorlik

Global raqobatbardoshlik va madaniyatlararo almashinuvni rivojlantirish uchun O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida modernizatsiyalash sa'y-harakatlariga ustuvor ahamiyat qaratilmoqda. Dunyo bo'ylab taniqli universitet va muassasalar bilan hamkorlikdagi talabalar va professor-o'qituvchilar almashinuvini, qo'shma ilmiy loyihalarni amalga oshirish hamda xalqaro konferensiya va seminarlarda ishtirok etishni osonlashtiradi. Bunday hamkorlik nafaqat akademik tajribani boyitadi, balki talabalar va o'qituvchilar o'rtasida madaniyatlararo tushunish va global fuqarolikni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi.

Axborot Kommunikatsiya Texnologiya integratsiyasi va elektron ta'lim

Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining (AKT) transformatsion salohiyatini e'tirof etgan holda, O'zbekiston raqamli vositalar va elektron ta'lim

³ Shamsiev, A.. Globallashuv sharoitida O'zbekistonda oliy ta'limning muammolari va istiqbollari. // Yevroosiyo tadqiqotlari jurnali, 2019.10(2), B-132

platformalarini oliy ta'lim tizimiga integratsiya qilmoqda. Texnologiyalar kuchidan foydalangan holda universitetlar ta'lim resurslaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirmoqda, masofaviy ta'lim imkoniyatlarini osonlashtirmoqda, o'qitish va baholash usullari samaradorligini oshirilmogda. Ushbu raqamli transformatsiya ta'lim tizimini inqilob qilishga va o'quvchilarga istalgan vaqtda va istalgan joyda bilim olish imkoniyatini berishga tayyorlanmogda. Axborot Kommunikatsiya Texnologiyalari rivojlanishi natijasida oliy talim tizimida online darslar tashkil qilinib, online platformalar yaratildi. Bu orqali offline darslarga qatnasha olmaydigan talabalar malakali ta'lim olishlari uchun qulay shart sharoitlar yaratildi.

Inklyuziv ta'lim va foydalanish imkoniyati

Ijtimoiy tenglik va inklyuzivlikni ta'minlash bo'yicha O'zbekiston jamiyatning barcha qatlamlari uchun oliy ta'limdan keng foydalanish imkoniyatini ta'minlashga intilmogda. Inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlar nogiron talabalar uchun qo'llab-quvvatlash xizmatlarini ko'rsatish, stipendiyalar va moliyaviy yordam dasturlarini kengaytirish va kam ta'minlangan hududlarda ta'lim imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Turli va inklyuziv ta'lim muhitini yaratish orqali O'zbekiston o'z inson kapitalining to'liq salohiyatidan foydalanishga, ijtimoiy hamjihatlik mustahkamlashga intiladi.⁴

Xulosa qilib aytganda, O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar va islohotlar mamlakatning ta'limda mukammallik, innovatsiyalar va inklyuzivlikni qo'llab-quvvatlashga bo'lgan qat'iy intilishidan dalolat beradi. O'quv dasturlarini modernizatsiya qilish, o'quv sifatini ta'minlashni kuchaytirish, tadqiqot va zamon talablariga mos ravishda rag'batlantirish, AKTni integratsiyalash va inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish orqali O'zbekiston bilim, ijodkorlik va inson kapitalini rivojlantirish asosidagi yorqin kelajak uchun zamin yaratmogda.

Ushbu kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish siyosatchilar, ta'lim muassasalari va boshqa manfaatdor tomonlardan O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim sifati, foydalanish imkoniyati va dolzarbligini oshirish uchun birgalikdagi sa'y-harakatlarni talab qiladi.

⁴ Akramov, K.. O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimini isloh qilishning muammolari va imkoniyatlari. // Ta'lim va amaliyot jurnali, 2019.10(20), B - 18-23.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Akramov, K. (2019). O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimini isloh qilishning muammolari va imkoniyatlari. Ta'lim va amaliyot jurnali, 10(20), 18-23.
2. Tashkent Times. (2021). O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim sohasida katta islohotlar amalga oshiriladi. <https://tashkenttimes.uz/national/6591-uzbekistan-to-implement-major-reforms-in-higher-education> dan olindi
3. Mo'minov, T. (2020). O'zbekistonda ta'lim islohotlari: hozirgi holati va istiqbollari. Markaziy Osiyo dasturi, Jorj Vashington universiteti.
4. YUNESKO. (2023). O'zbekistonda oliy ta'limni isloh qilish: siyosat va institutsional asoslar. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000375579> dan olindi
5. Naroditskiy, V. va Samadov, B. (2022). O'zbekistonda oliy ta'limni o'zgartirish: Sovet merosidan global raqobatbardoshlikka. Xalqaro oliy ta'lim, (111), 9-11.
6. Rashidov, F. va To'raev, B. (2021). O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim islohotlari: yutuq va muammolar. Toshkent: O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti matbuoti
7. Shamsiev, A. (2019). Globallashuv sharoitida O'zbekistonda oliy ta'limning muammolari va istiqbollari. Yevroosiyo tadqiqotlari jurnali, 10(2), 125-138.

AXBOROT-TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA TARMOQLARINING ISHLASH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH

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Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy jamiyatning hayoti ma'lumotlarni uzatish turli jinsli tizimlardan keng foydalanishsiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi. Bu vositalar uzluksiz takomillashmoqda va rivojlanmoqda. Yildan-yilga ma'lumotlar hajmlari ortmoqda, aloqa masofasi oshmoqda, uzatish sifatiga talablar ortmoqda. Shunga ko'ra, murakkab tizimlarni (MT) boshqarish masalasi oldingi o'rinlarga chiqmoqda. Boshqarish deganda murakkab tizimlarni ularning turli ishlash bosqichlarida ratsional o'zini tutishini shakllantirish jarayoni tushuniladi. Boshqarishning mazmunini mos mansabdor shaxslarning qarorni tayyorlash va qabul qilish, uni aloqa rejalashtirishning borishida batafsillashtirish, kuchlar va vositalarini qurish va qo'llash, o'zaro ta'sirlashishni tashkil etish va har tomonlama ta'minlash, shuningdek ularning bajarilishini nazorat qilish jarayonlari tashkil etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ulanish va ulanish tezligi, ma'lumotlar uzatish tezligi, xavfsizlik, skalalashuv, qo'llab-quvvatlashish va boshqaruv

EVALUATION OF THE PERFORMANCE OF INFORMATION AND TELECOMMUNICATION NETWORKS

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Abstract. The life of modern society cannot be imagined without the widespread use of various systems for data transmission. These tools are constantly being improved and developed. Data volumes are increasing year by year, the communication distance is increasing, and the requirements for transmission quality are increasing. Accordingly, the issue of managing complex systems (MT) is coming to the fore. Control is understood as the process of forming rational behavior of complex systems at different stages of their operation. The content of the management is the preparation and adoption of the decision by the appropriate officials, its elaboration in the course of communication planning, the construction and use of forces and means, the organization and comprehensive provision of interaction, as well as the processes of monitoring their implementation.

Keywords: Connection and connection speed, data transfer speed, security, scaling, support and management.

Axborot-telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari, bugünning dunyoda bizning hayotimizning ahamiyatli qismlaridan biri haline keldi. Bu tarmoqlar, xabarlarini o'zaro almashish, ma'lumotlarni uzatish va axborotlarni saqlash uchun axborotni almashishning asosiy vositalari sifatida xizmat qiladi. Ishlash samaradorligi, tarmoqlar uchun juda muhimdir, chunki ularga qo'yilgan investitsiyalar va xizmatlarining qiymati, tarmoqlarning ishlash samaradorligi bilan bog'liq bo'ladi.

Ulanish va ulanish tezligi: Tarmoqqa ulanishning tezligi va ustuvorligi, tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlarni jo'natish va qabul qilish samaradorligini ta'minlaydi. Bu ko'rsatkich, tarmoqdagi ustunlik va qo'llab-quvvatlashishning muhim belgisi hisoblanadi.

Ma'lumotlar uzatish tezligi: Tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlar uzatish tezligi, tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlar paketlarining o'tish tezligi bilan bog'liq bo'ladi. Bu tezlik, tarmoqda ma'lumotlar almashishining tezligini belgilaydi.

Ulanish nisbatlarining sifati: Tarmoqning ishlash samaradorligini ta'minlashdagi birinchi parametr, tarmoqdagi ulanishni sifatini o'rganishdir. Ulanish nisbatlarining yuqori bo'lishi va tarmoqdagi xatoliklar sonining pastligi, tarmoqni qo'llab-quvvatlashishning samaradorligini oshiradi.

Xavfsizlik: Tarmoqning xavfsizligi, ma'lumotlarni yo'qotish, talonlarni yuzaga keltirish, hujjatlarni so'rib olish va boshqa xavfli tarmoq operatsiyalari bilan bog'liq xavfsizlik muhim ko'rsatkichidir. Xavfsizlikni ta'minlash, tarmoqdagi ishlash samaradorligini oshiradi.

Skalalashuv: Tarmoqdagi tizimning skalalashuvi, tarmoqdagi qo'llab-quvvatlashishni osonlashtiradi. Tarmoq kengayishi va qo'llanuvchi qurilmalar sonini oshirish, tarmoqdagi ishlash samaradorligini oshiradi.

Qo'llab-quvvatlashish va boshqaruv: Tarmoqdagi qo'llab-quvvatlashish va boshqaruv jarayonlari, tarmoqdagi muammo yechish va tarmoqni yangilashni osonlashtiradi. Qo'llab-quvvatlashishning samaradorligi, tarmoqni ishga tushirish va tarmoqdagi muammo yechish jarayonlarini osonlashtiradi.

Axborot-telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlarining ishlash samaradorligini tahlil qilishning bir nechta asosiy yo'llari va muhim ko'rsatkichlari mavjud. Bu, tarmoqning o'rtacha boshqaruv va boshqaruvga ishlatiladigan resurslar, tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlar almashishining tezligi, tarmoqdagi qurilmalar va vositalarning ishlab chiqarish va ularga qo'yilgan mablag'lar, tarmoqdagi xizmatlarning sifati va xavfsizligi, tarmoqdagi xizmatlarni taqdim etish va ularga qo'yilgan bojxona infrastrukturasi o'z ichiga oladi.

Tarmoqning boshqaruv va boshqaruvga ishlatiladigan resurslari, tarmoqni boshqarish, ma'lumotlar almashish va tashqarida xizmatlarni taqdim etishning

muhim qismlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Boshqaruv resurslari, tarmoqni boshqarish uchun kerakli xizmatlarni taqdim etish, tarmoq tashqi aloqalarni boshqarish, xavfsizlik va monitoringni ta'minlash va tarmoqdagi muammo yechish jarayonlarini osonlashtirishga yordam beradi.

Tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlar almashish tezligi, ma'lumotlar almashishning tezligini ta'minlashda muhimdir. Bu, tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlar almashishning boshqa tarmoqlarga qaraganda qanchalik tez va samarali bo'lishini bildiradi. Ma'lumotlar almashish tezligi, tarmoqdagi qurilmalar, protokollar, ulanish tezligi va ma'lumotlar uzatish tezligi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Tarmoqdagi qurilmalar va vositalar, tarmoqning ishlash samaradorligini ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ulanish vositalari, tarmoqqa ulanishni tashkil etish va ma'lumotlarni jo'natish va qabul qilishni osonlashtiradi. Ularning ustuvorligi, ulanishning tezligi, xavfsizligi va boshqa ko'rsatkichlarga bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Tarmoqdagi serverlar, routerlar, switchlar va boshqa vositalar, ma'lumotlarni o'zaro almashish va ulanishni ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Tarmoqdagi xizmatlar, tarmoq foydalanuvchilari uchun ma'lumotlarga kirish, axborot almashish va axborotni saqlashning imkoniyatlarini taqdim etadi. Bu xizmatlar, elektron pochta, veb-saytlar, multimedia ijro etish, videokonferensiyalar, voIP (Internet orqali ovozli aloqa) va boshqalar kabi turli xizmatlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Xavfsizlik, tarmoqdagi axborotlarni himoya qilish va xavfli operatsiyalarning oldini olishga oid muhim bir ko'rsatkichdir. Xavfsizlik, ma'lumotlarni shifrlash, autentifikatsiya protokollari, xavfsizlik protokollari va tarmoqdagi xavfli tashkilotlarning qo'llanilishi bilan ta'minlanishi mumkin.

Bojxona infrastrukturasi samaradorligi ham muhimdir, chunki tarmoqdagi bojxona vositalari, serverlar va tarmoqdagi qurilmalar to'plamining ishlash samaradorligini ta'minlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bojxona tuzish va boshqarish, qurilish va sozlash, serverlar va xotiralar, tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlarni saqlash va o'qish, ma'lumotlar almashish va ulanishning samaradorligini ta'minlash va boshqa amaliyotlar uchun muhimdir.

Tarmoqlar bo'yicha ishlash samaradorligini baholash uchun, yuqoridagi ko'rsatkichlarning har birini o'rganish va baholashning bir nechta usullaridan foydalanish mumkin. Buning orqali, tarmoqni mustahkam qilish va ishlash samaradorligini oshirish uchun muhim yo'nalishlarni aniqlash va takomillashtirish mumkin.

Xulosa. Umuman olganda, tarmoqdagi ishlash samaradorligini baholash, tarmoqning to'liq va samarali ishlashi uchun muhimdir. Bu baholash, tarmoqdagi har bir jihatni tahlil qilish, ularga tegishli ko'rsatkichlarni qo'llash, samaradorlik yuqori darajada bo'lgan tarmoqni belgilash va muammolarni aniqlash uchun yordam beradi. Baholash natijalari, tarmoqdagi muammolarni aniqlash, tarmoqdagi optimallashtirish va yangilanishlarni identifikatsiyalashga yordam beradi va tarmoqni yanada samarali qilish uchun yo'l harakatini belgilashga imkon beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabyotlar

1. Inshakova E G 2015 "E-government" in public administration: administrative and legal problems of organization and functioning (Voronezh: Voronezh State University)
2. Popov V D, Bepalov P V, Tavokin E P et al. 2003 Information policy (Moscow: Publishing house of RASS)
3. Brukhanova Ye, Rozanova N 2017 The role of information technology in the development of public administration 113-116
4. www.arxiv.uz

ALLERGIK KASALLIKLAR VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISHDA QO‘LLANILADIGAN PREPARATLAR

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Annotatsiya: Allergiya – bu hozirgi zamon “Sivilizatsiya kasalligi” hisoblanadi. Jahon sog‘liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) ma’lumotlariga ko‘ra, allergik kasalliklar yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari va saratondan keyin uchinchi o‘rinda turadi. Bizning maqsadimiz allergik kasalliklarni oldini oluvchi va rivojlanishiga to‘sqinlik qiluvchi dorivor vositalar bilan tanishish hamda ular haqida ma’lumotlar yig‘ishdir.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ekzoallergenlar, autoallergenlar, antihistaminlar, kromoglik kislota (cromoglycic acid), ketotifen, oksatomid

ALLERGIC DISEASES AND DRUGS USED FOR THEIR TREATMENT

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Abstract: Allergy is a modern "disease of civilization". According to the World Health Organization (WHO), allergic diseases rank third after cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Our goal is to get acquainted with drugs that prevent and prevent the development of allergic diseases and to collect information about them.

Key words: exoallergens, autoallergens, antihistamines, cromoglycic acid, ketotifen, oxatamide

Mavzuning dolzarbligi: Allergiya (yunon. allos-boshqa, ergon-ta'sir) – bu organizmning ko'pincha antigenik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan ba'zi moddalarga sezgirligining oshishidir. Allergiyaga olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan moddalar allergenlar deb ataladi. Allergenlar asosan tashqi muhitdan kirganligi uchun, ular ekzoallergenlar ham deb ataladi. Ba'zi hollarda organizmning o'zi ishlab chiqarishi mumkin allergenlar – autoallergenlar (endoallergenlar) deyiladi.

Ekzoallergenlarga quyidagilar misol bo'la oladi: o'simliklar (terak, yopishqoq alder, gul changlari, mevalar va h.k), hayvon junlari, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari (sut, go'sht, yong'oqlar, dengiz mahsulotlari, sitrus mevalar), dori vositalari (antibiotiklar, sulfanilamidlar, gormonlar), turli xil sanoat kimyoviy birikmalari (benzopirin, etilendiamin), organik erituvchilar, bo'yoqlar va h.k.

Allergiyaga qarshi qo'llaniladigan turli xil dorilar guruhi bu – antigistaminlardir. Ular gistamin ta'siriga sezgir bo'lgan tanadagi retseptorlarga raqobatbardosh tarzda to'sqinlik qiladi. Ushbu dorilar allergiya paytida to'qimalarda yallig'lanishni qo'zg'atadigan mast hujayralaridan mediatorlarning chiqarilish tezligini cheklaydi. Gistamin moddasining ishlab chiqarilishi organizmda terining shishishi, lakrimatsiya qichishish, burun tiqilishi kabi allergik kasalliklarni keltirib chiqaradi.

Kromoglik kislotasi (cromoglycic acid) turli savdo nomlari ostida va turli dozalash shakllarida mavjud. Kromolin natriy 15ml li qutilarda (1 mg 200 bir martalik dozada) aerezolli qadoqdagi (sprey) preparatning 2 %li eritmasi; nafas olish uchun kromogeksal eritmasi 10 mg/ml/2ml, burun uchun sprej 2% li 15 ml; optikrom (lekrolin) ko'z tomchilari 20 mg/ml kabi qo'llaniladi.

Antigistamin va antiallergik ta'sirga ko'ra ketotifen (zaditen, astafen) kromoglik kislotasiga yaqin, ammo undan farqli o'laroq sedativ ta'sirga ega, ya'ni gistamin retseptorlarini bloklaydi. Aniq terapevtik ta'sir 6-8 haftadan keyin rivojlanadi. 1mg tabletkalarda va shishalarda sirop shaklida mavjud. Oksatomid (tinset, fensedil) farmokologik xususiyatiga ko'ra kromoglik kislotaga o'xshaydi.

Uning 30 mg tabletkalarda mavjud bo'lib, kuniga 2 marta 1-2 tabletkadan iste'mol qilinadi.

Allergiyaning namoyon bo'lishi zararsiz bo'lib ko'rinishi mumkin, chunki birinchi qarashda terida qizarish, toshmalar yoki burun oqishi, aksa urish, bronxial astma va anafilaktik shok kabi kabi jiddiy kasallilarning rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tganimdek, allergiya bu – “sivilizatsiya kasalligi” hisoblanadi. Dunyoda kattalar aholining 1/10 (o'ndan bir qismi) astma bilan va bolalar orasida har to'rttadan bittasi allergiyadan aziyat chekadi. Ekologik jihatdan noqulay hududlarda kasallanish ancha yuqori. Har yili “allergiya” bilan kasallanganlar soni 35- 40 mln. kishiga ko'payadi va 10 baravar ko'payadi. Bundan tashqari so'nggi 20 yil ichida sanoati rivojlangan mamlakatlarda bolalar va o'smirlar orasida astma kasalligining tarqalishi 3-4 barobarga oshdi.

Xulosa: Hozirgi vaqtda allergik kasalliklarning turli shakllarini davolash va kuchayishining oldini olish bo'yicha mavjud yondashuvlar “hayot sifati” ni sezilarli darajada ta'minlashi va bemorning normal yoki optimal hayotiy faoliyatini ta'minlashi mumkin. Bunday maqsadga erishish faqat shifokor va bemorning yaqin hamkorligi bilan amalga oshishi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. <https://mosapteki.ru/material/allergicheskie-zabolevaniya-preparaty-vybora-2128>
2. Farmokologiya asoslari M.N. Mahsumov, X. Aliyev, M.A. Odilov, N.A. Musayeva Toshkent - “ILM ZIYO”-2007
3. Najmiddinov, X. B., Dilmurodov, Sh. N., & Raymkulova, Ch. A. (2021). Inson Ekshalatsiyasida Ammiakni Invaziv Bo'lmagan Usul Bilan Aniqlash. Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali, 1(5), 50-54.
4. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbaev, S. D., Vasina, S. M., & Aronbaev, D. M. (2020). Exhaled air as an object of studying the functional state of the organism. Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences, (1-2), 47-51.
5. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbayev, S. D., & Aronbayev, D. M. (2021). Ekshalatsiyalangan havoda ammiakni aniqlash muammosiga. Universum: kimyo va biologiya, (1-1 (79)), 26-34.
6. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbayev, S. D., & Aronbayev, D. M. (2022). Biomarkerlar va xavflarni baholash. Universum: kimyo va biologiya, (1 (91)), 77-83.

7. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbayev, S. D., & Aronbayev, D. M. (2020). Ekshalatsiyalangan havoni tahlil qilish invaziv bo'lmagan diagnostika usuli sifatida. International scientific journal "Global science and innovations", 56-58.
8. Aronbayev, D. M., Aronbayev, S. D., Raimkulova, Ch.A., Isakova, D. T., & Shertaeva, A. A. (2021). Suv "tirik" va " o'lik". elektroaktiv suvning antioksidant va gevşeme xususiyatlari haqida yangi faktlar. Universum: kimyo va biologiya, (2 (80)), 26-31
9. Aronbayev, S. D., Aronbayev, D. M., Ismoilov, E. X., Islomov, L. B., Raimkulova, Ch.A., & Juraeva, S. B. (2020). Screen-printed elektrodleri og'ir metallarning inversion-voltammetrik ta'rifida. Universum: kimyo va biologiya, (5 (71)), 22-34.
10. Narbayev, K., & Raimkulova, Ch.A. (2022, February). Indofenol usuli bilan ammoniy ionlarini spektrofotometrik aniqlash shartlarini tanlash. In The 7 th International scientific and practical conference "Science, innovations and education: problems and prospects"(February 9-11, 2022. CPN Publishing Group, Tokyo, Japan. 2022. 842 p. (p. 161).
11. Raimkulova, C. A., Narbayev, K. M., Aronbayev, D. M., & Aronbayev, S. D. (2022). Ammoniy ionlarini spektrofotometrik aniqlash uchun indofenol kompleksining hosil bo'lish sharoitlarini optimallashtirish. Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science, (77-1), 3-9.
12. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbayev, S. D., & Aronbayev, D. M. (2020). Ekshalatsiyalangan havoda ammiakni ko'rsatishning vizual-rangli usuli va uni amalga oshirish uchun moslama. Universum: kimyo va biologiya, (7 (73)), 40-42.
13. Raimkulova, Ch.A., & Soibov, X. J. (2023). Avitsennaning biz nafas olayotgan va chiqaradigan havo haqidagi fikrlari, uning tanaga ta'siri. ammiakni invaziv bo'lmagan usul bilan aniqlash. Ta'lim fidoyilari, 4 (1), 74-78.
14. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbayev, S. D., & Aronbayev, D. M. (2023). Salivodiagnostika: o'tmish, hozirgi, kelajak. Universum: kimyo va biologiya, (1-2 (103)), 27-37.
15. Raimkulova, C. A., & Xolmurodova, D. K. (2022). Ba'zi klinik ahamiyatga ega biomarkerlarni invaziv bo'lmagan nazorat qilish usullari va qurilmalarini ishlab chiqish. Gepato-gastroenterologik tadqiqotlar jurnali, (SI-2).
16. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbayev, S. D., & Aronbayev, D. M. (2022). Potansiyometrik oqim-in'ektsiya sensori yordamida aralash tupurikning PH qiymatini o'lchash. Universum: kimyo va biologiya, (6-2 (96)), 5-12.
17. Isa o'g'li, X. A. (2023). O'zbek terminologiyasida soha terminlarining o'rganilishi. The theory of recent scientific research in the field of pedagogy, 2(16), 118-120..
18. Xasanov, A. (2023). Etymological analysis of special terms. Международный журнал языка, образования, перевода, 4(3).
19. ўғли Ҳасанов, А. И. (2023, January). С. Айнийнинг "судхўрнинг ўлими" қиссасида қўлланган арабча терминларнинг семантик-структур таҳлили. In International conferences (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 32-37)..
20. Hasanov, A. (2023). Study of field terms in world terminology. Science and innovation, 2(C12), 151-155.

21. Isaevich, H. A. (2022). Studying the notion of term in the uzbek and world linguistics. *British View*, 7(4)..
22. Hasanov, A. I. (2022). Analysis of economic and banking terms used in the epic "Death of a usurer". *Международный журнал языка, образования, перевода*, 3(3).
23. Isa o'g'li, H. A. (2022). Sadriddin ayniyning "Sudxo'ring o'limi" asarida qo'llangan ijtimoiy terminlarning semantik tahlili. *Fan, ta'lim va amaliyotning integratsiyasi*, 3(8), 5-9.
24. Ahmad, X. (2022). Sadriddin ayniyning "Sudxo'ring o'limi" asarida qo'llangan davlat boshqaruvi tizimiga oid terminlarning pragmatik tahlili. *Science and innovation*, 1(Special Issue 2), 574-576.
25. Ahmad, H. (2022). Xarakterni tasvirlashda dialog va monolog. *fan, ta'lim va amaliyotning integratsiyasi*, 858-861.
26. Isa o'g'li, X. A. (2021). Ruhiyat tasvirida peyzajning o'rni. *fan, ta'lim va amaliyotning integratsiyasi*, 2(5), 98-105..

JISMONIY TARBIYANING INSON TANASIGA TA`SIRI

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O`zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiva va sport universiteti Farg`ona filiali o`qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Jismoniy tarbiyaning hayotimizda tutgan o`rni beqiyosligi, u insonning ruhan va jismonan yetuk bo`lishida katta ahamiyat kasb etishi va yoshlarni sog`ligini mustahkamlash vatan himoyasiga va mehnatga bo`lgan layoqatini kamol toptirishda alohida o`rin kasb etishi haqida so`z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Jismoniy mashq, tarbiya, jismoniy sifatlar pedagogik, biologik va fiziologik, sog`lik

THE EFFECT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Annotation. This article will talk about the incomparable role of physical education in our lives, its great importance in the spiritual and physical maturity of a person, and the strengthening of the health of young people has a special place in the protection of the motherland and the maturation of working capacity.

Keywords: exercise, education, physical qualities, pedagogical, biological and physiological, health

Xalqimiz qadimdan yosh avlod tarbiyasida «Sog'lom tanda — sog` aql» tamoiiliga asoslanib, ulami ruhan faol, axloqli va ma`naviy yuksak, ishchan qilib tarbiyalashga alohida e`tibor berib kelishgan. **Jismoniy tarbiya**, badan tarbiya — sog`liqni mustahkamlashga, odam organizmini uyg'un ravishda rivojlantirishga qaratilgan umumiy tarbiyaning uzviy qismi. jismoniy tarbiyaning asosiy vositasi jismoniy mashqlar bo`lib u tarixan gimnastika, o`yinlar, sport va turizm tarzida guruhlarga ajratilib, tarbiya jarayonining vositasi sifatida foydalanib kelindi. Jismoniy mashq deb jismoniy tarbiya qonuniyatlari talablariga javob beruvchi, ongli ravishda bajariladigan ixtiyoriy harakat faoliyatlarining turli turkumi tushuniladi.

Jismoniy mashqning vujudga kelishida obyektiv sabab qilib ibtidoiy odamning qorin to‘ydirish maqsadida ov qilishi, subyektiv sabab sifatida ongning shakllanishi deb qaraldi. Ibtidoiy qurollarni ishlatishni bilmagan ibtidoiy odam o‘z o‘ljasini holdan toldirguncha quvlagan. Bu bilan ovchi organizmi katta jismoniy tayyorgarlikka muhtojlik sezgan. Jismoniy tayyorgarligi etarli bo‘lmaganlarining o‘zlari o‘ljasiga yem bo‘lgan. Shunga ko‘ra vaqt o‘tishi bilan ibtidoiy odamlar ovga gala-gala bo‘lib chiqadigan bo‘ldilar. Ibtidoiy qurollar: tosh, qirrali tosh boylangan nayza, xas-cho‘p bilan nomigagina berkitilib qo‘yilgan chohlardan va boshqalardan ovchilar foydalana boshlashgan, ijtimoiy ong shakllana boshlangan. Ovda ishtirok etolmay qolgan qabilani qariyalari yoshlarga toshni nishinga otish, uni zarbini kuchaytirishni mashq qildiradi boshlagan va bu bilan tarbiyaga asos solingan tarbiya jarayonining elementlari shakllana boshlagan. Keyinchalik uloqtirish, quvib yetish yoki qochish uchun yugurish, sakrashlar mashq qilina boshlangan. Bu esa jismoniy mashqlarni hamda jismoniy tarbiyaning elementlarini vujudga kelishi va shakllanish davri deb qaralgan. Shu kunga kelib bu mashqlar hozirgi zamonning yengil atletika, gimnastika, sport o‘yinlari, yakka kurashlari, turizm va sportning boshqa turlari tarzida jismoniy tarbiya jarayoni uchun asosiy vosita sifatida foydalanilmoqda. Jismoniy mashqlar xillarining ko‘payishiga insonning mehnat faoliyati ham ta’sir ko‘rsatdi. Ma’lumki, mehnat jismoniy kuch, chidamlilik, tezkorlik, chaqqonlikdek insonning jismi (harakat) sifatlarining ma’lum darajadagi tayyorgarligi, uning rivojlanganligini talab qiladi. Tarbiya amaliyotida, asosan, inson mehnat faoliyatida qo‘llaydigan harakatlarini ko‘proq mashq qiladi. Jismoniy mashqning rivojlanishida diniy marosimlar, bayramlardagi o‘yinlar, raqslar, harbiy faoliyatdagi, sanoatdagi ongli ravishda bajariladigan ixtiyoriy harakatlar vosita bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Jismoniy mashqlar tabiatini tabiiy qonunlar I.M. Sechenov va I.P. Pavlovning ilmiy dunyo qarashlarida ochib berilgan. Ixtiyoriy harakat Sechenovning fikricha, ong va aql bilan boshqariladi hamda biror maqsadga yo‘naltirilgan bo‘ladi. Pavlov esa harakatlarni fiziologik mexanizmini ochib, harakatlar bosh miya po‘stloq qismining to‘plash xususiyati bilan bog‘liqligini birinchi, ikkinchi signal sistemasi, shartli hamda shartsiz reflekslarning aktiv ishtirokida vujudga kelishligini ilmiy isbotladi.

Pedagogik nuqtai nazardan harakat vazifasini oson samarali hal qilish uchun tanlangan harakat faoliyatini jismoniy mashq texnikasi deb atash qabul qilingan. Samaradorlik o‘quvchilar organizmiga eng oqilona ta’sir o‘tkazish bilan ifodalanadi.

Jismoniy mashqlarning mazmuni va shakli. Barcha hodisa va jarayonlarga o'xshash jismoniy mashqlar o'zining mazmuni va shakliga ega. Jismoniy mashqni bajarishda sodir bo'ladigan mexanik, biologik, psixologik jarayonlarning to'plami jismoniy mashqlarning mazmunini vujudga keltiradi, ularning ta'siridan harakat faoliyati uchun qobiliyat rivojlanadi. Shuningdek mashq mazmuniga uning bo'laklarini to'plami, masalan, uzunlikka sakrashda tanaga tezlik berish, depsinish havoda uchish, erga tushish zvenolari hamda mashqni bajarishda hal qilinadigan vazifalar, shuningdek mashqni bajarishdan organizmda sodir bo'ladigan funksional o'zgarishlar haqidagi nazariy bilim va amaliy harakat malakalari kiradi. Bu elementlarning barchasi jismoniy mashqning umumiy mazmunini vujudga keltiradi.

Jismoniy mashqlar ta'sirida inson tanasida yuz beradigan biologik va fiziologik o'zgarishlar haqida to'xtalib o'tamiz, Jismoniy mashq qilib yurgan kishilarning yuragi 250-300 grammni tashkil etsa, sportchilarda bu 350-500 grni tashkil etishi aniqlangan. Asosiy qism. Shu sababli o'quvchi-yoshlar va talabalar yurak-qon tomirlari tizimidagi faoliyatini yaxshilash uchun doimo jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan shug'ullanishlari lozim, chunki yurak devorlari qanchalik qalin, mustahkam va uning hajmi keng, og'irligi katta bo'lsa, yashash va mehnat (jismoniy va aqliy) qilish qobiliyati shuncha mustahkam bo'ladi. Qon bosimi va uning qon aylanishiga ta'siri Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, yurakka qonning kelib quyilishi va chi-qib ketishida yurak qorinchalarining ish faoliyati (qisqarishi) asosiy o'rin egallaydi va qon bosimi (qon aylanishini tezligi)ni ta'minlaydi. Sog'lom kishilarda qon bosimi simob ustutining 120/70 mm.da bo'ladi. Bunda qorinchalarning qisqarish (qonni haydash) tartibi (ritmi) yurak urishini bildiradi va ko'krak qafasida bevosita bilinadi. Uning qon tomirlardagi harakat ta'siri (qonning oqim darajasi) pulsni bildiradi. Buni bilak va boshqa a'zolaridagi vena qon tomirlarini barmoq bilan bosib ko'rish, aniqrog'i tonometr orqali o'lchash bilan aniqlash mumkin. Jismoniy chiniqmaganlarda puls tinch holda har daqiqada 70-80, sportchilarda 50-60 va ayollarda esa 75-85 (chiniqqanlarda 60-70) marta urishi kuzatiladi. Nafas olish jarayonlari Havo nafas olganda og'iz va burun bo'shliqlari orqali o'pkaga boradi. Toza havo o'pkaga etib borgach, undagi eski havoni (uglevod) siqib chiqaradi. Bunda o'pkaning harakatlanuvchi (nasos) xususiyati asosiy o'rin egallaydi. Tinch turgan va mehnat qilgan (jismoniy mashqlar) paytlarda nafas olishning tezligi susayishi va kuchayishi sodir bo'ladi. Bu paytlarda o'pkaning havo sig'imi muhim ahamiyatga egadir. Sportchilar tinch holda turganda har daqiqada 8-12 marotabagacha nafas olishi mumkin. Mashg'ulotlar, musobaqalarda esa ularning soni sport tulariga qarab, 20-28

marotabagacha yetishi mumkin. Chang'ichi-larda bu ko'rsatkich 20-28, suzuvchilarda 36-40 va suvosti sportchi-larida 45-50 marotabagacha yetadi. Ba'zi bir hollarda sportchilarda nafas olish har daqiqada 75 marotabagacha yetishi kuzatilgan. Jismoniy tarbiya va sport bilan muntazam ravishda shuqullanish, o'pkaning havo sig'imini kengaytirib, nafas olish miqdorini kamaytiradi. O'pkada havo almashishi (ventilyatsiya) turlicha bo'lishi mumkin. Tinch turgan holda har daqiqada 5-9 litr havo almashishi kuzatilgan. Yuqori malakali sportchilarda bu ko'rsatkich 15-20 barobar ortishi ham aniqlangan.

Jismoniy tarbiyaning sog'liqqa foydalari:

- sport bilan muntazam shug'ullanish uzoq umr ko'rishning eng oddiy yo'lidir.

- kishi sport bilan shug'ullanganida organizmi yaxshi chiniqadi, muskullari tez charchamaydi. Chiniqqan odamning nerv-endokrin, yurak-qon tomir, nafas olish va boshqa hayotiy muhim a'zolari hamda to'qimalarining ish faoliyati ortadi.

- sport mashg'ulotlari odam tanasidagi to'qimalarning tez yangilanishi, uning yosh, sog'lom va tetik saqlanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

- taloqda limfotsitlar hosil bo'lishi ko'payib, organizmning yuqumli kasalliklardan himoyalaniq qobiliyati (immunitet) kuchayadi.

- kam harakatlilik (gipodinamiya) yurak faoliyatini kuchsizlantiradi. Natijada yurak-qon tomir va boshqa kasalliklar yuzaga keladi.

- mashqlar orqali qon aylanishi tezlashadi, miyamizga kislorod boradi, mushaklar kuchayib, bo'g'imlarning harakatini ta'minlaydi, ruhiy taranglik yo'qolib, energiya ortadi.

- sport bilan shug'ullanuvchilarda yurak klapanlari va muskullari yaxshi rivojlanib, uning hajmi boshqalarnikiga qaraganda kattaroq bo'ladi.

- o'pkaning tiriklik sig'imi ortadi (4500-6500 ml.ga etadi), nafas olish va qon aylanish a'zolari yaxshi rivojlanadi.

- odatda zaiflashgan, chiniqmagan tanada mikroblar yashashi va ko'payishi uchun qulay sharoit topadi. Natijada bunday odam kasallanadi.

- jismoniy mashqlar tufayli yurak, buyrak, o'pka va tomirlar kuchga to'ladi, tomirlar kengayadi va elastik holatga keladi. Shunday qilib tomirlardagi yog' nisbati, xolesterin, shakar va insulin pasayadi. Tananing yog' nisbati kamaysa, o'zimizni kuchli his etamiz, asab tizimi sog'lom bo'ladi.

- xotirani kuchaytirishning eng muhim sharti asablarning sog'lom bo'lishidir. Buning uchun esa badantarbiya bilan shug'ullanish lozim.

- uy sharoitida jismoniy mashqlar bajarish yoki biron sport turi bilan shug'ullanish hozirda keng tarqalgan semirishning oddiy davosidir. Zero, semirish ish faoliyatini pasaytiradi, sog'liqni zaiflashtiradi.

- jismoniy tarbiya mashqlari kishiga ko'tarinkilik va ruhiy dalda bag'ishlaydi. Bunday holda ishlar unumli va sog'liq joyida bo'ladi.

- agar kishi bir kunda 10 daqiqa jismoniy mashqlar bajarsa, u daqiqasiga yuragining 10 marta urishini "tejab" qolar ekan. Bu bir yilda 500.000 martani tashkil qiladi. Mana shu yo'l bilan yurak-qon tomir kasalliklaridan forig' bo'lish, yurakni sog'lom qilish, infarktdan qutulish mumkin.

- aqliy mehnat jismoniy mehnat bilan almashtirib turilsa, odam uzoq vaqt charchamaydi, ishi unumli bo'ladi. Chunki aqliy mehnat davrida miyadagi qo'zg'algan markazlar jismoniy mehnat vaqtida dam oladi. Chunonchi, ilm olishda har 40-60 daqiqada 5-6 daqiqa badantarbiya mashqlari bajarilsa, miyaning zo'riqishidan paydo bo'ladigan nevroz kasalligining oldi olinadi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki yoshlarning jismoniy barkamolligini tarbiyalashdek o'ta muhim, muammolarni hal etishda jismoniy tarbiya va sport, uning tabiiy-ilmiy asoslari va shu bilan birgalikda jamiyat rivojlanishda inson salomatligi, jismoniy holatlar, jismoniy rivojlanish va chiniqishlar muhim ahamiyatga ega.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Safoyev H.A. Involta Ilmiy Jurnal Uzbekiston: Vol. 1 –No.4 2022.–P.275-281.
2. Rajabov, G. U., & Mamatqulov, X. (2023). Bokschilarning musobaqa faoliyati xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda texnik-taktik harakatlarini takomillashtirish. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(13), 36-45.
3. Вахтийор огли М. Х. Bokschilarning zarbalarini rivojlantirish uchun kuch jismoniy sifatini samaradorligini oshirish //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 18. – С. 19-22.

VOLEYBOLDA TO'PNI O'YINGA KIRITISH TEXNIKASI

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O'zbekiston davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti Farg'ona filiali Sport o'yinlari nazariyasi va uslubiyati kafedrsi assistent o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Voleybolda to'pni o'yinga kiritish texnikasi o'yinning asosiy jihati bo'lib, maydonda muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqola to'pni kiritish orqali o'yinni samarali boshlash uchun o'yinchilar va murabbiylar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan turli usullar va strategiyalarni o'rganadi. Muvaffaqiyatli servislar, paslar va setlarni bajarishda aniqlik, vaqt va jamoaviy ishning ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada to'pni kiritish usullarini optimallashtirishda jamoa a'zolari o'rtasidagi aloqa va muvofiqlashtirishning roli muhokama qilinadi. Voleybolning ushbu muhim jihatining nozik tomonlarini tahlil qilib, ushbu maqola o'yinchilarning ishlashi va jamoa dinamikasini yaxshilashga yordam beradigan tushunchalarni taqdim etishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Voleybol, To'p bilan tanishtirish, Xizmat qilish, O'tkazish, Set, Texnika, Strategiya, Jamoada ishlash.

TECHNIQUE OF ENTERING THE BALL INTO THE GAME IN VOLLEYBALL

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Abstract. In volleyball, passing technique is a key aspect of the game and is crucial to success on the court. This article explores the various techniques and strategies used by players and coaches to effectively start the game by fielding the ball. It discusses the importance of accuracy, timing and teamwork in executing successful serves, passes and sets. In addition, the article discusses the role of communication and coordination between team members in optimizing ball entry methods. By analyzing the nuances of this important aspect of volleyball, this article aims to provide insights that can help improve player performance and team dynamics.

Keywords: Volleyball, Introducing the ball, Serving, Passing, Set, Technique, Strategy, Teamwork.

Kirish. Voleybolda to'pni o'yinga kiritish, bu to'pni maydonning oxirgi chizig'i orqasidan o'yinga kiritish harakati. O'yinchilar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan turli xil xizmat ko'rsatish usullari mavjud, ularning har biri o'zining afzalliklari va qiyinchiliklariga ega. Bularga quyidagilar kiradi:

- o'yinchi to'pni havoga otish, sakrab, to'pni katta kuch va aylanish bilan uradigan kuchli faoliyat.

- minimal aylanishli harakat, havoda oldindan aytib bo'lmaydigan tarzda "suzish" uchun mo'ljallangan, bu esa qabul qiluvchiga uning traektoriyasini bashorat qilishni qiyinlashtiradi.

- to'pni traektoriyasining oxirigacha keskin tushib ketishiga olib keladi, bu esa qabul qiluvchining aniq o'tishini qiyinlashtiradi.

- o'yinchilar mudofaa tuzilmalarini buzish va ustunlikka ega bo'lish uchun raqib maydonining muayyan joylarini nishonga olishni maqsad qiladi.

- qabul qilish deb ham ataladigan uzatma, raqibning xizmat yoki hujumini qabul qilishni va hujumkor o'yinni o'rnatish uchun to'pni jamoadoshiga yo'naltirishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Otishning asosiy jihatlariga quyidagilar kiradi:

- bilaklardan foydalanib, to'pning orqaga qaytishi uchun tekis platforma yaratish, nazorat ostida va aniq uzatmalarni amalga oshirish imkonini beradi.

- to'pni jamoadoshiga yo'naltirish uchun qo'llardan foydalanish, ko'pincha to'p bilakdan uzatish uchun juda baland bo'lganda foydalaniladi.

Muvaffaqiyatli uzatma to'pni samarali uzatishni ta'minlash va ralli uzluksizligini ta'minlash uchun yaxshi oyoq harakati, kutish va jamoadoshlar o'rtasidagi muloqotni talab qiladi.

- urganning yondashuvi va vaqtini hisobga olgan holda to'pni to'r yaqinidagi kerakli holatga aniq o'rnatish.

- to'pni to'g'ri vaqtda qo'yib yuborish, zarba beruvchiga kuchli va o'z vaqtda zarba berish imkonini beradi.

- raqib blokerlarini taxmin qilishda davom etish va jamoaning hujum strategiyalarining samaradorligini oshirish uchun o'zgaruvchan to'plamlar.

Setterlar mukammal qaror qabul qilish qobiliyatiga, fazoviy xabardorlikka va bosim ostida samarali to'plamlarni etkazib berish uchun o'yinni o'qish qobiliyatiga ega bo'lishi kerak.

Umuman olganda, voleybolda to'pni o'yinga kiritish texnikasi individual mahorat, jamoaviy ish va strategik ongni uyg'unlashtirishni talab qiladi. O'yinchilar va jamoalar o'zlarining ish faoliyatini optimallashtirish va maydonda raqobatbardosh ustunlikka ega bo'lish uchun ushbu usullarni doimiy ravishda takomillashtirishlari va moslashtirishlari kerak.

Xulosa. Voleybolda to'pni o'yinga kiritish texnikasi o'yinni boshlashda va muvaffaqiyatli o'yin uchun zamin yaratishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan xizmat ko'rsatish, paslar va to'plarni o'z ichiga oladi. Xizmat ko'rsatish usullari turlicha bo'lib, kuchli sakrashdan tortib aniq suzib yurishgacha, o'yinchilar raqib himoyasini buzish va strategik ustunlikka ega bo'lishni maqsad qilgan. To'pni to'g'ri qabul qilish va hujumkor o'yinlarni o'rnatish uchun to'pni yo'naltirishni o'z ichiga oladi, bu nazorat va barqarorlikning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. To'plar hujum qilish imkoniyatlari uchun to'pni joylashtirishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi, mahoratli ijro va jamoadoshlarning imkoniyatlarini tushunishni talab qiladi. To'pni samarali joriy etish jamoa a'zolari o'rtasidagi muloqot, muvofiqlashtirish va moslashishga bog'liq bo'lib, voleybolning hamkorlik xarakterini ta'kidlaydi. Ushbu texnika va strategiyalarni o'zlashtirgan holda, o'yinchilar va jamoalar o'zlarining ko'rsatkichlarini oshirishlari va maydonda muvaffaqiyatga erishishlari mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. FIVB - Xalqaro voleybol federatsiyasi. (nd). Rasmiy voleybol qoidalari 2024-2028.
2. https://www.fivb.org/EN/FIVB/Document/RuleBook/Rules_VB2024-2028_EN_2024-07.

3. Karpov, A. (2019). Voleybolga xizmat ko'rsatish san'ati: texnika va strategiya. Sport fanlari va murabbiylik jurnali, 14(3), 385-398.
4. Smit, J. va Jons, L. (2021). Voleybolda o'tish asoslari: texnika va mashqlar. Sport fanlari va murabbiylik xalqaro jurnali, 16(2), 201-215.
5. Stivens, M. va Tompson, R. (2018). Voleybolni o'rnatish fani: tamoyillar va amaliyot. Amaliy sport fanlari jurnali, 23(4), 567-580.
6. Solijonovich, S. J., & Xasanov, A. T. (2023). Kasb-hunar maktabida voleybol seksiyasi ishini tashkillash samaradorligi. O'zbekistonda fanlararo.
7. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Voleybolda hujum va himoya texnikasini egallash. sport va xorijiy tillar integratsiyasining amalga oshirish muammolari va yechimlari, 1(1), 203-205.
8. Abduraxmonov, S. (2023). Gandbolchilarning sport tayyorgarligi tizimi. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(10), 195-197.
9. Mirzatillo o'g'li, A. D. (2024). Kroll usulida ko'krakda suzish. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(17), 400-402.
10. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda to 'pni o 'yinga kiritish texnikasi. IMRAS, 6(6), 366-373.
11. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda hujum qilish texnikasi. Научный Фокус, 1(7), 570-574.
12. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida voleybol seksiyasining maqsad va vazifalari. Pedagog, 7(2), 122-127.
13. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Professional ta'lim muassasalarida voleybol bo'yicha sport seksiyalarini tashkil etish metodikasini takomillashtirish.(yosh voleybolchilarda jismoniy va maxsus ish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion metodlari asosida). Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(17), 63-66.
14. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida voleybol seksiyasining maqsad va vazifalari. Pedagog, 7(2), 122-127.
15. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda to 'pni uzatish texnikasi. Pedagog, 6(11), 14-18.
16. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Voleybolda o 'rgatish metodlarining umumiy asoslari. sport va xorijiy tillar integratsiyasining amalga oshirish muammolari va yechimlari, 1(1), 206-209.

XABARCHI MILLIY IJTIMOYIY TARMOG'INING XAVFSIZLIKGINI TA'MINLASH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola, "Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmoq'ining xavfsizligini ta'minlash mavzusida yozilgan bo'lib, O'zbekistonda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va messengerlar yaratishning ahamiyati hamda ularning xavfsizligini ta'minlashdagi dolzarb masalalarni o'rganadi. Maqolada, milliy kontentni rivojlantirish, foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish va zararli axborotlardan saqlanish yuzasidan amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, shuningdek, bu borada qabul qilingan qonun va qarorlar tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, maqola O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasiga yuborilgan parlament so'rovi va uning natijalari, shuningdek, milliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va messengerlar yaratish bo'yicha olib borilayotgan ishlar haqida ma'lumot beradi. Ushbu maqola, milliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning xavfsizligini ta'minlash sohasida mutaxassislar, olimlar va qaror qabul qiluvchilar uchun foydali manba bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy tarmoq xavfsizligi, milliy messengerlar shaxsiy ma'lumotlar himoyasi, zararli axborotlardan saqlanish, qonun va qarorlar tahlili, parlament so'rovlari, texnologik rivojlanish

ENSURING THE SECURITY OF THE NATIONAL SOCIAL NETWORK "KHABARCHI".

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Abstract: This article is written on the topic of ensuring the security of the national social network "Messenger" and examines the importance of creating social networks and messengers in Uzbekistan and current issues in ensuring their security. The article analyzes the work being done on the development of national content, the protection of users' personal data and the prevention of harmful information, as well as the laws and decisions adopted in this regard. In addition, the article provides information about the parliamentary inquiry sent to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its results, as well as the ongoing work on the creation of national social networks and messengers. This article can be a useful resource for professionals, scientists and decision makers in the field of security of national social networks.

Keywords: Social network security, national messengers, personal data protection, prevention of harmful information, law and decision analysis, parliamentary inquiries, technological development

Kirish. Zamonaviy dunyoda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va messenjerlar kundalik hayotimizning ajralmas qismiga aylanmoqda. Ular bizga yaqinlarimiz bilan aloqada bo'lish, yangiliklarni kuzatib borish va turli xil ma'lumotlar almashish imkonini beradi. Biroq, shu bilan birga, foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarining xavfsizligi ham doimo muhim masala bo'lib qolmoqda. "Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i ham O'zbekiston foydalanuvchilari uchun yaratilgan platforma bo'lib, uning xavfsizligi ko'plab foydalanuvchilarni qiziqtiradi. Ushbu maqola orqali biz "Xabarchi" tarmog'ining xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, qabul qilingan qonunlar va qarorlar, shuningdek, kelajakdagi rejalarni tahlil qilamiz. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi - milliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va messenjerlar yaratishning ahamiyatini ta'kidlash va ularning xavfsizligini ta'minlashdagi zamonaviy yondashuvlarni o'rganishdir.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining xavfsizligi mavzusida yozilgan adabiyotlar ko'plab muhim mavzularni qamrab oladi. Ushbu tahlilda, mavjud adabiyotlardan olingan asosiy g'oyalar va ularning "Xabarchi"ning xavfsizligini ta'minlash kontekstidagi ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi.

Karimov va Turgunovning "Axborot xavfsizligi asoslari" darsligida axborot xavfsizligi va uning muhofaza qilish tushunchalari, himoyalangan axborotga tahdidlar, axborot xavfsizligi bo'yicha normativ huquqiy hujjatlar kabi mavzular batafsil yoritilgan¹. Ushbu manba, "Xabarchi" kabi milliy tarmoqlarning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan axborotni texnik va kriptografik himoyalash usullari haqida ham qimmatli ma'lumotlar taqdim etadi.

Vikipediya sahifasida axborot xavfsizligi, uning asosiy maqsadi, tahdid manbalari, zaifliklar va xavflarni boshqarish jarayoni kabi umumiy tushunchalar haqida ma'lumot beriladi². Bu ma'lumotlar "Xabarchi"ning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda duch keladigan umumiy xavflarni tushunish va ularni boshqarish uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Oriens.uz saytida chop etilgan maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlovchi huquqiy hujjatlar va ularning tahlili keltirilgan³. Ushbu maqola, "Xabarchi"ning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda qo'llaniladigan huquqiy asoslar va me'yoriy hujjatlarni tushunishda yordam beradi.

Shuningdek, kiberxavfsizlikka oid milliy va xorijiy me'yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlar tahlili haqida yozilgan maqolada, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari va zamonaviy boshqaruv tizimlarining ajralmas qismi sifatida axborot xavfsizligi muhokama qilinadi⁴. Bu maqola, "Xabarchi"ning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda qo'llaniladigan xalqaro standartlar va amaliyotlarni o'rganishda foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Ushbu adabiyotlar tahlili, "Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining xavfsizligini ta'minlash mavzusida chuqurroq tushuncha hosil qilish va mavjud bilimlarni kengaytirish uchun asos yaratadi.

"Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'i foydalanuvchilarga xavfsiz va ishonchli axborot almashinuvi platformasini taqdim etish bilan birga, ko'plab ijobiy jihatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu tarmoqning xavfsizligini ta'minlashning asosiy afzalliklari quyidagilardan iborat:

1. Shaxsiy ma'lumotlarning himoyasi: "Xabarchi"ning kuchli xavfsizlik tizimi foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini noqonuniy kirish va suiste'mol qilinishdan himoya qiladi.

2. Zararli kontentdan saqlanish: Xavfsizlik protokollari va filtratsiya tizimlari orqali zararli va noto'g'ri ma'lumotlarning tarqalishini oldini oladi.

3. Milliy ma'lumotlar suvereniteti: Ma'lumotlarni mahalliy serverlarda saqlash orqali milliy ma'lumotlar suverenitetini ta'minlaydi va chet el kuchlarining aralashuviga yo'l qo'ymaydi.

4. Iqtisodiy mustaqillik: Mahalliy ijtimoiy tarmoqlarni rivojlantirish orqali iqtisodiy mustaqillikni oshiradi va milliy brendlarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

5. Madaniy qadriyatlarni saqlash: "Xabarchi" milliy madaniyat va qadriyatlarni aks ettiruvchi kontentni targ'ib qilish imkonini beradi.

6. Huquqiy javobgarlik: Milliy qonunchilikka muvofiq ishlaydigan tarmoq sifatida, "Xabarchi" foydalanuvchilarni huquqiy himoya qilishda ancha samarali.

7. Ta'lim va tarbiya: Foydalanuvchilarga ta'limiy va tarbiyaviy ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish orqali jamiyatning axborot savodxonligini oshirishga hissa qo'shadi.

Ushbu afzalliklar "Xabarchi"ni nafaqat O'zbekiston foydalanuvchilari uchun, balki butun dunyo bo'ylab raqamli xavfsizlikni qadrlaydiganlar uchun ham jozibador qiladi. "Xabarchi"ning xavfsizligini ta'minlash, shu bilan birga, milliy axborot tizimlarini mustahkamlash va raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Har qanday texnologik platforma kabi, "Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining xavfsizligi ham ba'zi kamchiliklarga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu kamchiliklar quyidagilarni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin:

1. Texnik xatolar va nosozliklar: Har qanday dasturiy ta'minotda bo'lgani kabi, "Xabarchi"da ham texnik xatolar yuzaga kelishi mumkin, bu esa foydalanuvchilarning tajribasiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

2. Yangilanish va o'zgartirishlar: Tarmoqni doimiy ravishda yangilab turish va xavfsizlik tizimini takomillashtirish zarurati, ba'zan foydalanuvchilarga noqulaylik tug'dirishi mumkin.

3. Serverlarning ortiqcha yuklanishi: Foydalanuvchilar sonining keskin oshishi serverlarga ortiqcha yuk keltirib chiqarishi va natijada tizimning sekinlashishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

4. Xavfsizlik tahdidlari: Kiberhujumlar va zararli dasturlar kabi xavfsizlik tahdidlari har doim mavjud bo'lib, ularni oldini olish uchun doimiy ehtiyotkorlik va texnik yangilanishlar talab etiladi.

5. Foydalanuvchilarning xavfsizlik madaniyati: Foydalanuvchilarning xavfsizlikka bo'lgan e'tiborsizligi ham tarmoqning xavfsizligiga tahdid solishi mumkin, chunki ko'pincha xavfsizlik muammolari foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini ehtiyotsiz boshqarishidan kelib chiqadi.

6. Qonunchilikdagi o'zgarishlar: Milliy va xalqaro qonunchilikdagi tez-tez sodir bo'ladigan o'zgarishlar tarmoqning xavfsizlik siyosatini doimiy ravishda yangilab turishni talab qiladi.

7. Ma'lumotlarning lokalizatsiyasi: Ma'lumotlarni faqat milliy serverlarda saqlash, xalqaro foydalanuvchilar uchun ma'lumotlarga kirishni cheklashi mumkin.

Ushbu kamchiliklar "Xabarchi" tarmog'ining xavfsizligini ta'minlash jarayonida e'tiborga olinishi va yechimlar ishlab chiqilishi kerak bo'lgan masalalardir.

1. Foydalanuvchilar ishonchi: "Xabarchi"ning xavfsizligi bo'yicha amalga oshirilgan chora-tadbirlar natijasida foydalanuvchilar orasida tarmoqqa bo'lgan ishonch sezilarli darajada oshdi.

2. Ma'lumotlar suvereniteti: Mahalliy serverlarda ma'lumotlarni saqlash orqali milliy ma'lumotlar suvereniteti mustahkamlanib, ma'lumotlarning chet elga chiqib ketish xavfi kamaydi.

3. Xavfsizlik madaniyati: Foydalanuvchilarning xavfsizlik madaniyatini oshirishga qaratilgan tadbirlar natijasida, ularning xavfsizlikka bo'lgan e'tibori va mas'uliyati yuqori darajaga ko'tarildi.

4. Huquqiy tizimning mustahkamlanishi: Xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan qonun va qarorlar qabul qilinishi bilan birga, huquqiy tizim yanada mustahkamlandi.

5. Texnik yutuqlar: Xavfsizlikni ta'minlash bo'yicha texnik yechimlar va yangilanishlar joriy etilishi natijasida tarmoqning umumiy ishlash samaradorligi oshdi.

Shu bilan birga, mavjud kamchiliklar ham aniqlandi va ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha ishlar davom ettirilmoqda. Jumladan, texnik nosozliklar va serverlarning ortiqcha yuklanishi kabi muammolar hal etilmoqda, xavfsizlik tahdidlariga qarshi

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kurashish bo'yicha yangi strategiyalar ishlab chiqilmoqda, va foydalanuvchilarning xavfsizlik madaniyatini yanada oshirishga qaratilgan tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Natijada, "Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha erishilgan yutuqlar, tarmoqning kelajakdagi rivojlanishi va foydalanuvchilarga xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini oshirishda muhim qadam bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda.

Xulosa qilib aytganda "Xabarchi" milliy ijtimoiy tarmog'ining xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqot va ishlar, ushbu sohada muhim yutuqlarga erishilganini ko'rsatmoqda. Tarmoqning xavfsizligi foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish, zararli kontentdan saqlanish va milliy axborot suverenitetini ta'minlash kabi bir qator afzalliklarni taqdim etadi. Biroq, texnik nosozliklar, serverlarning ortiqcha yuklanishi va xavfsizlik tahdidlari kabi kamchiliklar ham mavjud bo'lib, ularni bartaraf etish uchun doimiy e'tibor va ishlar talab etiladi.

Natijada, "Xabarchi"ning xavfsizligini ta'minlash sohasidagi ishlar, tarmoqning ishonchliligini oshirish, foydalanuvchilarning xavfsizlik madaniyatini yuksaltirish va milliy axborot tizimlarini mustahkamlashga xizmat qilmoqda. Kelajakda ham ushbu yo'nalishdagi ishlar davom ettirilishi, "Xabarchi"ni yanada xavfsiz va ishonchli platformaga aylantirishga yordam beradi. Tarmoqning rivojlanishi va xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha erishilgan natijalar, O'zbekistonning raqamli iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirish va jamiyatning axborot savodxonligini oshirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib qoladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Davlat xavfsizlik xizmati - Vikipediya¹
2. Prezident raisligida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Milliy xavfsizlik xizmatining kengaytirilgan hay'at yig'ilishi bo'lib o'tdi²
3. SQ-479-IV-coh 04.02.2022. Internet jahon axborot tarmog'ida yoshlar va voyaga yetmaganlar uchun milliy kontentni rivojlantirish, ularni milliy veb-resurslar va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishga jalb etish yuzasidan mutasaddi vazirlik va idoralarning amaliy ishlarida natijadorlik sezilmayapti³
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yil 14 martdagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Milliy xavfsizlik xizmati organlarini isloh qilish to'g'risida"gi PQ-3555-sonli qarori
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisining 2018 yil 29 martdagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Milliy xavfsizlik xizmati organlarining tarkibiy tuzilishini qayta ko'rib chiqish to'g'risida"gi Q-766-sonli qarori

15-16 YOSHDAGI O'G'IL BOLALARDA VOLEYBOL O'YININING UMUMIY VA MAXSUS JISMONIY SIFATLAR ORQALI O'YIN TEXNIKASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada 15-16 yoshli o'g'il bolalarda voleybol o'ynashda umumiy va maxsus jismoniy fazilatlarni oshirishga qaratilgan o'yin texnikasini rivojlantirishning kompleks metodologiyasi keltirilgan. Ko'nikmalarni egallashda ushbu rivojlanish bosqichining ahamiyatini e'tirof etgan holda, metodologiya voleybolning asosiy ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish va bir vaqtning o'zida optimal ishlash uchun zarur bo'lgan jismoniy xususiyatlarni yaxshilashga qaratilgan maqsadli o'quv dasturlarini birlashtiradi. Maqolada yosh sportchilarning fiziologik va psixologik xususiyatlariga moslashtirilgan yoshga mos tayyorgarlik metodologiyalarining ahamiyati ta'kidlangan. Ixtisoslashtirilgan mashqlar, mashqlar va mashg'ulotlar sxemalarini birlashtirgan holda, ushbu metodologiya yosh voleybolchilarda mahorat, jismoniy tayyorgarlik va umumiy ishlash potentsialini maksimal darajada oshiradigan yaxlit rivojlanish yondashuvini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Voleybol, O'yin texnikasi, Ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish, Jismoniy fazilatlar, Yosh sportchilar, Mashg'ulotlar metodikasi.

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF GAME TECHNIQUE THROUGH GENERAL AND SPECIAL PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF VOLLEYBALL GAME IN 15-16-YEAR-OLD BOYS

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Abstract: This article presents a comprehensive methodology for the development of game techniques aimed at improving general and special physical qualities in playing volleyball in 15-16-year-old boys. Recognizing the importance of this developmental stage in skill acquisition, the methodology combines targeted training programs aimed at improving the fundamental skills of volleyball while improving the physical characteristics necessary for optimal performance. The article emphasizes the importance of age-appropriate training methodologies adapted to the physiological and psychological characteristics of young athletes. Combining specialized drills, exercises and training schemes, this methodology aims to develop a holistic development approach that maximizes skill, fitness and overall performance potential in young volleyball players.

Key words: Volleyball, Game technique, Skill development, Physical qualities, Young athletes, Training methodology.

Kirish. 15-16 yoshli o'g'il bolalarning voleybol bo'yicha rivojlanish bosqichi mahoratni egallash va jismoniy tayyorgarlik uchun muhim davr hisoblanadi. Bu yoshda sportchilar o'rganish va rivojlanish uchun katta salohiyatga ega bo'lib, o'yin texnikasi va jismoniy xususiyatlarni yaxshilashga qaratilgan maqsadli mashg'ulotlar metodologiyasini amalga oshirish uchun qulay vaqt. Ushbu maqolada yosh voleybolchilarning o'ziga xos ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun mo'ljallangan, maydondagi ish faoliyatini optimallashtirish uchun umumiy va maxsus jismoniy fazilatlarni birlashtirishga e'tibor qaratiladigan metodologiya keltirilgan. Ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga tizimli va progressiv yondashuvni ta'kidlagan holda, ushbu metodologiya voleybolda kelajakdagi muvaffaqiyatlar uchun mustahkam poydevor yaratishga qaratilgan.

Baholash: Har bir o'yinchining hozirgi mahorat darajasini va jismoniy imkoniyatlarini baholash uchun keng qamrovli baholashlarni o'tkaziladi. O'yin texnikasi va jismoniy sifatlarini yaxshilash uchun kuchli, zaif tomonlarni va sohalarni aniqlanadi.

- to'p uzatish, zarba berish va blokirovka qilish kabi asosiy voleybol ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan tuzilgan trening mashg'ulotlarini o'tkaziladi.

Texnik mahorat va taktik tushunchani oshirish uchun yoshga mos mashqlar va mashqlardan foydalanish.

Jismoniy holat:

Umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini, jumladan, yurak-qon tomir chidamliligi, mushaklarning kuchi, chaqqonlik va moslashuvchanlikni yaxshilash uchun umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlik mashqlarini birlashtiriladi.

Voleybolga xos harakatlar va energiya tizimlariga qaratilgan sportga xos konditsioner mashqlarini qo'shiladi.

O'yinchilarni bosqichma-bosqich chaqirish va moslashishni rag'batlantirish uchun jismoniy tayyorgarlik mashqlarining intensivligi va murakkabligini asta-sekin oshirib boriladi.

Shaxsiy o'yinchilarning ehtiyojlariga moslashtirilgan o'yin texnikasi va jismoniy fazilatlarining o'ziga xos jihatlariga qaratilgan maxsus o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqish.

Chaqqonlikni, reaksiya vaqtini, vertikal sakrash balandligini va qo'l-ko'zni muvofiqlashtirishni yaxshilashga qaratilgan mashqlar va mashqlarni bajariladi, bularning barchasi voleybolda muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun zarurdir.

O'yinchilarga o'yinga o'xshash vaziyatlarni mashq qilish va bosim ostida ishlashni yaxshilash uchun o'yin sharoitlarini simulyatsiya qilish imkoniyatini taqdim etish kerak.

XULOSA

Ushbu maqolada keltirilgan metodologiya voleybol o'ynagan 15-16 yoshli o'g'il bolalarda umumiy va maxsus jismoniy fazilatlarni birlashtirish orqali o'yin texnikasini rivojlantirishga tizimli yondashuvni taklif qiladi. Maqsadli mahoratni rivojlantirishni har tomonlama jismoniy tayyorgarlik bilan uyg'unlashtirgan holda, ushbu metodologiya yosh sportchilarning salohiyatini maksimal darajada oshirishga, voleybol bo'yicha kelajakdagi muvaffaqiyatlarga zamin yaratishga qaratilgan. Bu o'yinchilarni rivojlantirishga yaxlit yondashuvni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi, yosh sportchilarning o'ziga xos ehtiyojlari va imkoniyatlarini inobatga olgan holda, yoshga mos mashg'ulotlar metodologiyasining muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Balyi, I. va Hamilton, A. (2004). Sportchining uzoq muddatli rivojlanishi: bolalik va o'smirlik davridagi mashg'ulotlar. Olimpiya murabbiyi, 16(1), 4-9.
2. Fleck, SJ, & Kraemer, WJ (2014). Qarshilik ko'rsatish bo'yicha o'quv dasturlarini loyihalash (4-nashr). Inson kinetikasi.
3. Platonov, V. N. (2015). Sportchilar va olimpiya sportlari tizimi Olimpiya sport turlari bo'yicha sportchilarni tayyorlash tizimi. SportAkademPress.
4. AQSH Voleybol. (2020). Voleybol konditsioneri. [<https://www.teamusa.org/usa-volleyball/athletes/indoors/volleyball>].
5. <https://www.teamusa.org/usa-volleyball/athletes/indoors/volleyball> conditioning.
6. Solijonovich, S. J., & Xasanov, A. T. (2023). Kasb-hunar maktabida voleybol seksiyasi ishini tashkillash samaradorligi. O'zbekistonda fanlararo.
8. Abduraxmonov, S. (2023). Gandbolchilarning sport tayyorgarligi tizimi. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(10), 195-197.
9. Mirzattoo o'g'li, A. D. (2024). Kroll usulida ko'krakda suzish. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(17), 400-402.
10. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda to'pni o'yinga kiritish texnikasi. IMRAS, 6(6), 366-373.
11. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda hujum qilish texnikasi. Научный Фокус, 1(7), 570-574.
12. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida voleybol seksiyasining maqsad va vazifalari. Pedagog, 7(2), 122-127.

13. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Professional ta'lim muassasalarida voleybol bo'yicha sport seksiyalarini tashkil etish metodikasini takomillashtirish. (Yosh voleybolchilarda jismoniy va maxsus ish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion metodlari asosida). Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(17), 63-66.
14. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Maktab va professional ta'lim tizimida voleybol seksiyasining maqsad va vazifalari. Pedagog, 7(2), 122-127.
15. Solijonovich, S. J. (2023). Zamonaviy voleybolda to'pni uzatish texnikasi. Pedagog, 6(11), 14-18.
16. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Voleybolda o'rgatish metodlarining umumiy asoslari. Sport va xorijiy tillar integratsiyasining amalga oshirish muammolari va yechimlari, 1(1), 206-209.
17. Solijonovich, S. J. (2024). Voleybolda hujum va himoya texnikasini egallash. sport va xorijiy tillar integratsiyasining amalga oshirish muammolari va yechimlari, 1(1), 203-205.

THE PROBLEM OF FORMATION OF THE CREATIVE ABILITY OF STUDENTS OF ARTISTIC POTTERY IN THE HIGHER PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article, creativity in the process of pottery training, development of creative competence of pedagogues, introduction to the processes of creating artworks, innovative activities of students, preparation of future potters in the higher education system, interactive education, innovative education and information- communication technologies, factors that develop students' creativity skills are described.*

Keywords. *Applied art, ceramic creativity, ceramic technology, artistic ceramics, European equivalents, Architectural art, ceramics, creativity, painting, skills, interactive methods, innovation, education*

ПРОБЛЕМА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ГОНЧАРНОГО ДЕЛА В ВЫСШЕМ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ.

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Аннотация. *В данной статье творчество в процессе обучения гончарному делу, развитие творческой компетентности педагогов, знакомство с процессами создания художественных произведений, инновационная деятельность студентов, подготовка будущих гончаров в системе высшего образования, интерактивное образование, инновационное образование и информационно-Описаны коммуникативные технологии, факторы, развивающие творческие способности студентов.*

Ключевые слова. *Прикладное искусство, керамическое творчество, керамическая технология, художественная керамика, европейские эквиваленты, Архитектурное искусство, керамика, творчество, живопись, навыки, интерактивные методы, инновации, образование.*

Introduction. Pottery, Pottery is a type of craft that makes various objects from clay (terracotta, earthenware, building materials). The main raw material in pottery is soil. The process of making different types of pottery from clays of different origin and composition. People have been engaged in pottery since the Neolithic period. Special clay products are made by hand, dried and heated in a fire. Pottery is one of the types of applied folk art, and it belongs to the field of crafts that makes various objects, dishes, building materials from clay. The main raw material in pottery is natural soil, and the longer the clay is baked, the better the quality of the pottery. The art of tiling, which is the decorative art of pottery, has developed widely in the architecture of Central Asia. The availability of clay used in pottery in all parts of the world ensured the widespread use of pottery in almost all nations. At first, women were engaged in pottery, and with the appearance of the pottery wheel, men were also involved in this work. Dishes were cooked in special ovens and steam ovens. Simple methods of pottery still exist among the peoples living in the mountainous regions of Asia. Excavated remains of Neolithic settlements show that during that period the vessels were made with pointed bottoms (vessels were pressed into the ground). In the Eneolithic period, the production of elegant pottery and the use of pottery in architecture flourished in the countries of the East, in Greece. As glazing techniques were discovered, the artistic value of pottery increased. From the 20s of the 20th century, attention was paid to the externalization of pottery. Experimental pottery was opened in Tashkent, pottery workshops were opened in Samarkand, educational production, art workshop was launched in Tashkent (1932), short-term courses were organized, potters were trained and their skills improved. Potters such as T. Miraliyev (Tashkent), R. Egamberdiyev, A. Hazratkulov (Shahrisabz), Muhammad Siddiq, Usman Umarov (Gijduvan) taught young people.

People's Artist of Uzbekistan Muhyiddin Rahimov has made a great contribution to the research and development of pottery and the preparation of potters from young people. Pottery is one of the oldest and most interesting types of folk art of Uzbekistan. There are many main schools and centers of pottery in our country. Rishton, Bukhara, Gurumsarai, Tashkent, Khorezm, Samarkand and Kashkadarya pottery schools can be counted. These pottery schools differ from each other in the way of making the products, patterns, colors and finish.

Literature analysis and methodologies. The Uzbek people are famous all over the world for their ancient and rich culture. Ancient monuments and the underground part of Uzbekistan are a huge historical museum. Every architectural

monument in Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, Khiva, Termiz and other cities is a great work, rare manuscripts, examples of folk art, testify to the high culture of the Uzbek people at that time. For example, buildings built by our ancestors, architectural decorations, their variety, geometric and plant-like patterns, composite images, all our monuments invite to enjoy and aesthetic education. Through them, our ancestors expressed their hopes and dreams to the people. Our cultural wealth acquired over the centuries, some types of folk art, their specific types, real Uzbek names, work technologies and the names of our masters who created them are slowly on the verge of being forgotten. Therefore, preserving, appreciating and using the historical monuments and other monuments of our applied art created as a result of the creative work of our people over the centuries is one of the most important tasks of the present era.

Students of the "Art Pottery" department should have the following knowledge.

- the methodology and principles of teaching pottery art in lyceums, schools and colleges:

- Content and purpose of the national personnel training program of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- use of didactic principles in teaching methodology of "art pottery".

Students should develop the following skills in this subject:

- organization of educational processes;

- problematic organization of the subject;

- best practices methodology;

- the methodology of teaching the art of "artistic pottery";

Discussion and results. Ceramic art, like other disciplines, has its own characteristics and terms. But this dictionary of art has not been created. Thousands of young people in Uzbekistan face certain difficulties in learning the secrets of artistic pottery. In the main areas of higher education reform, it is necessary to "develop a sense of beauty, form a healthy artistic taste, and develop the ability to correctly understand and appreciate works of art, beauty and wealth." " is called. Mother Nature." In fact, there are explanatory dictionaries that are currently in high demand. Students of Art Secrets encounter a lot of concepts and terms in the process of reading, it is difficult to find such terms and concepts in the relevant literature at any time. For example , in the interesting pamphlet "Sanatim-bakhtim" by the national artist of Uzbekistan Mahmud Usmanov, there are a number of motivational terms, namely: "hashti tufсор, sarnigon, tufсорi wing, crane wing, house decorator, hasti davra, chorsar, round star, shashdona, parrak, lola islami, bafta islami, free islami, turunj, bandi rumi, islami guldona, islami

madohil, lola hoshiya" and other terms are given, but the dictionary meaning of these terms can be found in the relevant books.

Some of the terms created during the creative activity of the Uzbek people are being forgotten, in the process of reading brochures, articles, documents and archive materials, there are many words in them, hundreds of our phrases, we are written differently. see used in meanings. Some research has been done to eliminate the diversity in such expressions. For example, when we asked students to answer questions with potters, they could not clearly state the dictionary meaning of many terms found in folk art. For example, among such terms: morpech, kundal, ruta, madokhil, minqar, Islamic duraftor, namoen, etc. This shows that the terms of pottery art have been studied very little on a scientific basis. First of all, it is advisable to open the column "Folk practical ornaments" in the newspapers and magazines of our republic and enrich your vocabulary with art, and secondly, to create a scientifically based explanatory dictionary of folk decorative arts. Genres called nature art, artistic pottery or aesthetic art all have their own characteristics. They are mainly based on the depiction of natural scenes, people or animals, and have characteristics that strive to create a sought-after feeling. Artistic pottery is based on the production of the best and aesthetic spectacles of people. Artistic pottery, which includes an international orientation, actively participates in the purpose of uniting humanity by making communication between people.

Summary. In short, artistic pottery is a masterpiece of folk decorative art that has been carefully preserved by our ancestors for centuries. These types of applied arts, preserved in history and to this day, will be more appreciated and respected in the future. After all, unique patterns carved, drawn, scratched, and painted are an expression of human perception and human feelings. Bamisoli is a song of life written in black clay. and the song of life rings from time to time. Our huge cultural wealth created over the centuries, in particular, the unique aspects of the widespread types of Uzbek national artistic pottery, schools, execution techniques, and the blessed names of the masters who created them, are on the verge of disappearing forever. . Therefore, it is important to preserve these unique art masterpieces and teach them to young people. Ceramic art is a culture that is acceptable to a wide range of people, combining several arts (pen, painting, music, dramatic arts, etc.) and connecting it with human spirit and spirituality. lays Achievements such as the initial reference to these art forms, the control of human activity, the principles of relevance of creativity, the power of human emotions, and the ability to be a unique child are important. Pottery is about gaining value, bringing out the best in people, encouraging creative behavior, bringing all the

looks and colors to life. The art of ceramic art is related to the formation of creative abilities of students. This art form is important for the development of culture, creativity and aesthetic skills. Art pottery helps us to express students' learning, creative thinking and personal historical information. In this article, the art of pottery is important for students, as it is necessary to develop their ways of self-expression and creative exploration, and to pass on folk crafts to the next generation.

References:

1. M.Rahimov. O'zbekiston badiiy keramikasi. T., 1961 y.
2. E.Xoxlova. Badiiy keramika. M., 1978 y.
3. V.Xaxlov. Badiiy keramika asoslari. S., 1988 y.
4. E.Sayko. Keramika ishlab chiqarish texnikasi va texnologiyasining tarixiy taraqqiyoti. M., 1982 y.
5. A.Turg'unov. O'zbek kulolchiligi san'atining hududiy xususiyatlari. T. 2001.
6. Рўзинов, Б. А., Нуриддинов, Б. Х., & Умаров, Х. Фарғона водийси амалий санъатининг таълим тарбиядаги ўрни.
7. Umarov, X. (2023). The role of the type of applied art in architectural monuments (on the example of the hojaamin grave complex). *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(3), 182-187.
8. Шарипжонов, М., & Икромова, М. Д. (2018). Tasviriy san'atda animalizm janri. *Научное знание современности*, (5), 94-96.
9. oglu Sharipjonov, M. S. Oliy pyedagogik ta'limda talabalarga muammoli mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish texnologiyalari.
10. Temirova, M. (2023). The ability of the teacher to apply the technologies of individual work when teaching students the lessons of skillful painting. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(3), 177-181.
11. Темирова, М. И. (2022). Изобразительное искусство и его содержательная сущность. *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches*, 1(2).
12. Temirova Muqaddas, & Turg'unboyeva Maftunaxon. (2023). Tasviriy san'at fanlarini maktablarda o'qitishning zamonaviy texnologiyalari. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10337479>
13. Temirova Muqaddas, & Nazarov Murodjon. (2023). Mahobatli rangtasvir kompozitsiyasining zamonaviy uslublari, shakllarini talabalariga o'qitishda yangicha yondashuv. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10322777>
14. Amanullaev, A. (2022). Specific factors of comprehensive study and analysis of the history and culture of the uzbek people. *Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(02), 1-4.
15. Amanullaev, A. A. (2022). Current issues in the training of future teachers of fine arts. *Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(03), 1-3.
16. Абдимуминова, Д. А., & Амануллаев, А. А. (2018). Использование традиций этики "устоз-шогирид"(мастер и ученик) на занятиях прикладного искусства. *NovaInfo. Ru*, 2(85), 203-206

PREGNANT WOMAN WITH DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITRE

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Annotation. *The influence of diffuse toxic goiter on the course and outcome of pregnancy was studied. 67 pregnant women with diffuse toxic goiter were examined. The comparison group consisted of 38 pregnant women without thyroid pathology. The examination included determination of free thyroxine, TSH, autoantibodies to the TSH receptor and thyroid peroxidase in the blood of pregnant women and umbilical cord blood, as well as ultrasound of the thyroid gland of newborns and the TSH/free ratio. T4. In women with unresolved thyrotoxicosis, pregnancy and childbirth were more often complicated by the threat of miscarriage, gestosis, chronic placental insufficiency, fetal malnutrition and hypoxia, and untimely rupture of amniotic fluid. The high frequency of subclinical hypothyroidism (more than 50%) in newborns is associated with the transplacental transfer of thyreostatic drugs. Subclinical hyperfunction of the thyroid gland in 17% of newborns should be associated with the transplacental transfer of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor from mother to fetus.*

Keywords: *pregnancy; diffuse toxic goiter; newborns; thyroid.*

БЕРЕМЕННАЯ ЖЕНЩИНА С ДИФFUЗНЫМ ТОКСИЧЕСКИМ ЗОБОМ

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Аннотация. Изучено влияние диффузного токсического зоба на течение и исход беременности. Обследовано 67 беременных с диффузным токсическим зобом. Группу сравнения составили 38 беременных без патологии щитовидной железы. Обследование включало определение свободного тироксина, ТТГ, аутоантител к рецептору ТТГ и тиреоидной пероксидазе в крови беременных и пуповинной крови, а также УЗИ щитовидной железы новорожденных и соотношения ТТГ/свободный. Т4. У женщин с неразрешенным тиреотоксикозом беременность и роды чаще осложнялись угрозой выкидыша, гестозами, хронической плацентарной недостаточностью, гипотрофией и гипоксией плода, преждевременным излитием околоплодных вод. Высокая частота субклинического гипотиреоза (более 50%) у новорожденных связана с трансплацентарным переносом тиреостатических препаратов. Субклиническая гиперфункция щитовидной железы у 17% новорожденных должна быть связана с трансплацентарной передачей аутоантител к рецептору ТТГ от матери к плоду.

Ключевые слова: беременность; диффузный токсический зоб; новорожденные; щитовидная железа.

Introduction. Diffuse toxic goiter (DTG) is an organ autoimmune disease, the pathogenesis of which is based on the production of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor, which do not block, but, on the contrary, stimulate the function of the thyroid gland. The frequency of detection of thyrotoxicosis during pregnancy varies widely - from 0.05 to 3% [1–5,7,9,10,14] and requires clarification, since the clinical picture of thyrotoxicosis can be caused by other pathological

conditions, for example, gestational thyrotoxicosis, destructive thyrotoxicosis in autoimmune thyroiditis, toxic nodular goiter, trophoblastic disease [1–5]. Untreated thyrotoxicosis has an adverse effect on the course of pregnancy (threat of miscarriage, gestosis), childbirth (premature rupture of amniotic fluid, rapid labor) [5–9], as well as on the condition of the fetus and newborn [6,7,9–11]: risk of congenital anomalies, intrauterine growth retardation, stillbirth, the formation of intrauterine and congenital thyrotoxicosis [3,5,8,9,11–13]. To eliminate thyrotoxicosis during pregnancy, thyreostatic drugs are used: derivatives of imidazole (merkazolyl - MKI) or thiouracil (propylthiouracil - PTU), however, these drugs carry the risk of hypothyroidism in the fetus and newborn. It is believed that PTU penetrates to a lesser extent through the placenta to the fetus and into the mammary epithelium due to greater binding to plasma proteins [5,9,10,11,14–21]. There are separate descriptions of fetal development disorders (scalp disorder, choanal atresia) while taking thyreostatic drugs [3,9,20], but no convincing data on the teratogenic effect of MKI and PTU have been obtained [11,20,21]. The influence of thyroid-stimulating autoantibodies to the TSH receptor, which also easily pass through the placenta from mother to fetus, can be the cause of intrauterine and congenital thyrotoxicosis in 2–3% of newborns from mothers with DTG [3,10]. Its actual frequency, including subclinical forms, is unknown, since most women with DTG during pregnancy receive thyreostatic drugs that penetrate the placental barrier. The purpose of the study was to study the effect of DTG on the course and outcome of pregnancy.

Materials and methods of research. 67 pregnant women with DTD were examined. The age of the patients ranged from 19 to 37 years and averaged 27.4 ± 0.5 years. The duration of the disease ranged from several weeks to 7 years. In 52 women, the diagnosis of thyrotoxicosis was established before pregnancy, in 36 women pregnancy occurred while taking thyrostatic drugs, in 25, in the period from the 6th to the 32nd week of pregnancy, there was a relapse of thyrotoxicosis after remission of thyrotoxicosis by the time of pregnancy after conservative therapy (from 1 year to 3 years). In 43 pregnant women, thyroid disease was combined with autoimmune thyroiditis. All women with DTG received thyreostatic drugs during pregnancy: 38 patients took MKI and 29 took PTU. The initial dose of MKI was 20 mg/day, the “maintenance” dose was 5–10 mg/day. The initial dose of PTU was 100–200 mg/day, the “maintenance” dose was 50 mg/day. The functional state of the thyroid gland of patients before and during the use of thyreostatic drugs was assessed by the content of free. T4, free T3 and TSH in the blood. The average delivery time was 38.9 ± 0.2 weeks. The comparison

group included 38 women without thyroid pathology. The age of the patients ranged from 18 to 34 years and averaged 27.2 ± 0.7 years. The average delivery time was 39.3 ± 0.1 weeks. 38 children were born from mothers in this group. The average body weight of newborns was 3431.8 ± 55.7 g, body length - 51.7 ± 0.2 cm. The content of free thyroxine (free T4), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and autoantibodies to thyroid peroxidase in the blood of patients and umbilical cord blood (Abs to TPO) were determined by the enzyme immunoassay using standard kits; antibodies to the TSH receptor were determined by the enzyme immunoassay using kits from DRG Diagnostics (Germany). To assess the functional state of the newborn's thyroid gland, the free level was determined. T4 and TSH in umbilical cord blood and the TSH/free ratio was calculated. T4, which was developed for the purpose of differential diagnosis of congenital subclinical hypothyroidism and physiological hyperthyroidism of newborns [23]. In both cases, there is an increase in the level of TSH in the blood, while free. T4 in subclinical hypothyroidism tends to decrease, and in neonatal hyperthyroidism it tends to increase. In healthy newborns, the TSH/free ratio is T4 fluctuates at $p = 0.001$ from 0.27 to 0.72. Values outside the specified limits indicate the presence of hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism in the newborn. In women without thyroid pathology, there was a significant decrease in free. T4 throughout pregnancy, which is associated with an increase in thyroxine-binding globulin in the blood. However, the TSH level did not change significantly during pregnancy. Ultrasonography of the newborn's thyroid gland was performed on days 4–7 of life using a multifrequency sensor (frequency 6.9 MHz) on a Voluson 730, Expert GE device. Measurement of the thyroid lobes was performed using longitudinal and transverse scanning. The volume of the thyroid gland was calculated using the formula J. Brunn [22]. The average size of the thyroid gland in newborns from mothers from the comparison group was 0.60 ± 0.01 cm³ ($p < 0.001$). The range of fluctuations of this indicator ($p = 0.001$) varied from 0.36 to 0.71 cm³. The results obtained were processed using the standard SPSS program (version 6.0) on a personal computer using the variation statistics method. The hypothesis of equality of two means was tested using Student's t-test. Differences between the compared values were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and its discussion. The frequency of complications of pregnancy and childbirth in the examined women is presented. In women with DTG and unresolved thyrotoxicosis, pregnancy was more often complicated by early toxicosis, threat of miscarriage, spontaneous miscarriages, chronic placental insufficiency, gestosis and fetal malnutrition. Against the background of

eliminated thyrotoxicosis, the frequency of these complications was significantly lower, but still exceeded these indicators in the comparison group. The most common complications of childbirth in women with DTG were premature birth, untimely rupture of amniotic fluid, and fetal hypoxia. The frequency of labor anomalies and operative delivery significantly exceeded these indicators in the comparison groups. The incidence of complications of pregnancy and childbirth was significantly lower in the group of pregnant women with DTG receiving thyrostatic therapy, compared with these indicators in pregnant women with DTG with unresolved thyrotoxicosis. The period of delivery in the group of women with DTG varied from 34 to 41 weeks and averaged $38.6 + 0.2$ weeks, which was noticeably different from the indicator ($39.3 + 0.2$ weeks) ($p < 0.05$) in the group comparisons. All women with DTG showed a decrease in the level of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor at the time of delivery. 68 living children (one twin) were born to mothers with DTD. Height and weight indicators and Apgar scores of newborns from mothers with DTD are presented. The average body weight of full-term newborns from mothers with DTD (3279.2 ± 55.8 g) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than in the comparison group (3480 ± 74.9 g). Functional parameters of the thyroid gland in newborns varied widely. According to the TSH/free ratio. T4, 36 newborns from mothers with DTG were diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism, 11 with subclinical hyperthyroidism, and in 21 newborns, indicators of the functional state of the thyroid gland did not go beyond physiological values. Hyperthyroidism in newborns of mothers with DTG can be associated with the transplacental transfer of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor, which is confirmed by a higher level of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor in newborns with subclinical hyperthyroidism. Clinically significant congenital thyrotoxicosis was diagnosed in only one newborn (TSH/free T4 ratio was 0.002). The level of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor in the umbilical cord blood of this child was 36.9 IU/L. In 36 of 68 newborns from mothers with DTG, subclinical hypothyroidism was detected (TSH/free T4 coefficient more than 0.72, average value - 1.1 ± 0.1). The average TSH level in the blood of newborns with subclinical hypothyroidism was significantly higher than this indicator in the blood of newborns from mothers without thyroid pathology, while the content of free. T4 did not differ in the compared groups. Hypofunction of the thyroid gland was detected mainly in newborns from mothers who took thyreostatic drugs in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy. Subclinical hypothyroidism was diagnosed in 20 of 39 newborns ($51.3 \pm 8.0\%$) whose mothers received MCI and in 16 of 29 newborns ($55.2 \pm 9.2\%$) whose mothers received PTU during

pregnancy. The results obtained confirm the data on the possibility of transplacental transfer of PTU [24].

Conclusions

1. With diffuse toxic goiter, pregnancy is often complicated by gestosis, chronic placental insufficiency, fetal malnutrition, untimely rupture of amniotic fluid, and premature birth.

2. The volume of the thyroid gland in newborns from mothers with thyroid disease significantly exceeds the volume of the thyroid gland in newborns from mothers without thyroid pathology, which is likely due to the transplacental transfer of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor from mother to fetus.

3. In 17% of newborns from mothers with DTG, hyperfunction of the thyroid gland is detected, caused by the transplacental transfer from mother to fetus of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor. Explicit thyrotoxicosis is relatively rare among the total number of children from mothers with thyrotoxicosis (1.4%).

4. In 52% of newborns from mothers with DTG, subclinical hypothyroidism is detected (average TSH - 13.6 ± 0.9 mIU/l, average free T4 - 12.6 ± 0.4 pmol/l, average TSH/free coefficient T4 1.1 ± 0.1), probably due to the transplacental transfer of thyreostatic drugs, derivatives of both imidazole and thiouracil.

5. In newborns from mothers with DTG who received thyreostatic therapy throughout pregnancy, hypofunction of the thyroid gland (TSH/free T4 coefficient 1.34 ± 0.2) occurs significantly ($p < 0.05$) more often than among newborns mothers whose thyreostatic therapy was discontinued at an earlier stage (before the third trimester) (average TSH/free T4 ratio 0.82 ± 0.1).

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of*

- biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
 7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондигов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
 8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
 9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
 10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет И COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*.2022;2(13):190-204.
 11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
 12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
 13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
 14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
 15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensialdiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash.*Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
 16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.I. 2021;2(3):37-41.
 17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection.*Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
 18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188

19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinova MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 Special):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinova XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors Determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *Journal NX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Hakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 special):259-264.

34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o`zgarishlar.so `ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Худайбердиева О. К. Инновации и научный прогресс–фундамент устойчивого развития национальной экономики //ББК 65.0501 А 43. – 2022. – С. 331.
45. Qurbonovna, Xudoyberdiyeva Oysha. "Turizmni rivojlantirishda milliy madaniyatning o'rni." *Научный Фокус 1.8 (2023)*: 1024-1027.
46. Худайбердиева О. К. Экономические реформы сферы услуг в узбекистане //Актуальные проблемы развития национальной и региональной экономики. – 2021. – С. 216-220.
47. Ochilov S. B., Tagaev A. N., Khudayberdieva O. K. Other ways to build correlation models //International Journal of Human Computing Studies. – 1935. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 1-5.
48. Ochilov S. B., Khasanova G. D., Khudayberdieva O. K. Method for constructing correlation dependences for functions of many variables used finite differences //The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 46-52.
49. Ochilov S. B. O. S. B., Khudayberdieva O. K., Mehriniso K. Differential method for forecasting labor resources based on correlation models //The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 04. – С. 21-27.

HYPOTHYROIDISM IS A PROBLEM OF THE XXI ERA

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Annotation. *The article reflects issues of epidemiology, classification, and clinical picture of hypothyroidism. The incidence of hypothyroidism increases significantly with age. The most common form is primary hypothyroidism, caused by a pathological process in the thyroid gland itself. Secondary or tertiary hypothyroidism is caused by insufficient secretion of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), or thyrotropin-releasing hormone. The article discusses the main causes of primary and secondary hypothyroidism. The most common cause of primary hypothyroidism is autoimmune thyroiditis, which can develop either separately or simultaneously with other autoimmune diseases, as part of polyglandular syndrome. Changes in thyroid status as a consequence of adverse side reactions when using a number of drugs deserve special attention. Questions have been raised about the mechanisms of development of thyroid failure as a result of adverse side reactions when using a number of drugs (lithium preparations, iodine-containing compounds, tyrosine kinase inhibitors, etc.).*

Keywords: *hypothyroidism, autoimmune thyroiditis, TSH, thyroid hormones, drug-induced hypothyroidism, replacement therapy, levothyroxine.*

ГИПОТИРЕОЗ – ПРОБЛЕМА XXI ЭПОХИ

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Аннотация. В статье отражены вопросы эпидемиологии, классификации и клиники гипотиреоза. Заболеваемость гипотиреозом значительно увеличивается с возрастом. Наиболее распространенной формой является первичный гипотиреоз, вызванный патологическим процессом в самой щитовидной железе. Вторичный или третичный гипотиреоз вызван недостаточной секрецией тиреотропного гормона (ТТГ) или тиреотропин-рилизинг-гормона. В статье рассмотрены основные причины первичного и вторичного гипотиреоза. Наиболее частой причиной первичного гипотиреоза является аутоиммунный тиреоидит, который может развиваться как отдельно, так и одновременно с другими аутоиммунными заболеваниями, в рамках полигландулярного синдрома. Особого внимания заслуживают изменения тиреоидного статуса как следствие побочных реакций при применении ряда препаратов. Поднимаются вопросы о механизмах развития тиреоидной недостаточности в результате побочных реакций при применении ряда лекарственных средств (препаратов лития, йодсодержащих соединений, ингибиторов тирозинкиназ и др.).

Ключевые слова: гипотиреоз, аутоиммунный тиреоидит, ТТГ, гормоны щитовидной железы, лекарственный гипотиреоз, заместительная терапия, левотироксин

Introduction. Hypothyroidism is one of the most common diseases of the endocrine system. Despite the well-studied etiology, pathogenesis and simple diagnosis, in some cases the disease remains unrecognized for a long time, which is due to the slow increase in thyroid insufficiency and, accordingly, the severity of the clinical picture. The biological action of thyroid hormones is very diverse: by activating the transcription of numerous genes, they participate in the regulation of basic physiological processes in the body, so their deficiency can manifest itself in a wide variety of clinical manifestations and symptoms and imitate diseases of almost all body systems. Interestingly, hypothyroidism is the first endocrine disease for which replacement therapy was used. The first description of hypothyroidism was made by W. Gall in 1873 [1]. Later, V. Ordom proposed the term “myxedema” (myxa - mucus, oidema - swelling, edema; Greek) - mucous swelling of the skin and subcutaneous tissue (Fig. 1). Nowadays, this term is used to characterize the most severe forms of thyroid insufficiency. This is one of the common diseases of the thyroid gland: the prevalence, according to various studies, ranges from 0.2 to 3.7% and depends on age, gender, and level of iodine consumption [2, 3]. The annual incidence of primary hypothyroidism is 3.5 per 1 thousand women and 0.6 per 1 thousand men. The incidence of hypothyroidism increases significantly with age. In the age population over 60 years, taking into account subclinical forms, it can reach 6–12% of cases, more often in women [4, 5]. The Framingham Study found hypothyroidism (TSH > 10 mU/L) in 5.9% of women and 2.4% of men over 60 years of age [6]. Primary hypothyroidism is much more common (95%), caused by a pathological process in the thyroid gland (TG) itself [4, 7]. Thyroid pathology can be detected from birth (congenital hypothyroidism) in the presence of thyroid embryopathy (agenesis, hypogenesis, dystopia) or congenital failure of enzymatic systems involved in the biosynthesis of thyroid hormones. The cause of congenital hypothyroidism may be gene mutations that lead to disturbances in the anlage, migration, and differentiation of the thyroid gland; defects in the biosynthesis of thyroid hormones (TTF1, TTF2, PAX-8, NIS, TPO, iodotyrosine deiodinase gene) [8]. In adults, the most common cause of primary hypothyroidism is autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT), the prevalence of which, according to various studies, despite some differences in gender, age, race and iodine intake, reaches about 5% among the population [7, 9, 10]. The natural pattern of development of AIT is a gradual decrease in thyroid function to overt hypothyroidism with a progression rate of about 2–4% per year [9]. It should be remembered that AIT can develop either separately or simultaneously with other autoimmune diseases,

for example, as part of polyglandular syndrome [10]. Other causes of hypothyroidism due to destruction of the thyroid gland include thyroidectomy, radioactive iodine therapy, external irradiation during radiation therapy of malignant neoplasms outside the thyroid gland. It is always necessary to remember that the persistent nature of hypothyroidism can be judged no earlier than after 6 months. after similar interventions [11–13]. After thyroidectomy or a significant part of it, the operated patient (ultimate subtotal resection) develops postoperative hypothyroidism, the likelihood of which is determined by the purpose and scope of the operation. After hemithyroidectomy, the incidence of hypothyroidism ranges from 5 to 40% and depends on the period of time that has passed since surgery. It has been shown that in 67–90% of patients, thyroid insufficiency is observed after 12 months. after surgery [11, 12]. Disorders of thyroid function in response to exposure to external and internal ionizing radiation, in terms of the mechanism of their development and clinical manifestations, differ from thyroid hypofunction of other origins. In particular, post-radiation hypothyroidism can develop in the long term after irradiation (6–7 years), which requires an appropriate assessment of thyroid function over time. In these cases, hypothyroidism can occur with significantly lower doses of thyroid radiation (9.0–15.0 Gy) than with the use of radioactive iodine for therapeutic purposes (35–40 Gy) [13].

Clinical picture and diagnostics. A patient with hypothyroidism can be encountered in the practice of a doctor of any profile. Moreover, the diagnosis is often made late, even with severe symptoms; Most researchers point to the time frame for establishing the correct diagnosis from several months to 2–3 years or more from the onset of the disease and, accordingly, a later start of replacement therapy [27–29]. Undiagnosed hypothyroidism is a risk factor for the progression of existing cardiovascular diseases due to indirect hyperhomocysteinemia, dyslipidemia and endothelial dysfunction [30–32]. In this regard, it is extremely necessary to know the principles of diagnosis and treatment methods for the disease. The variety of clinical manifestations of hypothyroidism is due to a decrease in the concentration of thyroid hormones, as a result of which the main metabolic reactions are inhibited and, most importantly, oxidative processes, basal metabolism, thermogenesis slow down, the activity of various enzyme systems and general blood flow decreases. The accumulation of protein and fluid in tissues and serous cavities is caused by increased extravasation of plasma proteins and insufficient lymphatic drainage [2, 30, 33]. The main pathogenetic mechanism of symptoms of thyroid insufficiency is the development of so-called mucinous (mucosal) edema, which is caused by decreased clearance, increased

synthesis and accumulation of hydrophilic glycosaminoglycans in the intercellular substance of the dermis and other tissues [27, 29, 33].

Treatment of hypothyroidism. Currently, synthetic analogues of thyroid hormones are used to treat hypothyroidism. Since the discovery and synthesis of the physiological L-form of thyroxine, drugs of this class have fully confirmed their priority in the treatment of hypothyroidism. Today, levothyroxine (LT4) is one of the 10 most prescribed drugs in the world [20, 52]. Since the main amount of triiodothyronine (T3) is formed in the periphery from T4 by deiodination, due to its depot properties and conversion according to individual needs into the metabolically more active triiodothyronine, synthetic levothyroxine has become the drug of choice [2, 53]. Clinically, the depot effect is extremely important: with a single dose of L-Thyroxine, due to deiodination, a constant T3 concentration is maintained throughout the day, which allows you to take the drug once a day, avoiding sharp peaks in triiodothyronine activity. In contrast, taking T3 drugs is accompanied by the achievement of a peak non-physiological level, followed by a fairly rapid decrease [7, 54, 55]. The goal of replacement therapy for primary hypothyroidism is to achieve and maintain normal serum TSH concentrations (blood sampling is carried out before taking the daily dose of L-T4) [53, 56]. The initial dose of L-Thyroxine and the time to reach the full replacement dose are determined individually, taking into account the patient's age, body weight, comorbidities, especially cardiovascular diseases [20, 52, 56]. Eating reduces the absorption of levothyroxine, so the entire individually selected dose is taken in the morning on an empty stomach, optimally 60 minutes before meals. The absorption of levothyroxine may be reduced in case of simultaneous use of aluminum-containing antacids (antacids, sucralfate), iron-containing drugs and calcium-containing drugs. Therefore, L-Thyroxine should be taken at least 2 hours before taking these medications [56, 57]. When taken orally, about 70–80% of the dose of L-Thyroxine taken is absorbed (Table 3), if it is a sodium salt; absorption is reduced when using pure T4, after meals (1–20%) or very large doses. The peak absorption of the drug occurs between 30 and 60 minutes after administration; it is completely absorbed after 90 minutes. 24–48 hours after the start of treatment with L-Thyroxine, the metabolic effect becomes noticeable, and after 14 days the clinical symptoms of hypothyroidism become less clear [52, 54]. L-Thyroxine therapy can be initiated immediately with a full replacement dose or with a minimum dose with a gradual increase in dose until the target TSH level in the blood is achieved. Traditionally, in young patients without cardiovascular pathology, replacement therapy is initiated with a full dose of L-Thyroxine (without preliminary titration) at the rate of 1.6–1.8 mcg per 1 kg of body weight per day (on average 75–112 mcg/day for women, 125–200 mcg/day for men).

Some patients with hypothyroidism and obesity may require 20% higher doses. In obese patients, it is better to calculate the dose based on the ideal weight, which allows achieving a therapeutic effect and compensating for hypothyroidism [53, 55]. Full replacement therapy for hypothyroidism is prescribed on the first day after thyroidectomy when hypothyroidism is diagnosed during pregnancy [54, 56].

Conclusion. To summarize, it should be noted that, despite the well-known clinical picture, the diagnosis of hypothyroidism can cause significant difficulties, since the deficiency of thyroid hormones is masked by various diseases. The decisive condition for successful medical care for patients with hypothyroidism is the timely administration of replacement therapy, which is lifelong in most patients. Taking into account individual sensitivity, the presence of comorbid pathology of internal organs, and drug interactions makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of treatment of hypothyroidism, minimize possible side effects and improve patient compliance.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабилова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет и COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржоновна КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensialdiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidsis. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of*

- Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal.* 2022;3(02):73-76.
doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):381-386.
 24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования.* 2023;4(1):131-133.
 25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 special):269-274.
 26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovna XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *PEDAGOG.* 2022;5(5):341-345.
 27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health.* 2022;8:67-72.
 28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
 29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(11).
 30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7820412
 31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR).* 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
 32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX.* Published online 2020:460-461.
 33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 Special):259-264.
 34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149).* 2023;1(9):121-123.
 35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
 36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(12):107-117.
 37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud.* 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. *I.* Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149).* 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o`zgarishlar.so`ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Pretibial myxedema: pathogenetic features and clinical aspects. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):695-702.
45. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilanbirgalikdakechishxususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(2):516-519.
46. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.* 2023;34:78-81.
47. .Худайбердиева О. Формирование цифровой экономики в Узбекистане //in Library. – 2021. – Т. 21. – №. 4. – С. 431-433.
48. Daminov AT, Sa`dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):139-142.
- 49.Худайбердиева О. К. Тенденции стремительного развития сферы услуг в узбекистане // Инновационное развитие: потенциал науки, бизнеса, образования. – 2021. – С. 102-113.
- 50.Очилов СБОСБ, Худайбердиева О.К., Мехринисо К. Дифференциальный метод прогнозирования трудовых ресурсов на основе корреляционных моделей //Американский журнал социальных наук и инноваций в образовании. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 04. – С. 21-27.
- 51.Худайбердиева О., Баратович Ш., Хусенова М. Дифференциальный метод прогнозирования трудовых ресурсов на основе корреляционных моделей //in Library. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 21-27.
- 52.Курбановна, Худайбердиева Айша и Убайтова Мохитабон. «Современные кластеры в национальной экономике являются эффективным средством социально-экономического развития». *Новости образования: исследование XXI века* 1.11 (2023): 177-185.

MODERN ENDOCRINE-ONCOLOGY AND RADIOTHERANOSTICS

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Annotation. Radiotheranostics is radionuclide therapy based on the results of molecular imaging with various radiopharmaceuticals, allowing in vivo visualization (using single photon emission tomography (SPECT) and/or positron emission tomography (PET)), and then systemically and selectively influencing the pathological metabolic processes caused by pathological process. In recent years, thanks to advances in the development of nuclear medicine (an increase in the number of cyclotrons, SPECT/CT and PET/CT in medical institutions) and, above all, radiopharmaceuticals, radiotheranostics is developing very rapidly in the world. The emergence of new radioligands based on ^{177}Lu , ^{131}I , ^{225}Ac and other radioactive isotopes in the world has initiated a large number of clinical studies of radioligand therapy for neuroendocrine and chromaffin tumors, prostate cancer, etc. Radiotheranostics as a new and very promising area of nuclear medicine is perfectly integrated into modern diagnostic algorithms in the field of endocrinology and oncology. Intraoperative radionavigation methods can improve the efficiency and safety of surgical methods, external beam radiation therapy, and brachytherapy. In my opinion, the future of personalized medicine will largely be determined by the integration of radiotheranostics, multimodal imaging, intraoperative navigation and existing/new diagnostic and treatment methods in combination with applied genomic and post-genomic technologies.

Keywords: radiotheranostics; PAT; SPECT; endocrinology; oncology.

СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ЭНДОКРИНООНКОЛОГИЯ И РАДИОТЕРАНОСТИКА

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Аннотация. Радиотерапевтика — радионуклидная терапия, основанная на результатах молекулярной визуализации с использованием различных радиофармпрепаратов, позволяющая *in vivo* визуализировать (с помощью однофотонной эмиссионной томографии (ОФЭКТ) и/или позитронно-эмиссионной томографии (ПЭТ)), а затем системно и избирательно воздействовать на вызванные патологические метаболические процессы. патологическим процессом. В последние годы благодаря успехам в развитии ядерной медицины (увеличение количества циклотронов, ОФЭКТ/КТ и ПЭТ/КТ в медицинских учреждениях) и, прежде всего, радиофармпрепаратов, в мире очень быстро развивается радиотерапевтика. Появление в мире новых радиолигандов на основе ^{177}Lu , ^{131}I , ^{225}Ac и других радиоактивных изотопов инициировало большое количество клинических исследований радиолигандной терапии нейроэндокринных и хромаффинных опухолей, рака предстательной железы и др. Радиотерапевтика как новое и весьма перспективное направление ядерная медицина прекрасно интегрирована в современные диагностические алгоритмы в области эндокринологии и онкологии. Интраоперационные радионавигационные методы позволяют повысить эффективность и безопасность хирургических методов, дистанционной лучевой терапии и брахитерапии. На мой взгляд, будущее персонализированной медицины во многом будет определяться интеграцией радиотерапевтики, мультимодальной визуализации, интраоперационной навигации и существующих/новых методов диагностики и лечения в сочетании с прикладными геномными и постгеномными технологиями.

Ключевые слова: радиотерапевтика; ПАТ; ОФЭКТ; эндокринология; онкология.

Introduction. Radioisotope (molecular) imaging of thyroid pathology in the 1940s. laid the foundation and determined the vector of development of nuclear medicine throughout the world. It was endocrinologists who were the first to use radioactive iodine to treat thyrotoxicosis and thyroid cancer, laying the foundation for radiotheranostics as such. The term “theranostics” refers to diagnostic-based therapy. From this point of view, probably, any therapy can be considered theranostics, because no therapy, in fact, can do without diagnostics. The fundamental nuance of radiotheranostics is that radioisotope imaging allows, using single photon emission tomography (SPECT) and/or positron emission tomography (PET) methods of the whole body, to detect in vivo the focus(s) of the disease, using hybrid methods PET/CT, PET/MRI , SPECT/CT to establish their anatomical localization and metabolic features, and using object (voxel) dosimetry methods to assess the dynamics of accumulation/removal of a diagnostic radiopharmaceutical (RP), which will ultimately make it possible to carry out systemic radionuclide therapy with the expectation that tumor foci will selectively accumulate and will retain the therapeutic radiopharmaceutical, just as they did with the diagnostic one. Over the past seven decades, the list of diagnostic and therapeutic radioisotopes and the “smart” ligands labeled with them (metabolites, antigens, antibodies) for anatomical and metabolic imaging and subsequent precision radionuclide therapy of not only endocrine and oncoendocrine diseases, but also other diseases (oncology, cardiology, neurology).

Molecular visualization of various metabolism disorders. PET allows in vivo study of various metabolic disorders using targeted chemical compounds labeled with positron-emitting radioisotopes. The development of a research method consists of selecting a molecule of interest (substrate or analogue) and an effective method for labeling it with atoms ^{11}C , ^{18}F or others. A molecular substrate labeled with a radioisotope undergoes an enzyme-mediated metabolic transformation in the body with subsequent accumulation in tissues, which can be assessed over time and quantitatively (standardized uptake rate, SUV) using PET. Since the uptake of a targeted molecular substrate by cells is mediated by specific enzymes (such as chemokinasases, thymidine kinases, etc.), the accumulation of radiolabels in tissues reflects the degree of enzymatic expression in it.

Pet imaging of glucose metabolism. The most important molecule for providing cells with energy for many biochemical reactions is adenosine triphosphate (ATP), which is produced in mitochondria due to glucose metabolism through oxidative phosphorylation to provide energy for cellular life

processes. Brain cells work exclusively on the energy of ATP breakdown, while the metabolism of the myocardium and adipose tissue is the main source of ATP production. Increased glucose metabolism is found in tumor cells, and it is based on aerobic glycolysis, or the phenomenon of the so-called “Warburg effect”, in which intensive glucose metabolism is maintained even under hypoxic conditions. Glucose is mainly transported into the cell by diffusion through specific transporters in the cell membrane, and in tumor cells, mainly through the GLUT-1 transporter. In the cytosol, glucose is converted by phosphorylation with the enzyme chemokinase into glucose-6-phosphate, which is subsequently metabolized into carbon dioxide and water. It has been shown that the hydroxyl group on the second carbon atom is not required for phosphorylation by chemokinase. Deoxyglucose enters the cell and is converted into deoxyglucose-6-phosphate, but does not undergo further catabolism, accumulating in the cell. For PET/CT, a 2-deoxy-2-fluoro-deoxyglucose (FDG) molecule is used as a radiopharmaceutical, in which the hydrogen atom in the second position is replaced by ^{18}F for molecular imaging of glucose metabolism. Moreover, the bond between carbon and fluorine atoms is even more stable than the bond between carbon and hydrogen, and the chemicals are not recognized by chemokinase. As a result, in addition to glucose, FDG-6-phosphate, introduced as a radiopharmaceutical, accumulates in the cells. In tumor cells, increased glycolysis and high FDG uptake are also associated with increased activity of the aforementioned glucose transporter GLUT-1 (insulin-dependent) and intracellular chemokinase expression.

Pet imaging of bone metabolism. Due to its high affinity for calcium, sodium ^{18}F -fluoride is ideal for assessing bone metabolism. Sodium ^{18}F fluoride has demonstrated high bone uptake with good clearance into the bloodstream, leading to improved contrast in PET bone imaging (increased bone-to-background ratio). PET with ^{18}F -sodium fluoride is widely used to assess bone metabolism in oncoendocrinology for thyroid cancer, parathyroid tumors, osteolytic syndrome due to fibroblast growth factor FR23 neoplasia, orphan endocrinopathies and other endocrine diseases complicated by osteopathies. This method successfully complements osteoscintigraphy (SPECT), illustrating the activity of osteoblasts, allowing molecular visualization of osteolytic processes in bone tissue.

Conclusion. The most distinctive feature of molecular imaging and radiotheranostics is the ability to see a pathological process in vivo and assess its metabolism, potential threat to the health and life of the patient, thoughtfully

select management tactics, promptly adjust during treatment, assessing its effectiveness. At the same time, the forecast of effectiveness and potential toxicity can be assessed already at the diagnostic stage (SPECT/CT, PET/CT), and the management of these parameters is impossible without the development and implementation of individual dosimetric and genetic (radiogenomic) and metabolomic (biomarkers) studies. Thus, establishing a hereditary predisposition to the development of a disease makes it possible to predict the risk of its development throughout life, and biomarkers and imaging methods allow us to detect the disease at an early stage and establish its localization/stage, and promptly perform adequate treatment.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбилов АН угли, Сабирава ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод при резус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиеров ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. САХАРНЫЙ ДИАБЕТ И COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.

11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *Miasto Przyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminnov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmun tireoidit bilan kasallangan bemorlardagi funksional buzilishlarning differensial diagnostikasida qalqonsimon bez zichligini aniqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2. *I*. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidsis. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.

24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Худайбердиева О. К. Инновации и научный прогресс–фундамент устойчивого развития национальной экономики //ББК 65.0501 А 43. – 2022. – С. 331.
34. Qurbonovna, Xudoyberdiyeva Oysha. "Turizmni rivojlantirishda milliy madaniyatning o'rni." *Научный Фокус 1.8 (2023): 1024-1027.*
35. Худайбердиева О. К. Экономические реформы сферы услуг в узбекистане //Актуальные проблемы развития национальной и региональной экономики. – 2021. – С. 216-220.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).

41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. *I*. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o`zgarishlar. *so`ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Ochilov S. B., Tagaev A. N., Khudayberdieva O. K. Other ways to build correlation models //International Journal of Human Computing Studies. – 1935. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 1-5.
45. Ochilov S. B., Khasanova G. D., Khudayberdieva O. K. Method for constructing correlation dependences for functions of many variables used finite differences //The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 46-52.
46. Худайбердиева О. Формирование цифровой экономики в Узбекистане //in Library. – 2021. – Т. 21. – №. 4. – С. 431-433

MEN AND HYPERANDROGENIA

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Annotation. *The term “hyperandrogenism” refers to excessive synthesis of androgenic hormones [1]. Although this condition can develop in both sexes, the concept is currently used primarily in relation to women. Today, the problem of hyperandrogenism in women is a widely studied and discussed issue, addressed at every reproductive health conference, while in relation to men this issue is practically not addressed. If we consider hyperandrogenism as an independent nosological unit, then we can conditionally distinguish physiological hyperandrogenism - caused by overproduction of testosterone and/or dihydrotestosterone (DHT) with normal levels of luteinizing hormone (LH) and pathological - accompanied by suppression of LH caused by serious concomitant somatic pathology of the adrenal glands, testicles or taking drugs with an androgenic effect, anabolic steroids [2]. A separate type of hyperandrogenism is an increase in androgens in men with androgen-producing tumors of the testicles or adrenal glands [3, 4]. Our study characterized variants of physiological hyperandrogenism in men.*

Keywords: *androgens, LH, DHT, testosterone, acne*

МУЖЧИНЫ И ГИПЕРАНДРОГЕНИЯ

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Аннотация. Термин «гиперандрогения» относится к избыточному синтезу андрогенных гормонов [1]. Хотя это состояние может развиваться у представителей обоих полов, в настоящее время это понятие используется преимущественно по отношению к женщинам. Сегодня проблема гиперандрогении у женщин является широко изучаемой и обсуждаемой проблемой, рассматриваемой на каждой конференции по репродуктивному здоровью, в то время как в отношении мужчин этот вопрос практически не рассматривается. Если рассматривать гиперандрогению как самостоятельную нозологическую единицу, то условно можно выделить гиперандрогению физиологическую - вызванную гиперпродукцией тестостерона и/или дигидротестостерона (ДГТ) при нормальном уровне лютеинизирующего гормона (ЛГ) и патологическую - сопровождающуюся подавлением ЛГ, вызванную тяжелыми заболеваниями. сопутствующая соматическая патология надпочечников, яичек или прием препаратов с андрогенным действием, анаболических стероидов [2]. Отдельным видом гиперандрогении является повышение уровня андрогенов у мужчин с андрогенпродуцирующими опухолями яичек или надпочечников [3, 4]. В нашем исследовании охарактеризованы варианты физиологической гиперандрогении у мужчин.

Ключевые слова: андрогены, ЛГ, ДГТ, тестостерон, акне.

Purpose of the study. To characterize the variants of physiological hyperandrogenism in men.

Materials and methods. Place and time of the study. Samarkand branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Endocrinology. The study was carried out between September 2021 and January 2023.

Populations studied. The formation of groups was carried out from patients who sought medical help at the SFRSNPTSE. Inclusion criteria were male gender; age over 18 years; elevated levels of total testosterone and/or DHT; normal LH level. Non-inclusion criteria were neoplasms of the hypothalamic-pituitary region, testicles, and adrenal glands; congenital dysfunction of the adrenal cortex; use of any drugs from the groups of antiestrogens, estrogens, gestagens, aromatase inhibitors, antiandrogens, gonadotropins, anabolic steroids, steroidogenesis inhibitors; alcoholism/drug addiction; diabetes mellitus types 1 and 2; hypercortisolism syndrome. Exclusion criteria were not provided. A total of 100 patients were included in the study, age 26 (minimum 18; maximum 58) years.

Method of forming a sample from the population being studied. The sample was formed using a continuous method.

Study design. A continuous, cross-sectional study of men with elevated levels of total testosterone and/or DHT.

Methods. During the study, the volume and structure of the prostate, the volume of the testicles were assessed using ultrasound using the Aplio 500 device No. 416508; the levels of LH (norm 2.5–11.0 U/l), total testosterone (norm 12.0–30.0 nmol/l), sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG) (norm 12–65 nmol/l) were determined; DHT (norm 250–990 pg/ml) on a Vitros ECi automatic analyzer (Johnson and Johnson (UK)) using the enhanced chemiluminescence method. The level of free testosterone was determined by the calculation method according to Vermeullen (norm 243–900 pmol/l) [5]. Analysis of the hormonal status of patients with hyperandrogenism made it possible to form 4 groups of patients based on laboratory characteristics.

1. Patients with elevated levels of total testosterone and SHBG (n=12).
2. Patients with elevated total testosterone levels and normal SHBG levels (n=15).

3. Patients with elevated levels of total testosterone, DHT with normal levels of SHBG (n=11).

4. Patients with elevated DHT levels with normal levels of total testosterone and SHBG (n=62).

Statistical analysis. Principles for calculating sample size Pilot study. The sample size was not previously calculated.

Methods of statistical data analysis. The obtained data were processed using the statistical software package STATISTICA 13.0 (StatSoft

Inc., USA) [6]. Differences between groups were determined using the Mann–Whitney U test for quantitative characteristics and Fisher's exact test for qualitative ones. Differences between groups were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. When comparing the groups, statistically significant differences were revealed in a number of indicators. The first group of patients was statistically significantly different from the other groups of patients in that they were older; these patients were also characterized by the presence of excess mass. The prostate volume of men in this group was statistically significantly higher than that of men in other groups. In addition, for this group of patients, despite the high level of total testosterone (the level of free testosterone was statistically significantly lower compared to that in patients of the 2nd and 3rd groups, but higher than in men of the 4th group), there was no Acne complaints are typical. Alopecia was also rare. On the contrary, patients of group 2 complained of acne, but the prevalence of this symptom even in this group was statistically significantly lower than in patients of group 3. At the same time, the incidence of alopecia was significantly lower than in patients of both groups 3 and 4. Patients with elevated levels of total testosterone and DHT (group 3) had the most striking clinical manifestations of hyperandrogenism. All patients from this group complained of acne, as well as increased hair loss on the head. Alopecia was also typical for patients in group 4. Complaints about the presence of acne were present, but their frequency differed statistically significantly compared to group 1, increasing, and compared to other groups, decreasing. Men in group 4 were characterized by statistically significantly lower levels of free testosterone compared to patients in other groups.

Discussion Representativeness of samples. It is not possible to assess the representativeness of the sample in relation to the general population, since the selection of the sample was carried out using a continuous method from patients observed only in the federal research center.

Comparison with other publications. In clinical practice, hyperandrogenism can cause the development of a number of diseases [7]. Increased levels of testosterone, DHT, or genetically determined sensitivity of androgen receptors can lead to the development of a disease such as androgenetic

alopecia [8]. In our study, it was identified in men with elevated DHT levels, regardless of testosterone levels, which is consistent with the modern concept of the influence of elevated DHT levels on the development of androgenetic alopecia [9]. Thus, in a study by H. Schweikert et al. It has been demonstrated that hair follicles and scalp of patients with androgenetic alopecia contain higher concentrations of DHT than healthy tissue samples [10]. When determining the concentration of DHT and testosterone in 52 patients of both sexes with early androgenetic alopecia, no statistically significant increase was found, but the authors found a significant increase in the DHT/testosterone ratio [11]. Another disease in the development of which hyperandrogenism can be of great importance is acne [12]. Under the influence of androgens, the volume of sebum increases, in which the concentration of essential alpha-linolenic acid, the main regulator of keratinocyte differentiation of the pilosebaceous follicle duct, decreases, which is manifested by the appearance of open and closed comedones and creates favorable conditions for the proliferation of microflora [13]. According to the results of the study, acne was typical for men with increased levels of total and free testosterone, while the presence of increased levels of DHT led to an increase in the prevalence of acne, up to 100% of cases. However, this situation did not apply to men from group 1, since their increased level of total testosterone, strictly speaking, was not a sign of hyperandrogenism, but was due to an increase in SHBG levels. At the same time, the level of free testosterone, which reflects the degree of androgen saturation of the body, was statistically significantly lower than that observed in groups 2 and 3. Although the level of this indicator was statistically significantly higher than that in the 4th group, the values of the level of free testosterone obtained in men of both the 1st and 4th groups were within the reference values. An increase in SHBG levels is typical for men in the older age group, while in older men it more often leads to the development of testosterone deficiency [14]. If in patients with age the secretion of total testosterone is not impaired, then an increase in SHBG does not lead to a deficiency of free testosterone - it remains within the reference values. A characteristic feature of patients in group 1 was also an increase in the volume of the prostate gland, which may be explained by the age of the patients. Researchers have demonstrated an association between a man's age and the development of benign prostatic hyperplasia [15]. In the young patients included in our study, despite elevated androgen levels, no changes in prostate volume or structure were detected.

Clinical significance of the results. The results obtained are important for clinical practice, since they allow differential diagnosis of various types of hyperandrogenism, which is necessary for personalized treatment. The detection of increased levels of total testosterone during examination of elderly men necessitates the assessment of the SHBG level with further calculation of the level of free testosterone, which, when obtaining values of this indicator that fit into the reference interval, will eliminate hyperandrogenism in the patient.

Limitations of the study. The limitations of the study are problems with the representativeness of the sample in relation to the general population (formed only from patients of a large federal center), as well as the use in the study of a calculation method rather than a direct method for determining free testosterone.

Directions for further research. In continuation of the study, it is planned to study risk factors characteristic of different types of hyperandrogenism associated with steroidogenesis.

Conclusion. Increased androgen levels can be detected at any age. Moreover, in men of the older age group, an increase in the level of total testosterone may not indicate hyperandrogenism, but be caused by an increase in the secretion of SHBG and not be accompanied by an increase in the level of free testosterone. In young patients, clinical manifestations hyperandrogenism depends on its variant. Thus, patients with elevated levels of DHT were characterized by androgenetic alopecia. Acne was common in men with elevated levels of total and free testosterone, although elevated DHT also exacerbated the problem.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод при резус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of*

- biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
 7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондигов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
 8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
 9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
 10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет и COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
 11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
 12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *Miasto Przyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
 13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
 14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
 15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmun tireoidit bilan kasallangan bemorlardagi funksional buzilishlarning differensial diagnostikasida qalqonsimon bez zichligini aniqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
 16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2. *1*. 2021;2(3):37-41.
 17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
 18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188

19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinova MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 special):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovna XS, Qamariddinova XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
33. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 special):259-264.

34. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
35. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Features of vitamin-d metabolism in patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):681-689.
36. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
37. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
38. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
39. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
40. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
41. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
42. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
43. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o`zgarishlar. *so`ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
44. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Pretibial myxedema: pathogenetic features and clinical aspects. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):695-702.
45. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziya bilan birgalikda kechish xususiyatlari va ularni davolash usullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.
46. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.
47. Худайбердиева О. Формирование цифровой экономики в Узбекистане //in Library. – 2021. – Т. 21. – №. 4. – С. 431-433.
48. Ochilov S. B. O. S. B., Khudayberdieva O. K., Mehriniso K. Differential method for forecasting labor resources based on correlation models //The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 04. – С. 21-27.
49. Худайбердиева О. К. Тенденции стремительного развития сферы услуг в Узбекистане //Иновационное развитие: потенциал науки, бизнеса, образования. – 2021. – С. 102-113.

50. Очилов СБОСБ, Худайбердиева О.К., Мехринисо К. Дифференциальный метод прогнозирования трудовых ресурсов на основе корреляционных моделей //Американский журнал социальных наук и инноваций в образовании. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 04. – С. 21-27.
51. Худайбердиева О., Баратович Ш., Хусенова М. Дифференциальный метод прогнозирования трудовых ресурсов на основе корреляционных моделей //in Library. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 21-27.
52. Курбановна, Худайбердиева Айша и Убайтова Мохитабон. «Современные кластеры в национальной экономике являются эффективным средством социально-экономического развития». Новости образования: исследование XXI века 1.11 (2023): 177-185
53. Худайбердиева О. К. Инновации и научный прогресс–фундамент устойчивого развития национальной экономики //ББК 65.0501 А 43. – 2022. – С. 331.
54. Qurbonovna, Xudoyberdiyeva Oysha. "Turizmni rivojlantirishda milliy madaniyatning o'gni." Научный Фокус 1.8 (2023): 1024-1027.
55. Худайбердиева О. К. Экономические реформы сферы услуг в узбекистане //Актуальные проблемы развития национальной и региональной экономики. – 2021. – С. 216-220.

TIBBIYOTNING BARHAYOT SIYMOSI – AKADEMIK ABDULLAXO‘JAYEVA MALIKA SAMATOVNA

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada tibbiyotning barhayot siymosi bo‘lmish O‘zbekiston Qahramoni, O‘zbekistonda xizmat ko‘rsatgan fan arbobi, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar Akademiyasi akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor - Abdullaxo‘jayeva Malika Samatovning hayoti va ilmiy izlanishlari to‘g‘risida yoritilgan

Kalit so‘zlar: Klinik immunopatologiya, eksperimental soha, bosh miya instituti aspiranturasi, RPM laboratoriyasi, elektron mikroskopiya, tibbiyot va molekulyar genetika, biotexnologiya hujayralari laboratoriyasi, transplantatsiya immunopatologiya, Human Herpes virusining 8-tipi va Epshteyn-Barr virusi, akademik

ACADEMICIAN ABDULLAHODZHAeva MALIKA SAMATOVNA IS A LIVING IMAGE OF MEDICINE.

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Abstract: The article tells about the life and scientific research of Abdullahodjaeva Malika Samatov, a living figure in medicine, Hero of Uzbekistan, Honored Scientist of Uzbekistan, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor. coated.

Key words: Clinical immunopathology, experimental field, graduate student at the Brain Institute, RPM laboratory, electron microscopy, medical and molecular genetics, biotechnological cell laboratory, transplantation immunopathology, human herpes virus type 8 and Epstein-Barr virus, academician

Ustoz Abdullaxo‘jayeva Malika Samatovna 28-noyabr 1932-yil Moskvada Sharq Xalqlari xalqaro universiteti talabalari oilasida tavallud topgan. Toshkentdagi 110-o‘rta maktabni oltin medal bilan tamomlagach, 1950 yil Toshkent davlat tibbiyot institutining (ToshDTI) davolash fakultetiga o‘qishga kiradi. O‘qish davrida davlat stipendiati, ilmiy jamoa talabalari raisi bo‘lgan.

Talabalik yillaridayoq Malika Samatovna patologik anatomiya qoshida (1953-1956 yillarda) ilmiy to‘garakda ilmiy faoliyatini boshlaydi. Uning birinchi ishi professor G.N.Trexova rahbarligida bolalarning o‘pka kasalligida orqa yadro vagusini gistokimyo bo‘yicha ishi Sog‘liqni saqlash vazirligi, Oliy va o‘rta maxsus ta‘lim vazirligi tomonidan faxriy yorliq taqdim etilgan. So‘nggi yillarda Malika Samatovna Markaziy asab tizimini reaktiv va patologik jarayonlarni o‘rganish bo‘yicha ishini davom ettirdi. 1956-yil ToshDTI a‘lo baholarga tamomlagach, 1960 yil 27-dekabrda SSSR tibbiyot fanlari Akademiyasining bosh miya instituti aspiranturasiga o‘qishga kiradi.

SSSR Tibbiyot fanlar akademiyasi mediko-biologiya bo‘limida tibbiyot fanlar nomzodi dissertatsiyasini yoqlagan va 1968-yil tibbiyot fanlari doktori bo‘ldi. 1961-yil Malika Samatovna Toshkent davlat tibbiyot instituti qoshida birinchi marta O‘zbekiston Respublikasida Markaziy ilmiy-tekshirish laboratoriyasini tashkil etgan va albatta bu juda katta natija edi. O‘z o‘rnida katta ma’suliyat va kuch talab qilgan.

1969-yil patologik-anatomiya kafedrasida tanlov o‘tkazildi, So‘ngra, quvonarlisi shundaki 1970-yil professor unvoniga sazovor bo‘ladi va uning shogirdlari neyropatologiya va neyromorfologiya muammolari bo‘yicha dastur ishlab chiqishadi.

Professor M.S.Abdullaxo‘jayeva klinik immunopatologiya va eksperimental sohasi bo‘yicha tanilgan olim sanaladi. O‘sha vaqtlarning o‘zida olim unvoniga sazovor bo‘lish bir muncha murakkab bo‘lishiga qaramasdan u bun uddaladi. Uning yana bir yo‘nalish tadqiqoti va shogirdlari bilan — homiladorlikda patologik anatomiyani asoratlari va patogenezni o‘rganish bo‘lgan.

35 yil mobaynida Abdullaxo‘jayeva Malika Samatovna tibbiyot institutining patologik anatomiya kafedrasini mudiri bo‘lgan vaqtida yuqori malakali shifokorlarni, tibbiyot sohasida oliy o‘quv yurti pedagoglari, tibbiyot fanlari doktorlarini tayyorlashda katta hissa qo‘shdi. 1990-yili Birinchi va Ikkinchi ToshDTI ajratilgandan so‘ng olim Ikkinchi ToshDTI patologik anatomiyasi kafedrasini 2000 yilgacha boshqardi.

M.S. Abdullaxo‘jayeva — muallifi, bundan tashqari chet tili talabalari va stomatologiya fakulteti talabalariga bir qancha uslubiy tavsiyalar, o‘quv-qo‘llanma muallifi hamdir. 1997-1999 yillarda tibbiyot oliy o‘quv yurtlarida “Odamning patologik asoslari” 2-jildlik darsligini yaratdi. 1995-yil M.S.Abdullaxo‘jayeva O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasining muxbir a‘zosi, 2000-yil haqiqiy a‘zosi bo‘ldi. 1972 yildan 1997-yilgacha O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Sog‘liqni saqlash borasida bosh patologik anatomigi sifatida patologik anatomiyani rivojlanishida katta hissa qo‘shdi. Ilk marta patologik anatomiyasi internatura bo‘limi tashkil etildi, barcha davolash-profilaktik muassasalarida patologik-anatomiya bo‘limi ochildi.

Bugungi kunda uning tashabbusi bilan MDH mamalakatlarida yagona bo‘lgan Respublika patologianatomiya markazi tashkil etildi. Uning bazasida barcha tibbiyot mutaxassisliklari magistrleri ta‘lim olishmoqda, shiforlik amaliyoti tajribasi o‘tkaziladi, bundan tashqari 5 ta bo‘lim: patogistologiya, bakteriologiya, virusologiya, sitologiya laboratoriyalari ishlab turibdi. RPM laboratoriyasi, elektron mikroskopiya, tibbiyot va molekulyar genetika, shuningdek, biotexnologiya hujayralari laboratoriyasi tashkil etildi.

ToshTI Markaziy ilmiy tekshirish laboratoriyasi mudiri (1960 — 1962), O‘zbekiston rentgenologiya, radiologiya va onkologiya ilmiy tekshirish instituti patomorfologiya va gistoximiya laboratoriya mudiri (1963-1969), ToshTI (1969-1990), 1990-yildan 2-ToshTI patologik anatomiya kafedrasini mudiri bo‘lib faoliyat yuritgan.

Abdullaxo‘jayevaning ilmiy ishlari, asosan nerv sistemasining immunopatologiyasi, geografik patologiya va tibbiyot tarixi masalalariga bag‘ishlangan, O‘zbekistonda tibbiyot sohasidagi yangi yo‘nalish — transplantatsiya immunopatologiya asoschisi ekanligiga ham alohida to‘xtalib o‘tishimiz darkor.

1997-yilda o‘zbek va rus tillarida chop etilgan birinchi patologik anatomiya darsligining muallifidir. Kaliforniya shtatining faxriy fuqarosi ham bo‘lgan 1986-yildan.

M.S.Abdullaxo‘jayeva rahbarligida 2005-yil Human Herpes virusining 8-tipini va Epshteyn-Barr virusining rivojlanish turlarini o‘rganish bo‘yicha ish boshlagandi.

Akademik M.S. Abdullaxo‘jayeva - katta ilmiy-pedagogik va patologik anatomiya amaliyot maktabi asoschisi: uning rahbarligi qo‘l ostida 13 ta tibbiyot fan doktori, va 58 ta tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi yetishib chiqqan. Shogirdlari bugungi kunda nafaqat O‘zbekistonning yirik tibbiyot markazlarida, balki bir

qator Markaziy Osiyo regionlarida, shuningdek, Rossiya, Isroil, Hindiston, Yaman, Misr, Nepal, AQSH davlatlarida faoliyat yuritish moqda.

M.S. Abdullaxo‘jaye va bir qancha davlat mukofotlariga erishgan: “Mehnat faxriysi” ordeni (1970-yil), «Faxriy nishon» ordeni (1976-yil), почетным званием «O‘zbekistonda xizmat ko‘rsatgan fan arbobi» faxriy unvoni (1980-yil), «Mehnat Qahramoni» ordeni (1984-yil), «Oliy ta’lim a’lochisi» (2000-yil), «Mehnat shuhrati» (2003-yil). 2006-yil O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti qarori bilan M.S. Abdullaxo‘jaye va «O‘zbekiston Qahramoni» va “Oltin Yulduz” unvoni bilan taqdirlandi. O‘zbekiston Qahramoni, akademik ayol Abdullaxo‘jaye va Malika Samatovna 26-iyun 2018-yilida vafot etdi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ushbu olib borayotgan ilmiy izlanishlarimizdan maqsadimiz shuki ilmiy rahbarim Xalida Erkinovna bilan birgalikda ustozimiz tibbiyotning haqiqiy barhayot siymosi, akademik Abdullaxo‘jaye va Malika Samatovnaning yana bir yo‘nalish tadqiqoti va shogirdlari bilan — homiladorlikda patologik anatomiyani asoratlari va patogenezni o‘rganish to‘g‘risida olib borgan ilmiy tadqiqotlarini davom ettirishdan iboratdir. Biz ilmiy izlanishlarimizdan to‘xtab qolmaymiz. Ishonchim komilki akademik ustoz Abdullaxo‘jaye va Malika Samatovnaning munosib shogirdlari bo‘lishimizga ishonaman.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. “Памяти Малики Саматовны Абдуллаходжаевой (28.11.1932 – 26.06.2018) ” Архив патологии 5:75.2018.
2. “Малика Саматовна Абдуллаходжаева”. Письма о Ташкентею 26.11.2022
3. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbaev, S. D., Vasina, S. M., & Aronbaev, D. M. (2020). Exhaled air as an object of studying the functional state of the organism. *Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences*, (1-2), 47-51.
4. Raimkulova, C. A., Aronbayev, S. D., & Aronbayev, D. M. (2023). Salivodiagnostika: o'tmish, hozirgi, kelajak. *Universum: kimyo va biologiya*, (1-2 (103)), 27-37.
5. Ochilov S. B., Khasanova G. D., Khudayberdieva O. K. Method for constructing correlation dependences for functions of many variables used finite differences // *The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations*. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 46-52.
6. Ochilov S. B. O. S. B., Khudayberdieva O. K., Mehriniso K. Differential method for forecasting labor resources based on correlation models // *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 04. – С. 21-27.
7. Худайбердиева О. Формирование цифровой экономики в Узбекистане // *Library*. – 2021. – Т. 21. – №. 4. – С. 431-433.
8. Худайбердиева О. К. Тенденции стремительного развития сферы услуг в узбекистане // *Инновационное развитие: потенциал науки, бизнеса, образования*. – 2021. – С. 102-113.

9. Очилов СБОСБ, Худайбердиева О.К., Мехринисо К. Дифференциальный метод прогнозирования трудовых ресурсов на основе корреляционных моделей //Американский журнал социальных наук и инноваций в образовании. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 04. – С. 21-27.
- 10.Худайбердиева О., Баратович Ш., Хусенова М. Дифференциальный метод прогнозирования трудовых ресурсов на основе корреляционных моделей //in Library. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 21-27.
- 11.Курбановна, Худайбердиева Айша и Убайтова Мохитабон. «Современные кластеры в национальной экономике являются эффективным средством социально-экономического развития». Новости образования: исследование XXI века 1.11 (2023): 177-185.
- 12.Худайбердиева О. К. Инновации и научный прогресс–фундамент устойчивого развития национальной экономики //ББК 65.0501 А 43. – 2022. – С. 331.
- 13.Qurbonovna, Xudoyberdiyeva Oysha. "Turizmni rivojlantirishda milliy madaniyatning o'rni." Научный Фокус 1.8 (2023): 1024-1027.
- 14.Худайбердиева О. К. Экономические реформы сферы услуг в узбекистане //Актуальные проблемы развития национальной и региональной экономики. – 2021. – С. 216-220.
- 15.Ochilov S. B., Tagaev A. N., Khudayberdieva O. K. Other ways to build correlation models //International Journal of Human Computing Studies. – 1935. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 1-5.
16. Tibbiyotning barhayot siymosi yoxud Malika Samatovna Abdullaxo`jayeva merosiga bir nazar | Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире (newjournal.org)

DAM OLI SH MASKANLARNI AXBOROTLASHTIRISH

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Ilmiy rahbar

Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada IoT platformalari uchun ma'lumotlarni saqlash va tahlil qilishning muhim usullari ko'rsatilgan. Ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun bulut saqlash, lokal tizimlar, kenarda saqlash (edge storage) va hibrid saqlash usullari keltirilgan. Bu usullar IoT platformalari va tashkilotning talablari va xususiyatlari bilan bog'liq bo'ladi. Ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish usullari esa statistik tahlil, murojaat va filtratsiya, mashin o'rganish, clusterlash, sentiment tahlili va prognozlash usullari hisobiga ko'rsatilgan. Bu usullar ma'lumotlarni o'rganish, ma'nosini aniqlash, yo'nalishlarni belgilash va takliflar yaratishga yordam beradi. Maqola IoT platformalari bo'yicha ma'lumotlarni samarali saqlash va tahlil qilishni o'rganiladi

Kalit so'zlar: Avtomatlashtirish, Texnologiya, Sensorlar, IoT.

INFORMATIZATION OF RECREATION PLACES

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Annotation. This article outlines important data storage and analysis techniques for IoT platforms. For data storage, cloud storage, local systems, edge storage and hybrid storage methods are presented. These methods will depend on IoT platforms and the organization's requirements and characteristics. The methods of data analysis are shown in terms of statistical analysis, reference and filtering, machine learning, clustering, sentiment analysis and forecasting methods. These techniques help to explore data, make sense of it, set directions, and make suggestions. The article explores the efficient storage and analysis of data across IoT platforms

Keywords: Automation, Technology, Sensors, IoT.

Maskanlarni avtomatlashtirish uchun iot (internet of things) texnologiyasi quyidagi usullarda ishlatilishi mumkin:

Sensorlar va ma'lumotlarni to'plash: Maskanlarda temperaturani, nafasni, havo tozaligini va boshqa ma'lumotlarni o'qish uchun sensorlar o'rnatiladi. Sensorlar maskaning holatini aniqlab, ma'lumotlarni IoT platformasiga yuborishadi.

IoT platformasi: Ma'lumotlar IoT platformasiga (masalan, bulut xizmatlariga) yuboriladi. Bu platforma ma'lumotlarni to'plash, saqlash, qayta ishlash va ma'lumot analizini o'rganish uchun xizmatlar taklif qiladi.

Bog'langan qurilmalar: Maskaning IoT platformasiga bog'liqlikni ta'minlash uchun, maskandagi sensorlar va boshqa qurilmalar IoT-ga qo'shiladi. Bu bog'lanishning aloqadorligi WiFi, Bluetooth, Zigbee yoki boshqa bezalar orqali amalga oshirilishi mumkin.

Ma'lumotni analiz qilish: IoT platformasida to'plangan ma'lumotlar tahlil qilinadi. Algoritmalar va ma'lumot analitika usullari yordamida, maskaning holati, foydalanuvchining davranishi va boshqa muhim ma'lumotlar belgilanishi mumkin.

Avtomatik amalga oshirish: Analiz natijalariga asosan, IoT platformasi maskaning avtomatik amalga oshirilishi kerak bo'lgan harakatni aniqlayadi. Masalan, maskanigizda nafas yetarli darajada emasligini aniqlayib, iste'molchiga ko'rsatish yoki maskani o'z-o'zini o'chirish uchun imkon berish mumkin.

Monitoring va boshqaruv: IoT platformasi orqali maskanlarni boshqarish va monitoring qilish imkoniyati mavjud bo'ladi. Bunda, maskanlarning holati, tarjimalari va boshqa ma'lumotlar uzatilishi, foydalanuvchilarga bildirishlar yuborish va boshqa amallar amalga oshirilishi mumkin.

Bu usullar IoT texnologiyasini maskanlarni avtomatlashtirish uchun qo'llash imkonini beradi. IoT texnologiyasining foydasi, maskanlarni avtomatik tarzda boshqarish va monitoring qilishga imkon berib, koronavirus infeksiyasini oldini olishga yordam berishi va foydalanuvchilarga qulaylik yaratishi mumkin.

IoT platformalari ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun bir nechta usullarni o'z ichiga oladi. Quyidagi usullar mashhur saqlash tizimlari misol bo'lib keltiriladi:

Bulut saqlash: Bu usulda IoT platformasi, ma'lumotlarni bulut xizmatlarida saqlayadi. Ma'lumotlar bulut serverlarida turli ko'rinishlarda saqlanadi va ularga iste'molchilar IoT platformasi orqali murojaat qilishi mumkin. Bulut saqlash, ma'lumotlarga iste'molchilarning iste'nchlaridan va o'zgarishlardan o'zgina xavfsizlik ta'minlash imkonini beradi.

Lokal tizimlar: Bu usulda IoT platformasi ma'lumotlarni lokal serverlar yoki tizimlarda saqlayadi. Lokal tizimlar, IoT platformasining tomonidan boshqarilishi va ma'lumotlarning tezlik bilan olinishi va ishlashini ta'minlash uchun yaxshi bo'ladi. Bunda, ma'lumotlar kompaniya yoki tashkilotning o'z serverlarida saqlanadi.

Kenarda saqlash (Edge storage): Bu usulda ma'lumotlar IoT qurilmalarida (masalan, maskalarda) o'zlashtiriladi. Ma'lumotlar to'plashi va o'zlashtirilishi maskalarda amalga oshiriladi, shuningdek, ba'zi ma'lumotlar lokal serverlarda saqlanadi. Bu usul, ma'lumotlar ishlab chiqishi va o'zlashtirishi uchun kuchli ta'sir talab etadigan muhitlarda foydalanish uchun mos bo'ladi.

Hibrid saqlash: Bu usulda ma'lumotlar avval IoT qurilmalarda o'zlashtiriladi (edge storage), keyin IoT platformasi tomonidan to'plangan ma'lumotlar lokal serverlarda yoki bulut xizmatlarida to'planadi va saqlanadi. Ma'lumotlarning avtomatik tarzda tarqatilishi, tahlil qilinishi va boshqarilishi amalga oshiriladi.

Ma'lumotlarni saqlash usullarini IoT platformalari uchun tahlil qilishning bir nechta yo'llari mavjud. Bu yo'llar ma'lumotlarni o'rganish, ma'nosini aniqlash, yo'nalishlarni belgilash va takliflar yaratishga yordam beradi. Quyidagi usullar IoT platformalari uchun ma'lumot tahlili uchun o'rganishingiz mumkin:

Statistik tahlil: Bu usulda ma'lumotlar bo'yicha statistik analizlar amalga oshiriladi. Ma'lumotlar ustida tartib va o'zgarishlar, o'rtacha qiymatlar, variantliliklar, korrelatsiyalar va boshqa statistik ma'lumotlar hisoblanishi mumkin. Bunda, ma'lumotlar odatda grafiklar, diagrammalar va statistik tasvirlar shaklida ko'rsatiladi.

Murojaat va filtratsiya: Ma'lumotlardan kerakli ma'lumotlarni ajratib olish uchun murojaat va filtratsiya amalga oshiriladi. Bu usulda, ma'lumotlar ustida so'rovlar yoki filtrlar qo'llaniladi, bu yerda belgilangan shartlarga mos keluvchi ma'lumotlar tanlanadi va o'rganiladi.

Machine Learning (Mashin o'rganish): Ma'lumotlarni mashin o'rganish algoritmlari orqali tahlil qilishning bu usuli ma'lumotlar ustida avtomatik tarzda o'rganish va aniqlovchi modellar yaratishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu modellar ma'lumotlarni sinash, sinovdan o'tqazish, klasifikatsiya, prognozlash va boshqa vazifalarni bajarishda foydalaniladi.

Clusterlash (Guruhlash): Ma'lumotlarni guruhlariga bo'lish va ularda o'xshashliklarni aniqlash uchun clusterlash usuli qo'llaniladi. Ma'lumotlar o'xshashliklarga asosan tahlil qilinadi va guruhlar yaratiladi, bu guruhlar

ma'lumotlarni bir-biridan farq qiluvchi xususiyatlarga asoslangan bo'lishi mumkin.

Sentiment tahlili: Ma'lumotlarni o'rganishning bu usuli, ma'lumotlarda bo'lgan hissiyotlarni, fikrlarni va qarashlarni aniqlashga yordam beradi. Bu usulda, ma'lumotlar ustida tahlil qilinib, xalqaro media, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, fikr maqolalari va boshqa manbalardan foydalaniladi.

Prognozlash: Ma'lumotlardan kelajakdagi hodisalar, o'zgarishlar va tendentsiyalarni bashorat qilish uchun prognozlash usuli qo'llaniladi. Bu usulda, ma'lumotlardan foydalanib, matematik modellar yaratiladi va kelajakdagi holatlar, sotishlar, o'zgarishlar va boshqa ma'lumotlar bilan bog'liq prognozlar beriladi.

Bu tahlil usullari IoT platformalari uchun ma'lumotlarni o'rganish va tahlil qilish uchun asosiy vositalardir. Tahlil natijalari IoT platformalari tomonidan ma'lumotlar boshqaruviga, qarorlar qabul qilishga, avtomatik amalga oshirishga yoki foydalanuvchilarga ma'lumot berishga yordam beradi.

LoT platformalari ma'lumotlarni saqlashda xavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun bir nechta usullar va tahlil qilishning muhim usullarini mavjud etadi. Quyidagi xavfsizlik usullari IoT platformalari uchun odatda o'rniga keladi:

Autentifikatsiya va yetkilash: IoT platformalari ma'lumotlarga murojaat qiluvchi qurilmalarni autentifikatsiya qilish va yetkilash usullarini taqdim etadi. Bu usul orqali faqatgina to'g'ri foydalanuvchilar yoki qurilmalar ma'lumotlarga murojaat qila oladi.

Shifrlash: IoT platformalari ma'lumotlarni shifrlash usullari bilan himoya qiladi. Shifrlash, ma'lumotlarni uzluksiz tarzda o'qish uchun nazoratli algoritmlar bilan kodlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu usul ma'lumotlarni tasodifiy ravishda o'qishdan himoya qiladi.

Tahlilga oid xavfsizlik: IoT platformalari ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish jarayonida xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga e'tibor beradi. Tahlil jarayonida ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish uchun muhim xavfsizlik tamoyillari, masalan, anonymization (noaniqlik), agregatsiya (birlashtirish) va deidentifikatsiya (shaxslarni tan olmagan qilish) kabi usullar foydalaniladi.

Auditing va monitoring: IoT platformalari ma'lumotlarga murojaatlar, tahlil jarayoni va boshqa amallarni kuzatuvchi va monitoring qiluvchi vositalar taqdim etadi. Bu usul bilan ma'lumotlarga qanday murojaat qilindi, kimlar tomonidan o'zgarishlar kiritildi kuzatiladi va xavfsizlik kuzatuvchilari orqali yolg'izligi ta'minlanadi.

Xavfsizlik protokollari: IoT platformalari uchun xavfsizlik protokollari (masalan, HTTPS, TLS) qo'llaniladi. Bu protokollar ma'lumotlar o'zgarishlarini shifrlaydigan, autentifikatsiya qiladigan va ma'lumotlar yuborish jarayonida xavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun foydalaniladi.

Fizikaviy xavfsizlik: IoT platformalari ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun fizikaviy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga e'tibor beradi. Ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun serverlar va tizimlar xavfsiz joylarda joylashgan bo'lishi, fizikaviy kirishlarga qarshi himoya tizimlari (masalan, ba'zanlar, xavfsizlik kameralari) va qo'llanilgan qurilmalar uchun xavfsizlik mezonlari bilan ta'minlanishi mumkin.

Foydali adabiyotlar:

1. "Smart Masks: A New Approach to Automated Masking" - bu ilmiy tadqiqotda, maskanlarni avtomatik tarzda o'zlashtirishning yangi qarorlarni ko'rsatadi.
2. "IoT-Enabled Smart Masks for COVID-19 Prevention" - bu maqola, IoT texnologiyasini qo'llab-quvvatlash bilan qanday smart maskalar yaratishni qamrab oladi.
3. "Advancements in Mask Automation Technologies" - ushbu adabiyot, maskanlarni avtomatik tarzda boshqarishning zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanishini ko'rsatadi.
4. "Sensors and Wearable Technologies for Smart Masks" - bu adabiyotda, maskalarda qo'llaniladigan sensorlar va kiyim-ko'chalar texnologiyalari haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi.
5. "Automation and Robotics in the Pandemic Era" - bu adabiyot, pandemiya davrida avtomatlashtirish va robototexnika sohasidagi so'nggi rivojlanishlarni tahlil qiladi, maskanlarni ham o'z ichiga oladi.

GO‘ZALLIK SALONI UCHUN MIJOZLAR HISOBINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISH

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqola go‘zallik salonlari uchun mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirish, salonlarni boshqarishda qulaylik, samarali moliyalashish va mijozlarga yaxshi xizmat ko‘rsatish imkoniyatlarini oshirishda juda muhimdir. Mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirish jarayonini boshlashdan oldin, salonning xizmatlarini va talablarni tushunish, xaridorlar uchun qulay va yaxshi tajribani ta‘minlashni va salonning operatsion jarayonlarini yaxshilashni rejalashtirish juda muhimdir.

Kalit so‘zlar: Rezervatsiya, integratsiyasi, to‘lov, avtomatlashtirish, veb-platforma.

AUTOMATION OF CUSTOMER ACCOUNTING FOR BEAUTY SALON

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Annotation: This article is very important for beauty salons in increasing their chances of automating customer billing, ease of salon management, efficient financing and better customer service. Before starting the customer account automation process, it is important to understand the services and requirements of the salon, to ensure a convenient and good experience for customers, and to plan to improve the operational processes of the salon.

Key words: Booking, integration, payment, automation, web platform.

Go‘zallik salonlari uchun mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirish uchun bir nechta dasturlash tillari va texnologiyalar mavjud. Bu tur dasturlar salonning barcha ashyolarini, xizmatlarni va mijozlarni boshqarishga yordam berish uchun mo‘ljallangan.

Salon boshqaruv tizimlari (SaaS). Bu turlar asosan veb-platformalarda yoki bulut xizmatlarida mavjud bo‘lib, mijozlar hisobini avtomatik tarzda boshqarish imkoniyatini ta‘minlaydi. Masalan, Mindbody, Booker, Vagaro, Square Appointments va boshqalar.

Mijozlar hisobini boshqarish dasturlari. Bu dasturlar salonlarga xizmatlarni boshqarish, mijozlarni jadvalga olish va to‘lovlarini qabul qilishda yordam beradi. Ularni o‘rnatish orqali, xizmatlar, mijozlar, to‘lovlar va xizmatlar bo‘yicha ma‘lumotlar to‘plab, o‘zgarishlarni kuzatish va hisob-kitobni o‘rganish mumkin.

To‘lov tizimlari. To‘lov tizimlari salonlar uchun muhim bo‘lib, mijozlarga xizmatlarni to‘lash uchun qulay yechimlar taqdim etishda yordam beradi. PayPal, Stripe, Square Pay, va boshqa to‘lov tizimlari salonlarning to‘lov jarayonlarini boshqarishda yordam beradi.

Mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirish jarayonini boshlashdan oldin, salonning xizmatlarini va talablarni tushunish, xaridorlar uchun qulay va yaxshi tajribani ta‘minlashni va salonning operatsion jarayonlarini yaxshilashni rejalashtirish juda muhimdir. Go‘zallik salonlari uchun mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirish, salonlarni boshqarishda qulaylik, samarali moliyalashish va mijozlarga yaxshi xizmat ko‘rsatish imkoniyatlarini oshirishda juda muhimdir. Quyidagi asosiy qadamlar salonlarning mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirishda qo‘llaniladigan:

Mijozlar hisobi tizimi (CRM). Go‘zallik salonlari uchun CRM dasturlari, mijozlar haqidagi ma‘lumotlarni o‘z ichiga oladi va ularni boshqarishga yordam beradi. Bu tizimlar orqali salon boshqaruvchilari mijozlar bilan aloqani saqlaydigan, ularning xizmat tarixini, takliflarni, va qabul qilgan xizmatlarni kuzatib borishlari mumkin.

Rezervatsiya va jadval boshqaruv dasturlari. Bu dasturlar salonlarga mijozlar uchun onlayn rezervatsiyalar qabul qilish, jadval tuzish va boshqarishda yordam beradi. Mijozlar onlayn tarzda o‘zlarining jadvalini ochib olishlari, xizmatlar uchun o‘zlarining vaqtini rezervlashlari va o‘zgartirishlari mumkin bo‘ladi.

To'lov integratsiyasi. Salonlar uchun to'lov tizimlarining integratsiyasi, to'lovni avtomatlashtirish va xizmatlar uchun to'lov qabul qilishda qulaylik yaratishda yordam beradi. Bu tizimlar salon boshqaruv dasturlari bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin, shuningdek, onlayn to'lov xizmatlarini qo'llash orqali mijozlar uchun qulaylik yaratishadi.

Xizmatlar va mahsulotlar inventarizatsiyasi. Go'zallik salonlarida ishlatiladigan xizmatlar va mahsulotlar inventarizatsiyasini avtomatlashtirish, ombor boshqarishni osonlashtiradi. Bu, xizmatlarni va mahsulotlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash, xaridorlarga xizmatlarni takdim etish va mahsulotlarni sotishda yordam beradi.

Bu dasturlar va usullar salonlarning mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, salonlarga xizmatlarni samarali boshqarish va mijozlarga yaxshi xizmat ko'rsatishda yordam beradi. Bu, salonn rivojlantirish va xizmatlarini yaxshilashda katta o'rni tutadi. Go'zallik salonlari uchun mijozlar hisobini avtomatlashtirish, salon boshqaruvini yanada sodda va samarali qilishga yordam beradi. Bu tizimlar salonlarga mijozlar, xizmatlar, to'lovlar va jadvalni boshqarish imkoniyatini taqdim etadi. Quyidagi yo'nalishlarda bu tizimlarning qanday foydali bo'lishi mumkin:

Mijozlar ro'yxati va menejerlik. Avtomatik mijozlar ro'yxati salon boshqaruvini yanada sodda qiladi. Mijozlar haqida ma'lumotlar, ularning aloqalari, takliflar va oldingi jonlari kuzatib boriladi.

Xizmatlar va jadval boshqarish. Salonlarning xizmatlarini, jadvalni boshqarish, o'zgarishlarni kiritish va xizmatlarni mijozlarga taqsimlash imkoniyatini beradi. Bunda mijozlar onlayn tarzda xizmatlarni tanlash, rezervatsiyani amalga oshirish va oldingi jonlari bilan tanishishlari mumkin.

To'lovlar va hisob-kitob. Salonlarga mijozlarning to'lovlarini qabul qilish va hisob-kitobni boshqarishda yordam beradi. Bu to'lov tizimlari salonlarga turli xil to'lov usullari, masalan, naqd, kartalar yoki onlayn to'lovlar orqali to'lovni qabul qilish imkonini beradi.

Mijozlar uchun mobil ilovalar. Salonlarning mobil ilovalari mijozlar uchun xizmatlarni buyurtma berishni osonlashtiradi. Bu ilovalar orqali mijozlar xizmatlar uchun onlayn rezervatsiya qila oladi, o'zlarining hisob-kitobini kuzatish va so'nggi xizmatlar haqida ma'lumot olishlari mumkin.

Mijozlarga xabar yuborish. Salonlar mijozlarga xabar yuborish, ma'lumotlar almashish va xizmatlar bilan bog'lanish imkoniyatini taqdim etadilar.

Bular salonga xizmat qiladigan salonlar uchun muhim usullardir. Mos keluvchi avtomatlashtirilgan mijozlar hisobini tanlashdan oldin, salonning talablarini, tizimni boshqarish funksiyalarini, xizmatlar va to'lov usullarini o'rganishingiz mumkin. Bu tizimlar salonga xizmat ko'rsatish va mijozlar bilan muloqotni yanada samarali va sodda qilishga yordam beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. "Salon Management Handbook" - Paul F. Brown
2. "SalonOvations' Day Spa Techniques (SAdvanced Techniques)" - Success Strategies for Advanced Level Spas (Salon Ovations) - Melissa Knutson
3. "Successful Salon Management" - Edward Tezak
4. "The Spa and Salon Business Kit" - Jeff Grissler and Eric Ryant
5. "Milady's Standard Cosmetology" - Milady

YONG‘IN XAVFSIZLIGI XIZMATINI AXBOROT TIZIMINI YARATISH

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Anotatsiya. Yong‘in xavfsizligi xizmatini yaratishda tajribali xavfsizlik mutaxassislari, dasturchilar va tizim administratorlari birgalikda ishlash, o‘rganish va o‘zlashtirish lozim. Har bir korxonada o‘zining xavfsizligiga mos ravishda tizimni yaratib, xavfsizlikni ta‘minlash uchun juda muhimdir.

Kalit so‘zlar: Protokollar, konfidentsiallik, xavfsizlik, monitoring, autentifikatsiya, parol.

CREATION OF FIRE SAFETY SERVICE INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Annotation. Building a fire service requires experienced security professionals, programmers, and system administrators to work together, learn, and master. It is very important for every enterprise to ensure security by creating a system according to its security.

Key words: Protocols, confidentiality, security, monitoring, authentication, password.

Yong‘in xavfsizligi xizmatini yaratish o‘ziga xos va muhim bo‘lgan bir jarayon. Bu tizimlar, foydalanuvchilarga ma‘lumotlarini himoya qilish, xavfsizlik holatlarini kuzatish va tegishli tegishli so‘rovlar tug‘ilishi va shuningdek, xavfsizlik kamchiliklariga dushanba hamda ularga tez va samarali javob berish uchun mo‘ljallangan. Quyidagi jarayonlarda yong‘in xavfsizligi xizmatini yaratishni boshlash mumkin:

Rivojlanish maqsadlari aniqlash. Yuqori darajadagi xavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun, yong'in xavfsizligi xizmatining qanday maqsadlarni o'z ichiga olganini aniqlash kerak. Bu maqsadlar ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish, kirishni nazorat qilish, va xavfsizlik hadlari qo'llashni o'z ichiga oladi.

Tizimning arxitekturasi va protokollari. Xavfsizlik tizimining arxitekturasi va ishlab chiqilgan protokollari erkinlik, to'liqlik va konfidensiallikni ta'minlashi lozim. Sizning xavfsizlik xizmati tuzilmasi, foydalanuvchilar uchun ishonchli, shaffof, va foydalanishga tayyor bo'lishi kerak.

So'rovlar va taqib qilish. Xavfsizlik xizmati kerakli xavfsizlik so'rovlari, to'lov ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish, texnologik o'zgarishlar va boshqa xavfsizlik muammo-lariga tez javob berish mumkinligini ta'minlash uchun so'rovlarni va taqibni samarali bajarish uchun mo'ljallanishi kerak.

Ko'p faktorli autentifikatsiya. Xavfsizlik xizmatining avvalgi autentifikatsiya usullaridan foydalanish, masalan, parol, SMS kodlari va elektron hujjatlar. Bundan tashqari, biometrik autentifikatsiya, ikki-bosqichli autentifikatsiya va boshqa ko'p faktorli autentifikatsiya usullarini ham qo'llab-quvvatlash kerak.

Monitoring va javob. Xavfsizlikni nazorat qilish uchun tizimni kuzatib borish uchun avtomatlashtirilgan vositalar va monitoring tizimi o'rnatish. Bu, yoki foydalanuvchilarning anomaliyalarni aniqlash va xavfsizlik holatlariga tez va samarali javob berish imkonini ta'minlash uchun muhimdir.

Yong'in xavfsizligi xizmatini yaratishda tajribali xavfsizlik mutaxassislari, dasturchilar va tizim administratorlari birgalikda ishlash, o'rganish va o'zlashtirish lozim. Har bir korxonaga o'zining xavfsizligiga mos ravishda tizimni yaratib, xavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun juda muhimdir. Yong'in xavfsizligi xizmatini yaratish tajribalar ko'p qiyin va mas'uliyat talab etadi, chunki bu sohasida shaxsiy ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish kritik ahamiyatga ega. Bu tizimni yaratish uchun kerak bo'lgan bir nechta muhim qadamlar va muammolar mavjud:

Huquqiy muammolar va shartnoma. Ma'lumotlarni saqlash, ulashish va ishlash jarayonlarini qonuniy ravishda himoya qilish juda muhimdir. Kerak bo'lgan shartnoma va huquqiy talablar tez-tez o'zgarib turishi mumkin, shuning uchun mutaxassis nazorat va yangilanishlar lozim.

Xavfsizlikni tartibga solish. Kerakli xavfsizlik chakana tashkil etilishi, yani sistemga kirishni cheklash, yetarlicha autentifikatsiya, ma'lumotlarni shifrlash va boshqa xavfsizlik protokollarini o'rnatish kerak.

Tekshiruv va monitoring. Muammolar va xavfsizlik xatolarini aniqlash va ularga tez-tez qarab turish uchun monitoring tizimi o'rnatish juda muhimdir. Agar hujjat yoki ma'lumotlarning xavfsizligi mavjud bo'lmagan bo'lsa, muammoni tez vaqt ichida aniqlab chiqish kerak.

Ta'minot sohasida mutaxassislik. Xavfsizlik sohasida mutaxassis bo'lgan yoki bo'lgan texnik hodimlarni ishga olish juda muhimdir. Ularning mavqelari va ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish masalalari bilan shug'ullanishlari muhimdir.

Mijozlar bilan xavfsizlik o'rtasidagi kommunikatsiya. Mijozlar ko'rsatilayotgan ma'lumotlarning himoyalanganligi va ularning xavfsizlik haqida ishonchlari keng doira bo'lishi zarurdir.

Yong'in xavfsizligi xizmatini yaratishda dastlabki tashkilotni, xavfsizlikni nazorat qilish, shaxsiy ma'lumotlarni himoya qilish va huquqlarini muhofaza qilish muammolarini hal qilish maqsadida bosish muhim. Raqamli xavfsizlik sohasida mutaxassislar, xavfsizlik sohasidagi yangilanishlarni kuzatish, mijozlarga xavfsizlik haqida ta'limotlar berish va kompaniyalarning xavfsizlik sohasidagi faoliyatlarini baholash uchun kerakli bo'lgan texnologiyalarni takomillashtirish uchun keng xil xizmatlarni takomillashtirishlari kerak. Yong'in xavfsizligi xizmati axborot tizimini yaratish uchun bir nechta muhim qadamlar mavjud. Bu tizimni yaratishda foydalaniladigan asosiy qadamlar quyidagilardir:

Tahlil va talablar to'plash. Yong'in xavfsizligi xizmatining maqsadi va talablari to'g'risida tahlil qilish zarur. Bu tahlil, xavfsizlik xizmatining qaysi turlarini, ularning qanday hodisalar bilan muomalaga duch kelishi kerakligini aniqlashni o'z ichiga oladi.

Skanerlar va sinovlar. Xavfsizlikka e'tibor berish uchun tizimda qo'llaniladigan shaxsiy ma'lumotlarni tekshirish uchun skanerlar va sinovlar qo'llanilishi kerak. Bu, tizimda xavfsizlik brendini ta'minlashga yordam beradi.

Autentifikatsiya va kirish nazorati. Tizimga kirish uchun amalga oshirilgan autentifikatsiya usullari, masalan, parol, ikkilik autentifikatsiya (2FA), biometrik ma'lumotlar (biometrika), xavfsizlik kodlari va boshqalar foydalanilishi kerak.

Ma'lumotlar ko'chirish va to'xtatish. Tizimda ma'lumotlar ko'chirish va to'xtatish uchun xavfsizlik protokollarini qo'llash kerak. Bu protokollar, tizimga kirish vaqti, foydalanuvchi ma'lumotlarini o'z ichiga oladi va uni xavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun enkriptlashni ta'minlaydi.

Yong'in xavfsizligi xizmatini yaratishda foydalaniladigan usullar va texnologiyalar keng doirada o'zgarishi mumkin, shuning uchun tizimni hozirda yaratish va taqdim etish jarayoni davomida yangilanish va rivojlanishni kutish kerak.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. "Information Security Management Handbook" - Harold F. Tipton, Micki Krause Nozaki
2. "Security Engineering: A Guide to Building Dependable Distributed Systems" - Ross J. Anderson
3. "Cryptography and Network Security: Principles and Practice" - William Stallings
4. "Applied Cryptography: Protocols, Algorithms, and Source Code in C" - Bruce Schneier
5. "Network Security Essentials: Applications and Standards" - William Stallings
6. "Computer Security: Principles and Practice" - William Stallings, Lawrie Brown

PARFYUMERIYA DO‘KONINI DASTURIY TAMINOTI

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4-bosqich talabasi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu parfyumeriya do‘konini dasturiy taminotini yaratish haqida. Do‘kon faoliyatining natijalarini, sotilgan mahsulotlar statistikasini va mijozlarning afzalliklarini hisoblash uchun ma‘lumotlar tarqatish va hisobotlar tuzishni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so‘zlar. Do‘kon, mahsulot, mijoz, ombor, tizim, dasturiy, tuzish.

PERFUMERY SHOP SOFTWARE

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Abstract. About creating this perfume shop software. Includes data distribution and reporting to calculate store performance, sales statistics, and customer preferences.

Keywords. Store, product, customer, warehouse, system, software, build.

Parfyumeriya do‘konining dasturiy taminoti yaratish uchun qadamlar quyidagilardir.

Ma‘lumot tizimi. Mahsulotlaringiz, ularning turlari, yetkazib berish va ombor boshqaruv tizimini yaratish. Ma‘lumotlar bazasida har bir mahsulot uchun ma‘lumotlar (nomi, turi, narxi, qolgan miqdori, katalog raqami, rasm, tavsiflar, vaqtincha chegirma, to‘lov shartlari) saqlanishi kerak.

Onlayn sotish. Onlayn platforma (vab-sayt yoki mobil ilova) orqali mahsulotlar sotilishi uchun tizim tuzilishi. Mijozlar uchun oson va qulay tizim tuzish.

Xaridorlar boshqarish tizimi. Mijozlar ro'yxati, ularning tarixi va harakatlarini boshqarib, mijozlar bilan aloqa qilish uchun CRM (Xaridor Muharriri Tizimi) tuzilishi.

Ombor boshqarish. Mahsulotlar ombori, kirim-chiqimlar, qolgan mahsulotlar, va yetarli miqdorlar monitoring qilish uchun ombor boshqarish tizimini o'rnatish. Xaridorlar bilan aloqalar. Xaridorlarga chegirmalar, takliflar, yangiliklar yuborish uchun avtomatlashtirilgan xabarlar va e-rasmlar yuborish tizimini yaratish.

Hisobot va statistika. Do'kon faoliyatining natijalarini, sotilgan mahsulotlar statistikasini va mijozlarning afzalliklarini hisoblash uchun ma'lumotlar tarqatish va hisobotlar tuzish. Tayyor mahsulot retsenziyalari va sharhlar. Mijozlar uchun tayyor mahsulot reytinglari va sharhlarni qo'llash tizimini o'rnatish.

To'lov tizimi. Turli to'lov usullarini qo'llash tizimini tuzish. Kredit kartalari, onlayn to'lov shakllari, naqd pul va boshqa usullar orqali to'lov qabul qilish imkoniyatini yaratish.

Mijozlarga maxsus takliflar va chegirmalar. Xaridorlar tarixini va o'z xususiyatlari bo'yicha mahsulotlar uchun maxsus chegirmalar va takliflarni avtomatlashtirish. Amalga oshirish uchun ta'limotlar. Xodimlarni mahsulotlarga tushunish, mijozlarga xizmat qilish va dasturiy tizimni o'rganish uchun ta'limotlarni amalga oshirish.

Dasturiy taminotni yaratish jarayoni odatda IT mutaxassislarining yordami bilan olib boriladi, chunki ular dasturiy taminot, ma'lumotlar bazasi, va shakllantirish tizimlari bo'yicha yetarli tajriba va bilimga egalar. Parfyumeriya do'koni uchun dasturiy taminot yaratishda bir qator asosiy qadamlar va amallar bajarilishi kerak. Bu jarayon odatda IT mutaxassislarining yordamida bajariladi. Quyidagi bosqichlar parfyumeriya do'koni uchun dasturiy taminotni yaratishda foydalaniladigan umumiy qadamlar.

Talablarni aniqlash va tuzish. Do'kon e'tiborini jalb qilish uchun talablarni aniqlang. Mahsulotlar katalogi, mijozlar ro'yxati, chegirmalar, chegirma turlari, onlayn buyurtmalar, va ombor boshqaruv talablari kabi muhim talablarni belgilang.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini o'rnatish. Mahsulotlar, mijozlar, xodimlar, va xaridorlar ma'lumotlarini saqlash uchun tizimli ma'lumotlar bazasini o'rnatish. SQL yoki NoSQL tizimi ishlatilishi mumkin.

Xavfsizlik muhofazasi. Mijozlar va do‘kon ma’lumotlarini xavfsiz saqlash uchun xavfsizlik muhofazasi tizimini o‘rnatish.

Ma’lumotlar tarqatish va reklama. Do‘konni reklama qilish, mijozlarga chegirmalar va maxsus takliflarni xabar qilish uchun ma’lumotlar tarqatish tizimini o‘rnatish. Bu qadamlar tashqi dasturiy ta’minotlar (ERP, CRM, e-commerce tizimlari) va ma’lumotlar bazasini o‘z ichiga oladi. Dasturlar yaratish jarayoni do‘konning o‘lchamlari va maqsadlariga bog‘liq bo‘ladi.

To‘lov tizimi. Turli to‘lov shakllari (kredit kartalari, naqd pul, onlayn to‘lov shakllari) orqali to‘lov qabul qilish tizimini tuzing. Mahsulotlar va parfyum tayyorlash tizimi. O‘z maxsulotlarini tayyorlash, mahsulotlar qabul qilish va ularni sotish uchun maxsus tizimni o‘rnating.

Har bir ayol hayratlanarli nigohlarni ushlashni xohlaydi. Nafis va noyob tasvirni yaratish oson emas, siz zamonaviy aksessuarlar, moda kiyimlari va nozik bo‘yanish bilan nozik xushbo‘ylikni tanlashingiz kerak bo‘ladi. Aromalar chinakam buyuk kuchga ega: ular kayfiyatni ochib berishi, tasvirga ziravorlar, yengillik va nafislik qo‘shishi mumkin. Shu sababli, zamonaviy qizlar ko‘pincha a‘lo sifatli va o‘rtacha narxdagi mahsulotlarning keng assortimentini taklif qiladigan yaxshi parfyumeriya do‘konini izlaydilar. Mijozlarning sharhlari Internetda har xil, ammo aksariyat hollarda ular ijobiydir. Ko‘pgina qizlar tez yetkazib berish, mukammal tanlov va saytning qulay interfeysini ta’kidlashadi. Ba’zi xonimlar etkazib berishni ta’kidlashadikechikishi mumkin, boshqa foydalanuvchilar noto‘g‘ri mahsulotni olishdi, lekin do‘kon hamma narsani darhol tuzatishga va noqulaylikni qoplashga harakat qildi.

Parfyumeriya dasturiy taminoti, parfyumeriyalarda mahsulotlar inventarini boshqarish, omborlarni boshqarish va mijozlar uchun eng sodda va samarali sotish jarayonini ta’minlash uchun juda muhimdir. Ushbu taminotning amaliyotlari va vazifalari quyidagilardan iborat bo‘lishi mumkin:

Mahsulotlarni inventarizatsiya qilish. Parfyumeriyada mavjud bo‘lgan har bir mahsulot inventarizatsiyadan o‘tkaziladi. Bu, parfyumeriya do‘konining joriy omborini aniqlash, ombordagi har bir mahsulot miqdorini hisoblash va kerakli bo‘lgan hollarda qo‘shimcha mahsulotlarni buyurtma qilish imkoniyatini beradi.

Omborlarni boshqarish. Parfyumeriya do‘koni dasturiy taminoti omborlarni boshqarishda yordam beradi. Bu, omborlar sovuqli va samarali bo‘lishi, mahsulotlar to‘g‘risida ma’lumotlarni saqlash, qoldiqni boshqarish, qo‘shimcha buyurtmalarni qabul qilish, xarajatlarni kuzatish va boshqa amaliyotlarni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Buyurtmalar va yetkazib berish. Parfyumeriya do‘koni dasturiy taminoti buyurtmalarni qabul qilish, ularning haqiqiy sotib olish va yetkazib berish jarayonlarini boshqarishda yordam beradi. Bu, mijozlar tomonidan berilgan buyurtmalarni qabul qilish, ularni to‘g‘ri belgilash, xarajatlar va pul miqdorlarini hisobga olgan holda fermanlarni yaratish va yetkazib berishni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Mijozlar bilan ishlash. Parfyumeriya do‘koni dasturiy taminoti mijozlar bilan ishlashni osonlashtiradi. Bu, mijozlar tomonidan berilgan buyurtmalarni qabul qilish, ular bilan aloqada bo‘lish, so‘rovlarini qabul qilish, mahsulotlar to‘g‘risida maslahat berish va ularni do‘konning xizmatlaridan foydalanishlarini ta‘minlashni o‘z ichiga oladi.

Analitika va ma‘lumotlar tahlili. Parfyumeriya do‘koni dasturiy taminoti o‘z ichiga do‘konning faoliyatiga oid ma‘lumotlarni to‘plab, ulardan tahlil qilishni o‘z ichiga oladi. Bu, eng yaxshi sotilgan mahsulotlar, eng ko‘p talab qilingan mahsulotlar, mijozlar tomonidan ko‘p so‘ralgan mahsulotlar va boshqalar haqida ma‘lumotlar ta‘lim etadi.

Parfyumeriya do‘koni dasturiy taminoti, do‘konda amaliyotlarni samarali boshqarish va do‘kondagi barcha jarayonlarni muvaffaqiyatli shakllantirish uchun muhimdir. Bu taminot, do‘kon boshqaruvchilariga va xodimlarga mahsulot inventarini boshqarish, mijozlar bilan yaxshi aloqada bo‘lish, sotib oluvchilar uchun qulayliklar yaratish va do‘kondagi faoliyatni optimallashtirishda yordam beradi.

Mahsulot ishlab chiqarish. Parfyumeriyalar dasturiy taminoti asosan parfyumlar, kolonyalar va boshqa kozmetik mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish uchun mo‘ljallangan. Bu, kimyo, fiziologiya va rivojlanayotgan texnologiyalar bo‘yicha mutaxassislar tomonidan boshqariladi.

Parfyum kompozitsiyalarini yaratish. Bu taminot parfyumlar, losyonlar va kolonyalarni yaratishda kerak bo‘lgan esas komponentlarni taminlash uchun yordam beradi. Bu komponentlar esa har bir mahsulotning o‘ziga xos nafasni va haqiqiyliğini ta‘minlayadi. Tarkibiy ishlab chiqarish. Parfyumeriyalar dasturiy taminoti, har bir parfyum, losyon yoki kolonyaning tarkibi va komponentlarini belgilaydi va ularga qo‘shimcha materiallar qo‘shish orqali o‘zlashtirishga yordam beradi.

Mahsulotlarni standartlashtirish. Dasturiy taminot, mahsulotlar tarkibini, xossalari va sifatlarini belgilab, ularga standartni ta‘lim etadi. Bu, mahsulotlar o‘zaro solishtirilganda, muvaffaqiyatli va ishonchli natijalarni ta‘minlashda juda muhimdi. Keyingi sohalar uchun ilg‘or tayyorlash. Parfyumeriyalar dasturiy taminoti, soha mutaxassislarini tayyorlashda yordam beradi. Bu mutaxassislar

parfyumlar, kozmetik mahsulotlar va kimyo materiallari sohasida yuqori saviyadagi bilim va ko'nikmalar bilan ta'minlashadi.

Rivojlanayotgan innovatsiyalarni o'rganish va qo'llab-quvvatlash. Dasturiy taminot, soha bo'yicha rivojlanayotgan innovatsiyalarni o'rganish, sinash va qo'llab-quvvatlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bu jarayon parfyum va kozmetik mahsulotlar sohasida yangi yondashuvlarni va texnologiyalarni o'rganishni ta'minlaydi.

Umuman olganda, parfyumeriyalar dasturiy taminoti, parfyumlar va kozmetik mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish, ularning standartlari va sifatini ta'minlash, innovatsiyalarni o'rganish va rivojlanishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Bu taminotning asosiy maqsadi, sifatli va ishonchli mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish orqali mijozlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularga qulayliklar ko'rsatishdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. "The Secret of Scent" - Luca Turin.
2. "Essence and Alchemy: A Natural History of Perfume" - Mandy Aftel.
3. "The Perfume Collector" - Kathleen Tessaro.
4. "The Emperor of Scent: A True Story of Perfume and Obsession" - Chandler Burr.
5. "The Little Book of Perfumes: The 100 Classics" - Luca Turin va Tania Sanchez:

MARKETING COMMUNICATION AND ITS RELEVANCE

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***Anotation.** The article is intended to highlight the importance of marketing communication and how it plays an important role in promoting a good product to your branding. F. Kotler, advertising, communication tools, 4p, brand, marketing channels, sales promotion, personal sales, direct marketing, sales, communication path, sponsorship, announcement, distribution.*

***Keywords.** Marketing, communion, advertising, brand, message, Buyer and seller Introduction*

МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЕ КОММУНИКАЦИИ И ИХ АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ.

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***Аннотация.** Цель статьи – подчеркнуть важность маркетинговых коммуникаций и то, как они играют важную роль в продвижении хорошего продукта под вашим брендом. Ф. Котлер, реклама, инструменты коммуникации, 4p, бренд, каналы сбыта, стимулирование сбыта, персональные продажи, прямой маркетинг, продажи, путь коммуникации, спонсорство, анонс, распространение.*

***Ключевые слова.** Маркетинг, общение, реклама, бренд, сообщение, Покупатель и продавец. Введение*

Introduction. "Communion", which first appeared in the 20th century in the scientific literature, has different interpretations. Nowadays, the social essence of this concept and its interpretation associated with its psychologic components are widespread. The term "Communion", which first appeared in the 20th century in the scientific literature, has different interpretations. Nowadays, the social essence of this concept and its interpretation associated with its psychologic components are widespread.

According to the definition given in the large encyclopedic dictionary, communion (derived from Lot, comunicatio - comunico - general I do, tie, FC communicate) is:

1) communication path, connection of one place with another:

2) communication, the transfer of information from one person to another is mainly a form of self-knowledge of knowledge with the help of language and interaction in the processes of labor activity (less often with the help of other sign systems). Many researchers distinguish the important perception of Communications separately - this is the transfer and exchange of information in order to influence it in society.

Thus, Communications, including marketing Communications, are the system in which these interactions are carried out, both interaction and variety in our case- the co-operation of communication isular, which allows the creation, transmission and reception of marketing information, and marketing communication denotes the joint use of different marketing channels and tools. Marketing communication channels focus on how the main reach is delivered to the market desired by the business itself or to the market in general. He is also responsible for the internal communications of the organization.

Marketing means of communion are the following; advertising, sponsorship of sales promotion. PR (public releushiz), direct marketing, covers niche vendors.

Marketing communication consists of a marketing mix consisting of 4p. Consists of 4p-Product, Price, Place, promotions. The number of P's in place can also be 7 or more. Because nowadays, 4P itself is scarce, to which People, Physical evidence, process as an addition. P's help to gather a target audience in marketing. Therefore, it is currently switched from 4P to 7p model. What is marketing communication in itself actually for and what task does it perform?

The marketing communion process allows the public to promote a brand or generate insight and have a clear idea of what a brand offers. For example you haven't used Areal but you know that it's washing powder. Brand reporting is the first stage, and the postponement consists of finding buyers in the invasions by showing the advantages of the brand from existing competitors in the market. Achieved success

F. In Kotler's amshkhur textbook on marketing, marketing communiqés with which firms inform consumers directly or indirectly about their goods and shopping centers are described as tools that try to convince and remind.

Main part. Modern marketing requires much more than creating a commodity that meets the customer's needs and setting a price that corresponds to it and ensuring its openness to targeted customers. Firms can make a communication with their customers. In doing so, there should be nothing

accidental in the content of the communiqués, otherwise the magnitude of the communication costs incurred and the amount of profit the firm receives will be reduced due to the damage to the firm.

Management-marketing activities provide information about business strategy and decision making. Marketing information and concepts help with product development, pricing, and distribution decisions.

The market system, also known as the free market system, is an economic system in which the distribution of prices, production and goods and services is determined by the forces of supply and demand. In the market system, individuals and enterprises make economic decisions based on their personal interests, the interaction of buyers and sellers in the market determines the distribution of resources, the distribution of goods and services. The market system is based on the principle of competition, which encourages enterprises to produce high-quality goods and services at competitive prices to attract buyers. The market system is based on the principle of competition, which encourages enterprises to produce high-quality goods and services at competitive prices to attract buyers. Competition also encourages innovation and efficiency as businesses seek to improve their products and processes to gain a competitive advantage in the market. The market system relies on the price mechanism to allocate resources and determine the value of goods and services. Prices are determined by the forces of supply and demand, and they reflect the wishes of consumers and the costs of production. In a market system, prices serve as a signal for economic decision-making and efficient allocation of resources.

Marketing plays a decisive role in the market system by facilitating the exchange of goods and services between buyers and sellers. Through market research and analysis, businesses can identify customer needs and desires and develop products and services that meet these needs. Marketing also helps businesses stand out from competitors and bring the value of their products and services to customers.

Marketing plays a key role in creating and supporting competition in the market system. By promoting their products and services, businesses can attract customers and gain market share. The competition between businesses encourages them to innovate and improve their products and services to meet the changing needs of customers. Marketing also plays an important role in determining the price of goods and services in the market system. By analyzing production costs and demand for their products and services, businesses can set prices that reflect the value of their offerings and consumer preferences.

Marketing is an important function in the market system, as it helps enterprises to identify and meet the needs of customers, differentiate from competitors, facilitate the exchange of goods and services in the market. Through effective marketing, enterprises can create and support competition, update and improve their products and services, effectively allocate resources in the market system.

Marketing plays an important role in the market system by facilitating the exchange of goods and services between buyers and sellers. Marketing activities such as market research and analysis, product development and Design, Promotion and advertising, sales and distribution help businesses identify and meet customer needs, differentiate from competitors, and convey the value of their offerings.

Marketing also plays a decisive role in creating and supporting competition in the market system. Through effective marketing, businesses can attract customers and gain market share, leading to innovation, improved products and services, and efficient resource allocation.

Marketing also helps to determine prices in the market system. By analyzing production costs and demand for their products and services, businesses can set prices that reflect the value of their offerings and consumer preferences.

Communication between Marketing and other business functions:

Marketing is an important business function that interacts with and affects other business functions. For example:

Finance-marketing activities require financial resources, such as funds for market research, product development, and advertising.

The application of modern information technologies to automate the activities of small and medium-sized economic objects, government bodies, transport, construction, trade and other economic objects carries out information systems on the basis of "electronic offices", that is, distributed databases and local computing networks that combine separate automated workplaces.

Automated training systems. The use of Information Technology in the training and training of personnel leads to the creation of automated training systems (AOTS), which are used in training processes in all branches of the continuing education system.

The introduction of information technologies into the bodies of the God-administrative management leads to the God information systems (letters). They create to provide the analysis and management functions of local government bodies and management.

The activities of the holy system are aimed at qualitatively carrying out management work in the region, forming a report, providing quick information to state and local oxen bodies.

In accordance with the structural-territorial bodies of management, the following systems are distinguished:

- information systems of autonomous republics, regions;
- information system of urban management;
- the information system of the administrative district.

According to the level of quality, information systems are divided into the following classes: information search engine (AQT); information reference system (AAT); text processing information system (MQAT); data processing system (MQT); information management system (ICT); decision – making system (QQQT); expert systems (ET). Information-search engine. Carries out a search for documents, secondary documents (e.g. abstracts), the name of documents or the full text of addresses, which can be stored in or out of the EHM. In one case or another, the EXM stores a formalized statement of documents that have received the name of the search image and whose summary is described. Information consumers who want to find a document on the topic they need will send a request to Tazim. According to the search result, information is provided about the full text of the described documents or about the correct, incorrect, insufficient, level of reliability of the requested expenses.

The information and reference system is designed in many ways to provide, collect and store information of economic, technical or technological content at the request of users. It can be said that the information and reference system is aimed at working with digital or text-concretized data. Determines how to present the result according to the type and form of the request. Survey results can be issued in the form of a standard reference, or can be designed in an optional view during processing of a user's request according to their wishes. The text processing system (MQT) is designed to edit, store, and reproduce texts (letter, article, abstract, command, and hakazo) directly to the user. Ijallangan. Ma the ' data processing system (MQIT) is designed to calculate data on formalized algorithms of calculations in EHM. These recommendations are given to the discretion of the decision-making person. Various mathematical models are placed on the basis of an advisory (board) information system, similar to real reality, that is, a process in an object or in a control system.

The decision-making system (QQQT) is distinguished by the fact that the decision option developed in the EHM is made to fulfill. At the moment, the

production system (automated system of control of technological processes dispatcher control system) automatically carries out the execution of decisions made by the EHM through appropriate enforcement mechanisms

Expert systems – in addition to the database in EHM-are characterized by the presence of two more-knowledge and a database of goals. Databases (MB) have a quantitative formal description of the control system and object; the knowledge base (BB) Maintains a statement of informal semantic representations of external muxit, some qualitative description of objects, relations between them, possible actions, States, abstractions, streotypes. The base of goals has a tasvur on interconnected goals, younger goals, methods and means of reaching them, characteristic of the objects to be modeled. Such systems are very relevant in creative, R & D, design, management processes.

The growing flow of information in modern society, the diversity of Information Technologies, the complication of issues solved on the computer put a number of tasks before the user of these technologies. The question arises of the choice of the necessary options and the transfer of decision-making work from person to person. One of the ways to solve this task is to consider the creation and use of expert systems. The expert, based on himself, analyzes the conditions and identifies relatively useful information, gives rise to the most optimal ways to make a decision, abandoning unsecured paths.

The expert system uses a knowledge base that represents a specific subject area.

The expert system is a set of methods and tools for collecting and applying knowledge in certain subject areas. The expert system achieves an even higher effect for the abundance of alternatives when choosing a decision, relying on the high-quality experience of specialists. When drawing up a strategy, it evaluates new factors and analyzes their effects.

Expert systems are based on the use of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence is understood as the ability of the computer system in relation to mental actions. Often in this, the ability associated with human thinking is realized.

Conclusion.

Expert systems can be considered as a class of Information Systems. It has a data and knowledge base that can tah-lil and edit data regardless of the user's consent, analyze the decision, perform analytical-classification tasks. In particular, expert systems are able to divide incoming information into groups, draw conclusions, identify, diagnose, teach prediction, comment, etc.

In conclusion, marketing communication is a very important factor that allows the firm to create products, produce, Price, enter the market, find haridor, re-establish relations with haridors, from the sale of products. Marketing communication is a huge process that splits into many networks. For example, advertising, direct sales, direct marketing are among them. But the main goal of marketing communication is to introduce the product to the client, keep the connection and remind him. Because, having an understanding of the product, hairdo can buy when he needs it, even if he does not buy it at that time. Because a note is made using marketing communication. Therefore, marketing communication is relevant and it should be studied in depth.

Literature used

1. Ergashxodjaeva Sh.Dj., Samadov A.N., Alimxodjayeva, N.E., Sharipov I.B." Marketing kommunikatsiyasi"
2. Philip Kotler " Kotler on marketing"
3. Раматов, Ж. С., Муратова, Д., Султанов, С. Х., Тухтабоев, Э., Кушаков, Ф., & Хасанов, М. Н. (2022). Ижтимоий адолат ва кадриятлар плюрализми. World scientific research journal, 8(1), 102-108.
4. Ж. С. Раматов, Л. А. Валиев, & М. Н. Хасанов (2022). Ауробиндо гхош талқинида инсон борлигининг антропологик жиҳатлари. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (6), 688-695.
5. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/marketing-mix.asp>
6. <http://ebook.tsue.uz/public/ebooks/marketing-kommunikatsiyasi>
7. Раматов, Ж.С., Баратов, Р.Ў., Султанов, С.Х., Муратова, Д.А., Хасанов, М.Н., & Эрнийёзов, У.К. (2022). Ёшлар замонавий маданий қиёфаси ва умуминсоний кадриятлар тушунчасининг мазмунмоҳияти. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (10), 376-386

KITOBLARNI SOTISH UCHUN MOBIL PLATFORMA YARATISH

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Annotatsiya: Raqamli asrda kitob savdosi dunyosi o'zgaruvchan o'zgarishlarni boshdan kechirmoqda, mobil platformalar kitobxonlarni sevimli nomlari bilan bog'lashda asosiy o'yinchilar sifatida paydo bo'lmoqda. Ushbu maqola kitoblar savdosiga bag'ishlangan mobil platforma yaratishning nozik tomonlari va imkoniyatlarini o'rganadi, foydalanuvchi tajribasi, kontentni tanlash, texnologik integratsiya va bozorga moslashishning ahamiyatini yoritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Mobil platforma, mobil kitoblar, smartfonlar, imkoniyatlar, electron kitoblar, katakoglar, foydalanuvchilar

CREATING A MOBILE PLATFORM FOR SELLING BOOKS

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Abstract: In the digital age, the world of bookselling is undergoing transformative changes, with mobile platforms emerging as key players in connecting readers with their favorite titles. This article explores the ins and outs of creating a mobile bookselling platform, highlighting the importance of user experience, content selection, technology integration, and market fit.

Keywords: Mobile platform, mobile books, smartphones, opportunities, electronic books, catalogs, users

Mobil kitob sotish platformasini yaratish foydalanuvchilarga o'z smartfon yoki planshetlarida kitob sotib olish va o'qish imkonini beruvchi dasturdir. U kitoblarni qidirish, sharhlarni ko'rish, kitoblarni sotib olish va kitoblarni oflayn

o'qish kabi xususiyatlarni o'z ichiga olishi vas hu bilan birga foydalanuvchilar uchun qulaylik, savdo hajmini oshirish va marketingni yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Shuni ham qo'shimcha qilsak bo'ladi ya'ni mobil kitob sotish platformasidan pul ishlashning bir qancha usullari mavjud, jumladan: kitob savdosi, obunalar va reklama. Kitoblarni sotish - pul ishlashning eng keng tarqalgan usuli, ammo obuna va reklama ham foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Mobil kitob bozorini tushunish:

Smartfonlar va planshetlarning ko'tarilishi odamlarning kontent, jumladan, kitoblarni iste'mol qilish usullarini inqilob qildi. Mobil platformalar qulaylik, foydalanish imkoniyati va portativlikni taklif etadi, bu ularni kitob savdosi uchun ideal vositaga aylantiradi. Muvaffaqiyatli mobil platformani yaratish uchun mobil kitob bozori dinamikasini, jumladan, foydalanuvchilarning afzalliklarini, o'qish odatlarini va sotib olish xatti-harakatlarini tushunish juda muhimdir.

Foydalanuvchiga asoslangan dizayn va tajriba:

Mobil kitob platformasining muvaffaqiyati uning foydalanuvchiga yo'naltirilgan dizayni va tajribasiga bog'liq. Intuitiv navigatsiya, uzluksiz kezish va moslashtirilgan tavsiyalar foydalanuvchi ishtiroki va qoniqishini oshiradigan muhim xususiyatlardir. Foydalanuvchilarning fikr-mulohazalarini birlashtirish va foydalanish imkoniyatlarini sinovdan o'tkazish platforma dizaynini yaxshilash va foydalanuvchi tajribasini optimallashtirishda bebahodir.

Kompleks tarkibni boshqarish:

Turli va keng qamrovli kitoblar katalogi har qanday muvaffaqiyatli kitob platformasining asosidir. Turli janrlar, mualliflar va tillar bo'yicha yuqori sifatli kontentni tanlash foydalanuvchilarga ularning qiziqishlari va afzalliklariga mos keladigan keng sarlavhalardan foydalanish imkoniyatini ta'minlaydi. Noshirlar, mualliflar va distribyutorlar bilan litsenziya shartnomalari va huquqlarini ta'minlash uchun hamkorlik qilish mustahkam kitob katalogini yaratish uchun juda muhimdir.

Texnologik integratsiya va innovatsiyalar:

Raqobatbardosh mobil kitob platformasini yaratish uchun ilg'or texnologiyalardan foydalanish zarur. EPUB va PDF kabi elektron kitob formatlari, shuningdek audiokitob formatlari bilan integratsiya platforma takliflarini kengaytiradi va foydalanuvchi tanlovini kengaytiradi. Oflayn o'qish,

xatcho'plar qo'yish, izohlar va qurilmalarda sinxronlash kabi xususiyatlar o'qish tajribasini boyitadi va platformani raqobatchilardan ajratib turadi.

Uzluksiz to'lov va tranzaksiyalarni boshqarish:

Mobil platformada kitob xaridlarini osonlashtirish uchun silliq va xavfsiz to'lov jarayoni juda muhim. Xavfsiz to'lov shlyuzlarini integratsiyalash, bir nechta valyuta va to'lov usullarini qo'llab-quvvatlash va ishonchli tranzaksiyalarni boshqarish tizimlarini joriy etish foydalanuvchilarda ishonchni uyg'otadi va takroriy xaridlarni rag'batlantiradi. Ma'lumotlar xavfsizligini birinchi o'ringa qo'yish va sanoat standartlariga rioya qilish foydalanuvchi ma'lumotlarini himoya qilish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Jamiyat ishtiroki va ijtimoiy integratsiya:

Jamiyat va ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir tuyg'usini rivojlantirish foydalanuvchilarning faolligi va sodiqligini oshiradi. Foydalanuvchilar sharhlari, reytinglari, kitob klublari va muhokama forumlari kabi ijtimoiy xususiyatlarni birlashtirish o'quvchilar o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqani rag'batlantiradi, platforma atrofida jonli va faol hamjamiyatni rivojlantiradi. Ijtimoiy media integratsiyasi foydalanuvchilarga o'zlarining sevimli kitoblari, tavsiyalari va o'qish tajribalarini baham ko'rish imkonini beradi, platformaning qamrovi va ko'rinishini kengaytiradi.

Uzluksiz takomillashtirish uchun tahlillar va tushunchalar:

Foydalanuvchilarning xatti-harakatlari, afzalliklari va tendentsiyalarini kuzatish va tahlil qilish platformaning ishlashi va kontent takliflarini optimallashtirish uchun qimmatli tushunchalarni beradi. Foydalanuvchilar ishtiroki, konversiya stavkalari va saqlanish kabi asosiy ko'rsatkichlarni kuzatish uchun tahlil vositalaridan foydalanish ma'lumotlarga asoslangan qarorlar qabul qilish va doimiy takomillashtirish imkonini beradi. Foydalanuvchilarning fikr-mulohazalari va tahliliy ma'lumotlarga asoslangan takroriy yangilanishlar va yaxshilanishlar platforma doimiy ravishda rivojlanib borayotgan kitob bozorida dolzarb va raqobatbardosh bo'lib qolishini ta'minlaydi.

Xulosa:

Kitoblar savdosi uchun mobil platforma yaratish kitob savdosida inqilob qilish va kitobxonlarni o'zlarining sevimli nomlari bilan qulay va qiziqarli tarzda bog'lash uchun ko'plab imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi. Dasturchilar va manfaatdor

tomonlar foydalanuvchi tajribasi, kontentni tanlash, texnologik innovatsiyalar va hamjamiyat ishtirokiga ustuvor ahamiyat berib, nafaqat kitobxonlarning ehtiyojlari va umidlariga javob beradigan, balki raqobatbardosh kitob bozorida o'sish va muvaffaqiyatga olib keladigan mobil platformani yaratishi mumkin. Texnologiya taraqqiyotda davom etar ekan va iste'molchilarning xohish-istaklari rivojlanib borar ekan, mobil kitob platformasining yaratilishi o'qish tajribasini innovatsiyalar, kengaytirish va boyitish uchun cheksiz imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari izohli lug'ati, 2004 yil.
2. Anderson, T., & Dron, J. (2021). Three Generations of Distance Education Pedagogy. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 12(3), 80-97.
3. S.S.G'ulomov, B.A.Begalov. *Informatika va axborot texnologiyalari*. Toshkent – 2010. "Fan". 478-480 b.
4. Hedstrom, Margaret (1997-05-01). "Raqamli saqlash: raqamli kutubxonalar uchun vaqt bombasi"
5. Kizilcec, R. F., & Halawa, S. A. (2021). Attrition and Achievement Gaps in Online Learning. *Proceedings of the Second (2015) ACM Conference*

LOGISTIKA SOHASIDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINI JORIY ETISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada logistika axborot tizimlari va ularning qoidalari, korxonada axborot resurslarini boshqarishni taxlil qiladi. Maqolada Jahon logistikasini rivojlantirish vazifalari va tendensiyalari alohida ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Axborot, logistika, korxonada, raqamlashtirish, MDH va Boltiqbo'yi, Logistics Performance Index, funksional quyi, texnik yordam, qayta ishlash, kodifikatorlar

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTRODUCING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIELD OF LOGISTICS.

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Abstract: This article analyzes logistics information systems and their rules, management of enterprise information resources. In the article, the tasks and trends of the development of World logistics are shown separately.

Key words: Information, logistics, enterprise, digitization, CIS and Baltics, Logistics Performance Index, functional sub, technical support, processing, codifiers

Kirish. Jahonda logistika axborot tizimlari, bozor mexanizmining muhim qismi bo'lib, moddiy, moliyaviy va axborot oqimlaridan samarali foydalanish orqali bozor ishtirokchilari manfaatlarini amalga oshirish va uyg'unlashtirish uchun yaratilgan. Logistika axborot tizimlarini shakllantirish va boshqarish jarayonlari va ularning faoliyatining iqtisodiy mexanizmi ularni doimiy ravishda takomillashtirishni talab qiladi. Logistika axborot tizimlarini, bir tomondan, asosiy logistika qoidalarga (izchillik, ratsionallik va aniq hisoblash) asoslangan

korxonalar axborot resurslarini boshqarish tizimi, ikkinchi tomondan - logistika menejmentining qo'llab-quvvatlovchi funksiyasi yoki funksional sohasi sifatida ko'rib chiqish mumkin. Ushbu ikki yondashuv qarama-qarshi emas va so'zning keng va tor ma'nosida axborot logistikasining ta'riflari sifatida talqin qilinishi mumkin.

Mamlakatimizda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy masalalar va vazifalarni hal etishda axborotlashtirish va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini ahamiyatini muhimligini e'tiborga olgan holda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Raqamli O'zbekiston- 2030" strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" Farmoni[1], O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbekiston Respublikasi davlat boshqaruviga raqamli iqtisodiyot, elektron hukumat hamda axborot tizimlarini joriy etish bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi Farmoni [2] ushbu sohada olib borilayotgan islohatlar jumlasidandir.

Birinchi holda, axborot logistikasi logistika menejmentining funksional sohasini yoki logistikaning umumiy nazariyasini ta'minlaydi. Uni o'rganish ob'ekti moddiy oqimlarga hamroh bo'lgan axborot oqimlari bo'lib, asosiy maqsad - logistika tizimlarini kerakli vaqtda, kerakli hajmda, kerakli joyda va maqbul xarajatlar bilan ma'lumot bilan ta'minlashdir. Ikkinchi holda, axborot logistikasi - bu logistika qoidalariga (ratsionallik, o'z vaqtida, aniq hisoblash) asoslangan holda butun tashkilotga ma'lumot beradigan tizim hisoblanadi[3].

Jahonda logistika axborot tizimlari quyidagi asosiy vazifalarni bajarishi kerak:

- ✓ logistika tizimining boshqaruv organlarini buyurtmaning harakati haqida doimiy ishonchli ma'lumotlar bilan ta'minlashi kerak;
- ✓ korxonaning funksional bo'linmalari xodimlarini doimiy ravishda haqiqiy vaqtda ta'minot zanjiri bo'ylab mahsulotlarning harakati xaqidagi ma'lumotlar bilan ta'minlashi zarur;
- ✓ boshqaruv uchun investitsiya qilingan mablag'lardan foydalanish to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarning shaffofligini ta'minlash;
- ✓ korxonani strategik rejalashtirish uchun axborotlar bilan doimiy ta'minlash;
- ✓ iste'molchilar buyurtmalarini bajarish muddatlarini baholash imkoniyatini ta'minlash;
- ✓ korxonalar resurslarini qayta taqsimlash imkoniyatini ta'minlash;
- ✓ logistika biznes jarayonlarini optimallashtirish orqali korxonaning rentabelligini ta'minlash.

Har qanday logistika tizimining muhim elementi ma'lumotlarning o'tishi va qayta ishlanishini ta'minlaydigan quyi tizim bo'lib, u yaqinroq o'rganilganda turli quyi tizimlardan iborat murakkab axborot tizimiga aylanadi. Boshqa har qanday tizim singari, axborot tizimi ham tartibli o'zaro bog'langan elementlardan iborat bo'lishi va ma'lum bir integral sifat-larga ega bo'lishi kerak. Axborot tizimlarini tarkibiy elementlariga turli usullar bilan amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Ko'pincha axborot tizimlari ikkita quyi tizimga bo'linadi: funksional va yordamchi[4].

Jahon banki ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, logistika samaradorligi indeksi bo'yicha 2023 yil holatiga Singapur 1-o'rin, Fillandiya 2-o'rin, Germaniya va Avstriya 7-o'rin, Shvetsiya, Belgiya 7-o'rin, Konada 7-o'rin eng rivojlangan lo-gistika tizimlariga ega. Litva logistika samaradorligi indeksi bo'yicha MDH va Boltiqbo'yi mamlakatlari orasida yetakchi hisoblanadi (58-o'rin). Estoniya tomonidan ta'qib qilindi (26-o'rin), Ukraina (79-o'rin), Latviya (34-o'rin). Belorussiya Logistika samaradorligi indeksi (Logistics Performance Index) reytingida 79-o'rinni egallab, Rossiya (88-o'rin) va Qozog'istondan (79-o'rin), O'zbekiston 88-o'rinni egallagan[5].

Adabiyotlar tahlili va metodologiyal. Funksional quyi tizim umumiy maqsadga muvofiq guruhlangan hal qilinadigan vazifalar majmuasidan iborat bo'lib, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi quyi tizim, o'z navbatida, quyidagi elementlarni o'z ichiga oladi:

- ✓ texnik yordam, ya'ni. axborot oqimlarini qayta ishlash va uzatishni ta'minlovchi texnik vositalar majmui;
- ✓ turli ma'lumotnomalar, tasniflagichlar, kodifikatorlar, rasmiylashtirilgan ma'lumotlarni tavsiflash vositalarini o'z ichiga olgan axborot ta'minoti;
- ✓ matematik dasturiy ta'minot, ya'ni funksional muammolarni hal qilish usullari to'plami.

Jahonda logistika yondashuvlarini joriy etish va ulardan foydalanish hozirgi kunda yanada dolzarb bo'lib qoldi va har qanday mamlakat iqtisodiyoti samaradorligini oshirish omili hisoblanadi. Ko'pgina mamlakatlar, shu jumladan Belorusiya Respublikasi, ishlab chiqarish faoliyatida logistika sohasida faol siyosat olib bormoqda.

Shunga asoslanib, logistika sohasidagi axborot tizimini logistika tizimining ishlashini rejalashtirish, tartibga solish, nazorat qilish va tahlil qilish uchun logistika menejmenti tomonidan foydalaniladigan axborot oqimi bilan birlashtirilgan xodimlar, uskunalar va protseduralarni o'z ichiga olgan interaktiv tuzilma sifatida aniqlash mumkin.

Logistika axborot tizimlari, logistika jarayonlarini boshqarish uchun avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlardir. Shunday qilib, logistika axborot tizim-larida dasturiy ta'minot - bu moddiy oqimlarni boshqarish, matnni qayta ishlash, ma'lumotlarini olish va texnik vositalarning ishlashini ta'min-laydigan dasturlar va dasturiy vositalar to'plami hisoblanadi. Logistika axborot tizimlari dasturiy yechimlarning eng yuqori darajadagi integratsiya-si bilan tavsiflanadi, bu ularni ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirishning o'ziga xos shartlarini belgilaydi [6].

Logistika axborot tizimlari alohida korxonada darajasida moddiy oqimlarni boshqarish maqsadida yaratilishi mumkin va mintaqalar, mamlakatlar va hatto mamlakatlar guruhlarida logistika jarayonlarini tashkil etishga hissa qo'shishi mumkin. Logistika axborot tizimi elektron hisoblash uskunalari ishini logistika menejerlarining harakatlari bilan o'zaro bog'laydigan va ular uchun mavjud bo'lgan to'g'ri ma'lumotlarni olishlarini ta'minlaydigan, logistika operatsiyalarini rejalashtirish va bajarish jarayonlarini tashkil etish va amalga oshirishga imkon beradigan tizim sifatida tavsiflanadi.

Bugungi kunda logistika markazlari juda faol yaratilmoqda va rivojlanmoqda, yangi logistika yo'nalishlari ishlab chiqilmoqda va mavjudlari takomillashtirilmoqda. Mahsulotlarni reklama qilish va zaxiralarni saqlash jarayonlarini amalga oshirish, shuningdek, axborot logistika jarayonlarini amalga oshirish uchun turli xil texnik vositalardan foydalanish kerak. Ushbu vositalar, ulardan foydalanish usullari, shuningdek ularning ishlashini ta'minlash tizimlari logistika jarayonlarining o'ziga xos infratuzilmasini tashkil qiladi. U barcha asosiy logistika funksiyalarini uzluksiz va tejamkor ishlashini ta'minlashga yordam beradi.

Logistika jarayonlarining axborot oqimlari ommaviy xarakter, operatsion ishlov berish zarurati (real vaqtda), boshqaruv jarayonida axborot va uning tashuvchilaridan ko'p foydalanish bilan tavsiflanadi. Bularning barchasi tegishli axborotni qayta ishlash vositalari va texnologiyalaridan foydalanish uchun ob'ektiv sharoit yaratadi. Ular, shuningdek, korxonalarda logistika jarayoni infratuzilmasining muhim tarkibiy qismlari hisoblanadi.

Muhokama va natijalar. Axborot logistikasi mantiqiy tizimning barcha elementlarini bog'laydigan bog'lovchi iplar bo'lgan axborot oqimlarini ifodalaydi. Muammo shundaki, bozor korxonalarga jiddiy talablarni qo'yadi. Biz mahsulotlarni tez va tez modernizatsiya qilishimiz, narxlarni yaxshiroq nazorat qilishimiz, xarajatlarni hisobga olishimiz, individual buyurtmalar va mahsulotlar samaradorligini tahlil qilishimiz kerak. Katta hajmdagi mahsulotlardan "saqlash uchun" (ishlab chiqaruvchining ixtiyoriga ko'ra, ya'ni ishlab chiqarishni yo'lga qo'yish vaqtidagi aniq buyurtmalar) bir qator tarmoqlar tez yetkazib berish bilan aniq buyurtmalar uchun bo'lak ishlab chiqarishga o'tmoqda. Axborot

texnologiyalari ushbu talablarni qondirish va ushbu muammoni hal qilishga katta hissa qo'shishi mumkin. Muayyan balandlik samaradorlikka mahalliy hisoblash tizimlari yordamida erishish mumkin, ammo shaffoflik va moslashuvchanlik faqat korxonalar bo'linmalari o'rtasidagi chegaralardan "oshib o'tuvchi" integratsiyalashgan axborot va boshqaruv tizimlaridan foydalanish natijasida sezilarli darajada oshadi [3].

Raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish jarayoni bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshiriladi: - boshlang'ich bosqich - bu shaxsiy kompyuterdan foydalanish tajribasini to'plash va aniq vazifalar darajasida buxgalteriya hisoblarini avtomatlashtirish;

- shaxsiy kompyuterlar parkini barqarorlashtirish bosqichini nazorat qilish, ularni qo'llash sohasini aniqlash, Internetda ma'lumot qidirish va korxonada mahalliy tarmoqlarni tashkil etish;

- integratsiya bosqichi: turli darajadagi tarmoq yechimlari, shaxsiy kompyuterdan foydalangan holda boshqaruvni markazsizlashtirish va Internetga integratsiyalashgan murakkab korporativ axborot tizimlaridan keng foydalanishga asoslangan korxonalar uchun yangi tashkiliy asos [4].

Xususiy sektorda ko'plab rahbarlar ma'lumotlarning muhimligini va uning raqamli transformatsiya va innovatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi rolini allaqachon tan olishgan va Big Data kontseptsiyasini kelajakdagi muvaffaqiyat uchun birinchi o'rinlardan biri sifatida ta'kidlashgan. Ushbu texnologiyadan foydalanish uning narxi jihatidan arzonligi tufayli keng tarqaldi. Korxonalarining 79 foizi Big Data ularning daromadiga ko'proq ta'sir ko'rsatishiga ishonadi va rahbarlarning 59 foizi undan mijozlar ehtiyojlarini yaxshiroq tushunish uchun foydalanadi.

Katta ma'lumotlar texnologiyasi ta'minot zanjiri agentlari tomonidan yaratilgan ma'lumotlarni samarali olish, integratsiya qilish, saqlash va ulardan foydalanish imkonini beradi.

Logistikada axborot tizimlarining ma'lum bir sinfidan foydalanishning maqsadga muvofiqligini aniqlashda forsight tadqiqotlari metodologiyasidan foydalanish mumkin. Uning doirasida logistika sohasidagi asosiy tendentsiyalar va axborot texnologiyalari to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar yoritilgan va tizimlashtirilgan bo'lib, sanoat tashkilotlari faoliyatining siljish va innovatsion xarakterini ta'minlaydi. Bu jarayonda ekspertlarni tanlash, natijalarni tekshirish va ekspert hay'atlarini o'tkazish tamoyillari muhim o'rin tutadi.

Korxonaning logistika faoliyatida axborot texnologiyalarini tanlash bo'yicha tavsiyalar ma'lum bir kompaniya va uning sho'ba korxonalari faoliyatining ko'rsatkichlarini, atrof-muhit omillarini, mavjud va potentsial

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bozorlarni tahlil qilish, shuningdek, ishlab chiqarish faoliyatining tabiatini taqqoslash asosida amalga oshiriladi. tashkilotda allaqachon foydalanilgan axborot tizimlari/tehnologiyalari.

Bulutli xizmatlar - foydalanuvchi o'z vazifalari uchun tezda foydalanishi mumkin bo'lgan sozlanishi mumkin bo'lgan hisoblash resurslarining umumiy to'plamiga (masalan, tarmoqlar, serverlar, ma'lumotlarni saqlash, ilovalar va/yoki xizmatlar) qulay, talab bo'yicha tarmoqqa kirishni ta'minlash

Ushbu kontseptsiya hisoblash vositalarining mavjudligini oshirishga qaratilgan va uchta xizmat modelini o'z ichiga oladi:

1. Cloud Software as a Service (SaaS) - bulutli dasturiy ta'minot xizmat sifatida, - "xizmat sifatida dasturiy ta'minot";

2. Cloud Platform as a Service (PaaS) - bulutli platforma xizmat sifatida;

3. Cloud Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) - bulutli infratuzilma xizmat sifatida. Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqqan holda, kichik kompaniyalar uchun bulutli xizmatlar bulut orqali SaaS (xizmat sifatida dasturiy ta'minot) modelidan foydalangan holda tarqatiladigan biznesni avtomatlashtirish ilovalari bo'lib, mijozlarning keng doirasi uchun hamyonbop narxda mavjud [1].

Bugungi kunda bulutli xizmatlardan IT-kompaniyalari va tizim integratorlari (xususan, SAP, Oracle, Infor, IBM, Generix, Visagio va boshqalar) yetkazib berish zanjirlarida logistika biznes jarayonlarini boshqarish uchun keng qo'llaniladi. Logistika va protsessorda bulutli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning quyidagi afzalliklarini ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin:

Bulutli xizmatlar ta'minot zanjiri biznes jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirishni ancha qulayroq qiladi.

Bulutli xizmatlarning narxi doimiy ravishda pasayib bormoqda va bu turdagi ilovalarni amalga oshirish osonroq va tezlashmoqda. Bulutli echimlar hech qanday kapital xarajatlarni talab qilmaydi (server sotib olish, uni texnik qo'llab-quvvatlash va boshqalar), buning natijasida ishlab chiqarish xarajatlari va tarqatish xarajatlari kamayadi.

Bulutli texnologiyalar yetkazib berish zanjiri ishtirokchilariga asosiy logistika biznes-jarayonlarini amalga oshirish tezligi va aniqligini oshirish imkonini beradi, bu esa mijozning buyurtmasini bajarishda juda muhimdir. Bulutli xizmatlardan foydalanmaydigan kompaniyalar, AT tizimidagi nosozliklar yuzaga kelgan taqdirda, o'z vaqtlarini ma'lumotlarni zaxiralash va tiklashga sarflashga majbur bo'lishadi, bu esa ish tezligining pasayishiga olib keladi [4].

Xulosa. Ta'minot zanjirlarining yuqori darajadagi murakkabligi va talab va taklifga xos bo'lgan xavflar, ayniqsa, iqtisodiy tanazzul davrida, ta'minot zanjiri samaradorligining yuqori darajasiga erishishda asosiy cheklovlar sifatida e'tirof

etiladi. Zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari qarorlarini qo‘llab-quvvatlash tizimlaridan foydalanishning roli tezda murakkab ta‘minot zanjiri (SC) tarmoq tuzilmalarini loyihalash va boshqarish uchun ajralmas vositaga aylanib bormoqda.

Protsessorlar - ko‘p sonli tugunlarga va uning faol elementlari va ishtirokchilari o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro ta‘sirlarning murakkab tabiatiga ega bo‘lgan murakkab adaptiv tizimlar; tashqi muhitda sodir bo‘layotgan o‘zgarishlar sharoitida boshqaruv qarorlarini qabul qilish dinamikasi kuchayib bormoqda, bu keskin vaziyatlar va hodisalar, shuningdek, turli ishtirokchilar o‘rtasida yuzaga keladigan nizolar oldida tezkor, deyarli real vaqtda, buzilishlarga javob berishni talab qiladi.

Axborot texnologiyalarini o‘zlarining logistika quyi tizimlariga faol joriy etayotgan sanoat tashkilotlari uchun eng katta raqobat ustunligi texnologiyani "ilmiy va texnologik sinov maydonchasi - tajriba sanoat liniyalari - muhandislik markazi - sertifikatlashtirish markazi" kombinatsiyasida joriy etish orqali olinishi rejalashtirilgan. Hozirgi vaqtda logistika tizimlarida IT-texnologiyalarni joriy etishning eng katta rivojlanishi "Kompozit vodi" (Tula viloyati), "Boltiq vodiysi" (Kaliningrad viloyati) kabi loyihalarga xosdir.

Axborot texnologiyalari nafaqat logistika sifatini yaxshilaydi, balki zamonaviy dunyoda zarurat bo‘lib, turli darajadagi bozor ishtirokchilarining tashkiliy va kommunikativ imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etish jarayoni zamonaviy dunyoda logistika faoliyatining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Axborot texnologiyalari nafaqat axborotni qayta ishlash almashinuvi samaradorligini oshirishga, balki rejalashtirish bosqichida ham etkazib berish zanjirlari faoliyatidagi yo‘qotishlar va uzilishlarni kamaytirishga yordam beradi. Logistikaga axborot elementlarini joriy etishning dastlabki texnologik darajasida ham korxonada turli xil oqimlarni boshqarish jarayonlarining sifati oshadi. Tovarlar harakati va ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini real vaqt rejimida kuzatish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar paydo bo‘lmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PQ-4022-sonli “Raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish maqsadida raqamli infratuzilmani yanada modernizatsiya qilish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori. 2018 yil 11 noyabr.
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/effektivnost-primeneniya-logistiki-dlya-vnutrenneyi-vneshney-integratsii-predpriyatiya>
3. О. Сабден, Ж. Раимбеков. Логистика (экономика и управление). Учебник. © Издательство И ЭКНМОН РК 2011 г. -613 с.
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zarubezhnaya-praktika-logistiki-i-ee-ispolzovanie-vrf>

ФИРИБГАРЛИК ЖИНОЯТИ УЧУН ЖАВОБГАРЛИК ВА ЧЕТ ЭЛ ТАЖРИБАСИ

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Жиноят қонунчилигини қўллаш теорияси ва амалиёти, 2-курс магистранти

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада фирибгарлик жиноятининг Республикамиздаги жавобгарлик масаларари ҳақида маълумотлар берилган. Бундан ташқари фирибгарлик жиноятининг чет эл давлатлари қонунчилигидаги жавобгарлик масалалари ҳақида сўз юритилган.

Калим сўзлар: юридик таққослаш, жавобгарлик, ҳуқуқий нормалар, давлатлар қонунларининг таҳлили.

RESPONSIBILITY FOR FRAUD AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: This article provides information on issues of liability for fraud in our Republic. In addition, issues of liability for the crime of fraud in the legislation of foreign countries are discussed.

Key words: legal comparison, responsibility, legal norms, analysis of state laws

Фирибгарликни ҳуқуқий тартибга солиш масаласи бошқа хорижий давлатларда қандай ҳал қилинганлигини кўриб чиқиш фойдадан ҳоли эмас деб ўйлаймиз. Энг аввало шунини айтиш керакки, Болгария, Венгрия, Югославия республикаларининг жиноят қонунларида фирибгарлик фақат алдаш билан содир этилади дейилган. Ишончни суиистеъмол қилиш эса бошқа жиноят таркибини ҳосил қилади. Югославия ЖКнинг 260-моддасида ишончни суиистеъмол қилганлик учун жиноий жавобгарлик белгиланган. Унда ишонч суиистеъмол қилишга: “Шахсининг мулкӣ манфаатини ёки унинг мулкӣни назорат қила туриб, ўз бурчини бажармаслик ва унга берилган ваколатларни суиистеъмол қилиб, ўзи учун ёки учинчи бир шахс учун фойда олишга ҳаракат қилиб, мулкӣ устидан назорат қилиши керак

бўлган шахсга зарар етказиш” деб таъриф берилади. Худди шундай жиноят состави Болгария ЖКда (265-модда) ҳам бор. Бу ерда ишончни суистеъмол қилиш тушунчаси аниқроқ берилган: “Жавобгарга сақлаш ёки бошқариш учун ишониб топширилган бировнинг мулкига онгли равишда зарар етказиш”. Болгария ЖКнинг шу моддасида ваколат берган шахснинг ишончини суистеъмол қилиб, онгли равишда унинг қонуний манфаатларига зарар етказган вакил ҳам жиноий жавобгарликка тортилиши айтилган. Югославия ЖКнинг 260-моддаси адвокатлар ва васийлар ишончни суистеъмол қилганликлари учун жавобгарлик белгилайди.

Венгрия Республикаси ЖК “Жамоат ва гражданларнинг мулкига қарши жиноятлар” бобининг §293да “бировни янглиштириб, унга зарар етказиш ёки моддий фойда олиш мақсадида уни янглиштириш - фирибгарликдир” дейилган.

МДХ ва хорижий республикалар жиноят қонунларида фирибгарликка қарши қаратилган жиноят ва жазо ҳуқуқий нормаларини батафсил бўлмасида, қиёсий таҳлил қилиш, фирибгарликка берилган таърифларда принципиал фарқлар йўқ деган хулосага олиб келади.

Юқорида номлари келтирилган давлатлар қонунларини таҳлил этиб, ишончни суистеъмол қилишни алоҳида жиноят таркибига ажратиш керак деб ўйлаймиз. Бу моддани қуйидаги таҳрирда: “Ишончни суистеъмол қилиб, мулкӣ фойда олиш ёки мулкни эгаллаш, жарима ёки икки йилгача муддатга ахлоқ тузатиш ишлари билан, ёки уч йилгача муддатга озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб берилишини таклиф қиламиз.

Ривожланган ғарб давлатлари қонунларига назар ташлайдиган бўлсак, барча давлатларнинг жиноят қонунларида фирибгарлик учун жиноий жавобгарлик белгиланган. Бу жиноятни тижоратчилар ва бошқа соҳибкорлик – тижорат ишлари билан шуғулланувчи (бизнесмен)ларнинг кундалик фаолиятларидан ажратиш анча мураккабдир. Шу сабабли хорижий ҳуқуқшунослар бир томондан фирибгарлик билан ўғирлик, ишончни суистеъмол қилиш, сохтакорлик ўртасидаги фарқларни, иккинчи томондан фирибгарлик билан фуқаролик ҳуқуқий муносабатлари орасидаги фарқларни чуқур ўрганишга алоҳида эътибор бермоқдалар.

Бизнинг фикримизча, жиноят қонуниimizда талон-тарожнинг умумий тушунчасини бериш лозим. Монголия, Болгария давлатларининг ЖКларида бундай таъриф мавжуддир.

Польша Республикаси ЖК 120-моддасининг 8-параграфида талон-тарожга “ўзи ёки бошқа биров учун мулкый фойда олиш” деб таъриф берилган ва талон-тарожнинг кўринишлари сифатида ўғирлик, ўзлаштириш ва фирибгарлик кўрсатилган.

Юқоридаги мисоллар Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Жиноят кодексини талон-тарожнинг умумий тушунчаси ҳақидаги норма билан тўлдириш лозим, деган хулосаларимизни яна бир бор мустаҳкамлайди.

Фойдаланган адабиётлар

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг «Фирибгарликка оид ишлар бўйича суд амалиёти тўғрисида»ги 2009 йил 24 июль 8-сонли қарори // Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленуми қарорлари тўплами (2006–2014 йиллар). – Т., 2014. – Б. 183.
2. О'zbekiston Respublikasining Jinoyat kodeksi [2021 yil 1 aprelgacha bo'lgan o'zgartirishlar va qo'shimchalar bilan] – Т.: «Yuridik adabiyotlar publish», 2021y. –
3. Уголовный кодекс Федеративной Республики Германии, по состоянию на 15май 2003г. <https://constitutions.ru/?p=24969>
4. Jinoyat huquqi. (Umumiy qism) Darslik. Ma'sul muharrir: yu.f.f.d (PhD) X.Ochilov – Т.: Adolat nashriyoti, 2020.
5. Rustambayev M.X. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Jinoyat kodeksiga sharhlar. 3-Maxsus qism/M.Rustambayev. – Toshkent: «Yuridik adabiyotlar publish», 2021y. – 744b

USE OF COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY IN DENTISTRY. DENTO PROPRIETAS X-RAY

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Annotation. Multispiral computed tomography, a modern medical technique, is highly effective in diagnosing diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, injuries of the musculoskeletal system, and diseases of the musculoskeletal system. However, his diagnosis in the face-jaw area leads to the appearance of tumor diseases in patients. For this reason, we consider the Dento Proprietas X-ray setup based on the MSKT setup, the principle of operation of which is used to diagnose the maxillofacial area in dentistry. The lack of requirements for patients in the diagnostic process makes up for the shortcomings of previous diagnostic structures

Key words: Multispiral computed tomography, Dento Proprietas X-ray, stationary detectors, X-ray tube, diagnostics, scanning, hard and soft tissues

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ ТОМОГРАФИИ В СТОМАТОЛОГИИ. DENTO PROPERTIESRIETAS X-RAY

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Аннотация. Мультиспиральная компьютерная томография — современный медицинский метод, высокоэффективный в диагностике таких заболеваний, как рак, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, инфекционные заболевания, травмы опорно-двигательного аппарата, заболевания опорно-двигательного аппарата. Однако его диагностика в лице-челюстной области приводит к появлению у больных опухолевых заболеваний. По этой причине мы рассматриваем рентгеновскую установку Dento Proprietas на базе установки МСКТ, принцип действия которой используется для диагностики челюстно-лицевой области в стоматологии. Отсутствие требований к пациентам в диагностическом процессе компенсирует недостатки прежних диагностических структур.

Ключевые слова: мультиспиральная компьютерная томография, рентген Dento Proprietas, стационарные детекторы, рентгеновская трубка, диагностика, сканирование, твердые и мягкие ткани.

Introduction: Currently, it is impossible to imagine medicine without computer diagnostics. Technical progress and the advent of computers led to the development of tomographic methods, which today occupy a leading position in radiation diagnostics. The starting point for the development of radiation diagnostic methods was the advent of computed tomography (CT). In terms of its importance, the creation of CT is comparable to the discovery of X-rays. In 1998, another multispiral CT (MSKT) appeared in the development of CT. This is a type of computer tomography and is one of the most modern methods of viewing organs and tissues.

MSKT makes it possible to diagnose diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, injuries of the musculoskeletal system, bleeding in organs and tissues, diseases of the musculoskeletal system. The main idea of MSKT is to use multiple array detectors in combination with x-ray broadening in the z-direction for more efficient use of X-rays. This shows that data can be collected from multiple images at the same time. Real-size images are captured in a short time. However, the radiation dose is high. Even dynamic processes can be evaluated. In MSKT, each detector element is divided into several small detector elements in z-direction. These detector elements form a 2D image. In MSKT, the thickness of the detector is not determined by X-rays. Instead, it is determined by the detector configuration. The length of each detector is often called detector collimation. The difference with an X-ray is that many pictures are taken and all of them are combined into a 3D model, which is much easier to view. MRI is used to scan bones and look for tumors. Bones are immediately visible on CT, and tumors are clearly visible when contrast is used. CT is especially important in severe conditions, such as a closed fracture with minor internal bleeding. We can quickly assess the severity of the situation. In case of extensive internal bleeding, emergency surgery is indicated immediately. Diagnosis of the condition of the heart and blood vessels. Damage to the skeletal structure, including the skull. Diagnosis of diseases of the excretory system - gastrointestinal tract, kidneys, bladder, liver, etc. (with or without contrast). It is used in the examination of tumors for relapses and in the diagnosis of diseases of the respiratory system.

Fig. 1 Multispiral computed tomography (MSKT)

The main advantage of MSKT is that it is a painless, non-invasive and informative research method. There is no residual radiation in the body after the examination and a short diagnostic time, retrospective creation of thinner or thicker sections from different data sets, and improved 3D rendering. In addition, MSCT is superior to MRI in terms of the quality of visualization of bone tissue. Unlike MRI, the presence of metal in the body is not a contraindication for the study. It is less sensitive to the patient's movements and allows for fast, real-time visualization of tissues. Current developments and trends point to more fractional systems driven by clinical applications possible through the use of such detectors.[1.2] We learned how important the role of MSCT in medical diagnostics is. But like all modern medical techniques, it has its own requirements and disadvantages:

- pregnancy is a clear contraindication for MSCT and is performed only for health reasons,
- nursing mothers should avoid feeding the baby for 24 hours after the injection of contrast material,
- risk of serious allergic reaction to iodine-containing contrast agents,
- MSKT in children should be done only when necessary and not repeated.

This structure, which has an important place in the field of medicine, affects patients differently during the diagnostic process due to the above-mentioned shortcomings, and these effects are harmfully hidden in their place. As medicine develops, different approaches to solving these problems are emerging. Diagnostic infusion of different parts of the head without affecting other organs of the body can provide a positive solution to the problems that arise. This method is mainly aimed at wide application in the field of stomatology. This is why, according to statistics, one out of every twenty patients with toothache is diagnosed with tumor diseases. Examples of these diseases are organospecific

malignant mesenchymal tumors, osteosarcoma, adenocarcinoma, squamous cell cancer, angiosarcoma, odontogenic tumors.

In this proposed method, maxillofacial diagnosis is performed using the Dento Proprietas x-ray device, which sees hard and soft tissues together. The DentoPR device is used in maxillofacial surgery. It is designed to see both soft and hard cells at the same time. Due to its low harm, it can be used for pregnant women, children under 14 years old and patients weighing more than 120 kg.

Figure 2. Dento Proprietas radiograph (DentoPR) setup

The structure of the device is based on the structure of MSKT. That is, the X-ray tube and the detector are rotated behind a circular curtain. A conical X-ray tube and array of stationary detectors are configured to achieve very high temporal resolution, high-speed tomography imaging from the electromagnetic deflection of the electron beam. In the device, the source and detector move along a spiral path relative to the object. A spiral can achieve improved image resolution compared to individual slice acquisition for a given radiation dose. The trajectory of spiral rays is characterized by its step[3.4]. This is divided by cross-sectional collimation equal to the transmission distance over the scan range per gantry rotation. In this case, the X-rays are cone-shaped, meaning that the X-rays trace a spiral trajectory relative to the object, and a set of two-dimensional detectors measure the object. The source and array of detectors are installed on the portal. The 220 V voltage is reduced through a transformer and fed to the receiving board. During the diagnostic process, the patient is lying down and the DentoPR device is installed in the jaw area of the head. Therefore, the diagnosis in the DentoPR setup led to the healing of other parts of the patient's body from radiation. In this

case, the X-ray tube and detectors are installed on the internal rotating part of the measuring (circular) section. Taking into account that the device is mainly used in diagnostics of the head part, the number of its detector lines and the energy of the emitted X-ray beam were taken into account[5.6]. This ensures that the negative impact of X-rays on patients is minimal. During the diagnostic process, the internal rotating part moves and the image becomes invisible on the screen through the interface. It can be seen that the DentoPR system is much more effective and less harmful than MSKT in the diagnosis of the head, especially the face and jaw.

Summary. Multi-spiral computed tomography is an important structure of modern tibiology in the diagnosis of diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, injuries of the musculoskeletal system, bleeding in organs and tissues, diseases of the musculoskeletal system. But this structure, which has an important place in the field of medicine, affects patients differently due to the shortcomings it shows in the diagnostic process, and these effects are harmfully hidden in their place. Especially in the field of stomatology, most of the patients diagnosed with the facial part have tumors. As a modern solution to this, the Dento Proprietas x-ray system, which is based on the working principle of MSKT and which simultaneously sees hard and soft tissues in maxillofacial diagnostics, is shown. The simplicity of this method and the low requirements in the diagnostic process pave the way for a high level of service to patients and a great achievement in the field of medicine.

References

1. M. K. Bakhadirxhanov, N. F. Zikrillaev, K. S. Ayupov, D. T. Bobonov, F. A. Kadirova, and N. Il'khomzhonov Spectral Range of Current Self-Oscillation in Manganese-Doped Silicon Technical Physics, 2006, Vol. 51, No. 9, pp. 1235–1236
2. N.F. Zikrillaev, G.A. Kushiev, S.B. Isamov, B.A Abdurakhmanov, O.B. Tursunov. Photovoltaic Properties of Silicon Doped with Manganese and Germanium. J. Nano-electron. Phys. 15 №1, 01021 2023. N.F.Zikrillaev, G.A.Kushiev, Sh.I.Hamrokulov, Y.A.Abduganiev “Optical Properties of GexSi1-x binary compounds in silicon” Journal of nano- and electronic physics, Vol. 15, No. 3, pp. 03024-1 - 03024-4, 2023.
3. X.M. Iliyev, S.B. Isamov, B.O. Isakov, U.X. Qurbonova, and S.A. Abduraxmonov, “A surface study of Si doped simultaneously with Ga and Sb,” East Eur. J. Phys. 3, 303, 2023.
4. Iliyev, V.B. Odzhaev, S.B. Isamov, B.O. Isakov, B.K. Ismaylov, K.S. Ayupov, S.I. Hamrokulov, and S.O. Khasanbaeva, “X-ray diffraction and raman spectroscopy analyses of GaSb-enriched Si surface formed by applying diffusion doping technique,” East Eur. J. Phys. 3, 363 (2023).

5. Iliyev, X., Xudoynazarov, Z., Isakov, B., Uralbayev, X. and Kushiev, G., 2023. Impurity of atoms of manganese diffusion by outside electric field into silicon. Science and innovation, 2(A8), pp.107-111 B Isakov, Z Xudoynazarov, G Kushiev, A Sattorov, F Abduqahhorov, 2023. Thermodynamic conditions for the formation of gasb binary compound in Si sample. Science and innovation, 2(A10), pp.29-34.
6. N.F. Zikrillaev, G.A.Kushiev, S.V.Koveshnikov, B.A. Abdurakhmanov, U.Kh.Kurbanova, and A.A.Sattorov, "Current status of silicon studies with GexSi1-x binary compounds and possibilities of their applications in electronics" East European journal of physics, No. 3, pp. 334-339, 2023.
7. S Hamrokulov, G Kushiev, B Isakov, Z Umarkhodjaeva Digital microscope Analysis of chemically cleaned silicon surface Science and innovation, 2023. Т.2 №5 Pp.138-142 11. Абдурахманов Б.А., Исамов С.Б., Кушиев Г.А. Автоматизированная установка определения параметров полупроводников методом Ван Дер Пау. Приборы, 2022 №2. С.14-18.
8. N. F. Zikrillaev, O. B. Tursunov, G. A. Kushiev. "Development and Creation of a New Class of Graded-Gap Structures Based on Silicon with the Participation of Zn and Se Atoms". ISSN 1068-3755, Surface Engineering and Applied Electrochemistry, Vol. 59, No. 5, pp. 670–673. © Allerton Press, Inc., 2023

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